

Patterned Single Digits Representations of Natural Numbers

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Abstract

*This work brings patterned representations of natural numbers from 1 to 1000 in terms of **single digits** from 1 to 9. To bring these results, only **basic operations**, such as **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication** and **division** are used. This work is an extension of author's works [7, 13], in patterned form. Patterns representations are some what similar to symmetrical extensions. A similar kind of work in different ways is done by author [12].*

1 Introduction

Let us consider

$$f^n(10) = 10^n + 10^{n-1} + \dots + 10^2 + 10^1 + 10^0,$$

For $a \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$, we can write

$$af^n(10) = \underbrace{aaa\dots a}_{(n+1)\text{-times}},$$

In particular,

$$\begin{aligned} aa &:= f^1(10) = a10 + a \\ aaa &:= f^2(10) = a10^2 + a10 + a \\ aaaa &:= f^3(10) = a10^3 + a10^2 + a10 + a \\ aaaaa &:= f^4(10) = a10^4 + a10^3 + a10^2 + a10 + a \\ &\dots \end{aligned}$$

(1)

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For example, one can write

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{5} &:= \frac{aa-a}{a+a} = \frac{11-1}{1+1} = \frac{22-2}{2+2} = \frac{33-3}{3+3} = \frac{44-4}{4+4} = \frac{55-5}{5+5} = \frac{66-6}{6+6} = \frac{77-7}{7+7} = \frac{88-8}{8+8} = \frac{99-9}{9+9} \\
 \mathbf{56} &:= \frac{aaa+a}{a+a} = \frac{111+1}{1+1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3} = \frac{444+4}{4+4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6} = \frac{777+7}{7+7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9} \\
 \mathbf{111} &:= \frac{aaa}{a} = \frac{111}{1} = \frac{222}{2} = \frac{333}{3} = \frac{444}{4} = \frac{555}{5} = \frac{666}{6} = \frac{777}{7} = \frac{888}{8} = \frac{999}{9} \\
 &\dots\dots
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

The above representations are in **symmetrized** form. This allows us to write in a single letter **a**. Below are some examples, of non symmetrized representations of natural numbers in terms of each digit from 1 to 9.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{717} &:= (1+1)^{11} - 11^{(1+1+1)} &= 22^2 + 222 + 22/2 &= 3^{(3+3)} - 3 - 3 \times 3 \\
 &= 4 \times (4 \times 44 + 4) - 4 + 4/4 &= (55 \times (55 + 5 + 5) + 5 + 5)/5 &= (6 \times 6 / (6 + 6))^6 - 6 - 6 \\
 &= 777 - 7 \times 7 - 77/7 &= 8 \times 88 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8 &= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99 + 9)/9 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{923} &= (1+1)^{(11-1)} + 11 - 111 - 1 &= 2 \times (22^2 - 22) - 2/2 &= 33 + 33 \times 3^3 - 3/3 \\
 &= 44 + 44 \times (4 \times 4 + 4) - 4/4 &= 5 \times (55 + 5) + (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 &= (6 + 6 + 6/6) \times (66 + 6 - 6/6) \\
 &= 77 \times (77 + 7)/7 - 7/7 &= 888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8 &= 9 \times 99 + 9 + (99 + 99 + 9)/9 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{995} &= (11-1)^{(1+1+1)} - (11-1)/(1+1) &= 22 + 2 \times (22^2 + 2) + 2/2 &= 3 \times 333 - 3 - 3/3 \\
 &= 4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4) + 4 - 4/4 &= 5 \times (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5 &= 666 + 6 \times 66 - 66 - 6/6 \\
 &= (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) + 7 + 7 + 7/7 &= 888 + 88 + 8 + 88/8 &= 999 - (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)/9.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details on this work refer author's work [9]. Also for similar kind of work refer author's another works [4, 10] using **single letter a** instead of single digit. See below some examples,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{717} &:= ((aaa - a) \times aa / (a + a) + aaa + a) / a \\
 \mathbf{923} &:= (aaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a) / (aa + a) \\
 \mathbf{995} &:= (aaaa - aaa - a - a - a - a - a) \\
 &\dots \dots
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

We can bring patterned form of above six numbers given in (1) and (3). See below:

$$\begin{aligned} 5 &:= \frac{aa - a}{a + a} \\ 55 &:= \frac{aaa - a}{a + a} \\ 555 &:= \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a} \\ 5555 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a}{a + a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6 &:= \frac{aaa + a}{a + a} \\ 56 &:= \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a} \\ 556 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} \\ 5556 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a + a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 111 &:= \frac{aaa}{a} \\ 1111 &:= \frac{aaaa}{a} \\ 11111 &:= \frac{aaaaa}{a} \\ 111111 &:= \frac{aaaaaa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 717 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaa + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 1717 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaa + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 11717 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaaa + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 111717 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaaaa + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 923 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{aa + a} \\ 925923 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{aa + a} \\ 925925923 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{aa + a} \\ 925925925923 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{aa + a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 995 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 9995 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 99995 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 999995 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

Recently, author wrote natural numbers from 1 to 1000 in terms of patterned single letter similar to one given in above six numbers. The aim of this work is to write same numbers 1 to 1000 in patterns forms for each digit separately. This what we have in the section below.

2 Single Digits Pattern

This section brings natural numbers from 1 to 1000 written in patterned form for each digit 1 to 9.

$$\blacktriangleright \quad 1 := \frac{1}{1} = \frac{2}{2} = \frac{3}{3} = \frac{4}{4} = \frac{5}{5} = \frac{6}{6} = \frac{7}{7} = \frac{8}{8} = \frac{9}{9}$$

$$11 := \frac{11}{1} = \frac{22}{2} = \frac{33}{3} = \frac{44}{4} = \frac{55}{5} = \frac{66}{6} = \frac{77}{7} = \frac{88}{8} = \frac{99}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{111} := \frac{111}{1} = \frac{222}{2} = \frac{333}{3} = \frac{444}{4} = \frac{555}{5} = \frac{666}{6} = \frac{777}{7} = \frac{888}{8} = \frac{999}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1111} := \frac{1111}{1} = \frac{2222}{2} = \frac{3333}{3} = \frac{4444}{4} = \frac{5555}{5} = \frac{6666}{6} = \frac{7777}{7} = \frac{8888}{8} = \frac{9999}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{2} := \frac{1+1}{1} = \frac{2+2}{2} = \frac{3+3}{3} = \frac{4+4}{4} = \frac{5+5}{5} = \frac{6+6}{6} = \frac{7+7}{7} = \frac{8+8}{8} = \frac{9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{12} := \frac{11+1}{1} = \frac{22+2}{2} = \frac{33+3}{3} = \frac{44+4}{4} = \frac{55+5}{5} = \frac{66+6}{6} = \frac{77+7}{7} = \frac{88+8}{8} = \frac{99+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{112} := \frac{111+1}{1} = \frac{222+2}{2} = \frac{333+3}{3} = \frac{444+4}{4} = \frac{555+5}{5} = \frac{666+6}{6} = \frac{777+7}{7} = \frac{888+8}{8} = \frac{999+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1112} := \frac{1111+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3} = \frac{4444+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6} = \frac{7777+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{3} := \frac{1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3+3+3}{3} = \frac{4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6+6+6}{6} = \frac{7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{13} := \frac{11+1+1}{1} = \frac{22+2+2}{2} = \frac{33+3+3}{3} = \frac{44+4+4}{4} = \frac{55+5+5}{5} = \frac{66+6+6}{6} = \frac{77+7+7}{7} = \frac{88+8+8}{8} = \frac{99+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{113} := \frac{111+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+3+3}{3} = \frac{444+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+6+6}{6} = \frac{777+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1113} := \frac{1111+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3+3}{3} = \frac{4444+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6+6}{6} = \frac{7777+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9+9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{4} := \frac{1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{7+7+7+7}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{14} := \frac{11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{77+7+7+7}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{114} := \frac{111+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{444+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{777+7+7+7}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{888+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1114 &:= \frac{1111+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{4444+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{7777+7+7+7}{7} \\ &:= \frac{8888+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 5 := \frac{11-1}{1+1} = \frac{22-2}{2+2} = \frac{33-3}{3+3} = \frac{44-4}{4+4} = \frac{55-5}{5+5} = \frac{66-6}{6+6} = \frac{77-7}{7+7} = \frac{88-8}{8+8} = \frac{99-9}{9+9}$$

$$55 := \frac{111-1}{1+1} = \frac{222-2}{2+2} = \frac{333-3}{3+3} = \frac{444-4}{4+4} = \frac{555-5}{5+5} = \frac{666-6}{6+6} = \frac{777-7}{7+7} = \frac{888-8}{8+8} = \frac{999-9}{9+9}$$

$$555 := \frac{1111-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333-3}{3+3} = \frac{4444-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666-6}{6+6} = \frac{7777-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999-9}{9+9}$$

$$5555 := \frac{11111-1}{1+1} = \frac{22222-2}{2+2} = \frac{33333-3}{3+3} = \frac{44444-4}{4+4} = \frac{55555-5}{5+5} = \frac{66666-6}{6+6} = \frac{77777-7}{7+7} = \frac{88888-8}{8+8} = \frac{99999-9}{9+9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 6 := \frac{11+1}{1+1} = \frac{22+2}{2+2} = \frac{33+3}{3+3} = \frac{44+4}{4+4} = \frac{55+5}{5+5} = \frac{66+6}{6+6} = \frac{77+7}{7+7} = \frac{88+8}{8+8} = \frac{99+9}{9+9}$$

$$56 := \frac{111+1}{1+1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3} = \frac{444+4}{4+4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6} = \frac{777+7}{7+7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9}$$

$$556 := \frac{1111+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} = \frac{4444+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} = \frac{7777+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9}$$

$$5556 := \frac{11111+1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} = \frac{44444+4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} = \frac{77777+7}{7+7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 7 &:= \frac{11+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{22+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{33+3+3+3}{3+3} = \frac{44+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{55+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{66+6+6+6}{6+6} = \frac{77+7+7+7}{7+7} \\ &:= \frac{88+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{99+9+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 57 &:= \frac{111+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{222+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{333+3+3+3}{3+3} = \frac{444+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{555+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{666+6+6+6}{6+6} = \frac{777+7+7+7}{7+7} \\ &:= \frac{888+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{999+9+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$557 := \frac{1111+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+3+3+3}{3+3} = \frac{4444+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666+6+6+6}{6+6} = \frac{7777+7+7+7}{7+7}$$

$$:= \frac{8888+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+9+9+9}{9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5557 &:= \frac{11111+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+3+3+3}{3+3} = \frac{44444+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{66666+6+6+6}{6+6} = \frac{77777+7+7+7}{7+7} \\ &:= \frac{88888+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{99999+9+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 8 &:= \frac{11-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33-3-3-3}{3} = \frac{44-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98 &:= \frac{111-11-1-1}{1} = \frac{222-22-2-2}{2} = \frac{333-33-3-3}{3} = \frac{444-44-4-4}{4} = \frac{555-55-5-5}{5} = \frac{666-66-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777-77-7-7}{7} = \frac{888-88-8-8}{8} = \frac{999-99-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 998 &:= \frac{1111-111-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222-222-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333-333-3-3}{3} = \frac{4444-444-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555-555-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666-666-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-777-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888-888-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999-999-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9998 &:= \frac{11111-1111-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2222-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3333-3-3}{3} = \frac{44444-4444-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5555-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6666-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-7777-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888-8888-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999-9999-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 &:= \frac{11-1-1}{1} = \frac{22-2-2}{2} = \frac{33-3-3}{3} = \frac{44-4-4}{4} = \frac{55-5-5}{5} = \frac{66-6-6}{6} = \frac{77-7-7}{7} \\ &:= \frac{88-8-8}{8} = \frac{99-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 99 &:= \frac{111-11-1}{1} = \frac{222-22-2}{2} = \frac{333-33-3}{3} = \frac{444-44-4}{4} = \frac{555-55-5}{5} = \frac{666-66-6}{6} = \frac{777-77-7}{7} \\ &:= \frac{888-88-8}{8} = \frac{999-99-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 999 &:= \frac{1111-111-1}{1} = \frac{2222-222-2}{2} = \frac{3333-333-3}{3} = \frac{4444-444-4}{4} = \frac{5555-555-5}{5} = \frac{6666-666-6}{6} = \frac{7777-777-7}{7} \\ &:= \frac{8888-888-8}{8} = \frac{9999-999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$9999 := \frac{11111-1111-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2222-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3333-3}{3} = \frac{44444-4444-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5555-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6666-6}{6} = \frac{77777-7777-7}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{88888 - 8888 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{10} := \frac{11-1}{1} = \frac{22-2}{2} = \frac{33-3}{3} = \frac{44-4}{4} = \frac{55-5}{5} = \frac{66-6}{6} = \frac{77-7}{7} = \frac{88-8}{8} = \frac{99-9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{110} := \frac{111-1}{1} = \frac{222-2}{2} = \frac{333-3}{3} = \frac{444-4}{4} = \frac{555-5}{5} = \frac{666-6}{6} = \frac{777-7}{7} = \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{999-9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1110} := \frac{1111-1}{1} = \frac{2222-2}{2} = \frac{3333-3}{3} = \frac{4444-4}{4} = \frac{5555-5}{5} = \frac{6666-6}{6} = \frac{7777-7}{7} = \frac{8888-8}{8} = \frac{9999-9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{11110} := \frac{11111-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3}{3} = \frac{44444-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6}{6} = \frac{77777-7}{7} = \frac{88888-8}{8} = \frac{99999-9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{11} := \frac{11}{1} = \frac{22}{2} = \frac{33}{3} = \frac{44}{4} = \frac{55}{5} = \frac{66}{6} = \frac{77}{7} = \frac{88}{8} = \frac{99}{9}$$

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$$\mathbf{1111} := \frac{1111}{1} = \frac{2222}{2} = \frac{3333}{3} = \frac{4444}{4} = \frac{5555}{5} = \frac{6666}{6} = \frac{7777}{7} = \frac{8888}{8} = \frac{9999}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{11111} := \frac{11111}{1} = \frac{22222}{2} = \frac{33333}{3} = \frac{44444}{4} = \frac{55555}{5} = \frac{66666}{6} = \frac{77777}{7} = \frac{88888}{8} = \frac{99999}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{12} := \frac{11+1}{1} = \frac{22+2}{2} = \frac{33+3}{3} = \frac{44+4}{4} = \frac{55+5}{5} = \frac{66+6}{6} = \frac{77+7}{7} = \frac{88+8}{8} = \frac{99+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{112} := \frac{111+1}{1} = \frac{222+2}{2} = \frac{333+3}{3} = \frac{444+4}{4} = \frac{555+5}{5} = \frac{666+6}{6} = \frac{777+7}{7} = \frac{888+8}{8} = \frac{999+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1112} := \frac{1111+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3} = \frac{4444+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6} = \frac{7777+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9}$$

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$$\mathbf{113} := \frac{111+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+3+3}{3} = \frac{444+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+6+6}{6} = \frac{777+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1113} := \frac{1111+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3+3}{3} = \frac{4444+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6+6}{6} = \frac{7777+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{11113} := \frac{11111+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3+3}{3} = \frac{44444+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6+6}{6} = \frac{77777+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9+9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{14} := \frac{11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{77+7+7+7}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{114} := \frac{111+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{444+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{777+7+7+7}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{888+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1114} := \frac{1111+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{4444+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{7777+7+7+7}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{8888+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{11114} := \frac{11111+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{44444+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{77777+7+7+7}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{88888+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{15} := \frac{11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33+3+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66+6+6+6+6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99+9+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{115} := \frac{111+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+3+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{444+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+6+6+6+6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{777+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+9+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1115} := \frac{1111+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{4444+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6+6+6+6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{7777+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11115} &:= \frac{11111+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{44444+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{16} &:= \frac{11-1}{1+1} + \frac{11}{1} = \frac{22-2}{2+2} + \frac{22}{2} = \frac{33-3}{3+3} + \frac{33}{3} = \frac{44-4}{4+4} + \frac{44}{4} = \frac{55-5}{5+5} + \frac{55}{5} = \frac{66-6}{6+6} + \frac{66}{6} = \frac{77-7}{7+7} + \frac{77}{7} \\ &:= \frac{88-8}{8+8} + \frac{88}{8} = \frac{99-9}{9+9} + \frac{99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{116} &:= \frac{11-1}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1} = \frac{22-2}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2} = \frac{33-3}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3} = \frac{44-4}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4} = \frac{55-5}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5} = \frac{66-6}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6} = \frac{77-7}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7} \\ &:= \frac{88-8}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8} = \frac{99-9}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1116} &:= \frac{11-1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{1} = \frac{22-2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{2} = \frac{33-3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{3} = \frac{44-4}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{4} = \frac{55-5}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{5} = \frac{66-6}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{6} = \frac{77-7}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{7} \\ &:= \frac{88-8}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{8} = \frac{99-9}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11116} &:= \frac{11-1}{1+1} + \frac{11111}{1} = \frac{22-2}{2+2} + \frac{22222}{2} = \frac{33-3}{3+3} + \frac{33333}{3} = \frac{44-4}{4+4} + \frac{44444}{4} = \frac{55-5}{5+5} + \frac{55555}{5} = \frac{66-6}{6+6} + \frac{66666}{6} = \frac{77-7}{7+7} + \frac{77777}{7} \\ &:= \frac{88-8}{8+8} + \frac{88888}{8} = \frac{99-9}{9+9} + \frac{99999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{17} &:= \frac{11+1}{1+1} + \frac{11}{1} = \frac{22+2}{2+2} + \frac{22}{2} = \frac{33+3}{3+3} + \frac{33}{3} = \frac{44+4}{4+4} + \frac{44}{4} = \frac{55+5}{5+5} + \frac{55}{5} = \frac{66+6}{6+6} + \frac{66}{6} = \frac{77+7}{7+7} + \frac{77}{7} \\ &:= \frac{88+8}{8+8} + \frac{88}{8} = \frac{99+9}{9+9} + \frac{99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{117} &:= \frac{11+1}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1} = \frac{22+2}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2} = \frac{33+3}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3} = \frac{44+4}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4} = \frac{55+5}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5} = \frac{66+6}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6} = \frac{77+7}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7} \\ &:= \frac{88+8}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8} = \frac{99+9}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1117} &:= \frac{11+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{1} = \frac{22+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{2} = \frac{33+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{3} = \frac{44+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{4} = \frac{55+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{5} = \frac{66+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{6} = \frac{77+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{7} \\ &:= \frac{88+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{8} = \frac{99+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11117} &:= \frac{11+1}{1+1} + \frac{11111}{1} = \frac{22+2}{2+2} + \frac{22222}{2} = \frac{33+3}{3+3} + \frac{33333}{3} = \frac{44+4}{4+4} + \frac{44444}{4} = \frac{55+5}{5+5} + \frac{55555}{5} = \frac{66+6}{6+6} + \frac{66666}{6} = \frac{77+7}{7+7} + \frac{77777}{7} \\ &:= \frac{88+8}{8+8} + \frac{88888}{8} = \frac{99+9}{9+9} + \frac{99999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 18 &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 198 &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times (11+11)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times (22+22)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times (33+33)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times (44+44)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times (55+55)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times (66+66)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times (77+77)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times (88+88)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times (99+99)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1998 &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times (111+111)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times (222+222)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times (333+333)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times (444+444)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times (555+555)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times (666+666)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times (777+777)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times (888+888)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times (999+999)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19998 &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times (1111+1111)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times (2222+2222)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times (3333+3333)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times (4444+4444)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times (5555+5555)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times (6666+6666)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times (7777+7777)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times (8888+8888)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times (9999+9999)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 19 &:= \frac{11+11-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22+22-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33+33-3-3-3}{3} = \frac{44+44-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55+55-5-5-5}{5} \\ &:= \frac{66+66-6-6-6}{6} = \frac{77+77-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88+88-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99+99-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 119 &:= \frac{111+11-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{222+22-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{333+33-3-3-3}{3} = \frac{444+44-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{555+55-5-5-5}{5} \\ &:= \frac{666+66-6-6-6}{6} = \frac{777+77-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{888+88-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{999+99-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1119 &:= \frac{1111+11-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222+22-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333+33-3-3-3}{3} = \frac{4444+44-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555+55-5-5-5}{5} \\ &:= \frac{6666+66-6-6-6}{6} = \frac{7777+77-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888+88-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999+99-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 11119 &:= \frac{11111+11-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222+22-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333+33-3-3-3}{3} = \frac{44444+44-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555+55-5-5-5}{5} \\ &:= \frac{66666+66-6-6-6}{6} = \frac{77777+77-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888+88-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999+99-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad 20 := \frac{11+11-1-1}{1} = \frac{22+22-2-2}{2} = \frac{33+33-3-3}{3} = \frac{44+44-4-4}{4} = \frac{55+55-5-5}{5} = \frac{66+66-6-6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{77+77-7-7}{7} = \frac{88+88-8-8}{8} = \frac{99+99-9-9}{9}$$

$$120 := \frac{111+11-1-1}{1} = \frac{222+22-2-2}{2} = \frac{333+33-3-3}{3} = \frac{444+44-4-4}{4} = \frac{555+55-5-5}{5} = \frac{666+66-6-6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{777+77-7-7}{7} = \frac{888+88-8-8}{8} = \frac{999+99-9-9}{9}$$

$$1120 := \frac{1111+11-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222+22-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333+33-3-3}{3} = \frac{4444+44-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555+55-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666+66-6-6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{7777+77-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888+88-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999+99-9-9}{9}$$

$$11120 := \frac{11111+11-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222+22-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333+33-3-3}{3} = \frac{44444+44-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555+55-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666+66-6-6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{77777+77-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888+88-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999+99-9-9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad 21 := \frac{11+11-1}{1} = \frac{22+22-2}{2} = \frac{33+33-3}{3} = \frac{44+44-4}{4} = \frac{55+55-5}{5} = \frac{66+66-6}{6} = \frac{77+77-7}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{88+88-8}{8} = \frac{99+99-9}{9}$$

$$121 := \frac{111+11-1}{1} = \frac{222+22-2}{2} = \frac{333+33-3}{3} = \frac{444+44-4}{4} = \frac{555+55-5}{5} = \frac{666+66-6}{6} = \frac{777+77-7}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{888+88-8}{8} = \frac{999+99-9}{9}$$

$$1121 := \frac{1111+11-1}{1} = \frac{2222+22-2}{2} = \frac{3333+33-3}{3} = \frac{4444+44-4}{4} = \frac{5555+55-5}{5} = \frac{6666+66-6}{6} = \frac{7777+77-7}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{8888+88-8}{8} = \frac{9999+99-9}{9}$$

$$11121 := \frac{11111+11-1}{1} = \frac{22222+22-2}{2} = \frac{33333+33-3}{3} = \frac{44444+44-4}{4} = \frac{55555+55-5}{5} = \frac{66666+66-6}{6} = \frac{77777+77-7}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{88888+88-8}{8} = \frac{99999+99-9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad 22 := \frac{11+11}{1} = \frac{22+22}{2} = \frac{33+33}{3} = \frac{44+44}{4} = \frac{55+55}{5} = \frac{66+66}{6} = \frac{77+77}{7} = \frac{88+88}{8} = \frac{99+99}{9}$$

$$122 := \frac{111+11}{1} = \frac{222+22}{2} = \frac{333+33}{3} = \frac{444+44}{4} = \frac{555+55}{5} = \frac{666+66}{6} = \frac{777+77}{7} = \frac{888+88}{8} = \frac{999+99}{9}$$

$$1222 := \frac{1111+111}{1} = \frac{2222+222}{2} = \frac{3333+333}{3} = \frac{4444+444}{4} = \frac{5555+555}{5} = \frac{6666+666}{6} = \frac{7777+777}{7} = \frac{8888+888}{8} = \frac{9999+999}{9}$$

$$12222 := \frac{11111+1111}{1} = \frac{22222+2222}{2} = \frac{33333+3333}{3} = \frac{44444+4444}{4} = \frac{55555+5555}{5} = \frac{66666+6666}{6} = \frac{77777+7777}{7} = \frac{88888+8888}{8} = \frac{99999+9999}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 23 := \frac{11+11+1}{1} = \frac{22+22+2}{2} = \frac{33+33+3}{3} = \frac{44+44+4}{4} = \frac{55+55+5}{5} = \frac{66+66+6}{6} = \frac{77+77+7}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{88+88+8}{8} = \frac{99+99+9}{9}$$

$$123 := \frac{111+11+1}{1} = \frac{222+22+2}{2} = \frac{333+33+3}{3} = \frac{444+44+4}{4} = \frac{555+55+5}{5} = \frac{666+66+6}{6} = \frac{777+77+7}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{888+88+8}{8} = \frac{999+99+9}{9}$$

$$1223 := \frac{1111+111+1}{1} = \frac{2222+222+2}{2} = \frac{3333+333+3}{3} = \frac{4444+444+4}{4} = \frac{5555+555+5}{5} = \frac{6666+666+6}{6} = \frac{7777+777+7}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{8888+888+8}{8} = \frac{9999+999+9}{9}$$

$$12223 := \frac{11111+1111+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2222+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3333+3}{3} = \frac{44444+4444+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5555+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6666+6}{6} = \frac{77777+7777+7}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{88888+8888+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9999+9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 24 := \frac{11+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{22+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{33+33+3+3}{3} = \frac{44+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{55+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{66+66+6+6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{77+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{88+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{99+99+9+9}{9}$$

$$124 := \frac{111+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+33+3+3}{3} = \frac{444+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+66+6+6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{777+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+99+9+9}{9}$$

$$1224 := \frac{1111+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+33+3+3}{3} = \frac{4444+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+66+6+6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{7777+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+99+9+9}{9}$$

$$11124 := \frac{11111+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+33+3+3}{3} = \frac{44444+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+66+6+6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{77777+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+99+9+9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{25} := \frac{11+11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22+22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33+33+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{44+44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55+55+5+5+5}{5}$$

$$:= \frac{66+66+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{77+77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88+88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99+99+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{125} := \frac{111+11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+33+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{444+44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+55+5+5+5}{5}$$

$$:= \frac{666+66+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{777+77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+99+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1125} := \frac{1111+11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+33+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{4444+44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+55+5+5+5}{5}$$

$$:= \frac{6666+66+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{7777+77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+99+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{11125} := \frac{11111+11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+33+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{44444+44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+55+5+5+5}{5}$$

$$:= \frac{66666+66+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{77777+77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+99+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{26} := \frac{(11+1+1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} = \frac{(44+4+4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(66+6+6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} = \frac{(77+7+7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\mathbf{226} := \frac{(111+1+1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} = \frac{(444+4+4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(666+6+6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} = \frac{(777+7+7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\mathbf{2226} := \frac{(1111+1+1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} = \frac{(4444+4+4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5+5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(6666+6+6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} = \frac{(7777+7+7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\mathbf{22226} := \frac{(11111+1+1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} = \frac{(44444+4+4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5}$$

$$:= \frac{(66666+6+6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} = \frac{(77777+7+7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{27} := \frac{111-1-1-1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{222-2-2-2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{333-3-3-3}{3+3+3+3} = \frac{444-4-4-4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{555-5-5-5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{666-6-6-6}{6+6+6+6} = \frac{777-7-7-7}{7+7+7+7}$$

$$:= \frac{888-8-8-8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{999-9-9-9}{9+9+9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 277 &:= \frac{1111-1-1-1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{2222-2-2-2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{3333-3-3-3}{3+3+3+3} = \frac{4444-4-4-4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{5555-5-5-5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{6666-6-6-6}{6+6+6+6} = \frac{7777-7-7-7}{7+7+7+7} \\ &:= \frac{8888-8-8-8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{9999-9-9-9}{9+9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2777 &:= \frac{11111-1-1-1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{22222-2-2-2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{33333-3-3-3}{3+3+3+3} = \frac{44444-4-4-4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{55555-5-5-5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{66666-6-6-6}{6+6+6+6} = \frac{77777-7-7-7}{7+7+7+7} \\ &:= \frac{88888-8-8-8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{99999-9-9-9}{9+9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27777 &:= \frac{111111-1-1-1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{222222-2-2-2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{333333-3-3-3}{3+3+3+3} = \frac{444444-4-4-4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{555555-5-5-5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{666666-6-6-6}{6+6+6+6} = \frac{777777-7-7-7}{7+7+7+7} \\ &:= \frac{888888-8-8-8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{999999-9-9-9}{9+9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 28 := \frac{111+1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3+3+3} = \frac{444+4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6+6+6} = \frac{777+7}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9+9+9}$$

$$228 := \frac{1111+1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3+3+3} = \frac{4444+4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6+6+6} = \frac{7777+7}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9+9+9}$$

$$2778 := \frac{11111+1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3+3+3} = \frac{44444+4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6+6+6} = \frac{77777+7}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9+9+9}$$

$$27778 := \frac{111111+1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3+3+3} = \frac{444444+4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6+6+6} = \frac{777777+7}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9+9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 29 &:= \frac{11+11+11-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22+22+22-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33+33+33-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44+44+44-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55+55+55-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66+66+66-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77+77+77-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88+88+88-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99+99+99-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 129 &:= \frac{11+11+111-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22+22+222-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33+33+333-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44+44+444-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55+55+555-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66+66+666-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77+77+777-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88+88+888-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99+99+999-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$1129 := \frac{11+11+1111-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22+22+2222-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33+33+3333-3-3-3-3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11129} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{30} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{130} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1130} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11130} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{31} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3} = \frac{44 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} \\ &:= \frac{66 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} = \frac{77 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{131} := \frac{11 + 11 + 111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 333 - 3 - 3}{3} = \frac{44 + 44 + 444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 555 - 5 - 5}{5}$$

$$:= \frac{66+66+666-6-6}{6} = \frac{77+77+777-7-7}{7} = \frac{88+88+888-8-8}{8} = \frac{99+99+999-9-9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1131} := \frac{11+11+1111-1-1}{1} = \frac{22+22+2222-2-2}{2} = \frac{33+33+3333-3-3}{3} = \frac{44+44+4444-4-4}{4} = \frac{55+55+5555-5-5}{5}$$

$$:= \frac{66+66+6666-6-6}{6} = \frac{77+77+7777-7-7}{7} = \frac{88+88+8888-8-8}{8} = \frac{99+99+9999-9-9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{11131} := \frac{11+11+11111-1-1}{1} = \frac{22+22+22222-2-2}{2} = \frac{33+33+33333-3-3}{3} = \frac{44+44+44444-4-4}{4} = \frac{55+55+55555-5-5}{5}$$

$$:= \frac{66+66+66666-6-6}{6} = \frac{77+77+77777-7-7}{7} = \frac{88+88+88888-8-8}{8} = \frac{99+99+99999-9-9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{32} := \frac{11+11+11-1}{1} = \frac{22+22+22-2}{2} = \frac{33+33+33-3}{3} = \frac{44+44+44-4}{4} = \frac{55+55+55-5}{5} = \frac{66+66+66-6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{77+77+77-7}{7} = \frac{88+88+88-8}{8} = \frac{99+99+99-9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{132} := \frac{11+11+111-1}{1} = \frac{22+22+222-2}{2} = \frac{33+33+333-3}{3} = \frac{44+44+444-4}{4} = \frac{55+55+555-5}{5} = \frac{66+66+666-6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{77+77+777-7}{7} = \frac{88+88+888-8}{8} = \frac{99+99+999-9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1132} := \frac{11+11+1111-1}{1} = \frac{22+22+2222-2}{2} = \frac{33+33+3333-3}{3} = \frac{44+44+4444-4}{4} = \frac{55+55+5555-5}{5} = \frac{66+66+6666-6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{77+77+7777-7}{7} = \frac{88+88+8888-8}{8} = \frac{99+99+9999-9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{11132} := \frac{11+11+11111-1}{1} = \frac{22+22+22222-2}{2} = \frac{33+33+33333-3}{3} = \frac{44+44+44444-4}{4} = \frac{55+55+55555-5}{5} = \frac{66+66+66666-6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{77+77+77777-7}{7} = \frac{88+88+88888-8}{8} = \frac{99+99+99999-9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{33} := \frac{11+11+11}{1} = \frac{22+22+22}{2} = \frac{33+33+33}{3} = \frac{44+44+44}{4} = \frac{55+55+55}{5} = \frac{66+66+66}{6} = \frac{77+77+77}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{88+88+88}{8} = \frac{99+99+99}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{133} := \frac{11+11+111}{1} = \frac{22+22+222}{2} = \frac{33+33+333}{3} = \frac{44+44+444}{4} = \frac{55+55+555}{5} = \frac{66+66+666}{6} = \frac{77+77+777}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{88+88+888}{8} = \frac{99+99+999}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1133} := \frac{11+11+1111}{1} = \frac{22+22+2222}{2} = \frac{33+33+3333}{3} = \frac{44+44+4444}{4} = \frac{55+55+5555}{5} = \frac{66+66+6666}{6} = \frac{77+77+7777}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{88 + 88 + 8888}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 9999}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{11133} := \frac{11 + 11 + 11111}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 22222}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 33333}{3} = \frac{44 + 44 + 44444}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 55555}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 66666}{6} = \frac{77 + 77 + 77777}{7}$$

$$:= \frac{88 + 88 + 88888}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 99999}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{34} := \frac{11 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} = \frac{44 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{77 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{134} := \frac{11 + 11 + 111 + 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 222 + 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 333 + 3}{3} = \frac{44 + 44 + 444 + 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 555 + 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 666 + 6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{77 + 77 + 777 + 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 888 + 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 999 + 9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1134} := \frac{11 + 11 + 1111 + 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 2222 + 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 3333 + 3}{3} = \frac{44 + 44 + 4444 + 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 5555 + 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 6666 + 6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{77 + 77 + 7777 + 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 8888 + 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 9999 + 9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{11134} := \frac{11 + 11 + 11111 + 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 22222 + 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 33333 + 3}{3} = \frac{44 + 44 + 44444 + 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 55555 + 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 66666 + 6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{77 + 77 + 77777 + 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 88888 + 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 99999 + 9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{35} := \frac{11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} = \frac{44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5}$$

$$:= \frac{66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} = \frac{77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{135} := \frac{11 + 11 + 111 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 222 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 333 + 3 + 3}{3} = \frac{44 + 44 + 444 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 555 + 5 + 5}{5}$$

$$:= \frac{66 + 66 + 666 + 6 + 6}{6} = \frac{77 + 77 + 777 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 888 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 999 + 9 + 9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1135} := \frac{11 + 11 + 1111 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 2222 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 3333 + 3 + 3}{3} = \frac{44 + 44 + 4444 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 5555 + 5 + 5}{5}$$

$$:= \frac{66 + 66 + 6666 + 6 + 6}{6} = \frac{77 + 77 + 7777 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 8888 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 9999 + 9 + 9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{11135} := \frac{11 + 11 + 11111 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 22222 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 33333 + 3 + 3}{3} = \frac{44 + 44 + 44444 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 55555 + 5 + 5}{5}$$

$$:= \frac{66+66+66666+6+6}{6} = \frac{77+77+77777+7+7}{7} = \frac{88+88+88888+8+8}{8} = \frac{99+99+99999+9+9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{36} := \frac{11+11+11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22+22+22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33+33+33+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{44+44+44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55+55+55+5+5+5}{5}$$

$$:= \frac{66+66+66+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{77+77+77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88+88+88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99+99+99+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{136} := \frac{11+11+111+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22+22+222+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33+33+333+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{44+44+444+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55+55+555+5+5+5}{5}$$

$$:= \frac{66+66+666+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{77+77+777+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88+88+888+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99+99+999+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1136} := \frac{11+11+1111+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22+22+2222+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33+33+3333+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{44+44+4444+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55+55+5555+5+5+5}{5}$$

$$:= \frac{66+66+6666+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{77+77+7777+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88+88+8888+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99+99+9999+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{11136} := \frac{11+11+11111+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22+22+22222+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33+33+33333+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{44+44+44444+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55+55+55555+5+5+5}{5}$$

$$:= \frac{66+66+66666+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{77+77+77777+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88+88+88888+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99+99+99999+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{37} := \frac{111}{1+1+1} = \frac{222}{2+2+2} = \frac{333}{3+3+3} = \frac{444}{4+4+4} = \frac{555}{5+5+5} = \frac{666}{6+6+6} = \frac{777}{7+7+7} = \frac{888}{8+8+8} = \frac{999}{9+9+9}$$

$$\mathbf{370} := \frac{1111-1}{1+1+1} = \frac{2222-2}{2+2+2} = \frac{3333-3}{3+3+3} = \frac{4444-4}{4+4+4} = \frac{5555-5}{5+5+5} = \frac{6666-6}{6+6+6} = \frac{7777-7}{7+7+7} = \frac{8888-8}{8+8+8} = \frac{9999-9}{9+9+9}$$

$$\mathbf{3700} := \frac{11111-11}{1+1+1} = \frac{22222-22}{2+2+2} = \frac{33333-33}{3+3+3} = \frac{44444-44}{4+4+4} = \frac{55555-55}{5+5+5} = \frac{66666-66}{6+6+6} = \frac{77777-77}{7+7+7} = \frac{88888-88}{8+8+8} = \frac{99999-99}{9+9+9}$$

$$\mathbf{37000} := \frac{111111-111}{1+1+1} = \frac{222222-222}{2+2+2} = \frac{333333-333}{3+3+3} = \frac{444444-444}{4+4+4} = \frac{555555-555}{5+5+5} = \frac{666666-666}{6+6+6} = \frac{777777-777}{7+7+7} = \frac{888888-888}{8+8+8} = \frac{999999-999}{9+9+9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{38} := \frac{111-11-11-11-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{222-22-22-22-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{333-33-33-33-3-3}{3+3}$$

$$:= \frac{444-44-44-44-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{555-55-55-55-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{666-66-66-66-6-6}{6+6}$$

$$:= \frac{777-77-77-77-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{888-88-88-88-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{999-99-99-99-9-9}{9+9}$$

$$\mathbf{538} := \frac{1111-11-11-11-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222-22-22-22-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333-33-33-33-3-3}{3+3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5538} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55538} &:= \frac{111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{39} &:= \frac{111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3 + 3} = \frac{444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6 + 6} = \frac{777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{539} &:= \frac{1111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3 + 3} = \frac{4444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{6666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6 + 6} = \frac{7777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5539} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3 + 3} = \frac{44444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{66666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6 + 6} = \frac{77777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55539} &:= \frac{111111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3 + 3} = \frac{444444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{666666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6 + 6} = \frac{777777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{40} &:= \frac{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 440 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times (111-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times (222-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times (333-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times (444-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times (555-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times (666-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times (777-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times (888-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times (999-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4440 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times (1111-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times (2222-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times (3333-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times (4444-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times (5555-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times (666-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times (7777-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times (8888-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times (9999-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44440 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times (11111-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times (22222-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times (33333-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times (44444-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times (55555-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times (66666-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times (77777-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times (88888-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times (99999-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 41 &:= \frac{111+11+1}{1+1+1} = \frac{222+22+2}{2+2+2} = \frac{333+33+3}{3+3+3} = \frac{444+44+4}{4+4+4} = \frac{555+55+5}{5+5+5} \\ &:= \frac{666+66+6}{6+6+6} = \frac{777+77+7}{7+7+7} = \frac{888+88+8}{8+8+8} = \frac{999+99+9}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 411 &:= \frac{1111+111+11}{1+1+1} = \frac{2222+222+22}{2+2+2} = \frac{3333+333+33}{3+3+3} = \frac{4444+444+44}{4+4+4} = \frac{5555+555+55}{5+5+5} \\ &:= \frac{6666+666+66}{6+6+6} = \frac{7777+777+77}{7+7+7} = \frac{8888+888+88}{8+8+8} = \frac{9999+999+99}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4111 &:= \frac{11111+1111+111}{1+1+1} = \frac{22222+2222+222}{2+2+2} = \frac{33333+3333+333}{3+3+3} = \frac{44444+4444+444}{4+4+4} = \frac{55555+5555+555}{5+5+5} \\ &:= \frac{66666+6666+666}{6+6+6} = \frac{77777+7777+777}{7+7+7} = \frac{88888+8888+888}{8+8+8} = \frac{99999+9999+999}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41111 &:= \frac{111111+11111+1111}{1+1+1} = \frac{222222+22222+2222}{2+2+2} = \frac{333333+33333+3333}{3+3+3} = \frac{444444+44444+4444}{4+4+4} = \frac{555555+55555+5555}{5+5+5} \\ &:= \frac{666666+66666+6666}{6+6+6} = \frac{777777+77777+7777}{7+7+7} = \frac{888888+88888+8888}{8+8+8} = \frac{999999+99999+9999}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 42 &:= \frac{(11+11-1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22-2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33-3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} = \frac{(44+44-4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55-5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(66+66-6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} = \frac{(77+77-7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88-8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99-9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{242} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} = \frac{(444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} = \frac{(777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2242} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} = \frac{(4444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(6666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} = \frac{(7777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22242} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} = \frac{(44444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(66666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} = \frac{(77777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{43} &:= \frac{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{443} &:= \frac{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times 222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times 333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times 444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times 555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times 666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times 777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times 888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times 999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4443} &:= \frac{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times 1111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times 2222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times 3333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times 4444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times 5555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times 6666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times 7777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times 8888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times 9999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{44443} &:= \frac{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times 11111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times 22222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times 33333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times 44444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times 55555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times 66666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times 77777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times 88888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times 99999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{44} := \frac{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{444} &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4444} &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 1111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 2222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 3333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 4444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 5555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 6666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 7777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 8888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 9999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{44444} &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 11111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 22222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 33333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 44444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 55555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 66666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 77777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 88888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 99999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{45} &:= \frac{111+1}{1+1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3} - \frac{33}{3} = \frac{444+4}{4+4} - \frac{44}{4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5} - \frac{55}{5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6} - \frac{66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+7}{7+7} - \frac{77}{7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8} - \frac{88}{8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9} - \frac{99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{445} &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1} - \frac{111}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} - \frac{222}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} - \frac{333}{3} = \frac{4444+4}{4+4} - \frac{444}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} - \frac{555}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} - \frac{666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7} - \frac{777}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} - \frac{888}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} - \frac{999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4445} &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1} - \frac{1111}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} - \frac{2222}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} - \frac{3333}{3} = \frac{44444+4}{4+4} - \frac{4444}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} - \frac{5555}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} - \frac{6666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} - \frac{7777}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} - \frac{8888}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} - \frac{9999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{44445} &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} - \frac{11111}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} - \frac{22222}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} - \frac{33333}{3} = \frac{444444+4}{4+4} - \frac{44444}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} - \frac{55555}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} - \frac{66666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} - \frac{77777}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} - \frac{88888}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} - \frac{99999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 46 &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} = \frac{(44+44+4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(66+66+6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} = \frac{(77+77+7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 246 &:= \frac{(111+11+1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+22+2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+33+3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} = \frac{(444+44+4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+55+5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(666+66+6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} = \frac{(777+77+7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+88+8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+99+9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2246 &:= \frac{(1111+11+1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22+2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33+3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} = \frac{(4444+44+4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55+5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(6666+66+6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} = \frac{(7777+77+7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+88+8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+99+9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22246 &:= \frac{(11111+11+1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22+2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33+3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} = \frac{(44444+44+4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55+5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(66666+66+6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} = \frac{(77777+77+7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88+8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99+9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 47 &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times (1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times (2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times (3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times (4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times (5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times (6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times (7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times (8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times (9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 247 &:= \frac{(111+11+1) \times (1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+22+2) \times (2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+33+3) \times (3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+44+4) \times (4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+55+5) \times (5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+66+6) \times (6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+77+7) \times (7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+88+8) \times (8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+99+9) \times (9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2247 &:= \frac{(1111+11+1) \times (1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22+2) \times (2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33+3) \times (3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+44+4) \times (4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55+5) \times (5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66+6) \times (6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+77+7) \times (7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+88+8) \times (8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+99+9) \times (9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22247 &:= \frac{(11111+11+1) \times (1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22+2) \times (2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33+3) \times (3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+44+4) \times (4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55+5) \times (5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66+6) \times (6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+77+7) \times (7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88+8) \times (8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99+9) \times (9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad 48 := \frac{111-11-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{222-22-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{333-33-3-3-3-3}{3+3} = \frac{444-44-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{555-55-5-5-5-5}{5+5}$$

$$:= \frac{666-66-6-6-6-6}{6+6} = \frac{777-77-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{888-88-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{999-99-9-9-9-9}{9+9}$$

$$548 := \frac{1111-11-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222-22-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333-33-3-3-3-3}{3+3} = \frac{4444-44-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555-55-5-5-5-5}{5+5}$$

$$:= \frac{6666-66-6-6-6-6}{6+6} = \frac{7777-77-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888-88-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999-99-9-9-9-9}{9+9}$$

$$5548 := \frac{11111-11-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{22222-22-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{33333-33-3-3-3-3}{3+3} = \frac{44444-44-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{55555-55-5-5-5-5}{5+5}$$

$$:= \frac{66666-66-6-6-6-6}{6+6} = \frac{77777-77-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{88888-88-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{99999-99-9-9-9-9}{9+9}$$

$$55548 := \frac{111111-11-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{222222-22-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{333333-33-3-3-3-3}{3+3} = \frac{444444-44-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{555555-55-5-5-5-5}{5+5}$$

$$:= \frac{666666-66-6-6-6-6}{6+6} = \frac{777777-77-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{888888-88-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{999999-99-9-9-9-9}{9+9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad 49 := \frac{111-11-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{222-22-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{333-33-3-3}{3+3} = \frac{444-44-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{555-55-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{666-66-6-6}{6+6}$$

$$:= \frac{777-77-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{888-88-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{999-99-9-9}{9+9}$$

$$549 := \frac{1111-11-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222-22-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333-33-3-3}{3+3} = \frac{4444-44-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555-55-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666-66-6-6}{6+6}$$

$$:= \frac{7777-77-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888-88-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999-99-9-9}{9+9}$$

$$5549 := \frac{11111-11-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{22222-22-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{33333-33-3-3}{3+3} = \frac{44444-44-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{55555-55-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{66666-66-6-6}{6+6}$$

$$:= \frac{77777-77-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{88888-88-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{99999-99-9-9}{9+9}$$

$$55549 := \frac{111111-11-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{222222-22-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{333333-33-3-3}{3+3} = \frac{444444-44-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{555555-55-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{666666-66-6-6}{6+6}$$

$$:= \frac{777777-77-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{888888-88-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{999999-99-9-9}{9+9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad 50 := \frac{111-11}{1+1} = \frac{222-22}{2+2} = \frac{333-33}{3+3} = \frac{444-44}{4+4} = \frac{555-55}{5+5} = \frac{666-66}{6+6} = \frac{777-77}{7+7} = \frac{888-88}{8+8} = \frac{999-99}{9+9}$$

$$550 := \frac{1111-11}{1+1} = \frac{2222-22}{2+2} = \frac{3333-33}{3+3} = \frac{4444-44}{4+4} = \frac{5555-55}{5+5} = \frac{6666-66}{6+6} = \frac{7777-77}{7+7} = \frac{8888-88}{8+8} = \frac{9999-99}{9+9}$$

$$5550 := \frac{11111-11}{1+1} = \frac{22222-22}{2+2} = \frac{33333-33}{3+3} = \frac{44444-44}{4+4} = \frac{55555-55}{5+5} = \frac{66666-66}{6+6} = \frac{77777-77}{7+7} = \frac{88888-88}{8+8} = \frac{99999-99}{9+9}$$

$$55550 := \frac{111111-11}{1+1} = \frac{222222-22}{2+2} = \frac{333333-33}{3+3} = \frac{444444-44}{4+4} = \frac{555555-55}{5+5} = \frac{666666-66}{6+6} = \frac{777777-77}{7+7} = \frac{888888-88}{8+8} = \frac{999999-99}{9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 51 &:= \frac{111-11+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{222-22+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{333-33+3+3}{3+3} = \frac{444-44+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{555-55+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{666-66+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777-77+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{888-88+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{999-99+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 551 &:= \frac{1111-11+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222-22+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333-33+3+3}{3+3} = \frac{4444-44+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555-55+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666-66+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-77+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888-88+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999-99+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5551 &:= \frac{11111-11+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{22222-22+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{33333-33+3+3}{3+3} = \frac{44444-44+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{55555-55+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{66666-66+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-77+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{88888-88+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{99999-99+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55551 &:= \frac{111111-11+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{222222-22+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{333333-33+3+3}{3+3} = \frac{444444-44+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{555555-55+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{666666-66+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-77+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{888888-88+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{999999-99+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 52 &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times (1+1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (2+2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (3+3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times (4+4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (5+5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times (6+6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times (7+7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (8+8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (9+9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 452 &:= \frac{(111+1+1) \times (1+1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2) \times (2+2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3) \times (3+3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4+4) \times (4+4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5) \times (5+5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6) \times (6+6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7+7) \times (7+7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8) \times (8+8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9) \times (9+9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$4452 := \frac{(1111+1+1) \times (1+1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2) \times (2+2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3) \times (3+3+3+3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{44452} &:= \frac{(11111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{53} &:= \frac{111 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{1 + 1}{7 + 7} = \frac{222 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{2 + 2}{8 + 8} = \frac{333 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{3 + 3}{9 + 9} = \frac{444 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{4 + 4}{7 + 7} = \frac{555 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{5 + 5}{6 + 6} = \frac{666 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{6 + 6}{7 + 7} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{7 + 7}{8 + 8} = \frac{888 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{8 + 8}{9 + 9} = \frac{999 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{9 + 9}{7 + 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{553} &:= \frac{1111 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{1 + 1}{7 + 7} = \frac{2222 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{2 + 2}{8 + 8} = \frac{3333 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{3 + 3}{9 + 9} = \frac{4444 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{4 + 4}{7 + 7} = \frac{5555 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{5 + 5}{6 + 6} = \frac{6666 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{6 + 6}{7 + 7} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{7 + 7}{8 + 8} = \frac{8888 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{8 + 8}{9 + 9} = \frac{9999 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{9 + 9}{7 + 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5553} &:= \frac{11111 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{1 + 1}{7 + 7} = \frac{22222 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{2 + 2}{8 + 8} = \frac{33333 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{3 + 3}{9 + 9} = \frac{44444 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{4 + 4}{7 + 7} = \frac{55555 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{5 + 5}{6 + 6} = \frac{66666 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{6 + 6}{7 + 7} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{7 + 7}{8 + 8} = \frac{88888 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{8 + 8}{9 + 9} = \frac{99999 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{9 + 9}{7 + 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55553} &:= \frac{111111 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{1 + 1}{7 + 7} = \frac{222222 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{2 + 2}{8 + 8} = \frac{333333 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{3 + 3}{9 + 9} = \frac{444444 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{4 + 4}{7 + 7} = \frac{555555 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{5 + 5}{6 + 6} = \frac{666666 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{6 + 6}{7 + 7} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{7 + 7}{8 + 8} = \frac{888888 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{8 + 8}{9 + 9} = \frac{999999 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{9 + 9}{7 + 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{54} &:= \frac{111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} = \frac{444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{554} &:= \frac{1111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} = \frac{4444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5554} &:= \frac{11111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} = \frac{44444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$55554 := \frac{111111-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{222222-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{333333-3-3-3}{3+3} = \frac{444444-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{555555-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{666666-6-6-6}{6+6}$$

$$:= \frac{777777-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{888888-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{999999-9-9-9}{9+9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 55 := \frac{111-1}{1+1} = \frac{222-2}{2+2} = \frac{333-3}{3+3} = \frac{444-4}{4+4} = \frac{555-5}{5+5} = \frac{666-6}{6+6} = \frac{777-7}{7+7} = \frac{888-8}{8+8} = \frac{999-9}{9+9}$$

$$555 := \frac{1111-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333-3}{3+3} = \frac{4444-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666-6}{6+6} = \frac{7777-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999-9}{9+9}$$

$$5555 := \frac{11111-1}{1+1} = \frac{22222-2}{2+2} = \frac{33333-3}{3+3} = \frac{44444-4}{4+4} = \frac{55555-5}{5+5} = \frac{66666-6}{6+6} = \frac{77777-7}{7+7} = \frac{88888-8}{8+8} = \frac{99999-9}{9+9}$$

$$55555 := \frac{111111-1}{1+1} = \frac{222222-2}{2+2} = \frac{333333-3}{3+3} = \frac{444444-4}{4+4} = \frac{555555-5}{5+5} = \frac{666666-6}{6+6} = \frac{777777-7}{7+7} = \frac{888888-8}{8+8} = \frac{999999-9}{9+9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 56 := \frac{111+1}{1+1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3} = \frac{444+4}{4+4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6} = \frac{777+7}{7+7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9}$$

$$556 := \frac{1111+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} = \frac{4444+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} = \frac{7777+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9}$$

$$5556 := \frac{11111+1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} = \frac{44444+4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} = \frac{77777+7}{7+7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9}$$

$$55556 := \frac{111111+1}{1+1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} = \frac{444444+4}{4+4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} = \frac{777777+7}{7+7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 57 := \frac{111+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{222+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{333+3+3+3}{3+3} = \frac{444+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{555+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{666+6+6+6}{6+6}$$

$$:= \frac{777+7+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{888+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{999+9+9+9}{9+9}$$

$$557 := \frac{1111+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+3+3+3}{3+3} = \frac{4444+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666+6+6+6}{6+6}$$

$$:= \frac{7777+7+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+9+9+9}{9+9}$$

$$5557 := \frac{11111+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+3+3+3}{3+3} = \frac{44444+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{66666+6+6+6}{6+6}$$

$$:= \frac{77777+7+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{88888+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{99999+9+9+9}{9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55557 &:= \frac{111111+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{222222+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{333333+3+3+3}{3+3} = \frac{444444+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{555555+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{666666+6+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{888888+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{999999+9+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 58 &:= \frac{111+1}{1+1} + \frac{1+1}{7+7} = \frac{222+2}{2+2} + \frac{2+2}{7+7} = \frac{333+3}{3+3} + \frac{3+3}{7+7} = \frac{444+4}{4+4} + \frac{4+4}{7+7} = \frac{555+5}{5+5} + \frac{5+5}{7+7} = \frac{666+6}{6+6} + \frac{6+6}{7+7} \\ &:= \frac{777+7}{7+7} + \frac{7}{7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8} + \frac{8}{8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9} + \frac{9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 558 &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1} + \frac{1+1}{7+7} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} + \frac{2+2}{7+7} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} + \frac{3+3}{7+7} = \frac{4444+4}{4+4} + \frac{4+4}{7+7} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} + \frac{5+5}{7+7} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} + \frac{6+6}{7+7} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7} + \frac{7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} + \frac{8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} + \frac{9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5558 &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{1+1}{7+7} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{2+2}{7+7} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{3+3}{7+7} = \frac{44444+4}{4+4} + \frac{4+4}{7+7} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} + \frac{5+5}{7+7} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} + \frac{6+6}{7+7} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55558 &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{1+1}{7+7} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{2+2}{7+7} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{3+3}{7+7} = \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{4+4}{7+7} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{5+5}{7+7} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{6+6}{7+7} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 59 &:= \frac{111+11-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{222+22-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{333+33-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444+44-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{555+55-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{666+66-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777+77-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{888+88-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{999+99-9-9-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 559 &:= \frac{1111+11-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+22-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+33-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+44-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+55-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666+66-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+77-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+88-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+99-9-9-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$5559 := \frac{11111+11-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+22-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+33-3-3-3-3}{3+3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{44444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{55559} := \frac{111111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{60} &:= \frac{111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} = \frac{444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} = \frac{777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{610} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} = \frac{4444 + 444 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{6666 + 666 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} = \frac{7777 + 777 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6110} &:= \frac{11111 + 1111 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 2222 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 3333 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} = \frac{44444 + 4444 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 5555 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{66666 + 6666 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} = \frac{77777 + 7777 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 8888 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 9999 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{61110} &:= \frac{111111 + 11111 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22222 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33333 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} = \frac{444444 + 44444 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55555 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} \\ &:= \frac{666666 + 66666 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} = \frac{777777 + 77777 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88888 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99999 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{61} := \frac{111 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{222 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{333 + 33}{3 + 3} = \frac{444 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{555 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{666 + 66}{6 + 6} = \frac{777 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{888 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{999 + 99}{9 + 9}$$

$$\mathbf{561} := \frac{1111 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 33}{3 + 3} = \frac{4444 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66}{6 + 6} = \frac{7777 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99}{9 + 9}$$

$$\mathbf{5561} := \frac{11111 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33}{3 + 3} = \frac{44444 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66}{6 + 6} = \frac{77777 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99}{9 + 9}$$

$$\mathbf{55561} := \frac{111111 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33}{3 + 3} = \frac{444444 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66}{6 + 6} = \frac{777777 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99}{9 + 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 62 &:= \frac{111+11+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{222+22+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{333+33+3+3}{3+3} = \frac{444+44+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{555+55+5+5}{5+5} \\ &:= \frac{666+66+6+6}{6+6} = \frac{777+77+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{888+88+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{999+99+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 612 &:= \frac{1111+111+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+222+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+333+3+3}{3+3} = \frac{4444+444+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+555+5+5}{5+5} \\ &:= \frac{6666+666+6+6}{6+6} = \frac{7777+777+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+888+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+999+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6112 &:= \frac{11111+1111+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+2222+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+3333+3+3}{3+3} = \frac{44444+4444+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+5555+5+5}{5+5} \\ &:= \frac{66666+6666+6+6}{6+6} = \frac{77777+7777+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{88888+8888+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{99999+9999+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 61112 &:= \frac{111111+11111+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{222222+22222+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{333333+33333+3+3}{3+3} = \frac{444444+44444+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{555555+55555+5+5}{5+5} \\ &:= \frac{666666+66666+6+6}{6+6} = \frac{777777+77777+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{888888+88888+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{999999+99999+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 63 &:= \frac{111+11+1+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{222+22+2+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{333+33+3+3+3+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444+44+4+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{555+55+5+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{666+66+6+6+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777+77+7+7+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{888+88+8+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{999+99+9+9+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 613 &:= \frac{1111+111+1+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+222+2+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+333+3+3+3+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+444+4+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+555+5+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666+666+6+6+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+777+7+7+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+888+8+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+999+9+9+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6113 &:= \frac{11111+1111+1+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+2222+2+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+3333+3+3+3+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4444+4+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+5555+5+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{66666+6666+6+6+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7777+7+7+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{88888+8888+8+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{99999+9999+9+9+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 61113 &:= \frac{111111+11111+1+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{222222+22222+2+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{333333+33333+3+3+3+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44444+4+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{555555+55555+5+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{666666+66666+6+6+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77777+7+7+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{888888+88888+8+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{999999+99999+9+9+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 64 &:= \frac{(11+1) \times 11 - (1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2) \times 22 - (2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3) \times 33 - (3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4) \times 44 - (4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5) \times 55 - (5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6) \times 66 - (6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7) \times 77 - (7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8) \times 88 - (8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9) \times 99 - (9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 614 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times 11 - (1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times 22 - (2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times 33 - (3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 44 - (4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times 55 - (5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times 66 - (6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 77 - (7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times 88 - (8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times 99 - (9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6114 &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times 11 - (1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times 22 - (2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times 33 - (3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times 44 - (4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times 55 - (5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times 66 - (6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times 77 - (7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times 88 - (8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times 99 - (9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 61114 &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times 11 - (1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times 22 - (2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times 33 - (3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times 44 - (4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times 55 - (5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times 66 - (6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times 77 - (7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times 88 - (8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times 99 - (9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 65 &:= \frac{111+11+11-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{222+22+22-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{333+33+33-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444+44+44-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{555+55+55-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{666+66+66-6-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777+77+77-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{888+88+88-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{999+99+99-9-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 565 &:= \frac{1111+11+11-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+22+22-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+33+33-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+44+44-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+55+55-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666+66+66-6-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+77+77-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+88+88-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+99+99-9-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5565 &:= \frac{11111+11+11-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+22+22-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+33+33-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+44+44-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+55+55-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{66666+66+66-6-6-6}{6+6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55565} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{66} &:= \frac{111 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{222 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{333 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3+3} = \frac{444 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{566} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3+3} = \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5566} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3+3} = \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55566} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3+3} = \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{67} &:= \frac{111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3+3} = \frac{444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{567} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3+3} = \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5567} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3+3} = \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55567 &:= \frac{111111+11+11+1}{1+1} = \frac{222222+22+22+2}{2+2} = \frac{333333+33+33+3}{3+3} = \frac{444444+44+44+4}{4+4} = \frac{555555+55+55+5}{5+5} = \frac{666666+66+66+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77+77+7}{7+7} = \frac{888888+88+88+8}{8+8} = \frac{999999+99+99+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 68 &:= \frac{111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1}{1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2}{2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3}{3} = \frac{444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4}{4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5}{5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7}{7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8}{8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 568 &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3}{3} = \frac{4444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5568 &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3}{3} = \frac{44444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55568 &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3}{3} = \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 69 &:= \frac{111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3}{3} = \frac{444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5}{5} \\ &:= \frac{666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6}{6} = \frac{777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 569 &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3}{3} = \frac{4444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5}{5} \\ &:= \frac{6666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6}{6} = \frac{7777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5569 &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3}{3} = \frac{44444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5}{5} \\ &:= \frac{66666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6}{6} = \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55569 &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3}{3} = \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5}{5} \\ &:= \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6}{6} = \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 70 &:= \frac{111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5+5}{5} \\ &:= \frac{666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 570 &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{4444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5+5}{5} \\ &:= \frac{6666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{7777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5570 &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{44444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5+5}{5} \\ &:= \frac{66666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55570 &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3+3}{3} = \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5+5}{5} \\ &:= \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6+6}{6} = \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 71 &:= \frac{111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 571 &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5571 &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55571 &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 72 &:= \frac{(11+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} = \frac{(44+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(66+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} = \frac{(77+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 672 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} = \frac{(444+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(666+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} = \frac{(777+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6672 &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} = \frac{(4444+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(6666+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} = \frac{(7777+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 66672 &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} = \frac{(44444+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(66666+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} = \frac{(77777+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 73 &:= \frac{111+11+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{11}{1} = \frac{222+22+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{22}{2} = \frac{333+33+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+44+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{44}{4} = \frac{555+55+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{55}{5} = \frac{666+66+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+77+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{77}{7} = \frac{888+88+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{88}{8} = \frac{999+99+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 723 &:= \frac{1111+111+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1} = \frac{2222+222+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2} = \frac{3333+333+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+444+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4} = \frac{5555+555+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5} = \frac{6666+666+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+777+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7} = \frac{8888+888+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8} = \frac{9999+999+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7223 &:= \frac{11111+1111+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{1} = \frac{22222+2222+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{2} = \frac{33333+3333+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4444+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{4} = \frac{55555+5555+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{5} = \frac{66666+6666+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7777+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{7} = \frac{88888+8888+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{8} = \frac{99999+9999+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 72223 &:= \frac{111111+11111+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{11111}{1} = \frac{222222+22222+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{22222}{2} = \frac{333333+33333+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{33333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44444+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{44444}{4} = \frac{555555+55555+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{55555}{5} = \frac{666666+66666+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{66666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77777+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{77777}{7} = \frac{888888+88888+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{88888}{8} = \frac{999999+99999+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{99999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 74 &:= \frac{111+11+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1}{1} = \frac{222+22+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2}{2} = \frac{333+33+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+44+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4}{4} = \frac{555+55+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5}{5} = \frac{666+66+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+77+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7}{7} = \frac{888+88+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8}{8} = \frac{999+99+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 724 &:= \frac{1111+111+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{111+1}{1} = \frac{2222+222+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{222+2}{2} = \frac{3333+333+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+444+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{444+4}{4} = \frac{5555+555+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{555+5}{5} = \frac{6666+666+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+777+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{777+7}{7} = \frac{8888+888+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{888+8}{8} = \frac{9999+999+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7224 &:= \frac{11111+1111+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2222+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3333+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4444+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5555+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6666+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7777+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8888+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9999+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 72224 &:= \frac{111111+11111+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{11111+1}{1} = \frac{222222+22222+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{22222+2}{2} = \frac{333333+33333+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{33333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44444+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{44444+4}{4} = \frac{555555+55555+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{55555+5}{5} = \frac{666666+66666+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{66666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77777+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{77777+7}{7} = \frac{888888+88888+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{88888+8}{8} = \frac{999999+99999+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{99999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 75 &:= \frac{111-11-11-11-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{222-22-22-22-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{333-33-33-33-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444-44-44-44-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{555-55-55-55-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{666-66-66-66-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777-77-77-77-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{888-88-88-88-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{999-99-99-99-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 975 &:= \frac{1111-111-11-11-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222-222-22-22-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333-333-33-33-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-444-44-44-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555-555-55-55-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666-666-66-66-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-777-77-77-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888-888-88-88-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999-999-99-99-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9975 &:= \frac{11111-1111-11-11-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2222-22-22-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3333-33-33-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-4444-44-44-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5555-55-55-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6666-66-66-6-6-6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99975} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{76} &:= \frac{111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{976} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9976} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99976} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{77} &:= \frac{111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{977} := \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9977} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99977} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{78} &:= \frac{111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{978} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9978} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99978} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 79 &:= \frac{111 - 11 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 979 &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9979 &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 99979 &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 80 &:= \frac{111 - 11 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 980 &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9980 &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99980 &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 81 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 981 &:= \frac{(111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9981 &:= \frac{(1111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99981 &:= \frac{(11111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 82 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$982 := \frac{(11 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2) \times (222 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3) \times (333 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times (444-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times (555-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times (666-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times (777-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times (888-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times (999-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9982} &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times (1111-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times (2222-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times (3333-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times (4444-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times (5555-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times (6666-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times (7777-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times (8888-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times (9999-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99982} &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times (11111-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times (22222-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times (33333-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times (44444-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times (55555-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times (66666-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times (77777-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times (88888-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times (99999-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{83} &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times (44-4-4) + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times (55-5-5) + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times (66-6-6) + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times (77-7-7) + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times (88-8-8) + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times (99-9-9) + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{983} &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times (111-1-1) + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times (222-2-2) + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times (333-3-3) + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times (444-4-4) + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times (555-5-5) + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times (666-6-6) + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times (777-7-7) + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times (888-8-8) + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times (999-9-9) + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9983} &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times (1111-1-1) + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times (2222-2-2) + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times (3333-3-3) + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times (4444-4-4) + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times (5555-5-5) + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times (6666-6-6) + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times (7777-7-7) + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times (8888-8-8) + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times (9999-9-9) + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99983} &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times (11111-1-1) + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times (22222-2-2) + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times (33333-3-3) + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times (44444-4-4) + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times (55555-5-5) + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times (66666-6-6) + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times (77777-7-7) + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times (88888-8-8) + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times (99999-9-9) + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 84 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (11+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (22+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (33+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (44+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (55+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (66+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (77+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (88+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (99+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 784 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (999+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7784 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (1111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (2222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (3333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (4444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (5555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (6666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (7777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (8888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (9999+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 77784 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (11111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (22222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (33333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (44444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (55555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (66666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (77777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (88888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (99999+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 85 &:= \frac{111-11-11-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{222-22-22-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{333-33-33-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444-44-44-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{555-55-55-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{666-66-66-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777-77-77-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{888-88-88-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{999-99-99-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 985 &:= \frac{1111-111-11-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222-222-22-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333-333-33-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-444-44-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555-555-55-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666-666-66-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-777-77-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888-888-88-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999-999-99-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9985 &:= \frac{11111-1111-11-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2222-22-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3333-33-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-4444-44-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5555-55-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6666-66-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-7777-77-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888-8888-88-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999-9999-99-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99985 &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 86 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11 - (1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22 - (2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33 - (3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44 - (4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55 - (5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66 - (6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77 - (7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88 - (8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99 - (9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 886 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 111 - (1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 222 - (2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 333 - (3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 444 - (4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 555 - (5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 666 - (6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 777 - (7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 888 - (8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 999 - (9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8886 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 1111 - (1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 2222 - (2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 3333 - (3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 4444 - (4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 5555 - (5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 6666 - (6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 7777 - (7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 8888 - (8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 9999 - (9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 88886 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11111 - (1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22222 - (2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33333 - (3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44444 - (4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55555 - (5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66666 - (6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77777 - (7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88888 - (8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99999 - (9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 87 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$887 := \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8887} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88887} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 11111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 22222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 33333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 44444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 55555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 66666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 77777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 88888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 99999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{88} &:= \frac{111-11-11-1}{1} = \frac{222-22-22-2}{2} = \frac{333-33-33-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444-44-44-4}{4} = \frac{555-55-55-5}{5} = \frac{666-66-66-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777-77-77-7}{7} = \frac{888-88-88-8}{8} = \frac{999-99-99-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{988} &:= \frac{1111-111-11-1}{1} = \frac{2222-222-22-2}{2} = \frac{3333-333-33-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-444-44-4}{4} = \frac{5555-555-55-5}{5} = \frac{6666-666-66-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-777-77-7}{7} = \frac{8888-888-88-8}{8} = \frac{9999-999-99-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9988} &:= \frac{11111-1111-11-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2222-22-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3333-33-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-4444-44-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5555-55-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6666-66-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-7777-77-7}{7} = \frac{88888-8888-88-8}{8} = \frac{99999-9999-99-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999988} &:= \frac{111111-11111-11-1}{1} = \frac{222222-22222-22-2}{2} = \frac{333333-33333-33-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444-44444-44-4}{4} = \frac{555555-55555-55-5}{5} = \frac{666666-66666-66-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-77777-77-7}{7} = \frac{888888-88888-88-8}{8} = \frac{999999-99999-99-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{89} &:= \frac{111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{989} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9989} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99989} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{90} &:= \frac{111 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{990} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9990} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999990} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{91} &:= \frac{111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{991} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9991} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99991} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{92} &:= \frac{111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{992} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9992} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99992} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{93} &:= \frac{111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{993} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9993} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99993} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{94} := \frac{111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{994} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9994} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99994} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{95} &:= \frac{111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{995} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9995} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 99995 &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 96 &:= \frac{111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 996 &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9996 &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 99996 &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 97 &:= \frac{111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 997 &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9997} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99997} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{98} &:= \frac{111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{998} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9998} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99998} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{99} := \frac{111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 - 3}{3} = \frac{444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 - 6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{777-77-7}{7} = \frac{888-88-8}{8} = \frac{999-99-9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999} &:= \frac{1111-111-1}{1} = \frac{2222-222-2}{2} = \frac{3333-333-3}{3} = \frac{4444-444-4}{4} = \frac{5555-555-5}{5} = \frac{6666-666-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-777-7}{7} = \frac{8888-888-8}{8} = \frac{9999-999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9999} &:= \frac{11111-1111-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2222-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3333-3}{3} = \frac{44444-4444-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5555-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6666-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-7777-7}{7} = \frac{88888-8888-8}{8} = \frac{99999-9999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99999} &:= \frac{111111-11111-1}{1} = \frac{222222-22222-2}{2} = \frac{333333-33333-3}{3} = \frac{444444-44444-4}{4} = \frac{555555-55555-5}{5} = \frac{666666-66666-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-77777-7}{7} = \frac{888888-88888-8}{8} = \frac{999999-99999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{100} := \frac{111-11}{1} = \frac{222-22}{2} = \frac{333-33}{3} = \frac{444-44}{4} = \frac{555-55}{5} = \frac{666-66}{6} = \frac{777-77}{7} = \frac{888-88}{8} = \frac{999-99}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1100} := \frac{1111-11}{1} = \frac{2222-22}{2} = \frac{3333-33}{3} = \frac{4444-44}{4} = \frac{5555-55}{5} = \frac{6666-66}{6} = \frac{7777-77}{7} = \frac{8888-88}{8} = \frac{9999-99}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{11100} := \frac{11111-11}{1} = \frac{22222-22}{2} = \frac{33333-33}{3} = \frac{44444-44}{4} = \frac{55555-55}{5} = \frac{66666-66}{6} = \frac{77777-77}{7} = \frac{88888-88}{8} = \frac{99999-99}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{111100} := \frac{111111-11}{1} = \frac{222222-22}{2} = \frac{333333-33}{3} = \frac{444444-44}{4} = \frac{555555-55}{5} = \frac{666666-66}{6} = \frac{777777-77}{7} = \frac{888888-88}{8} = \frac{999999-99}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{101} &:= \frac{111-11+1}{1} = \frac{222-22+2}{2} = \frac{333-33+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444-44+4}{4} = \frac{555-55+5}{5} = \frac{666-66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777-77+7}{7} = \frac{888-88+8}{8} = \frac{999-99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1001} &:= \frac{1111-111+1}{1} = \frac{2222-222+2}{2} = \frac{3333-333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-444+4}{4} = \frac{5555-555+5}{5} = \frac{6666-666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-777+7}{7} = \frac{8888-888+8}{8} = \frac{9999-999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{10001} := \frac{11111-1111+1}{1} = \frac{22222-2222+2}{2} = \frac{33333-3333+3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{100001} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{102} &:= \frac{111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1102} &:= \frac{1111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11102} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111102} &:= \frac{111111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{103} &:= \frac{111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1003} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{10003} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{100003} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{104} &:= \frac{111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1004} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{10004} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{100004} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{105} &:= \frac{111-1-1-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{222-2-2-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{333-3-3-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444-4-4-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{555-5-5-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{666-6-6-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777-7-7-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{888-8-8-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{999-9-9-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1105} &:= \frac{1111-1-1-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222-2-2-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333-3-3-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-4-4-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555-5-5-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666-6-6-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-7-7-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888-8-8-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999-9-9-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11105} &:= \frac{11111-1-1-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2-2-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3-3-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-4-4-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5-5-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6-6-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-7-7-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888-8-8-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999-9-9-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111105} &:= \frac{111111-1-1-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{222222-2-2-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{333333-3-3-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444-4-4-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{555555-5-5-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{666666-6-6-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-7-7-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{888888-8-8-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{999999-9-9-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{106} &:= \frac{111-1-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{222-2-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{333-3-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444-4-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{555-5-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{666-6-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777-7-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{888-8-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{999-9-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1106} &:= \frac{1111-1-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222-2-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333-3-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-4-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555-5-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666-6-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-7-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888-8-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999-9-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11106} &:= \frac{11111-1-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-4-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6-6-6-6-6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777-7-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888-8-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999-9-9-9-9-9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111106} &:= \frac{11111-1-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-4-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-7-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888-8-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999-9-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{107} &:= \frac{111-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{222-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{333-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{555-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{666-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{888-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{999-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1107} &:= \frac{1111-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11107} &:= \frac{11111-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111107} &:= \frac{111111-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{222222-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{333333-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{555555-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{666666-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{888888-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{999999-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{108} &:= \frac{111-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{222-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{333-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{555-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{666-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{888-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{999-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{1108} := \frac{1111-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333-3-3-3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11108} &:= \frac{11111-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111108} &:= \frac{111111-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{222222-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{333333-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{555555-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{666666-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{888888-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{999999-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{109} &:= \frac{111-1-1}{1} = \frac{222-2-2}{2} = \frac{333-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444-4-4}{4} = \frac{555-5-5}{5} = \frac{666-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777-7-7}{7} = \frac{888-8-8}{8} = \frac{999-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1109} &:= \frac{1111-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11109} &:= \frac{11111-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111109} &:= \frac{111111-1-1}{1} = \frac{222222-2-2}{2} = \frac{333333-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444-4-4}{4} = \frac{555555-5-5}{5} = \frac{666666-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-7-7}{7} = \frac{888888-8-8}{8} = \frac{999999-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{110} := \frac{111-1}{1} = \frac{222-2}{2} = \frac{333-3}{3} = \frac{444-4}{4} = \frac{555-5}{5} = \frac{666-6}{6} = \frac{777-7}{7} = \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{999-9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1110} := \frac{1111-1}{1} = \frac{2222-2}{2} = \frac{3333-3}{3} = \frac{4444-4}{4} = \frac{5555-5}{5} = \frac{6666-6}{6} = \frac{7777-7}{7} = \frac{8888-8}{8} = \frac{9999-9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{11110} := \frac{11111-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3}{3} = \frac{44444-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6}{6} = \frac{77777-7}{7} = \frac{88888-8}{8} = \frac{99999-9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{111110} := \frac{111111-1}{1} = \frac{222222-2}{2} = \frac{333333-3}{3} = \frac{444444-4}{4} = \frac{555555-5}{5} = \frac{666666-6}{6} = \frac{777777-7}{7} = \frac{888888-8}{8} = \frac{999999-9}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{111} := \frac{111}{1} = \frac{222}{2} = \frac{333}{3} = \frac{444}{4} = \frac{555}{5} = \frac{666}{6} = \frac{777}{7} = \frac{888}{8} = \frac{999}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1111} := \frac{1111}{1} = \frac{2222}{2} = \frac{3333}{3} = \frac{4444}{4} = \frac{5555}{5} = \frac{6666}{6} = \frac{7777}{7} = \frac{8888}{8} = \frac{9999}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{11111} := \frac{11111}{1} = \frac{22222}{2} = \frac{33333}{3} = \frac{44444}{4} = \frac{55555}{5} = \frac{66666}{6} = \frac{77777}{7} = \frac{88888}{8} = \frac{99999}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{111111} := \frac{111111}{1} = \frac{222222}{2} = \frac{333333}{3} = \frac{444444}{4} = \frac{555555}{5} = \frac{666666}{6} = \frac{777777}{7} = \frac{888888}{8} = \frac{999999}{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{112} := \frac{111+1}{1} = \frac{222+2}{2} = \frac{333+3}{3} = \frac{444+4}{4} = \frac{555+5}{5} = \frac{666+6}{6} = \frac{777+7}{7} = \frac{888+8}{8} = \frac{999+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1112} := \frac{1111+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3} = \frac{4444+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6} = \frac{7777+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{11112} := \frac{11111+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3} = \frac{44444+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6} = \frac{77777+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{111112} := \frac{111111+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3} = \frac{444444+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6} = \frac{777777+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{113} &:= \frac{111+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1113} &:= \frac{1111+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11113} &:= \frac{11111+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111113} &:= \frac{111111+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{114} &:= \frac{111+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1114} &:= \frac{1111+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11114} &:= \frac{11111+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111114} &:= \frac{111111+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{115} &:= \frac{111+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1115} &:= \frac{1111+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11115} &:= \frac{11111+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111115} &:= \frac{111111+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{116} &:= \frac{11-1}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1} = \frac{22-2}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2} = \frac{33-3}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44-4}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4} = \frac{55-5}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5} = \frac{66-6}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77-7}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7} = \frac{88-8}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8} = \frac{99-9}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1116} &:= \frac{11-1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{1} = \frac{22-2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{2} = \frac{33-3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44-4}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{4} = \frac{55-5}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{5} = \frac{66-6}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77-7}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{7} = \frac{88-8}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{8} = \frac{99-9}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11116} &:= \frac{11-1}{1+1} + \frac{11111}{1} = \frac{22-2}{2+2} + \frac{22222}{2} = \frac{33-3}{3+3} + \frac{33333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44-4}{4+4} + \frac{44444}{4} = \frac{55-5}{5+5} + \frac{55555}{5} = \frac{66-6}{6+6} + \frac{66666}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77-7}{7+7} + \frac{77777}{7} = \frac{88-8}{8+8} + \frac{88888}{8} = \frac{99-9}{9+9} + \frac{99999}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111116} &:= \frac{11-1}{1+1} + \frac{111111}{1} = \frac{22-2}{2+2} + \frac{222222}{2} = \frac{33-3}{3+3} + \frac{333333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44-4}{4+4} + \frac{444444}{4} = \frac{55-5}{5+5} + \frac{555555}{5} = \frac{66-6}{6+6} + \frac{666666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77-7}{7+7} + \frac{777777}{7} = \frac{88-8}{8+8} + \frac{888888}{8} = \frac{99-9}{9+9} + \frac{999999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{117} &:= \frac{11+1}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1} = \frac{22+2}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2} = \frac{33+3}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44+4}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4} = \frac{55+5}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5} = \frac{66+6}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77+7}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7} = \frac{88+8}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8} = \frac{99+9}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1117} &:= \frac{11+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{1} = \frac{22+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{2} = \frac{33+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{4} = \frac{55+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{5} = \frac{66+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{7} = \frac{88+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{8} = \frac{99+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11117} &:= \frac{11+1}{1+1} + \frac{11111}{1} = \frac{22+2}{2+2} + \frac{22222}{2} = \frac{33+3}{3+3} + \frac{33333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44+4}{4+4} + \frac{44444}{4} = \frac{55+5}{5+5} + \frac{55555}{5} = \frac{66+6}{6+6} + \frac{66666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77+7}{7+7} + \frac{77777}{7} = \frac{88+8}{8+8} + \frac{88888}{8} = \frac{99+9}{9+9} + \frac{99999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111117} &:= \frac{11+1}{1+1} + \frac{111111}{1} = \frac{22+2}{2+2} + \frac{222222}{2} = \frac{33+3}{3+3} + \frac{333333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44+4}{4+4} + \frac{444444}{4} = \frac{55+5}{5+5} + \frac{555555}{5} = \frac{66+6}{6+6} + \frac{666666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77+7}{7+7} + \frac{777777}{7} = \frac{88+8}{8+8} + \frac{888888}{8} = \frac{99+9}{9+9} + \frac{999999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{118} &:= \frac{111+11-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{222+22-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{333+33-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+44-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{555+55-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{666+66-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+77-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{888+88-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{999+99-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{1118} := \frac{1111+11-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222+22-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333+33-3-3-3-3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11118} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111118} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{119} &:= \frac{111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1119} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11119} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111119} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{120} &:= \frac{111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1120} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11120} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111120} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{121} &:= \frac{111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1221} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{12221} &:= \frac{11111 + 1111 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 2222 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 3333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 4444 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 5555 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 6666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 7777 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 8888 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 9999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{122221} &:= \frac{111111 + 11111 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22222 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44444 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55555 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77777 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88888 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{122} &:= \frac{111 + 11}{1} = \frac{222 + 22}{2} = \frac{333 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 44}{4} = \frac{555 + 55}{5} = \frac{666 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77}{7} = \frac{888 + 88}{8} = \frac{999 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1122} &:= \frac{1111 + 11}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11122} &:= \frac{11111 + 11}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111122} &:= \frac{111111 + 11}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{123} &:= \frac{111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1123} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11123} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111123} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{124} &:= \frac{111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1124} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11124} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111124} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{125} := \frac{111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1125} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11125} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111125} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{126} &:= \frac{111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1126} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11126} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111126} &:= \frac{111111+11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+99+9+9+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{127} &:= \frac{111+11+1+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+22+2+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+33+3+3+3+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444+44+4+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+55+5+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+66+6+6+6+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777+77+7+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+88+8+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+99+9+9+9+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1127} &:= \frac{1111+11+1+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+22+2+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+33+3+3+3+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+44+4+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+55+5+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+66+6+6+6+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777+77+7+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+88+8+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+99+9+9+9+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{11127} &:= \frac{11111+11+1+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+22+2+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+33+3+3+3+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444+44+4+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+55+5+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+66+6+6+6+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777+77+7+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+88+8+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+99+9+9+9+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111127} &:= \frac{111111+11+1+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+22+2+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+33+3+3+3+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+44+4+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+55+5+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+66+6+6+6+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+77+7+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+88+8+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+99+9+9+9+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{128} &:= \frac{111+11+1+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+22+2+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+33+3+3+3+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444+44+4+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+55+5+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+66+6+6+6+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777+77+7+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+88+8+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+99+9+9+9+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1128} &:= \frac{1111+11+1+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+22+2+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+33+3+3+3+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+44+4+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+55+5+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+66+6+6+6+6+6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777+77+7+7+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+88+8+8+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+99+9+9+9+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11128} &:= \frac{11111+11+1+1+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+22+2+2+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+33+3+3+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+44+4+4+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+55+5+5+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+66+6+6+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+77+7+7+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+88+8+8+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+99+9+9+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111128} &:= \frac{111111+11+1+1+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+22+2+2+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+33+3+3+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44+4+4+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+55+5+5+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+66+6+6+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77+7+7+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+88+8+8+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+99+9+9+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{129} &:= \frac{11+11+111-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22+22+222-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33+33+333-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44+44+444-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55+55+555-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66+66+666-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77+77+777-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88+88+888-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99+99+999-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1129} &:= \frac{11+11+1111-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22+22+2222-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33+33+3333-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44+44+4444-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55+55+5555-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66+66+6666-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77+77+7777-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88+88+8888-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99+99+9999-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11129} &:= \frac{11+11+11111-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22+22+22222-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33+33+33333-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44+44+44444-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55+55+55555-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66+66+66666-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77+77+77777-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88+88+88888-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99+99+99999-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111129} &:= \frac{11+11+111111-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22+22+222222-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33+33+333333-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44+44+444444-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55+55+555555-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66+66+666666-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77+77+777777-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88+88+888888-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99+99+999999-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{130} := \frac{11+11+111-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22+22+222-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33+33+333-3-3-3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1130} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11130} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111130} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 111111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 222222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 333333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 444444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 555555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 666666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 777777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 888888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 999999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{131} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1131} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 1111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 2222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 3333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 4444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 5555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 6666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 7777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 8888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 9999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11131} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 11111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 22222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 33333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 44444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 55555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 66666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 77777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 88888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 99999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111131} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 111111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 222222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 333333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 444444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 555555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 666666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 777777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 888888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 999999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{132} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 111 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 222 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 444 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 555 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 777 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 888 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1132} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 1111 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 2222 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 3333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 4444 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 5555 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 6666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 7777 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 8888 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 9999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11132} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 11111 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 22222 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 33333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 44444 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 55555 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 66666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 77777 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 88888 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 99999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111132} &:= \frac{11 + 11 + 111111 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 22 + 222222 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 33 + 333333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 44 + 444444 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 55 + 555555 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 66 + 666666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 77 + 777777 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 88 + 888888 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 99 + 999999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{133} &:= \frac{111 + 11 + 11}{1} = \frac{222 + 22 + 22}{2} = \frac{333 + 33 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 44 + 44}{4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 55}{5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1133} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 11}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 22}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 44}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11133} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111133} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 44}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{134} &:= \frac{111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1134} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11134} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111134} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{135} := \frac{111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1135} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11135} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111135} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{136} &:= \frac{111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1136} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11136} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111136} &:= \frac{111111+11+11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+22+22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+33+33+3+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+44+44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+55+55+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+66+66+6+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+77+77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+88+88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+99+99+9+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{137} &:= \frac{111+11+11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+22+22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+33+33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444+44+44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+55+55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+66+66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777+77+77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+88+88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+99+99+9+9+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1137} &:= \frac{1111+11+11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+22+22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+33+33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+44+44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+55+55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+66+66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777+77+77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+88+88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+99+99+9+9+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{11137} &:= \frac{11111+11+11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+22+22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+33+33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444+44+44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+55+55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+66+66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777+77+77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+88+88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+99+99+9+9+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111137} &:= \frac{111111+11+11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+22+22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+33+33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+44+44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+55+55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+66+66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+77+77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+88+88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+99+99+9+9+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{138} &:= \frac{111+11+11+1+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+22+22+2+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+33+33+3+3+3+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444+44+44+4+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+55+55+5+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+66+66+6+6+6+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777+77+77+7+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+88+88+8+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+99+99+9+9+9+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1138} &:= \frac{1111+11+11+1+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+22+22+2+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+33+33+3+3+3+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+44+44+4+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+55+55+5+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+66+66+6+6+6+6+6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777+77+77+7+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+88+88+8+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+99+99+9+9+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11138} &:= \frac{11111+11+11+1+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+22+22+2+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+33+33+3+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+44+44+4+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+55+55+5+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+66+66+6+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+77+77+7+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+88+88+8+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+99+99+9+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111138} &:= \frac{111111+11+11+1+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+22+22+2+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+33+33+3+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44+44+4+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+55+55+5+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+66+66+6+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77+77+7+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+88+88+8+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+99+99+9+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{139} &:= \frac{1111+1}{11-1-1-1} = \frac{2222+2}{22-2-2-2} = \frac{3333+3}{33-3-3-3} = \frac{4444+4}{44-4-4-4} = \frac{5555+5}{55-5-5-5} = \frac{6666+6}{66-6-6-6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{77-7-7-7} = \frac{8888+8}{88-8-8-8} = \frac{9999+9}{99-9-9-9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1389} &:= \frac{11111+1}{11-1-1-1} = \frac{22222+2}{22-2-2-2} = \frac{33333+3}{33-3-3-3} = \frac{44444+4}{44-4-4-4} = \frac{55555+5}{55-5-5-5} = \frac{66666+6}{66-6-6-6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7}{77-7-7-7} = \frac{88888+8}{88-8-8-8} = \frac{99999+9}{99-9-9-9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{13889} &:= \frac{111111+1}{11-1-1-1} = \frac{222222+2}{22-2-2-2} = \frac{333333+3}{33-3-3-3} = \frac{444444+4}{44-4-4-4} = \frac{555555+5}{55-5-5-5} = \frac{666666+6}{66-6-6-6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{77-7-7-7} = \frac{888888+8}{88-8-8-8} = \frac{999999+9}{99-9-9-9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{138889} &:= \frac{1111111+1}{11-1-1-1} = \frac{2222222+2}{22-2-2-2} = \frac{3333333+3}{33-3-3-3} = \frac{4444444+4}{44-4-4-4} = \frac{5555555+5}{55-5-5-5} = \frac{6666666+6}{66-6-6-6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+7}{77-7-7-7} = \frac{8888888+8}{88-8-8-8} = \frac{9999999+9}{99-9-9-9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{140} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times (11-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times (22-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times (33-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times (44-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times (55-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times (66-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times (77-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times (88-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times (99-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{1140} := \frac{(111+1+1+1) \times (11-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2+2) \times (22-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3+3) \times (33-3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11140} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111140} &:= \frac{(11111 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{141} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1) \times 11 - (1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2) \times 22 - (2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3) \times 33 - (3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4) \times 44 - (4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5) \times 55 - (5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6) \times 66 - (6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7) \times 77 - (7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8) \times 88 - (8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9) \times 99 - (9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1441} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - (1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2) \times 222 - (2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3) \times 333 - (3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4) \times 444 - (4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5) \times 555 - (5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6) \times 666 - (6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7) \times 777 - (7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8) \times 888 - (8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9) \times 999 - (9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{14441} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1) \times 1111 - (1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2) \times 2222 - (2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3) \times 3333 - (3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4) \times 4444 - (4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5) \times 5555 - (5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6) \times 6666 - (6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7) \times 7777 - (7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8) \times 8888 - (8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9) \times 9999 - (9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{144441} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1) \times 11111 - (1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2) \times 22222 - (2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3) \times 33333 - (3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4) \times 44444 - (4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5) \times 55555 - (5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6) \times 66666 - (6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7) \times 77777 - (7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8) \times 88888 - (8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9) \times 99999 - (9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{142} &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1242} &:= \frac{(111+1+1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4+4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7+7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{12242} &:= \frac{(1111+1+1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4+4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5+5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6+6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7+7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{122242} &:= \frac{(11111+1+1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4+4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6+6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7+7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{143} &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1243} &:= \frac{(111+1+1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4+4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7+7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{12243} &:= \frac{(1111+1+1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4+4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5+5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6+6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7+7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 122243 &:= \frac{(11111+1+1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4+4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6+6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7+7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 144 &:= \frac{111+11+11+11}{1} = \frac{222+22+22+22}{2} = \frac{333+33+33+33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+44+44+44}{4} = \frac{555+55+55+55}{5} = \frac{666+66+66+66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+77+77+77}{7} = \frac{888+88+88+88}{8} = \frac{999+99+99+99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1144 &:= \frac{1111+11+11+11}{1} = \frac{2222+22+22+22}{2} = \frac{3333+33+33+33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+44+44+44}{4} = \frac{5555+55+55+55}{5} = \frac{6666+66+66+66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+77+77+77}{7} = \frac{8888+88+88+88}{8} = \frac{9999+99+99+99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 11144 &:= \frac{11111+11+11+11}{1} = \frac{22222+22+22+22}{2} = \frac{33333+33+33+33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+44+44+44}{4} = \frac{55555+55+55+55}{5} = \frac{66666+66+66+66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+77+77+77}{7} = \frac{88888+88+88+88}{8} = \frac{99999+99+99+99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 111144 &:= \frac{111111+11+11+11}{1} = \frac{222222+22+22+22}{2} = \frac{333333+33+33+33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44+44+44}{4} = \frac{555555+55+55+55}{5} = \frac{666666+66+66+66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77+77+77}{7} = \frac{888888+88+88+88}{8} = \frac{999999+99+99+99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 145 &:= \frac{(11+1) \times (11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2) \times (22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3) \times (33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4) \times (44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5) \times (55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6) \times (66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7) \times (77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8) \times (88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9) \times (99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1335 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777+7) \times (77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{13345} &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{133345} &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{146} &:= \frac{111+11+11+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+22+22+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+33+33+33+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+44+44+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+55+55+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+66+66+66+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+77+77+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+88+88+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+99+99+99+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1146} &:= \frac{1111+11+11+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+22+22+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+33+33+33+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+44+44+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+55+55+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+66+66+66+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+77+77+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+88+88+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+99+99+99+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11146} &:= \frac{11111+11+11+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+22+22+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+33+33+33+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+44+44+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+55+55+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+66+66+66+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+77+77+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+88+88+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+99+99+99+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111146} &:= \frac{111111+11+11+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+22+22+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+33+33+33+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44+44+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+55+55+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+66+66+66+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77+77+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+88+88+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+99+99+99+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{147} := \frac{111+11+11+11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+22+22+22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+33+33+33+3+3+3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1147} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11147} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111147} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{148} &:= \frac{111 \times 1 + 111 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 2 + 222 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 3 + 333 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 4 + 444 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 5 + 555 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 6 + 666 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 7 + 777 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 8 + 888 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 9 + 999 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1148} &:= \frac{111 \times 1 + 1111 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 2 + 2222 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 3 + 3333 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 4 + 4444 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 5 + 5555 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 6 + 6666 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 7 + 7777 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 8 + 8888 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 9 + 9999 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11148} &:= \frac{111 \times 1 + 11111 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 2 + 22222 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 3 + 33333 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 4 + 44444 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 5 + 55555 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 6 + 66666 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 7 + 77777 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 8 + 88888 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 9 + 99999 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111148} &:= \frac{111 \times 1 + 111111 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 2 + 222222 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 3 + 333333 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)} \\
 &:= \frac{444 \times 4 + 444444 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 5 + 555555 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 6 + 666666 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)} \\
 &:= \frac{777 \times 7 + 777777 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times (7+7+7)} = \frac{888 \times 8 + 888888 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times (8+8+8)} = \frac{999 \times 9 + 999999 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times (9+9+9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{149} &:= \frac{111 \times 1 + (111+1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 2 + (222+2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 3 + (333+3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)} \\
 &:= \frac{444 \times 4 + (444+4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 5 + (555+5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 6 + (666+6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)} \\
 &:= \frac{777 \times 7 + (777+7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times (7+7+7)} = \frac{888 \times 8 + (888+8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times (8+8+8)} = \frac{999 \times 9 + (999+9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times (9+9+9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1149} &:= \frac{111 \times 1 + (1111+1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 2 + (2222+2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 3 + (3333+3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)} \\
 &:= \frac{444 \times 4 + (4444+4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 5 + (5555+5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 6 + (6666+6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)} \\
 &:= \frac{777 \times 7 + (7777+7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times (7+7+7)} = \frac{888 \times 8 + (8888+8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times (8+8+8)} = \frac{999 \times 9 + (9999+9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times (9+9+9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{11149} &:= \frac{111 \times 1 + (11111+1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 2 + (22222+2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 3 + (33333+3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)} \\
 &:= \frac{444 \times 4 + (44444+4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 5 + (55555+5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 6 + (66666+6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)} \\
 &:= \frac{777 \times 7 + (77777+7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times (7+7+7)} = \frac{888 \times 8 + (88888+8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times (8+8+8)} = \frac{999 \times 9 + (99999+9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times (9+9+9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111149} &:= \frac{111 \times 1 + (111111+1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 2 + (222222+2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 3 + (333333+3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)} \\
 &:= \frac{444 \times 4 + (444444+4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 5 + (555555+5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 6 + (666666+6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)} \\
 &:= \frac{777 \times 7 + (777777+7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times (7+7+7)} = \frac{888 \times 8 + (888888+8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times (8+8+8)} = \frac{999 \times 9 + (999999+9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times (9+9+9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{150} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times (11-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times (22-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times (33-3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times (44-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times (55-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times (66-6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times (77-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times (88-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times (99-9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1650} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times (111-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times (222-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times (333-3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times (444-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times (555-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times (666-6)}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times (777-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times (888-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times (999-9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{16650} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times (1111-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times (2222-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times (3333-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times (4444-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times (5555-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times (6666-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times (7777-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times (8888-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times (9999-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{166650} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times (11111-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times (22222-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times (33333-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times (44444-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times (55555-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times (66666-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times (77777-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times (88888-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times (99999-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{151} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 11 - 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 22 - 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 33 - 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 44 - 4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 55 - 5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 66 - 6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 77 - 7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 88 - 8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 99 - 9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1551} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 111 - 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 222 - 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 333 - 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 444 - 4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 555 - 5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 666 - 6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 777 - 7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 888 - 8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 999 - 9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{15551} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 1111 - 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 2222 - 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 3333 - 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 4444 - 4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 5555 - 5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 6666 - 6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 7777 - 7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 8888 - 8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 9999 - 9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{155551} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 11111 - 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 22222 - 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 33333 - 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 44444 - 4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 55555 - 5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 66666 - 6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 77777 - 7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 88888 - 8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 99999 - 9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{152} := \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 11 - 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 22 - 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 33 - 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 44 - 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 55 - 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 66 - 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 77 - 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 88 - 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 99 - 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1552} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 111 - 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 222 - 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 333 - 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 444 - 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 555 - 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 666 - 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 777 - 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 888 - 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 999 - 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{15552} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 1111 - 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 2222 - 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 3333 - 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 4444 - 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 5555 - 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 6666 - 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 7777 - 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 8888 - 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 9999 - 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{155552} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 11111 - 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 22222 - 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 33333 - 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 44444 - 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 55555 - 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 66666 - 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 77777 - 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 88888 - 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 99999 - 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{153} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1553} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{15553} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 1111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 2222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 3333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 4444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 5555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 6666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 7777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 8888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 9999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{155553} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 11111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 22222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 33333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 44444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 55555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 66666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 77777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 88888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 99999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{154} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1554} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{15554} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 1111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 2222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 3333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 4444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 5555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 6666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 7777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 8888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 9999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{155554} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 11111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 22222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 33333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 44444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 55555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 66666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 77777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 88888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 99999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{155} &:= \frac{111+11+11+11+11}{1} = \frac{222+22+22+22+22}{2} = \frac{333+33+33+33+33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+44+44+44+44}{4} = \frac{555+55+55+55+55}{5} = \frac{666+66+66+66+66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+77+77+77+77}{7} = \frac{888+88+88+88+88}{8} = \frac{999+99+99+99+99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1155} &:= \frac{1111+11+11+11+11}{1} = \frac{2222+22+22+22+22}{2} = \frac{3333+33+33+33+33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+44+44+44+44}{4} = \frac{5555+55+55+55+55}{5} = \frac{6666+66+66+66+66}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11155} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111155} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{156} &:= \frac{111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1156} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11156} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111156} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{157} := \frac{111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1157} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11157} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111157} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{158} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2) \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3) \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4) \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5) \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6) \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7) \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8) \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9) \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1358} &:= \frac{(111 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2 + 2) \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3 + 3) \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4 + 4) \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5 + 5) \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6 + 6) \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7 + 7) \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8 + 8) \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9 + 9) \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{13358} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2 + 2) \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3 + 3) \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4 + 4) \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5 + 5) \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6 + 6) \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7 + 7) \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8 + 8) \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9 + 9) \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{133358} &:= \frac{(11111+1+1) \times (11+1) + (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2) \times (22+2) + (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3) \times (33+3) + (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444+4+4) \times (44+4) + (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5) \times (55+5) + (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6+6) \times (66+6) + (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777+7+7) \times (77+7) + (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8) \times (88+8) + (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9) \times (99+9) + (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{159} &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times (11+1) + (1+1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (22+2) + (2+2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (33+3) + (3+3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times (44+4) + (4+4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (55+5) + (5+5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times (66+6) + (6+6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times (77+7) + (7+7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (88+8) + (8+8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (99+9) + (9+9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1359} &:= \frac{(111+1+1) \times (11+1) + (1+1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2) \times (22+2) + (2+2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3) \times (33+3) + (3+3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444+4+4) \times (44+4) + (4+4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5) \times (55+5) + (5+5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6) \times (66+6) + (6+6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777+7+7) \times (77+7) + (7+7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8) \times (88+8) + (8+8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9) \times (99+9) + (9+9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{13359} &:= \frac{(1111+1+1) \times (11+1) + (1+1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2) \times (22+2) + (2+2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3) \times (33+3) + (3+3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444+4+4) \times (44+4) + (4+4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5+5) \times (55+5) + (5+5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6+6) \times (66+6) + (6+6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777+7+7) \times (77+7) + (7+7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8) \times (88+8) + (8+8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9) \times (99+9) + (9+9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{133359} &:= \frac{(11111+1+1) \times (11+1) + (1+1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2) \times (22+2) + (2+2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3) \times (33+3) + (3+3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444+4+4) \times (44+4) + (4+4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5) \times (55+5) + (5+5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6+6) \times (66+6) + (6+6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777+7+7) \times (77+7) + (7+7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8) \times (88+8) + (8+8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9) \times (99+9) + (9+9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{160} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1+1) \times (11-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2+2) \times (22-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3+3) \times (33-3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4+4) \times (44-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5+5) \times (55-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6+6) \times (66-6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7+7) \times (77-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8+8) \times (88-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9+9) \times (99-9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1160} &:= \frac{(111+1+1+1+1+1) \times (11-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2+2+2+2) \times (22-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3+3+3+3) \times (33-3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444+4+4+4+4+4) \times (44-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5+5+5+5) \times (55-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6+6+6+6) \times (66-6)}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777+7+7+7+7+7) \times (77-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8+8+8+8) \times (88-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9+9+9+9) \times (99-9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11160} &:= \frac{(1111+1+1+1+1+1) \times (11-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2+2+2+2) \times (22-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3+3+3+3) \times (33-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4+4+4+4+4) \times (44-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5+5+5+5+5) \times (55-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6+6+6+6+6) \times (66-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7+7+7+7+7) \times (77-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8+8+8+8) \times (88-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9+9+9+9) \times (99-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111160} &:= \frac{(11111+1+1+1+1+1) \times (11-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2+2+2+2) \times (22-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3+3+3+3) \times (33-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4+4+4+4+4) \times (44-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5+5+5+5) \times (55-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6+6+6+6+6) \times (66-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7+7+7+7+7) \times (77-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8+8+8+8) \times (88-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9+9+9+9) \times (99-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{161} &:= \frac{111 \times (1+1+1) - 11 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times (2+2+2) - 22 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times (3+3+3) - 33 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times (4+4+4) - 44 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times (5+5+5) - 55 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times (6+6+6) - 66 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times (7+7+7) - 77 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times (8+8+8) - 88 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times (9+9+9) - 99 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1661} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1+1) - 11 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2+2) - 22 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3+3) - 33 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4+4) - 44 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5+5) - 55 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6+6) - 66 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7+7) - 77 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8+8) - 88 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9+9) - 99 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{16661} &:= \frac{11111 \times (1+1+1) - 11 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{22222 \times (2+2+2) - 22 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{33333 \times (3+3+3) - 33 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 \times (4+4+4) - 44 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{55555 \times (5+5+5) - 55 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{66666 \times (6+6+6) - 66 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 \times (7+7+7) - 77 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{88888 \times (8+8+8) - 88 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{99999 \times (9+9+9) - 99 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{166661} &:= \frac{111111 \times (1+1+1) - 11 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222222 \times (2+2+2) - 22 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333333 \times (3+3+3) - 33 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (4+4+4) - 44 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555555 \times (5+5+5) - 55 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666666 \times (6+6+6) - 66 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (7+7+7) - 77 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888888 \times (8+8+8) - 88 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999999 \times (9+9+9) - 99 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{162} &:= \frac{(111-1-1-1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2-2-2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3-3-3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-4-4-4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5-5-5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6-6-6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7-7-7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8-8-8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9-9-9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1662} &:= \frac{(1111-1-1-1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222-2-2-2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333-3-3-3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-4-4-4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555-5-5-5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666-6-6-6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-7-7-7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888-8-8-8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999-9-9-9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{16662} &:= \frac{(11111-1-1-1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222-2-2-2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333-3-3-3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-4-4-4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555-5-5-5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666-6-6-6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-7-7-7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888-8-8-8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999-9-9-9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{166662} &:= \frac{(111111-1-1-1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222-2-2-2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333-3-3-3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444-4-4-4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555-5-5-5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666-6-6-6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777-7-7-7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888-8-8-8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999-9-9-9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{163} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 11 - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 22 - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 33 - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 44 - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 55 - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 66 - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 77 - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 88 - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 99 - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1263} &:= \frac{(111+1+1+1+1) \times 11 - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2+2+2) \times 22 - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3+3+3) \times 33 - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4+4+4+4) \times 44 - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5+5+5) \times 55 - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6+6+6) \times 66 - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7+7+7+7) \times 77 - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8+8+8) \times 88 - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9+9+9) \times 99 - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{12263} &:= \frac{(1111+1+1+1+1) \times 11 - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2+2+2) \times 22 - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3+3+3) \times 33 - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4+4+4+4) \times 44 - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5+5+5+5) \times 55 - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6+6+6+6) \times 66 - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777+7+7+7+7) \times 77 - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8+8+8) \times 88 - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9+9+9) \times 99 - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{122263} &:= \frac{(11111+1+1+1+1) \times 11 - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2+2+2) \times 22 - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3+3+3) \times 33 - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4+4+4+4) \times 44 - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5+5+5) \times 55 - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6+6+6+6) \times 66 - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7+7+7+7) \times 77 - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8+8+8) \times 88 - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9+9+9) \times 99 - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{164} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1264} &:= \frac{(111+1+1+1+1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2+2+2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3+3+3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4+4+4+4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5+5+5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6+6+6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7+7+7+7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8+8+8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9+9+9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{12264} &:= \frac{(1111+1+1+1+1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2+2+2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3+3+3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4+4+4+4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5+5+5+5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6+6+6+6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7+7+7+7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8+8+8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9+9+9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{122264} &:= \frac{(11111+1+1+1+1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2+2+2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3+3+3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4+4+4+4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5+5+5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6+6+6+6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7+7+7+7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8+8+8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9+9+9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{165} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1665} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{16665} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 1111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 2222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 3333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 4444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 5555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 6666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 7777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 8888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 9999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{166665} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 11111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 22222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 33333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 44444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 55555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 66666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 77777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 88888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 99999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{166} &:= \frac{111+111+111-1}{1+1} = \frac{222+222+222-2}{2+2} = \frac{333+333+333-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+444-4}{4+4} = \frac{555+555+555-5}{5+5} = \frac{666+666+666-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777+777-7}{7+7} = \frac{888+888+888-8}{8+8} = \frac{999+999+999-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1166} &:= \frac{1111+1111+111-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+2222+222-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+3333+333-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+4444+444-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+5555+555-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666+6666+666-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7777+777-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+8888+888-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+9999+999-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11166} &:= \frac{11111+11111+111-1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+22222+222-2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+33333+333-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+44444+444-4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+55555+555-5}{5+5} = \frac{66666+66666+666-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+77777+777-7}{7+7} = \frac{88888+88888+888-8}{8+8} = \frac{99999+99999+999-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111166} &:= \frac{111111+111111+111-1}{1+1} = \frac{222222+222222+222-2}{2+2} = \frac{333333+333333+333-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+444444+444-4}{4+4} = \frac{555555+555555+555-5}{5+5} = \frac{666666+666666+666-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+777777+777-7}{7+7} = \frac{888888+888888+888-8}{8+8} = \frac{999999+999999+999-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 167 &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 111 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1167 &:= \frac{1111 + 1111 + 111 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 2222 + 222 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 3333 + 333 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 4444 + 444 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 5555 + 555 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 6666 + 666 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 7777 + 777 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 8888 + 888 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 9999 + 999 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 11167 &:= \frac{11111 + 11111 + 111 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22222 + 222 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33333 + 333 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44444 + 444 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55555 + 555 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66666 + 666 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77777 + 777 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88888 + 888 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99999 + 999 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 111167 &:= \frac{111111 + 111111 + 111 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 222222 + 222 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 333333 + 333 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444444 + 444 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 555555 + 555 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 666666 + 666 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777777 + 777 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 888888 + 888 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 999999 + 999 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 168 &:= \frac{111 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{111 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{222 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{333 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{444 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{555 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{666 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{777 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{888 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{999 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1668 &:= \frac{1111 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{1111 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{2222 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{3333 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{4444 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{5555 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{6666 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{7777 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{8888 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{9999 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 16668 &:= \frac{11111 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11111 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22222 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33333 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44444 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55555 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66666 + 6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77777+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88888+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99999+9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{166668} &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{111111+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{222222+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{333333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{444444+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{555555+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{666666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{777777+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{888888+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{999999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{169} &:= \frac{111+1}{1+1} + \frac{111+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2} + \frac{222+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3} + \frac{333+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+4}{4+4} + \frac{444+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5} + \frac{555+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6} + \frac{666+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+7}{7+7} + \frac{777+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8} + \frac{888+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9} + \frac{999+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1669} &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{16669} &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11111+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22222+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33333+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44444+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55555+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66666+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77777+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88888+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99999+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{166669} &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{111111+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{222222+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{333333+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{444444+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{555555+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{666666+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{777777+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{888888+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{999999+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{170} &:= \frac{111+11}{1+1} + \frac{111-1-1}{1} = \frac{222+22}{2+2} + \frac{222-2-2}{2} = \frac{333+33}{3+3} + \frac{333-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+44}{4+4} + \frac{444-4-4}{4} = \frac{555+55}{5+5} + \frac{555-5-5}{5} = \frac{666+66}{6+6} + \frac{666-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+77}{7+7} + \frac{777-7-7}{7} = \frac{888+88}{8+8} + \frac{888-8-8}{8} = \frac{999+99}{9+9} + \frac{999-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{1670} := \frac{1111+11}{1+1} + \frac{1111-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222+22}{2+2} + \frac{2222-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333+33}{3+3} + \frac{3333-3-3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444+44}{4+4} + \frac{4444-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555+55}{5+5} + \frac{5555-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666+66}{6+6} + \frac{6666-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+77}{7+7} + \frac{7777-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888+88}{8+8} + \frac{8888-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999+99}{9+9} + \frac{9999-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{16670} &:= \frac{11111+11}{1+1} + \frac{11111-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222+22}{2+2} + \frac{22222-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333+33}{3+3} + \frac{33333-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+44}{4+4} + \frac{44444-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555+55}{5+5} + \frac{55555-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666+66}{6+6} + \frac{66666-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+77}{7+7} + \frac{77777-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888+88}{8+8} + \frac{88888-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999+99}{9+9} + \frac{99999-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{166670} &:= \frac{111111+11}{1+1} + \frac{111111-1-1}{1} = \frac{222222+22}{2+2} + \frac{222222-2-2}{2} = \frac{333333+33}{3+3} + \frac{333333-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44}{4+4} + \frac{444444-4-4}{4} = \frac{555555+55}{5+5} + \frac{555555-5-5}{5} = \frac{666666+66}{6+6} + \frac{666666-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77}{7+7} + \frac{777777-7-7}{7} = \frac{888888+88}{8+8} + \frac{888888-8-8}{8} = \frac{999999+99}{9+9} + \frac{999999-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{171} &:= \frac{111+11}{1+1} + \frac{111-1}{1} = \frac{222+22}{2+2} + \frac{222-2}{2} = \frac{333+33}{3+3} + \frac{333-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+44}{4+4} + \frac{444-4}{4} = \frac{555+55}{5+5} + \frac{555-5}{5} = \frac{666+66}{6+6} + \frac{666-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+77}{7+7} + \frac{777-7}{7} = \frac{888+88}{8+8} + \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{999+99}{9+9} + \frac{999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1671} &:= \frac{1111+11}{1+1} + \frac{1111-1}{1} = \frac{2222+22}{2+2} + \frac{2222-2}{2} = \frac{3333+33}{3+3} + \frac{3333-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+44}{4+4} + \frac{4444-4}{4} = \frac{5555+55}{5+5} + \frac{5555-5}{5} = \frac{6666+66}{6+6} + \frac{6666-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+77}{7+7} + \frac{7777-7}{7} = \frac{8888+88}{8+8} + \frac{8888-8}{8} = \frac{9999+99}{9+9} + \frac{9999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{16671} &:= \frac{11111+11}{1+1} + \frac{11111-1}{1} = \frac{22222+22}{2+2} + \frac{22222-2}{2} = \frac{33333+33}{3+3} + \frac{33333-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+44}{4+4} + \frac{44444-4}{4} = \frac{55555+55}{5+5} + \frac{55555-5}{5} = \frac{66666+66}{6+6} + \frac{66666-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+77}{7+7} + \frac{77777-7}{7} = \frac{88888+88}{8+8} + \frac{88888-8}{8} = \frac{99999+99}{9+9} + \frac{99999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{166671} &:= \frac{111111+11}{1+1} + \frac{111111-1}{1} = \frac{222222+22}{2+2} + \frac{222222-2}{2} = \frac{333333+33}{3+3} + \frac{333333-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44}{4+4} + \frac{444444-4}{4} = \frac{555555+55}{5+5} + \frac{555555-5}{5} = \frac{666666+66}{6+6} + \frac{666666-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77}{7+7} + \frac{777777-7}{7} = \frac{888888+88}{8+8} + \frac{888888-8}{8} = \frac{999999+99}{9+9} + \frac{999999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 172 &:= \frac{111+11}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1} = \frac{222+22}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2} = \frac{333+33}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+44}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4} = \frac{555+55}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5} = \frac{666+66}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+77}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7} = \frac{888+88}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8} = \frac{999+99}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1672 &:= \frac{1111+11}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{1} = \frac{2222+22}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{2} = \frac{3333+33}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+44}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{4} = \frac{5555+55}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{5} = \frac{6666+66}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+77}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{7} = \frac{8888+88}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{8} = \frac{9999+99}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 16672 &:= \frac{11111+11}{1+1} + \frac{11111}{1} = \frac{22222+22}{2+2} + \frac{22222}{2} = \frac{33333+33}{3+3} + \frac{33333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+44}{4+4} + \frac{44444}{4} = \frac{55555+55}{5+5} + \frac{55555}{5} = \frac{66666+66}{6+6} + \frac{66666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+77}{7+7} + \frac{77777}{7} = \frac{88888+88}{8+8} + \frac{88888}{8} = \frac{99999+99}{9+9} + \frac{99999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 166672 &:= \frac{111111+11}{1+1} + \frac{111111}{1} = \frac{222222+22}{2+2} + \frac{222222}{2} = \frac{333333+33}{3+3} + \frac{333333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44}{4+4} + \frac{444444}{4} = \frac{555555+55}{5+5} + \frac{555555}{5} = \frac{666666+66}{6+6} + \frac{666666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77}{7+7} + \frac{777777}{7} = \frac{888888+88}{8+8} + \frac{888888}{8} = \frac{999999+99}{9+9} + \frac{999999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 173 &:= \frac{111+11}{1+1} + \frac{111+1}{1} = \frac{222+22}{2+2} + \frac{222+2}{2} = \frac{333+33}{3+3} + \frac{333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+44}{4+4} + \frac{444+4}{4} = \frac{555+55}{5+5} + \frac{555+5}{5} = \frac{666+66}{6+6} + \frac{666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+77}{7+7} + \frac{777+7}{7} = \frac{888+88}{8+8} + \frac{888+8}{8} = \frac{999+99}{9+9} + \frac{999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1673 &:= \frac{1111+11}{1+1} + \frac{1111+1}{1} = \frac{2222+22}{2+2} + \frac{2222+2}{2} = \frac{3333+33}{3+3} + \frac{3333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+44}{4+4} + \frac{4444+4}{4} = \frac{5555+55}{5+5} + \frac{5555+5}{5} = \frac{6666+66}{6+6} + \frac{6666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+77}{7+7} + \frac{7777+7}{7} = \frac{8888+88}{8+8} + \frac{8888+8}{8} = \frac{9999+99}{9+9} + \frac{9999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 16673 &:= \frac{11111+11}{1+1} + \frac{11111+1}{1} = \frac{22222+22}{2+2} + \frac{22222+2}{2} = \frac{33333+33}{3+3} + \frac{33333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+44}{4+4} + \frac{44444+4}{4} = \frac{55555+55}{5+5} + \frac{55555+5}{5} = \frac{66666+66}{6+6} + \frac{66666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+77}{7+7} + \frac{77777+7}{7} = \frac{88888+88}{8+8} + \frac{88888+8}{8} = \frac{99999+99}{9+9} + \frac{99999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{166673} &:= \frac{111111+11}{1+1} + \frac{111111+1}{1} = \frac{222222+22}{2+2} + \frac{222222+2}{2} = \frac{333333+33}{3+3} + \frac{333333+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+44}{4+4} + \frac{444444+4}{4} = \frac{555555+55}{5+5} + \frac{555555+5}{5} = \frac{666666+66}{6+6} + \frac{666666+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+77}{7+7} + \frac{777777+7}{7} = \frac{888888+88}{8+8} + \frac{888888+8}{8} = \frac{999999+99}{9+9} + \frac{999999+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{174} &:= \frac{111+11}{1+1} + \frac{111+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+22}{2+2} + \frac{222+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+33}{3+3} + \frac{333+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444+44}{4+4} + \frac{444+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+55}{5+5} + \frac{555+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+66}{6+6} + \frac{666+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777+77}{7+7} + \frac{777+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+88}{8+8} + \frac{888+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+99}{9+9} + \frac{999+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1674} &:= \frac{1111+11}{1+1} + \frac{1111+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+22}{2+2} + \frac{2222+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+33}{3+3} + \frac{3333+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+44}{4+4} + \frac{4444+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+55}{5+5} + \frac{5555+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+66}{6+6} + \frac{6666+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777+77}{7+7} + \frac{7777+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+88}{8+8} + \frac{8888+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+99}{9+9} + \frac{9999+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{16674} &:= \frac{11111+11}{1+1} + \frac{11111+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+22}{2+2} + \frac{22222+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+33}{3+3} + \frac{33333+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444+44}{4+4} + \frac{44444+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+55}{5+5} + \frac{55555+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+66}{6+6} + \frac{66666+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777+77}{7+7} + \frac{77777+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+88}{8+8} + \frac{88888+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+99}{9+9} + \frac{99999+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{166674} &:= \frac{111111+11}{1+1} + \frac{111111+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+22}{2+2} + \frac{222222+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+33}{3+3} + \frac{333333+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+44}{4+4} + \frac{444444+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+55}{5+5} + \frac{555555+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+66}{6+6} + \frac{666666+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+77}{7+7} + \frac{777777+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+88}{8+8} + \frac{888888+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+99}{9+9} + \frac{999999+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{175} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1+1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2+2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3+3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4+4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5+5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6+6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7+7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8+8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9+9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1775} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1+1) \times 111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2+2) \times 222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3+3) \times 333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4+4) \times 444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5+5) \times 555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6+6) \times 666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7+7) \times 777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8+8) \times 888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9+9) \times 999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{17775} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1+1) \times 1111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2+2) \times 2222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3+3) \times 3333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4+4) \times 4444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5+5) \times 5555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6+6) \times 6666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7+7) \times 7777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8+8) \times 8888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9+9) \times 9999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{177775} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1+1) \times 11111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2+2) \times 22222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3+3) \times 33333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4+4) \times 44444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5+5) \times 55555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6+6) \times 66666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7+7) \times 77777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8+8) \times 88888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9+9) \times 99999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{176} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1+1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2+2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3+3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4+4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5+5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6+6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7+7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8+8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9+9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1776} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1+1) \times 111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2+2) \times 222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3+3) \times 333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4+4) \times 444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5+5) \times 555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6+6) \times 666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7+7) \times 777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8+8) \times 888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9+9) \times 999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{17776} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1+1) \times 1111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2+2) \times 2222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3+3) \times 3333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4+4) \times 4444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5+5) \times 5555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6+6) \times 6666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7+7) \times 7777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8+8) \times 8888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9+9) \times 9999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{177776} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1+1) \times 11111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2+2) \times 22222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3+3) \times 33333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4+4) \times 44444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5+5) \times 55555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6+6) \times 66666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7+7) \times 77777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8+8) \times 88888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9+9) \times 99999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{177} := \frac{(11+1) \times 11 + (1+1) \times 111}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2) \times 22 + (2+2) \times 222}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3) \times 33 + (3+3) \times 333}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44+4) \times 44 + (4+4) \times 444}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5) \times 55 + (5+5) \times 555}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6) \times 66 + (6+6) \times 666}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7) \times 77 + (7+7) \times 777}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8) \times 88 + (8+8) \times 888}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9) \times 99 + (9+9) \times 999}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1777} &:= \frac{(11+1) \times 11 + (1+1) \times 1111}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2) \times 22 + (2+2) \times 2222}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3) \times 33 + (3+3) \times 3333}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4) \times 44 + (4+4) \times 4444}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5) \times 55 + (5+5) \times 5555}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6) \times 66 + (6+6) \times 6666}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7) \times 77 + (7+7) \times 7777}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8) \times 88 + (8+8) \times 8888}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9) \times 99 + (9+9) \times 9999}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{17777} &:= \frac{(11+1) \times 11 + (1+1) \times 11111}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2) \times 22 + (2+2) \times 22222}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3) \times 33 + (3+3) \times 33333}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4) \times 44 + (4+4) \times 44444}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5) \times 55 + (5+5) \times 55555}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6) \times 66 + (6+6) \times 66666}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7) \times 77 + (7+7) \times 77777}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8) \times 88 + (8+8) \times 88888}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9) \times 99 + (9+9) \times 99999}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{177777} &:= \frac{(11+1) \times 11 + (1+1) \times 111111}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2) \times 22 + (2+2) \times 222222}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3) \times 33 + (3+3) \times 333333}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4) \times 44 + (4+4) \times 444444}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5) \times 55 + (5+5) \times 555555}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6) \times 66 + (6+6) \times 666666}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7) \times 77 + (7+7) \times 777777}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8) \times 88 + (8+8) \times 888888}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9) \times 99 + (9+9) \times 999999}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{178} &:= \frac{(111-11-11) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222-22-22) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333-33-33) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-44-44) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555-55-55) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666-66-66) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-77-77) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888-88-88) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999-99-99) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2178} &:= \frac{(1111-11-11) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222-22-22) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333-33-33) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-44-44) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555-55-55) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666-66-66) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-77-77) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888-88-88) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999-99-99) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22178} &:= \frac{(11111-11-11) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222-22-22) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333-33-33) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-44-44) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555-55-55) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666-66-66) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-77-77) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888-88-88) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999-99-99) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222178} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 - 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 - 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 - 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 - 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 - 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 - 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 - 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 - 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 - 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{179} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2179} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 - 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 - 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 - 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 - 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 - 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 - 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77 - 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 - 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 - 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22179} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 - 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 - 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 - 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 - 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 - 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 - 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77 - 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 - 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 - 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222179} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 - 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 - 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 - 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 - 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 - 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 - 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 - 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 - 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 - 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{180} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1680} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (222 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (333 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (444 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (555 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (666 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times (777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times (888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times (999+9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{16680} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times (1111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times (2222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times (3333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times (4444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times (5555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times (6666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times (7777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times (8888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times (9999+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{166680} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times (11111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times (22222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times (33333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times (44444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times (55555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times (66666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times (77777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times (88888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times (99999+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{181} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times (11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times (22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times (33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times (44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times (55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times (66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times (77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times (88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times (99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1381} &:= \frac{(111+1+1+1+1) \times (11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2+2+2) \times (22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3+3+3) \times (33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4+4+4+4) \times (44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5+5+5) \times (55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6+6+6) \times (66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7+7+7+7) \times (77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8+8+8) \times (88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9+9+9) \times (99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{13381} &:= \frac{(1111+1+1+1+1) \times (11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2+2+2) \times (22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3+3+3) \times (33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4+4+4+4) \times (44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5+5+5+5) \times (55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6+6+6+6) \times (66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7+7+7+7) \times (77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8+8+8) \times (88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9+9+9) \times (99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{133381} &:= \frac{(11111+1+1+1+1) \times (11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2+2+2) \times (22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3+3+3) \times (33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4+4+4+4) \times (44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5+5+5) \times (55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6+6+6+6) \times (66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7+7+7+7) \times (77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8+8+8) \times (88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9+9+9) \times (99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{182} := \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times (11+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times (22+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times (33+3+3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times (44+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times (55+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times (66+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times (77+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times (88+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times (99+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1482} &:= \frac{(111+1+1+1) \times (11+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2+2) \times (22+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3+3) \times (33+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4+4+4) \times (44+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5+5) \times (55+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6+6) \times (66+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7+7+7) \times (77+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8+8) \times (88+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9+9) \times (99+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{14482} &:= \frac{(1111+1+1+1) \times (11+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2+2) \times (22+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3+3) \times (33+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4+4+4) \times (44+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5+5+5) \times (55+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6+6+6) \times (66+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7+7+7) \times (77+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8+8) \times (88+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9+9) \times (99+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{144482} &:= \frac{(11111+1+1+1) \times (11+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2+2) \times (22+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3+3) \times (33+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4+4+4) \times (44+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5+5) \times (55+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6+6+6) \times (66+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7+7+7) \times (77+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8+8) \times (88+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9+9) \times (99+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{183} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times (11+1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times (22+2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times (33+3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times (44+4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times (55+5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times (66+6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times (77+7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times (88+8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times (99+9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1483} &:= \frac{(111+1+1+1) \times (11+1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2+2) \times (22+2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3+3) \times (33+3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4+4+4) \times (44+4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5+5) \times (55+5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6+6) \times (66+6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7+7+7) \times (77+7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8+8) \times (88+8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9+9) \times (99+9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{14483} &:= \frac{(1111+1+1+1) \times (11+1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2+2) \times (22+2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3+3) \times (33+3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4+4+4) \times (44+4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5+5+5) \times (55+5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6+6+6) \times (66+6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7+7+7) \times (77+7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8+8) \times (88+8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9+9) \times (99+9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{144483} &:= \frac{(11111 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{184} &:= \frac{(111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1684} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{16684} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{166684} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{185} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(11 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(22 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(33 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(44 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(55 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(66 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(77 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(88 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(99 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{185185} := \frac{(1111111 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(11 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(22 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(33 + 3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444444 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(44 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(55 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(66 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(77 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(88 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(99 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{185185185} &:= \frac{(1111111111 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(11 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222222 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(22 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333333 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(33 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444444 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(44 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555555 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(55 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666666 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(66 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777777 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(77 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888888 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(88 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999999 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(99 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{185185185185} &:= \frac{(111111111111 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(11 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222222222 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(22 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333333333 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(33 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444444444 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(44 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555555555 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(55 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666666666 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(66 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777777777 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(77 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888888888 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(88 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999999999 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(99 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{186} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1086} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{10086} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{100086} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 187 &:= \frac{(11+11-1) \times (11-1-1) - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22-2) \times (22-2-2) - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33-3) \times (33-3-3) - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44-4) \times (44-4-4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55-5) \times (55-5-5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66-6) \times (66-6-6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77-7) \times (77-7-7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88-8) \times (88-8-8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99-9) \times (99-9-9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1087 &:= \frac{(111+11-1) \times (11-1-1) - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+22-2) \times (22-2-2) - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+33-3) \times (33-3-3) - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+44-4) \times (44-4-4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+55-5) \times (55-5-5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+66-6) \times (66-6-6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+77-7) \times (77-7-7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+88-8) \times (88-8-8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+99-9) \times (99-9-9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10087 &:= \frac{(1111+11-1) \times (11-1-1) - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22-2) \times (22-2-2) - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33-3) \times (33-3-3) - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+44-4) \times (44-4-4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55-5) \times (55-5-5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66-6) \times (66-6-6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+77-7) \times (77-7-7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+88-8) \times (88-8-8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+99-9) \times (99-9-9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 100087 &:= \frac{(11111+11-1) \times (11-1-1) - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22-2) \times (22-2-2) - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33-3) \times (33-3-3) - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+44-4) \times (44-4-4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55-5) \times (55-5-5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66-6) \times (66-6-6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+77-7) \times (77-7-7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88-8) \times (88-8-8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99-9) \times (99-9-9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 188 &:= \frac{(11+11-1) \times (11-1-1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22-2) \times (22-2-2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33-3) \times (33-3-3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44-4) \times (44-4-4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55-5) \times (55-5-5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66-6) \times (66-6-6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77-7) \times (77-7-7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88-8) \times (88-8-8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99-9) \times (99-9-9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1088 &:= \frac{(111+11-1) \times (11-1-1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+22-2) \times (22-2-2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+33-3) \times (33-3-3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+44-4) \times (44-4-4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+55-5) \times (55-5-5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+66-6) \times (66-6-6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+77-7) \times (77-7-7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+88-8) \times (88-8-8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+99-9) \times (99-9-9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10088 &:= \frac{(1111+11-1) \times (11-1-1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22-2) \times (22-2-2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33-3) \times (33-3-3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+44-4) \times (44-4-4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55-5) \times (55-5-5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66-6) \times (66-6-6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+77-7) \times (77-7-7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+88-8) \times (88-8-8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+99-9) \times (99-9-9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{100088} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{189} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1089} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{10089} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{100089} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{190} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{1090} := \frac{(111 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{10090} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{100090} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{191} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1091} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{10091} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{100091} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{192} &:= \frac{(11+11-1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22-2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33-3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44-4) \times (44-4-4) + 4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55-5) \times (55-5-5) + 5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66-6) \times (66-6-6) + 6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77-7) \times (77-7-7) + 7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88-8) \times (88-8-8) + 8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99-9) \times (99-9-9) + 9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1092} &:= \frac{(111+11-1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+22-2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+33-3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+44-4) \times (44-4-4) + 4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+55-5) \times (55-5-5) + 5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+66-6) \times (66-6-6) + 6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+77-7) \times (77-7-7) + 7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+88-8) \times (88-8-8) + 8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+99-9) \times (99-9-9) + 9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{10092} &:= \frac{(1111+11-1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22-2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33-3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+44-4) \times (44-4-4) + 4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55-5) \times (55-5-5) + 5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66-6) \times (66-6-6) + 6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+77-7) \times (77-7-7) + 7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+88-8) \times (88-8-8) + 8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+99-9) \times (99-9-9) + 9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{100092} &:= \frac{(11111+11-1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22-2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33-3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+44-4) \times (44-4-4) + 4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55-5) \times (55-5-5) + 5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66-6) \times (66-6-6) + 6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+77-7) \times (77-7-7) + 7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88-8) \times (88-8-8) + 8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99-9) \times (99-9-9) + 9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{193} &:= \frac{(111-11-1-1-1) \times (1+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222-22-2-2-2) \times (2+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333-33-3-3-3) \times (3+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-44-4-4-4) \times (4+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555-55-5-5-5) \times (5+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666-66-6-6-6) \times (6+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-77-7-7-7) \times (7+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888-88-8-8-8) \times (8+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999-99-9-9-9) \times (9+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2193} &:= \frac{(1111-11-1-1-1) \times (1+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222-22-2-2-2) \times (2+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333-33-3-3-3) \times (3+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-44-4-4-4) \times (4+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555-55-5-5-5) \times (5+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666-66-6-6-6) \times (6+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-77-7-7-7) \times (7+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888-88-8-8-8) \times (8+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999-99-9-9-9) \times (9+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22193} &:= \frac{(11111-11-1-1-1) \times (1+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222-22-2-2-2) \times (2+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333-33-3-3-3) \times (3+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-44-4-4-4) \times (4+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555-55-5-5-5) \times (5+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666-66-6-6-6) \times (6+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-77-7-7-7) \times (7+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888-88-8-8-8) \times (8+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999-99-9-9-9) \times (9+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{222193} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{194} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1694} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (222 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (333 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (444 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (555 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (666 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (777 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (888 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (999 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{16694} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1111 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2222 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3333 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4444 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5555 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6666 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7777 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8888 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9999 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{166694} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (11111 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (22222 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (33333 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44444 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55555 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66666 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (77777 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (88888 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (99999 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{195} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{1695} := \frac{(11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (222 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (333 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times (444+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times (555+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times (666+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times (777+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times (888+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times (999+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{16695} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times (1111+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times (2222+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times (3333+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times (4444+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times (5555+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times (6666+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times (7777+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times (8888+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times (9999+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{166695} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times (11111+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times (22222+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times (33333+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times (44444+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times (55555+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times (66666+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times (77777+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times (88888+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times (99999+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{196} &:= \frac{111+111-11-11-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{222+222-22-22-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{333+333-33-33-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444-44-44-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{555+555-55-55-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{666+666-66-66-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777-77-77-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{888+888-88-88-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{999+999-99-99-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1196} &:= \frac{1111+111-11-11-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222+222-22-22-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333+333-33-33-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+444-44-44-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555+555-55-55-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666+666-66-66-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+777-77-77-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888+888-88-88-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999+999-99-99-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11196} &:= \frac{11111+111-11-11-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222+222-22-22-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333+333-33-33-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+444-44-44-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555+555-55-55-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666+666-66-66-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+777-77-77-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888+888-88-88-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999+999-99-99-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111196} &:= \frac{111111+111-11-11-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{222222+222-22-22-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{333333+333-33-33-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+444-44-44-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{555555+555-55-55-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{666666+666-66-66-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+777-77-77-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{888888+888-88-88-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{999999+999-99-99-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 197 &:= \frac{111 + 111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1197 &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 11197 &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 111197 &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 198 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1) \times (11 + 11)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2) \times (22 + 22)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3) \times (33 + 33)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4) \times (44 + 44)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5) \times (55 + 55)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6) \times (66 + 66)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7) \times (77 + 77)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8) \times (88 + 88)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9) \times (99 + 99)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1998 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1) \times (111 + 111)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2) \times (222 + 222)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3) \times (333 + 333)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4) \times (444 + 444)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5) \times (555 + 555)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6) \times (666 + 666)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7) \times (777 + 777)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8) \times (888 + 888)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9) \times (999 + 999)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19998 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1) \times (1111 + 1111)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2) \times (2222 + 2222)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3) \times (3333 + 3333)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4) \times (4444 + 4444)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5) \times (5555 + 5555)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6) \times (6666 + 6666)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7) \times (7777 + 7777)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8) \times (8888 + 8888)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9) \times (9999 + 9999)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 199998 &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times (11111+11111)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times (22222+22222)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times (33333+33333)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times (44444+44444)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times (55555+55555)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times (66666+66666)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times (77777+77777)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times (88888+88888)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times (99999+99999)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 199 &:= \frac{111+111-11-11-1}{1} = \frac{222+222-22-22-2}{2} = \frac{333+333-33-33-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444+444-44-44-4}{4} = \frac{555+555-55-55-5}{5} = \frac{666+666-66-66-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777+777-77-77-7}{7} = \frac{888+888-88-88-8}{8} = \frac{999+999-99-99-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1199 &:= \frac{1111+111-11-11-1}{1} = \frac{2222+222-22-22-2}{2} = \frac{3333+333-33-33-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+444-44-44-4}{4} = \frac{5555+555-55-55-5}{5} = \frac{6666+666-66-66-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777+777-77-77-7}{7} = \frac{8888+888-88-88-8}{8} = \frac{9999+999-99-99-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 11199 &:= \frac{11111+111-11-11-1}{1} = \frac{22222+222-22-22-2}{2} = \frac{33333+333-33-33-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444+444-44-44-4}{4} = \frac{55555+555-55-55-5}{5} = \frac{66666+666-66-66-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777+777-77-77-7}{7} = \frac{88888+888-88-88-8}{8} = \frac{99999+999-99-99-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 111199 &:= \frac{111111+111-11-11-1}{1} = \frac{222222+222-22-22-2}{2} = \frac{333333+333-33-33-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+444-44-44-4}{4} = \frac{555555+555-55-55-5}{5} = \frac{666666+666-66-66-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+777-77-77-7}{7} = \frac{888888+888-88-88-8}{8} = \frac{999999+999-99-99-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 200 &:= \frac{111+111-11-11}{1} = \frac{222+222-22-22}{2} = \frac{333+333-33-33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444+444-44-44}{4} = \frac{555+555-55-55}{5} = \frac{666+666-66-66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777+777-77-77}{7} = \frac{888+888-88-88}{8} = \frac{999+999-99-99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1200 &:= \frac{1111+111-11-11}{1} = \frac{2222+222-22-22}{2} = \frac{3333+333-33-33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+444-44-44}{4} = \frac{5555+555-55-55}{5} = \frac{6666+666-66-66}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 99 - 99}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11200} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111200} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{201} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) - 11 \times 1}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) - 22 \times 2}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) - 33 \times 3}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) - 44 \times 4}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) - 55 \times 5}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) - 66 \times 6}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) - 77 \times 7}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) - 88 \times 8}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) - 99 \times 9}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{20201} &:= \frac{111111 \times (1+1) - 11 \times 1}{11 \times 1} = \frac{222222 \times (2+2) - 22 \times 2}{22 \times 2} = \frac{333333 \times (3+3) - 33 \times 3}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (4+4) - 44 \times 4}{44 \times 4} = \frac{555555 \times (5+5) - 55 \times 5}{55 \times 5} = \frac{666666 \times (6+6) - 66 \times 6}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (7+7) - 77 \times 7}{77 \times 7} = \frac{888888 \times (8+8) - 88 \times 8}{88 \times 8} = \frac{999999 \times (9+9) - 99 \times 9}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2020201} &:= \frac{11111111 \times (1+1) - 11 \times 1}{11 \times 1} = \frac{22222222 \times (2+2) - 22 \times 2}{22 \times 2} = \frac{33333333 \times (3+3) - 33 \times 3}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (4+4) - 44 \times 4}{44 \times 4} = \frac{55555555 \times (5+5) - 55 \times 5}{55 \times 5} = \frac{66666666 \times (6+6) - 66 \times 6}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 \times (7+7) - 77 \times 7}{77 \times 7} = \frac{88888888 \times (8+8) - 88 \times 8}{88 \times 8} = \frac{99999999 \times (9+9) - 99 \times 9}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{202020201} &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (1+1) - 11 \times 1}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222222222 \times (2+2) - 22 \times 2}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333333333 \times (3+3) - 33 \times 3}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (4+4) - 44 \times 4}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555555555 \times (5+5) - 55 \times 5}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666666666 \times (6+6) - 66 \times 6}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (7+7) - 77 \times 7}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888888888 \times (8+8) - 88 \times 8}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999999999 \times (9+9) - 99 \times 9}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{202} := \frac{(111 - 11 + 1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 + 2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 + 3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2202} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22202} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222202} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{203} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2020203} &:= \frac{11111111 \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{22222222 \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{33333333 \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{55555555 \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{66666666 \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{88888888 \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{99999999 \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{202020203} &:= \frac{111111111111 \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{222222222222 \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{333333333333 \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{444444444444 \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{555555555555 \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{666666666666 \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{777777777777 \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{888888888888 \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{999999999999 \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2020202020203} &:= \frac{1111111111111111 \times (1+1) + 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222222222222222 \times (2+2) + 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333333333333333 \times (3+3) + 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444444444 \times (4+4) + 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555555555555555 \times (5+5) + 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666666666666666 \times (6+6) + 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777777777 \times (7+7) + 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888888888888888 \times (8+8) + 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999999999999999 \times (9+9) + 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{204} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + (1+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + (2+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + (3+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + (4+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + (5+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + (6+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + (7+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + (8+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + (9+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{20404} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + (1+1) \times 111111}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + (2+2) \times 222222}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + (3+3) \times 333333}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + (4+4) \times 444444}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + (5+5) \times 555555}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + (6+6) \times 666666}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + (7+7) \times 777777}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + (8+8) \times 888888}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + (9+9) \times 999999}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{202020404} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + (1+1) \times 1111111111}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + (2+2) \times 2222222222}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + (3+3) \times 3333333333}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + (4+4) \times 4444444444}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + (5+5) \times 5555555555}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + (6+6) \times 6666666666}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + (7+7) \times 7777777777}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + (8+8) \times 8888888888}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + (9+9) \times 9999999999}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{20202020404} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + (1+1) \times 111111111111}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + (2+2) \times 222222222222}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + (3+3) \times 333333333333}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + (4+4) \times 444444444444}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + (5+5) \times 555555555555}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + (6+6) \times 666666666666}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + (7+7) \times 777777777777}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + (8+8) \times 888888888888}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + (9+9) \times 999999999999}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{205} &:= \frac{111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1205} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11205} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111205} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{206} &:= \frac{111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1206} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11206} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111206} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{207} := \frac{111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1207} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11207} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111207} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{208} &:= \frac{111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1208} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11208} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111208} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{209} &:= \frac{111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1209} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{11209} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111209} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{210} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1210} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11210} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111210} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 - 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 - 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 - 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 - 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 - 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 - 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 - 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 - 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 - 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{211} &:= \frac{111 + 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1211} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11211} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111211} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{212} := \frac{111 + 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 - 33 + 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444 + 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1212} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11212} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111212} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{213} &:= \frac{111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1213} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11213} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111213} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{214} &:= \frac{111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1214} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11214} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111214} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{215} &:= \frac{111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1215} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777+777-77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+888-88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+999-99+9+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11215} &:= \frac{11111+111-11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+222-22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+333-33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+444-44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+555-55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+666-66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+777-77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+888-88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+999-99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111215} &:= \frac{111111+111-11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+222-22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+333-33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+444-44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+555-55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+666-66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+777-77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+888-88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+999-99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{216} &:= \frac{111+111-11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+222-22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+333-33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444-44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+555-55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+666-66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777-77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+888-88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+999-99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1216} &:= \frac{1111+111-11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+222-22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+333-33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+444-44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+555-55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+666-66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+777-77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+888-88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+999-99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111216} &:= \frac{11111+111-11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+222-22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+333-33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+444-44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+555-55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+666-66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+777-77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+888-88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+999-99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1111216} &:= \frac{111111+111-11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+222-22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+333-33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+444-44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+555-55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+666-66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+777-77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+888-88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+999-99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{217} := \frac{111+111-11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+222-22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+333-33+3+3+3+3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1217} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11217} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111217} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{218} &:= \frac{111 + 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1218} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11218} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111218} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{219} &:= \frac{111 + 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777 + 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1219} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{11219} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111219} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{220} &:= \frac{111 + 111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444 + 444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777 + 777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1220} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 6 - 6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 9 - 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11220} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111220} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{221} &:= \frac{111 + 111 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1221} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11221} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111221} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{222} := \frac{111 + 111}{1} = \frac{222 + 222}{2} = \frac{333 + 333}{3} = \frac{444 + 444}{4} = \frac{555 + 555}{5} = \frac{666 + 666}{6} = \frac{777 + 777}{7} = \frac{888 + 888}{8} = \frac{999 + 999}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{1222} := \frac{1111+111}{1} = \frac{2222+222}{2} = \frac{3333+333}{3} = \frac{4444+444}{4} = \frac{5555+555}{5} = \frac{6666+666}{6} = \frac{7777+777}{7} = \frac{8888+888}{8} = \frac{9999+999}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{11222} := \frac{11111+111}{1} = \frac{22222+222}{2} = \frac{33333+333}{3} = \frac{44444+444}{4} = \frac{55555+555}{5} = \frac{66666+666}{6} = \frac{77777+777}{7} = \frac{88888+888}{8} = \frac{99999+999}{9}$$

$$\mathbf{111222} := \frac{111111+111}{1} = \frac{222222+222}{2} = \frac{333333+333}{3} = \frac{444444+444}{4} = \frac{555555+555}{5} = \frac{666666+666}{6} = \frac{777777+777}{7} = \frac{888888+888}{8} = \frac{999999+999}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{223} &:= \frac{111+111+1}{1} = \frac{222+222+2}{2} = \frac{333+333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+4}{4} = \frac{555+555+5}{5} = \frac{666+666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777+7}{7} = \frac{888+888+8}{8} = \frac{999+999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1223} &:= \frac{1111+111+1}{1} = \frac{2222+222+2}{2} = \frac{3333+333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+444+4}{4} = \frac{5555+555+5}{5} = \frac{6666+666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+777+7}{7} = \frac{8888+888+8}{8} = \frac{9999+999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11223} &:= \frac{11111+111+1}{1} = \frac{22222+222+2}{2} = \frac{33333+333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+444+4}{4} = \frac{55555+555+5}{5} = \frac{66666+666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+777+7}{7} = \frac{88888+888+8}{8} = \frac{99999+999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111223} &:= \frac{111111+111+1}{1} = \frac{222222+222+2}{2} = \frac{333333+333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+444+4}{4} = \frac{555555+555+5}{5} = \frac{666666+666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+777+7}{7} = \frac{888888+888+8}{8} = \frac{999999+999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{224} &:= \frac{111+111+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+222+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+333+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+555+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+666+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+888+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+999+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1224} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11224} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111224} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{225} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1225} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11225} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111225} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{226} &:= \frac{111+111+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+222+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+333+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+555+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+666+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+888+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+999+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1226} &:= \frac{1111+111+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+222+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+333+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+444+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+555+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+666+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+777+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+888+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+999+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11226} &:= \frac{11111+111+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+222+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+333+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+444+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+555+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+666+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+777+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+888+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+999+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111226} &:= \frac{111111+111+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+222+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+333+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+444+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+555+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+666+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+777+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+888+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+999+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{227} &:= \frac{111+111+1+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+222+2+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+333+3+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+4+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+555+5+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+666+6+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777+7+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+888+8+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+999+9+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1227} &:= \frac{1111+111+1+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+222+2+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+333+3+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+444+4+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+555+5+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+666+6+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+777+7+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+888+8+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+999+9+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11227} &:= \frac{11111+111+1+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+222+2+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+333+3+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+444+4+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+555+5+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+666+6+6+6+6+6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111227} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{228} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1228} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11228} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111228} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{229} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{1229} := \frac{1111 + 111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11229} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111229} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{230} &:= \frac{11 + 111 + 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 222 + 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 333 + 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 444 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 555 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 666 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 777 + 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 888 + 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 999 + 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1230} &:= \frac{11 + 111 + 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 222 + 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 333 + 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 444 + 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 555 + 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 666 + 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 777 + 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 888 + 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 999 + 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11230} &:= \frac{11 + 111 + 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 222 + 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 333 + 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 444 + 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 555 + 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 666 + 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 777 + 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 888 + 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 999 + 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111230} &:= \frac{11 + 111 + 111111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22 + 222 + 222222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33 + 333 + 333333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 444 + 444444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55 + 555 + 555555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66 + 666 + 666666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 777 + 777777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88 + 888 + 888888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99 + 999 + 999999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{231} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1231} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11231} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111231} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{232} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1232} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11232} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111232} &:= \frac{11111 + 1111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{233} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 11}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 22}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 44}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 55}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 77}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 88}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1233} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 11}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 22}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 44}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 55}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 77}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 88}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11233} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 11}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 22}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 44}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 55}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 77}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 88}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111233} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 11}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 22}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 44}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 55}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 77}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 88}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{234} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1234} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 66 + 6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 99 + 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11234} &:= \frac{11111 + 1111 + 111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 2222 + 222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111234} &:= \frac{111111 + 1111 + 111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 2222 + 222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{235} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1235} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11235} &:= \frac{11111 + 1111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 2222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111235} &:= \frac{111111 + 1111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 2222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{236} := \frac{111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1236} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11236} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111236} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{237} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1237} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11237} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111237} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{238} &:= \frac{(11 + 11) \times 11 - 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22) \times 22 - 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33) \times 33 - 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44) \times 44 - 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55) \times 55 - 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66) \times 66 - 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77) \times 77 - 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88) \times 88 - 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99) \times 99 - 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2438} &:= \frac{(11 + 11) \times 111 - 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22) \times 222 - 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33) \times 333 - 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44) \times 444 - 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55) \times 555 - 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66) \times 666 - 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77) \times 777 - 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88) \times 888 - 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99) \times 999 - 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{24438} &:= \frac{(11 + 11) \times 1111 - 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22) \times 2222 - 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33) \times 3333 - 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44) \times 4444 - 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55) \times 5555 - 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66) \times 6666 - 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77) \times 7777 - 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88) \times 8888 - 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99) \times 9999 - 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{244438} &:= \frac{(11 + 11) \times 11111 - 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22) \times 22222 - 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33) \times 33333 - 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44) \times 44444 - 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55) \times 55555 - 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66) \times 66666 - 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77) \times 77777 - 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88) \times 88888 - 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99) \times 99999 - 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{239} &:= \frac{(11 + 11) \times 11 - 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22) \times 22 - 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33) \times 33 - 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44) \times 44 - 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55) \times 55 - 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66) \times 66 - 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77) \times 77 - 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88) \times 88 - 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99) \times 99 - 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2439} &:= \frac{(11 + 11) \times 111 - 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22) \times 222 - 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33) \times 333 - 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44) \times 444 - 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55) \times 555 - 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66) \times 666 - 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77+77) \times 777 - 7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 888 - 8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 999 - 9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{24439} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 1111 - 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 2222 - 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 3333 - 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 4444 - 4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 5555 - 5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 6666 - 6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 7777 - 7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 8888 - 8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 9999 - 9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{244439} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11111 - 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22222 - 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33333 - 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44444 - 4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55555 - 5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66666 - 6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77777 - 7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88888 - 8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99999 - 9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{240} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 - 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 - 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 - 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 - 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 - 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 - 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 - 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 - 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 - 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2440} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 111 - 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 222 - 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 333 - 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 444 - 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 555 - 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 666 - 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 777 - 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 888 - 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 999 - 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{24440} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 1111 - 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 2222 - 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 3333 - 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 4444 - 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 5555 - 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 6666 - 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 7777 - 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 8888 - 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 9999 - 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{244440} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11111 - 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22222 - 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33333 - 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44444 - 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55555 - 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66666 - 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77777 - 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88888 - 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99999 - 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{241} := \frac{(11+11) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2441} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{24441} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 1111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 2222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 3333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 4444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 5555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 6666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 7777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 8888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 9999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{244441} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{242} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2442} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{24442} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 1111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 2222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 3333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 4444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 5555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 6666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 7777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 8888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 9999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{244442} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{243} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2443} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 111 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 222 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 333 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 444 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 555 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 666 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 777 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 888 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 999 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{24443} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 1111 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 2222 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 3333 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 4444 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 5555 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 6666 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 7777 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 8888 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 9999 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{244443} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11111 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22222 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33333 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44444 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55555 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66666 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77777 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88888 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99999 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{244} &:= \frac{(111+11) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+22) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+33) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+44) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+55) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+66) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+77) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+88) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+99) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2244} &:= \frac{(1111+11) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+44) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22244} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222244} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{245} &:= \frac{(111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2245} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22245} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222245} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{246} := \frac{(111 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + ((1 + 1) \times 11)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + ((2 + 2) \times 22)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + ((3 + 3) \times 33)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (4+4) + ((4+4) \times 44)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (5+5) + ((5+5) \times 55)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (6+6) + ((6+6) \times 66)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (7+7) + ((7+7) \times 77)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (8+8) + ((8+8) \times 88)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (9+9) + ((9+9) \times 99)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2246} &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (1+1) + ((1+1) \times 11)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (2+2) + ((2+2) \times 22)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (3+3) + ((3+3) \times 33)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (4+4) + ((4+4) \times 44)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (5+5) + ((5+5) \times 55)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (6+6) + ((6+6) \times 66)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (7+7) + ((7+7) \times 77)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (8+8) + ((8+8) \times 88)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (9+9) + ((9+9) \times 99)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22246} &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (1+1) + ((1+1) \times 11)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (2+2) + ((2+2) \times 22)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (3+3) + ((3+3) \times 33)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (4+4) + ((4+4) \times 44)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (5+5) + ((5+5) \times 55)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (6+6) + ((6+6) \times 66)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (7+7) + ((7+7) \times 77)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (8+8) + ((8+8) \times 88)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (9+9) + ((9+9) \times 99)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222246} &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (1+1) + ((1+1) \times 11)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (2+2) + ((2+2) \times 22)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (3+3) + ((3+3) \times 33)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (4+4) + ((4+4) \times 44)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (5+5) + ((5+5) \times 55)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (6+6) + ((6+6) \times 66)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (7+7) + ((7+7) \times 77)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (8+8) + ((8+8) \times 88)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (9+9) + ((9+9) \times 99)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{247} &:= \frac{(111+11+1) \times (1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+22+2) \times (2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+33+3) \times (3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+44+4) \times (4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+55+5) \times (5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+66+6) \times (6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+77+7) \times (7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+88+8) \times (8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+99+9) \times (9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2247} &:= \frac{(1111+11+1) \times (1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22+2) \times (2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33+3) \times (3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+44+4) \times (4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55+5) \times (5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66+6) \times (6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+77+7) \times (7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+88+8) \times (8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+99+9) \times (9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22247} &:= \frac{(11111+11+1) \times (1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22+2) \times (2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33+3) \times (3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+44+4) \times (4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55+5) \times (5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66+6) \times (6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+77+7) \times (7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88+8) \times (8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99+9) \times (9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{222247} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{248} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2248} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{22248} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{222248} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{249} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2249} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22249} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222249} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{250} &:= \frac{1111 - 111}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2500} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 2222}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 3333}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 5555}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 6666}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 8888}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 9999}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{25000} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 22222}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 33333}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55555}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 66666}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88888}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99999}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{250000} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{251} := \frac{(11 + 11 + 1) \times 11 - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2) \times 22 - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3) \times 33 - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 44 - 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 55 - 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 66 - 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 77 - 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 88 - 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 99 - 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2551} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 111 - 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 222 - 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 333 - 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 444 - 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 555 - 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 666 - 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 777 - 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 888 - 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 999 - 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{25551} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 1111 - 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 2222 - 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 3333 - 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 4444 - 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 5555 - 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 6666 - 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 7777 - 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 8888 - 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 9999 - 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{255551} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 11111 - 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 22222 - 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 33333 - 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 44444 - 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 55555 - 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 66666 - 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 77777 - 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 88888 - 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 99999 - 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{252} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2552} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{25552} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 1111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 2222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 3333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 4444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 5555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 6666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 7777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 8888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 9999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{255552} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 11111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 22222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 33333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 44444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 55555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 66666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 77777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 88888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 99999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{253} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 99}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2553} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 333}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 666}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 999}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{25553} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 1111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 2222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 3333}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 4444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 5555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 6666}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 7777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 8888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 9999}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{255553} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 11111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 22222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 33333}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 44444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 55555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 66666}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 77777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 88888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 99999}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{254} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2554} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 111 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 222 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 333 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 444 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 555 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 666 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 777 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 888 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 999 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{25554} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 1111 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 2222 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 3333 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 4444 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 5555 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 6666 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 7777 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 8888 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 9999 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{255554} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 11111 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 22222 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 33333 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 44444 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 55555 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 66666 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 77777 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 88888 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 99999 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{255} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 11 + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 22 + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 33 + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 44 + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 55 + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 66 + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 77 + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 88 + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 99 + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2555} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 111 + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 222 + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 333 + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 444 + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 555 + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 666 + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 777 + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 888 + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 999 + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{25555} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 1111 + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 2222 + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 3333 + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 4444 + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 5555 + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 6666 + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 7777 + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 8888 + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 9999 + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{255555} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 11111 + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 22222 + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 33333 + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 44444 + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 55555 + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 66666 + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 77777 + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 88888 + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 99999 + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{256} := \frac{(11+11+1) \times 11 + 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 22 + 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 33 + 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 44+4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 55+5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 66+6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 77+7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 88+8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 99+9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2556} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 111+1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 222+2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 333+3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 444+4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 555+5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 666+6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 777+7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 888+8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 999+9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{25556} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 1111+1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 2222+2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 3333+3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 4444+4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 5555+5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 6666+6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 7777+7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 8888+8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 9999+9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{255556} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 11111+1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 22222+2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 33333+3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 44444+4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 55555+5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 66666+6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 77777+7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 88888+8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 99999+9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{257} &:= \frac{(111+11+1) \times (1+1)+11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+22+2) \times (2+2)+22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+33+3) \times (3+3)+33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+44+4) \times (4+4)+44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+55+5) \times (5+5)+55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+66+6) \times (6+6)+66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+77+7) \times (7+7)+77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+88+8) \times (8+8)+88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+99+9) \times (9+9)+99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2257} &:= \frac{(1111+11+1) \times (1+1)+11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22+2) \times (2+2)+22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33+3) \times (3+3)+33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+44+4) \times (4+4)+44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55+5) \times (5+5)+55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66+6) \times (6+6)+66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+77+7) \times (7+7)+77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+88+8) \times (8+8)+88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+99+9) \times (9+9)+99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22257} &:= \frac{(11111+11+1) \times (1+1)+11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22+2) \times (2+2)+22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33+3) \times (3+3)+33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+44+4) \times (4+4)+44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55+5) \times (5+5)+55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66+6) \times (6+6)+66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+77+7) \times (7+7)+77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88+8) \times (8+8)+88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99+9) \times (9+9)+99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{222257} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{258} &:= \frac{1111 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} - \frac{111 + 1}{444 + 4} = \frac{2222 - 2}{5555 - 5} - \frac{222 + 2}{555 + 5} = \frac{3333 - 3}{6666 - 6} - \frac{333 + 3}{666 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + 4 + 4}{7777 - 7} - \frac{4}{777 + 7} = \frac{5 + 5 + 5}{8888 - 8} - \frac{5}{888 + 8} = \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{9999 - 9} - \frac{6}{999 + 9} \\
 &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} - \frac{7}{7} = \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} - \frac{8}{8} = \frac{9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} - \frac{9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{370258} &:= \frac{1111111 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} - \frac{111 + 1}{444 + 4} = \frac{2222222 - 2}{5555555 - 5} - \frac{222 + 2}{555 + 5} = \frac{3333333 - 3}{6666666 - 6} - \frac{333 + 3}{666 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + 4 + 4}{7777777 - 7} - \frac{4}{777 + 7} = \frac{5 + 5 + 5}{8888888 - 8} - \frac{5}{888 + 8} = \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{9999999 - 9} - \frac{6}{999 + 9} \\
 &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} - \frac{7}{7} = \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} - \frac{8}{8} = \frac{9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} - \frac{9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{370370258} &:= \frac{1111111111 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} - \frac{111 + 1}{444 + 4} = \frac{2222222222 - 2}{5555555555 - 5} - \frac{222 + 2}{555 + 5} = \frac{3333333333 - 3}{6666666666 - 6} - \frac{333 + 3}{666 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + 4 + 4}{7777777777 - 7} - \frac{4}{777 + 7} = \frac{5 + 5 + 5}{8888888888 - 8} - \frac{5}{888 + 8} = \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{9999999999 - 9} - \frac{6}{999 + 9} \\
 &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} - \frac{7}{7} = \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} - \frac{8}{8} = \frac{9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} - \frac{9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{370370370258} &:= \frac{1111111111111 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} - \frac{111 + 1}{444 + 4} = \frac{2222222222222 - 2}{5555555555555 - 5} - \frac{222 + 2}{555 + 5} = \frac{3333333333333 - 3}{6666666666666 - 6} - \frac{333 + 3}{666 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + 4 + 4}{7777777777777 - 7} - \frac{4}{777 + 7} = \frac{5 + 5 + 5}{8888888888888 - 8} - \frac{5}{888 + 8} = \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{9999999999999 - 9} - \frac{6}{999 + 9} \\
 &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} - \frac{7}{7} = \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} - \frac{8}{8} = \frac{9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} - \frac{9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{259} &:= \frac{1111 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} - \frac{111}{444} = \frac{2222 - 2}{5555 - 5} - \frac{222}{555} = \frac{3333 - 3}{6666 - 6} - \frac{333}{666} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + 4 + 4}{7777 - 7} - \frac{4}{777} = \frac{5 + 5 + 5}{8888 - 8} - \frac{5}{888} = \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{9999 - 9} - \frac{6}{999} \\
 &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} - \frac{7}{7} = \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} - \frac{8}{8} = \frac{9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} - \frac{9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{370259} &:= \frac{1111111 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} - \frac{111}{444} = \frac{2222222 - 2}{5555555 - 5} - \frac{222}{555} = \frac{3333333 - 3}{6666666 - 6} - \frac{333}{666} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} - \frac{4}{4} = \frac{5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} - \frac{5}{5} = \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6} - \frac{6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777777-7}{7+7+7} - \frac{777}{7} = \frac{8888888-8}{8+8+8} - \frac{888}{8} = \frac{9999999-9}{9+9+9} - \frac{999}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{370370259} &:= \frac{1111111111-1}{1+1+1} - \frac{111}{444} = \frac{222222222-2}{555} - \frac{222}{666} = \frac{333333333-3}{777} - \frac{333}{888} \\ &:= \frac{444444444-4}{4+4+4} - \frac{444}{555} = \frac{555555555-5}{5+5+5} - \frac{555}{666} = \frac{666666666-6}{6+6+6} - \frac{666}{777} \\ &:= \frac{777777777-7}{7+7+7} - \frac{777}{888} = \frac{888888888-8}{8+8+8} - \frac{888}{999} = \frac{999999999-9}{9+9+9} - \frac{999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{370370370259} &:= \frac{111111111111-1}{1+1+1} - \frac{111}{444} = \frac{22222222222-2}{555} - \frac{222}{666} = \frac{33333333333-3}{777} - \frac{333}{888} \\ &:= \frac{444444444444-4}{4+4+4} - \frac{444}{555} = \frac{55555555555-5}{5+5+5} - \frac{555}{666} = \frac{66666666666-6}{6+6+6} - \frac{666}{777} \\ &:= \frac{777777777777-7}{7+7+7} - \frac{777}{888} = \frac{88888888888-8}{8+8+8} - \frac{888}{999} = \frac{99999999999-9}{9+9+9} - \frac{999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{260} &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times (11-1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (22-2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (33-3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times (44-4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (55-5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times (66-6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times (77-7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (88-8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (99-9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2260} &:= \frac{(111+1+1) \times (11-1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2) \times (22-2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3) \times (33-3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4+4) \times (44-4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5) \times (55-5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6) \times (66-6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7+7) \times (77-7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8) \times (88-8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9) \times (99-9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22260} &:= \frac{(1111+1+1) \times (11-1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2) \times (22-2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3) \times (33-3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4+4) \times (44-4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5+5) \times (55-5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6+6) \times (66-6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7+7) \times (77-7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8) \times (88-8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9) \times (99-9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222260} &:= \frac{(11111+1+1) \times (11-1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2) \times (22-2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3) \times (33-3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4+4) \times (44-4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5) \times (55-5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6+6) \times (66-6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7+7) \times (77-7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8) \times (88-8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9) \times (99-9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{261} := \frac{(11+11) \times (11+1) - (1+1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times (22+2) - (2+2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times (33+3) - (3+3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44+44) \times (44+4) - (4+4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times (55+5) - (5+5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times (66+6) - (6+6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times (77+7) - (7+7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times (88+8) - (8+8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times (99+9) - (9+9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2661} &:= \frac{(111+111) \times (11+1) - (1+1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222) \times (22+2) - (2+2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333) \times (33+3) - (3+3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444) \times (44+4) - (4+4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555) \times (55+5) - (5+5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666) \times (66+6) - (6+6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777) \times (77+7) - (7+7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888) \times (88+8) - (8+8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999) \times (99+9) - (9+9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{26661} &:= \frac{(1111+1111) \times (11+1) - (1+1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222) \times (22+2) - (2+2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333) \times (33+3) - (3+3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4444) \times (44+4) - (4+4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555) \times (55+5) - (5+5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666) \times (66+6) - (6+6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7777) \times (77+7) - (7+7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8888) \times (88+8) - (8+8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9999) \times (99+9) - (9+9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{266661} &:= \frac{(11111+11111) \times (11+1) - (1+1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22222) \times (22+2) - (2+2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33333) \times (33+3) - (3+3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+44444) \times (44+4) - (4+4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55555) \times (55+5) - (5+5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66666) \times (66+6) - (6+6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+77777) \times (77+7) - (7+7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88888) \times (88+8) - (8+8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99999) \times (99+9) - (9+9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{262} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times (11+1) - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times (22+2) - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times (33+3) - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times (44+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times (55+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times (66+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times (77+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times (88+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times (99+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2662} &:= \frac{(111+111) \times (11+1) - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222) \times (22+2) - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333) \times (33+3) - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444) \times (44+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555) \times (55+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666) \times (66+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777) \times (77+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888) \times (88+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999) \times (99+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{26662} &:= \frac{(1111+1111) \times (11+1) - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222) \times (22+2) - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333) \times (33+3) - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4444) \times (44+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555) \times (55+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666) \times (66+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7777) \times (77+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8888) \times (88+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9999) \times (99+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{266662} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{263} &:= \frac{(11 + 11) \times (11 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22) \times (22 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33) \times (33 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44) \times (44 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55) \times (55 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66) \times (66 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77) \times (77 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88) \times (88 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99) \times (99 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2663} &:= \frac{(111 + 111) \times (11 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222) \times (22 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333) \times (33 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444) \times (44 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555) \times (55 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666) \times (66 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 777) \times (77 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888) \times (88 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999) \times (99 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{26663} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111) \times (11 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222) \times (22 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333) \times (33 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444) \times (44 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555) \times (55 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666) \times (66 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777) \times (77 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888) \times (88 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999) \times (99 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{266663} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{264} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times 99}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2664} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times 111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times 222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times 333}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times 444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times 555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times 666}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77+77+7+7) \times 777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8) \times 888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9) \times 999}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{26664} &:= \frac{(11+11+1+1) \times 1111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2+2) \times 2222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3+3) \times 3333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4) \times 4444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5) \times 5555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6) \times 6666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7) \times 7777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8) \times 8888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9) \times 9999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{266664} &:= \frac{(11+11+1+1) \times 11111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2+2) \times 22222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3+3) \times 33333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4) \times 44444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5) \times 55555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6) \times 66666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7) \times 77777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8) \times 88888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9) \times 99999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{265} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times (11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times (22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times (33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times (44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times (55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times (66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times (77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times (88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times (99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2665} &:= \frac{(111+111) \times (11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222) \times (22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333) \times (33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444) \times (44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555) \times (55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666) \times (66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777) \times (77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888) \times (88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999) \times (99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{26665} &:= \frac{(1111+1111) \times (11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222) \times (22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333) \times (33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4444) \times (44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555) \times (55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666) \times (66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7777) \times (77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8888) \times (88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9999) \times (99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{266665} &:= \frac{(11111+11111) \times (11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22222) \times (22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33333) \times (33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+44444) \times (44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55555) \times (55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66666) \times (66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+77777) \times (77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88888) \times (88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99999) \times (99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{266} := \frac{(111+11+1+11-1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+22+2+22-2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+33+3+33-3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2266} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 + 1 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 + 2 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 + 3 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 + 4 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 + 5 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 + 6 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 7 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 8 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 9 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22266} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 1 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 2 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 3 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 4 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 5 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 6 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 7 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 8 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 9 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222266} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 1 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 2 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 3 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 4 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 5 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 6 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 7 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 8 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 9 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{267} &:= \frac{(11 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2667} &:= \frac{(111 + 111) \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222) \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333) \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444) \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555) \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666) \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777) \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888) \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999) \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{26667} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111) \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222) \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333) \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444) \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555) \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666) \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777) \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888) \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999) \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{266667} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{268} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2268} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 + 1 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 + 2 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 + 3 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 + 4 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 + 5 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 + 6 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 7 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 8 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 9 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{22268} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 1 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 2 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 3 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 4 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 5 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 6 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 7 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 8 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 9 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{222268} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 1 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 2 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 3 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 4 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 5 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 6 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 7 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 8 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 9 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{269} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2269} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 + 1 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 + 2 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 + 3 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 + 4 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 + 5 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 + 6 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 7 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 8 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 9 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22269} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 1 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 2 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 3 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 4 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 5 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 6 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 7 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 8 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 9 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222269} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 1 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 2 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 3 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 4 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 5 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 6 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 7 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 8 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 9 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{270} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2270} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 + 1 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 + 2 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 + 3 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 + 4 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 + 5 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 + 6 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 7 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 8 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 9 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22270} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 1 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 2 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 3 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 4 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 5 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 6 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 7 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 8 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 9 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222270} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 1 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 2 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 3 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 4 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 5 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 6 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 7 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 8 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 9 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{271} := \frac{(11 + 11 - 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 - 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 - 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44+44-4) \times (44+4+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55-5) \times (55+5+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66-6) \times (66+6+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77-7) \times (77+7+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88-8) \times (88+8+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99-9) \times (99+9+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2871} &:= \frac{(111+111-1) \times (11+1+1) - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222-2) \times (22+2+2) - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333-3) \times (33+3+3) - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444-4) \times (44+4+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555-5) \times (55+5+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666-6) \times (66+6+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777-7) \times (77+7+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888-8) \times (88+8+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999-9) \times (99+9+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{28871} &:= \frac{(1111+1111-1) \times (11+1+1) - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222-2) \times (22+2+2) - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333-3) \times (33+3+3) - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4444-4) \times (44+4+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555-5) \times (55+5+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666-6) \times (66+6+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7777-7) \times (77+7+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8888-8) \times (88+8+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9999-9) \times (99+9+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{288871} &:= \frac{(11111+11111-1) \times (11+1+1) - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22222-2) \times (22+2+2) - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33333-3) \times (33+3+3) - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+44444-4) \times (44+4+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55555-5) \times (55+5+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66666-6) \times (66+6+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+77777-7) \times (77+7+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88888-8) \times (88+8+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99999-9) \times (99+9+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{272} &:= \frac{1111-11-11-1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{2222-22-22-2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{3333-33-33-3}{3+3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-44-44-4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{5555-55-55-5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{6666-66-66-6}{6+6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-77-77-7}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{8888-88-88-8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{9999-99-99-9}{9+9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2772} &:= \frac{11111-11-11-1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{22222-22-22-2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{33333-33-33-3}{3+3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-44-44-4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{55555-55-55-5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{66666-66-66-6}{6+6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-77-77-7}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{88888-88-88-8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{99999-99-99-9}{9+9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{27772} &:= \frac{11111-11-11-1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{22222-22-22-2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{33333-33-33-3}{3+3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-44-44-4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{55555-55-55-5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{66666-66-66-6}{6+6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-77-77-7}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{88888-88-88-8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{99999-99-99-9}{9+9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 277772 &:= \frac{111111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 273 &:= \frac{(11 + 11 - 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 - 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 - 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44 - 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 - 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 - 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77 - 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 - 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 - 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2873 &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28873 &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111 - 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222 - 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333 - 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444 - 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555 - 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666 - 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 - 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 - 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 - 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 288873 &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 - 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 - 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 - 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 - 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 - 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 - 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 - 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 - 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 - 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 274 &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2774 &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times 222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times 333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times 444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times 555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times 666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77+77+7+7+7) \times 777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8+8) \times 888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9+9) \times 999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{27774} &:= \frac{(11+11+1+1+1) \times 1111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2+2+2) \times 2222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3+3+3) \times 3333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4+4) \times 4444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5+5) \times 5555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6+6) \times 6666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7+7) \times 7777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8+8) \times 8888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9+9) \times 9999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{277774} &:= \frac{(11+11+1+1+1) \times 11111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2+2+2) \times 22222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3+3+3) \times 33333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4+4) \times 44444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5+5) \times 55555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6+6) \times 66666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7+7) \times 77777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8+8) \times 88888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9+9) \times 99999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{275} := \frac{1111 - 11}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{2222 - 22}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{3333 - 33}{3+3+3+3} = \frac{4444 - 44}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{5555 - 55}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{6666 - 66}{6+6+6+6} = \frac{7777 - 77}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{8888 - 88}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{9999 - 99}{9+9+9+9}$$

$$\mathbf{2775} := \frac{11111 - 11}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{22222 - 22}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{33333 - 33}{3+3+3+3} = \frac{44444 - 44}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{55555 - 55}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{66666 - 66}{6+6+6+6} = \frac{77777 - 77}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{88888 - 88}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{99999 - 99}{9+9+9+9}$$

$$\mathbf{27775} := \frac{111111 - 11}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{222222 - 22}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{333333 - 33}{3+3+3+3} = \frac{444444 - 44}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{555555 - 55}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{666666 - 66}{6+6+6+6} = \frac{777777 - 77}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{888888 - 88}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{999999 - 99}{9+9+9+9}$$

$$\mathbf{277775} := \frac{1111111 - 11}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 22}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 33}{3+3+3+3} = \frac{4444444 - 44}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 55}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 66}{6+6+6+6} = \frac{7777777 - 77}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 88}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 99}{9+9+9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{276} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times (11+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times (22+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times (33+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times (44+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times (55+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times (66+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times (77+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times (88+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times (99+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2576} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times (111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times (222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times (333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times (444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times (555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times (666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times (777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times (888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times (999+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{25576} := \frac{(11+11+1) \times (1111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times (2222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times (3333+3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4) \times (4444 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5) \times (5555 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6) \times (6666 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7) \times (7777 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8) \times (8888 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9) \times (9999 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{255576} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1) \times (11111 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2) \times (22222 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3) \times (33333 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4) \times (44444 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5) \times (55555 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6) \times (66666 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7) \times (77777 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8) \times (88888 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9) \times (99999 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{277} &:= \frac{1111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2777} &:= \frac{11111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{27777} &:= \frac{111111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{277777} &:= \frac{1111111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{278} := \frac{1111 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} = \frac{4444 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} = \frac{7777 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9}$$

$$\mathbf{2778} := \frac{11111 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} = \frac{44444 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} = \frac{77777 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9}$$

$$27778 := \frac{111111+1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3+3+3} = \frac{444444+4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6+6+6} = \frac{777777+7}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9+9+9}$$

$$277778 := \frac{1111111+1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{2222222+2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{3333333+3}{3+3+3+3} = \frac{4444444+4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{5555555+5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{6666666+6}{6+6+6+6} = \frac{7777777+7}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{8888888+8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{9999999+9}{9+9+9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 279 &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1+1+1} + \frac{1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2+2+2} + \frac{2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3+3+3} + \frac{3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4+4+4} + \frac{4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5+5+5} + \frac{5}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6+6+6} + \frac{6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7+7+7} + \frac{7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8+8+8} + \frac{8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9+9+9} + \frac{9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2779 &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1+1+1} + \frac{1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2+2+2} + \frac{2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3+3+3} + \frac{3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4}{4+4+4+4} + \frac{4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5+5+5} + \frac{5}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6+6+6} + \frac{6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7+7+7} + \frac{7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8+8+8} + \frac{8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9+9+9} + \frac{9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27779 &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1+1+1} + \frac{1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2+2+2} + \frac{2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3+3+3} + \frac{3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4+4+4} + \frac{4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5+5+5} + \frac{5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6+6+6} + \frac{6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7+7+7} + \frac{7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8+8+8} + \frac{8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9+9+9} + \frac{9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 277779 &:= \frac{1111111+1}{1+1+1+1} + \frac{1}{1} = \frac{2222222+2}{2+2+2+2} + \frac{2}{2} = \frac{3333333+3}{3+3+3+3} + \frac{3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+4}{4+4+4+4} + \frac{4}{4} = \frac{5555555+5}{5+5+5+5} + \frac{5}{5} = \frac{6666666+6}{6+6+6+6} + \frac{6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+7}{7+7+7+7} + \frac{7}{7} = \frac{8888888+8}{8+8+8+8} + \frac{8}{8} = \frac{9999999+9}{9+9+9+9} + \frac{9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 280 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (11-1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(222+2) \times (22-2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(333+3) \times (33-3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (44-4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(555+5) \times (55-5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(666+6) \times (66-6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (77-7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(888+8) \times (88-8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(999+9) \times (99-9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2780 &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (11-1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (22-2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (33-3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (44-4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (55-5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (66-6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (77-7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (88-8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (99-9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{27780} &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (11-1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (22-2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (33-3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (44-4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (55-5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (66-6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (77-7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (88-8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (99-9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{277780} &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (11-1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (22-2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (33-3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (44-4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (55-5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (66-6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (77-7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (88-8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (99-9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{281} &:= \frac{1111+11+1+1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{2222+22+2+2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{3333+33+3+3}{3+3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+44+4+4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{5555+55+5+5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{6666+66+6+6}{6+6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+77+7+7}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{8888+88+8+8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{9999+99+9+9}{9+9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2781} &:= \frac{11111+11+1+1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{22222+22+2+2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{33333+33+3+3}{3+3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+44+4+4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{55555+55+5+5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{66666+66+6+6}{6+6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+77+7+7}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{88888+88+8+8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{99999+99+9+9}{9+9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{27781} &:= \frac{111111+11+1+1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{222222+22+2+2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{333333+33+3+3}{3+3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44+4+4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{555555+55+5+5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{666666+66+6+6}{6+6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77+7+7}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{888888+88+8+8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{999999+99+9+9}{9+9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{277781} &:= \frac{1111111+11+1+1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{2222222+22+2+2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{3333333+33+3+3}{3+3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+44+4+4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{5555555+55+5+5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{6666666+66+6+6}{6+6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+77+7+7}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{8888888+88+8+8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{9999999+99+9+9}{9+9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{282} := \frac{1111+11+1+1}{1+1+1+1} + \frac{1}{1} = \frac{2222+22+2+2}{2+2+2+2} + \frac{2}{2} = \frac{3333+33+3+3}{3+3+3+3} + \frac{3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} + \frac{4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} + \frac{5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} + \frac{6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} + \frac{7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} + \frac{8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} + \frac{9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2782} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} + \frac{1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} + \frac{2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} + \frac{3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} + \frac{4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} + \frac{5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} + \frac{6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} + \frac{7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} + \frac{8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} + \frac{9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{27782} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} + \frac{1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} + \frac{2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} + \frac{3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} + \frac{4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} + \frac{5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} + \frac{6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} + \frac{7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} + \frac{8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} + \frac{9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{277782} &:= \frac{1111111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} + \frac{1}{1} = \frac{2222222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} + \frac{2}{2} = \frac{3333333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} + \frac{3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} + \frac{4}{4} = \frac{5555555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} + \frac{5}{5} = \frac{6666666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} + \frac{6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} + \frac{7}{7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} + \frac{8}{8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} + \frac{9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{283} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2783} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{27783} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 277783 &:= \frac{1111111 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 284 &:= \frac{1111 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 1}{44 + 4} = \frac{2222 + 2}{5555 + 5} + \frac{22 + 2}{55 + 5} = \frac{3333 + 3}{6666 + 6} + \frac{33 + 3}{66 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{7777 + 7} + \frac{4 + 4}{77 + 7} = \frac{5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{8888 + 8} + \frac{5 + 5}{88 + 8} = \frac{6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{9999 + 9} + \frac{6 + 6}{99 + 9} \\
 &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{9 + 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2784 &:= \frac{11111 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 1}{44 + 4} = \frac{22222 + 2}{55555 + 5} + \frac{22 + 2}{55 + 5} = \frac{33333 + 3}{66666 + 6} + \frac{33 + 3}{66 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{77777 + 7} + \frac{4 + 4}{77 + 7} = \frac{5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{88888 + 8} + \frac{5 + 5}{88 + 8} = \frac{6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{99999 + 9} + \frac{6 + 6}{99 + 9} \\
 &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{9 + 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27784 &:= \frac{111111 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 1}{44 + 4} = \frac{222222 + 2}{555555 + 5} + \frac{22 + 2}{55 + 5} = \frac{333333 + 3}{666666 + 6} + \frac{33 + 3}{66 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{777777 + 7} + \frac{4 + 4}{77 + 7} = \frac{5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{888888 + 8} + \frac{5 + 5}{88 + 8} = \frac{6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{999999 + 9} + \frac{6 + 6}{99 + 9} \\
 &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{9 + 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 277784 &:= \frac{1111111 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 1}{44 + 4} = \frac{2222222 + 2}{5555555 + 5} + \frac{22 + 2}{55 + 5} = \frac{3333333 + 3}{6666666 + 6} + \frac{33 + 3}{66 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{7777777 + 7} + \frac{4 + 4}{77 + 7} = \frac{5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{8888888 + 8} + \frac{5 + 5}{88 + 8} = \frac{6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{9999999 + 9} + \frac{6 + 6}{99 + 9} \\
 &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{9 + 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 285 &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 11) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2) \times (22 + 22) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3) \times (33 + 33) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4) \times (44 + 44) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5) \times (55 + 55) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6) \times (66 + 66) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7) \times (77 + 77) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8) \times (88 + 88) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9) \times (99 + 99) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2485 &:= \frac{(111 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 11) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2 + 2) \times (22 + 22) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3 + 3) \times (33 + 33) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 4 + 4) \times (44 + 44) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5 + 5) \times (55 + 55) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6 + 6) \times (66 + 66) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777+7+7) \times (77+77) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8) \times (88+88) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9) \times (99+99) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{24485} &:= \frac{(1111+1+1) \times (11+11) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2) \times (22+22) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3) \times (33+33) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4+4) \times (44+44) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5+5) \times (55+55) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6+6) \times (66+66) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7+7) \times (77+77) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8) \times (88+88) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9) \times (99+99) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{244485} &:= \frac{(11111+1+1) \times (11+11) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2) \times (22+22) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3) \times (33+33) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4+4) \times (44+44) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5) \times (55+55) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6+6) \times (66+66) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7+7) \times (77+77) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8) \times (88+88) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9) \times (99+99) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{286} &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times (11+11)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (22+22)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (33+33)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times (44+44)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (55+55)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times (66+66)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times (77+77)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (88+88)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (99+99)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2886} &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times (111+111)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (222+222)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (333+333)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times (444+444)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (555+555)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times (666+666)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times (777+777)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (888+888)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (999+999)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{28886} &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times (1111+1111)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (2222+2222)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (3333+3333)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times (4444+4444)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (5555+5555)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times (6666+6666)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times (7777+7777)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (8888+8888)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (9999+9999)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{288886} &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times (11111+11111)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (22222+22222)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (33333+33333)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times (44444+44444)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (55555+55555)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times (66666+66666)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times (77777+77777)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (88888+88888)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (99999+99999)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{287} := \frac{(11+1+1) \times (11+11) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (22+22) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (33+33) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times (44+44) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (55+55) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times (66+66) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times (77+77) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (88+88) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (99+99) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2487} &:= \frac{(111+1+1) \times (11+11) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2) \times (22+22) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3) \times (33+33) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4+4) \times (44+44) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5) \times (55+55) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6) \times (66+66) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7+7) \times (77+77) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8) \times (88+88) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9) \times (99+99) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{24487} &:= \frac{(1111+1+1) \times (11+11) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2) \times (22+22) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3) \times (33+33) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4+4) \times (44+44) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5+5) \times (55+55) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6+6) \times (66+66) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7+7) \times (77+77) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8) \times (88+88) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9) \times (99+99) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{244487} &:= \frac{(11111+1+1) \times (11+11) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2) \times (22+22) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3) \times (33+33) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4+4) \times (44+44) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5) \times (55+55) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6+6) \times (66+66) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7+7) \times (77+77) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8) \times (88+88) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9) \times (99+99) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{288} &:= \frac{(11+11+1+1) \times (11+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2+2) \times (22+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3+3) \times (33+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4) \times (44+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5) \times (55+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6) \times (66+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7) \times (77+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8) \times (88+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9) \times (99+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2688} &:= \frac{(11+11+1+1) \times (111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2+2) \times (222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3+3) \times (333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4) \times (444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5) \times (555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6) \times (666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7) \times (777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8) \times (888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9) \times (999+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{26688} &:= \frac{(11+11+1+1) \times (1111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2+2) \times (2222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3+3) \times (3333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4) \times (4444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5) \times (5555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6) \times (6666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7) \times (7777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8) \times (8888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9) \times (9999+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{266688} &:= \frac{(11+11+1+1) \times (11111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2+2) \times (22222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3+3) \times (33333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4) \times (44444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5) \times (55555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6) \times (66666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7) \times (77777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8) \times (88888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9) \times (99999+9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{289} &:= \frac{(11+11+1+1) \times (11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2+2) \times (22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3+3) \times (33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4) \times (44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5) \times (55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6) \times (66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7) \times (77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8) \times (88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9) \times (99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2689} &:= \frac{(11+11+1+1) \times (111+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2+2) \times (222+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3+3) \times (333+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4) \times (444+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5) \times (555+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6) \times (666+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7) \times (777+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8) \times (888+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9) \times (999+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{26689} &:= \frac{(11+11+1+1) \times (1111+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2+2) \times (2222+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3+3) \times (3333+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4) \times (4444+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5) \times (5555+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6) \times (6666+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7) \times (7777+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8) \times (8888+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9) \times (9999+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{266689} &:= \frac{(11+11+1+1) \times (11111+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2+2) \times (22222+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3+3) \times (33333+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4) \times (44444+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5) \times (55555+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6) \times (66666+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7) \times (77777+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8) \times (88888+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9) \times (99999+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{290} &:= \frac{(111+11+11+11+1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+22+22+22+2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+33+33+33+3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444+44+44+44+4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+55+55+55+5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+66+66+66+6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777+77+77+77+7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+88+88+88+8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+99+99+99+9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2290} &:= \frac{(1111+11+11+11+1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22+22+22+2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33+33+33+3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444+44+44+44+4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55+55+55+5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66+66+66+6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22290} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222290} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{291} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - (11 + 1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) - (22 + 2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) - (33 + 3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) - (44 + 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - (55 + 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) - (66 + 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - (77 + 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - (88 + 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - (99 + 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30291} &:= \frac{111111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - (11 + 1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{222222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) - (22 + 2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{333333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) - (33 + 3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) - (44 + 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{555555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - (55 + 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{666666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) - (66 + 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - (77 + 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{888888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - (88 + 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{999999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - (99 + 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3030291} &:= \frac{11111111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - (11 + 1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{22222222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) - (22 + 2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{33333333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) - (33 + 3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) - (44 + 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{55555555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - (55 + 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{66666666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) - (66 + 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - (77 + 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{88888888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - (88 + 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{99999999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - (99 + 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{303030291} &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - (11 + 1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222222222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) - (22 + 2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333333333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) - (33 + 3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) - (44 + 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555555555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - (55 + 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666666666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) - (66 + 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - (77 + 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888888888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - (88 + 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999999999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - (99 + 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{292} := \frac{1111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30292} &:= \frac{111111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{222222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{333333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{555555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{666666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{888888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{999999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3030292} &:= \frac{11111111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{22222222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{33333333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{55555555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{66666666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{88888888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{99999999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{303030292} &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222222222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333333333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555555555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666666666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888888888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999999999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{293} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3293} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33293} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{333293} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{294} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3294} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{33294} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{333294} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{295} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3295} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33295} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333295} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{296} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3296} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33296} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333296} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{297} := \frac{(111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3297} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33297} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333297} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{298} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3298} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33298} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{333298} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{299} &:= \frac{(111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2999} &:= \frac{(1111 - 111) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 444) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 777) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{29999} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{299999} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{300} &:= \frac{(111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3000} &:= \frac{(1111 - 111) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 444) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 - 777) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30000} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{300000} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{301} &:= \frac{(111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3001} &:= \frac{(1111 - 111) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 444) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 777) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30001} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{300001} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{302} := \frac{1111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30302} &:= \frac{111111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{222222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{333333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{555555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{666666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{888888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{999999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3030302} &:= \frac{11111111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{22222222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{33333333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{55555555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{66666666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{88888888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{99999999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{303030302} &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222222222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333333333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555555555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666666666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888888888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999999999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{303} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30303} &:= \frac{111111 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{222222 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{333333 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{555555 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{666666 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{888888 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{999999 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3030303} &:= \frac{11111111 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{22222222 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{33333333 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{55555555 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{66666666 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{88888888 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{99999999 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{303030303} &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (1+1+1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222222222 \times (2+2+2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333333333 \times (3+3+3)}{33 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (4+4+4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555555555 \times (5+5+5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666666666 \times (6+6+6)}{66 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (7+7+7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888888888 \times (8+8+8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999999999 \times (9+9+9)}{99 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{304} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1+1) + 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2+2) + 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3+3) + 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4+4) + 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5+5) + 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6+6) + 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7+7) + 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8+8) + 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9+9) + 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{30304} &:= \frac{111111 \times (1+1+1) + 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{222222 \times (2+2+2) + 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{333333 \times (3+3+3) + 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 \times (4+4+4) + 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{555555 \times (5+5+5) + 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{666666 \times (6+6+6) + 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 \times (7+7+7) + 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{888888 \times (8+8+8) + 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{999999 \times (9+9+9) + 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3030304} &:= \frac{11111111 \times (1+1+1) + 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{22222222 \times (2+2+2) + 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{33333333 \times (3+3+3) + 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\
 &:= \frac{44444444 \times (4+4+4) + 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{55555555 \times (5+5+5) + 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{66666666 \times (6+6+6) + 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\
 &:= \frac{77777777 \times (7+7+7) + 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{88888888 \times (8+8+8) + 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{99999999 \times (9+9+9) + 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{303030304} &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (1+1+1) + 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222222222 \times (2+2+2) + 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333333333 \times (3+3+3) + 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (4+4+4) + 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555555555 \times (5+5+5) + 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666666666 \times (6+6+6) + 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (7+7+7) + 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888888888 \times (8+8+8) + 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999999999 \times (9+9+9) + 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{305} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 + 1) \times (1+1+1) + (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 + 2) \times (2+2+2) + (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 + 3) \times (3+3+3) + (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44 + 4) \times (4+4+4) + (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 + 5) \times (5+5+5) + (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 + 6) \times (6+6+6) + (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 77 + 7) \times (7+7+7) + (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 + 8) \times (8+8+8) + (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 + 9) \times (9+9+9) + (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3305} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 + 1) \times (1+1+1) + (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 + 2) \times (2+2+2) + (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 + 3) \times (3+3+3) + (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 + 4) \times (4+4+4) + (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 + 5) \times (5+5+5) + (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 + 6) \times (6+6+6) + (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33305} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333305} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{306} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30306} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3030306} &:= \frac{(11111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{303030306} &:= \frac{(1111111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(2222222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(3333333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(5555555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(6666666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(8888888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(9999999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{307} := \frac{(111 + 1) \times 11 - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 22 - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 33 - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 44 - (4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(555+5) \times 55 - (5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(666+6) \times 66 - (6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 77 - (7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(888+8) \times 88 - (8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(999+9) \times 99 - (9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3107} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times 111 - (1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(222+2) \times 222 - (2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(333+3) \times 333 - (3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 444 - (4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(555+5) \times 555 - (5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(666+6) \times 666 - (6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 777 - (7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(888+8) \times 888 - (8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(999+9) \times 999 - (9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{31107} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times 1111 - (1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(222+2) \times 2222 - (2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(333+3) \times 3333 - (3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 4444 - (4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(555+5) \times 5555 - (5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(666+6) \times 6666 - (6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 7777 - (7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(888+8) \times 8888 - (8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(999+9) \times 9999 - (9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{311107} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times 11111 - (1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(222+2) \times 22222 - (2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(333+3) \times 33333 - (3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 44444 - (4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(555+5) \times 55555 - (5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(666+6) \times 66666 - (6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 77777 - (7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(888+8) \times 88888 - (8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(999+9) \times 99999 - (9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{308} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times 11}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(222+2) \times 22}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(333+3) \times 33}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 44}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(555+5) \times 55}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(666+6) \times 66}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 77}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(888+8) \times 88}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(999+9) \times 99}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3058} &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times 11}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(2222+2) \times 22}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(3333+3) \times 33}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times 44}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(5555+5) \times 55}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(6666+6) \times 66}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times 77}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(8888+8) \times 88}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(9999+9) \times 99}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30558} &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times 11}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(22222+2) \times 22}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(33333+3) \times 33}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times 44}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(55555+5) \times 55}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(66666+6) \times 66}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times 77}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(88888+8) \times 88}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(99999+9) \times 99}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{305558} &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times 11}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(222222+2) \times 22}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(333333+3) \times 33}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times 44}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(555555+5) \times 55}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(666666+6) \times 66}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times 77}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(888888+8) \times 88}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(999999+9) \times 99}{(9+9) \times (9+9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{309} &:= \frac{111+111+111-11-11-1-1}{1} = \frac{222+222+222-22-22-2-2}{2} = \frac{333+333+333-33-33-3-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444+444+444-44-44-4-4}{4} = \frac{555+555+555-55-55-5-5}{5} = \frac{666+666+666-66-66-6-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777+777+777-77-77-7-7}{7} = \frac{888+888+888-88-88-8-8}{8} = \frac{999+999+999-99-99-9-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1309} &:= \frac{1111+111+111-11-11-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222+222+222-22-22-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333+333+333-33-33-3-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+444+444-44-44-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555+555+555-55-55-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666+666+666-66-66-6-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777+777+777-77-77-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888+888+888-88-88-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999+999+999-99-99-9-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{11309} &:= \frac{11111+111+111-11-11-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222+222+222-22-22-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333+333+333-33-33-3-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444+444+444-44-44-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555+555+555-55-55-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666+666+666-66-66-6-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777+777+777-77-77-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888+888+888-88-88-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999+999+999-99-99-9-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111309} &:= \frac{111111+111+111-11-11-1-1}{1} = \frac{222222+222+222-22-22-2-2}{2} = \frac{333333+333+333-33-33-3-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+444+444-44-44-4-4}{4} = \frac{555555+555+555-55-55-5-5}{5} = \frac{666666+666+666-66-66-6-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+777+777-77-77-7-7}{7} = \frac{888888+888+888-88-88-8-8}{8} = \frac{999999+999+999-99-99-9-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{310} &:= \frac{111+111+111-11-11-1}{1} = \frac{222+222+222-22-22-2}{2} = \frac{333+333+333-33-33-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444+444+444-44-44-4}{4} = \frac{555+555+555-55-55-5}{5} = \frac{666+666+666-66-66-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777+777+777-77-77-7}{7} = \frac{888+888+888-88-88-8}{8} = \frac{999+999+999-99-99-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1310} &:= \frac{1111+111+111-11-11-1}{1} = \frac{2222+222+222-22-22-2}{2} = \frac{3333+333+333-33-33-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+444+444-44-44-4}{4} = \frac{5555+555+555-55-55-5}{5} = \frac{6666+666+666-66-66-6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11310} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111310} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{311} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1311} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11311} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111311} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{312} := \frac{(11 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4) \times (44+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5) \times (55+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6) \times (66+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7) \times (77+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8) \times (88+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9) \times (99+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3192} &:= \frac{(11+11+1+1) \times (111+11+11)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2+2) \times (222+22+22)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3+3) \times (333+33+33)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4) \times (444+44+44)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5) \times (555+55+55)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6) \times (666+66+66)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7) \times (777+77+77)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8) \times (888+88+88)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9) \times (999+99+99)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{31992} &:= \frac{(11+11+1+1) \times (1111+111+111)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2+2) \times (2222+222+222)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3+3) \times (3333+333+333)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4) \times (4444+444+444)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5) \times (5555+555+555)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6) \times (6666+666+666)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7) \times (7777+777+777)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8) \times (8888+888+888)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9) \times (9999+999+999)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{319992} &:= \frac{(1+11+1+1) \times (11111+1111+1111)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+22+2+2) \times (22222+2222+2222)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+33+3+3) \times (33333+3333+3333)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+44+4+4) \times (44444+4444+4444)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+55+5+5) \times (55555+5555+5555)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+66+6+6) \times (66666+6666+6666)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+77+7+7) \times (77777+7777+7777)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+88+8+8) \times (88888+8888+8888)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+99+9+9) \times (99999+9999+9999)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{313} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + 111 \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + 222 \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + 333 \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + 444 \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + 555 \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + 666 \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + 777 \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + 888 \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + 999 \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1313} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + 1111 \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + 2222 \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + 3333 \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + 4444 \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + 5555 \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + 6666 \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + 7777 \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + 8888 \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + 9999 \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11313} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + 11111 \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + 22222 \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + 33333 \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + 44444 \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + 55555 \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + 66666 \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + 77777 \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + 88888 \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + 99999 \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111313} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + 111111 \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + 222222 \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + 333333 \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + 444444 \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + 555555 \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + 666666 \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + 777777 \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + 888888 \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + 999999 \times 99}{99 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{314} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + (111+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + (222+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + (333+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + (444+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + (555+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + (666+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + (777+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + (888+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + (999+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1314} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + (1111+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + (2222+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + (3333+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + (4444+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + (5555+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + (6666+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + (7777+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + (8888+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + (9999+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{11314} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + (11111+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + (22222+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + (33333+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + (44444+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + (55555+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + (66666+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + (77777+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + (88888+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + (99999+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111314} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + (111111+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + (222222+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + (333333+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + (444444+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + (555555+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + (666666+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + (777777+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + (888888+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + (999999+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{315} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + (111+1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + (222+2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + (333+3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + (444+4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + (555+5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + (666+6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + (777+7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + (888+8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + (999+9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1315} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + (1111+1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + (2222+2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + (3333+3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + (4444+4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + (5555+5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + (6666+6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + (7777+7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + (8888+8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + (9999+9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11315} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + (11111+1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + (22222+2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + (33333+3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + (44444+4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + (55555+5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + (66666+6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + (77777+7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + (88888+8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + (99999+9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111315} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + (1111111+1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + (2222222+2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + (3333333+3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + (4444444+4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + (5555555+5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + (6666666+6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + (7777777+7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + (8888888+8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + (9999999+9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{316} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + (111+1+1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + (222+2+2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + (333+3+3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + (444+4+4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + (555+5+5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + (666+6+6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + (777+7+7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + (888+8+8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + (999+9+9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1316} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + (1111+1+1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + (2222+2+2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + (3333+3+3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + (4444+4+4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + (5555+5+5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + (6666+6+6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + (7777+7+7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + (8888+8+8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + (9999+9+9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11316} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + (11111+1+1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + (22222+2+2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + (33333+3+3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + (44444+4+4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + (55555+5+5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + (66666+6+6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + (77777+7+7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + (88888+8+8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + (99999+9+9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111316} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1) + (1111111+1+1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2) + (2222222+2+2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3) + (3333333+3+3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4) + (4444444+4+4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5) + (5555555+5+5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6) + (6666666+6+6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7) + (7777777+7+7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8) + (8888888+8+8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9) + (9999999+9+9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{317} := \frac{(1111+11) \times (1+1+1) + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(2222+22) \times (2+2+2) + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(3333+33) \times (3+3+3) + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30317} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3030317} &:= \frac{(11111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{303030317} &:= \frac{(1111111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(2222222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(3333333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(5555555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(6666666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(8888888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(9999999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{318} &:= \frac{(111 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - (11 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - (22 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - (33 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - (44 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - (55 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - (66 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - (77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - (88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - (99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3318} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - (11 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - (22 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - (33 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - (44 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - (55 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - (66 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - (77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - (88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - (99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33318} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - (11 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - (22 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - (33 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - (44 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - (55 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - (66 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - (77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - (88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - (99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{333318} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - (11 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - (22 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - (33 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - (44 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - (55 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - (66 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - (77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - (88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - (99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{319} &:= \frac{(111 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3319} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{33319} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{333319} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{320} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1320} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11320} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111320} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{321} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1321} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11321} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111321} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{322} := \frac{111 + 111 + 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333 - 33}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1322} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11322} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111322} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{323} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1323} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11323} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111323} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 999 - 99 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{324} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3324} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{33324} &:= \frac{(11111 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{333324} &:= \frac{(111111 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{325} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3325} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (7+7+7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (8+8+8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (9+9+9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33325} &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (1+1+1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (2+2+2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (3+3+3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (4+4+4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (5+5+5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (6+6+6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (7+7+7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (8+8+8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (9+9+9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333325} &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (1+1+1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (2+2+2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (3+3+3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (4+4+4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (5+5+5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (6+6+6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (7+7+7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (8+8+8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (9+9+9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{326} &:= \frac{(111-1-1) \times (1+1+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222-2-2) \times (2+2+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333-3-3) \times (3+3+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-4-4) \times (4+4+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555-5-5) \times (5+5+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666-6-6) \times (6+6+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7-7) \times (7+7+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888-8-8) \times (8+8+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999-9-9) \times (9+9+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3326} &:= \frac{(1111-1-1) \times (1+1+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222-2-2) \times (2+2+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333-3-3) \times (3+3+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-4-4) \times (4+4+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555-5-5) \times (5+5+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666-6-6) \times (6+6+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-7-7) \times (7+7+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888-8-8) \times (8+8+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999-9-9) \times (9+9+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33326} &:= \frac{(11111-1-1) \times (1+1+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222-2-2) \times (2+2+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333-3-3) \times (3+3+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-4-4) \times (4+4+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555-5-5) \times (5+5+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666-6-6) \times (6+6+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-7-7) \times (7+7+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888-8-8) \times (8+8+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999-9-9) \times (9+9+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333326} &:= \frac{(111111-1-1) \times (1+1+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222-2-2) \times (2+2+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333-3-3) \times (3+3+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444-4-4) \times (4+4+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555-5-5) \times (5+5+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666-6-6) \times (6+6+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777-7-7) \times (7+7+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888-8-8) \times (8+8+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999-9-9) \times (9+9+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{327} := \frac{(111-1-1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222-2-2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333-3-3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3327} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33327} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333327} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{328} &:= \frac{(111 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3328} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33328} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{333328} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{329} &:= \frac{(111 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3399} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{33399} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{333399} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{330} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3630} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times (111 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times (222 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times (333 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times (444 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times (555 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times (666 - 6)}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (777-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (888-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (999-9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{36630} &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (1111-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (2222-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (3333-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (4444-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (5555-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (6666-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (7777-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (8888-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (9999-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{366630} &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (11111-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (22222-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (33333-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (44444-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (55555-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (66666-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (77777-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (88888-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (99999-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{331} &:= \frac{111+111+111-1-1}{1} = \frac{222+222+222-2-2}{2} = \frac{333+333+333-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+444-4-4}{4} = \frac{555+555+555-5-5}{5} = \frac{666+666+666-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777+777-7-7}{7} = \frac{888+888+888-8-8}{8} = \frac{999+999+999-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1331} &:= \frac{111+111+1111-1-1}{1} = \frac{222+222+2222-2-2}{2} = \frac{333+333+3333-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+4444-4-4}{4} = \frac{555+555+5555-5-5}{5} = \frac{666+666+6666-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777+7777-7-7}{7} = \frac{888+888+8888-8-8}{8} = \frac{999+999+9999-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11331} &:= \frac{111+111+11111-1-1}{1} = \frac{222+222+22222-2-2}{2} = \frac{333+333+33333-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+44444-4-4}{4} = \frac{555+555+55555-5-5}{5} = \frac{666+666+66666-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777+77777-7-7}{7} = \frac{888+888+88888-8-8}{8} = \frac{999+999+99999-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111331} &:= \frac{111+111+111111-1-1}{1} = \frac{222+222+222222-2-2}{2} = \frac{333+333+333333-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+444444-4-4}{4} = \frac{555+555+555555-5-5}{5} = \frac{666+666+666666-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777+777777-7-7}{7} = \frac{888+888+888888-8-8}{8} = \frac{999+999+999999-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{332} := \frac{111+111+111-1}{1} = \frac{222+222+222-2}{2} = \frac{333+333+333-3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1332} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 1111 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 2222 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 3333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 4444 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 5555 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 6666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 7777 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 8888 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 9999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11332} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 11111 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 22222 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 33333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 44444 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 55555 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 66666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 77777 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 88888 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 99999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111332} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 111111 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222222 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444444 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555555 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777777 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888888 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{333} &:= \frac{(1+1+1) \times 111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2) \times 222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3) \times 333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4) \times 444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5) \times 555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6) \times 666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7) \times 777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8) \times 888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9) \times 999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3333} &:= \frac{(1+1+1) \times 1111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2) \times 2222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3) \times 3333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4) \times 4444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5) \times 5555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6) \times 6666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7) \times 7777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8) \times 8888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9) \times 9999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33333} &:= \frac{(1+1+1) \times 11111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2) \times 22222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3) \times 33333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4) \times 44444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5) \times 55555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6) \times 66666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7) \times 77777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8) \times 88888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9) \times 99999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333333} &:= \frac{(1+1+1) \times 111111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2) \times 222222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3) \times 333333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4) \times 444444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5) \times 555555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6) \times 666666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7) \times 777777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8) \times 888888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9) \times 999999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{334} &:= \frac{111+111+111+1}{1} = \frac{222+222+222+2}{2} = \frac{333+333+333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+444+4}{4} = \frac{555+555+555+5}{5} = \frac{666+666+666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777+777+7}{7} = \frac{888+888+888+8}{8} = \frac{999+999+999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1334} &:= \frac{111+111+1111+1}{1} = \frac{222+222+2222+2}{2} = \frac{333+333+3333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+4444+4}{4} = \frac{555+555+5555+5}{5} = \frac{666+666+6666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777+7777+7}{7} = \frac{888+888+8888+8}{8} = \frac{999+999+9999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11334} &:= \frac{111+111+11111+1}{1} = \frac{222+222+22222+2}{2} = \frac{333+333+33333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+44444+4}{4} = \frac{555+555+55555+5}{5} = \frac{666+666+66666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777+77777+7}{7} = \frac{888+888+88888+8}{8} = \frac{999+999+99999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111334} &:= \frac{111+111+111111+1}{1} = \frac{222+222+222222+2}{2} = \frac{333+333+333333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+444444+4}{4} = \frac{555+555+555555+5}{5} = \frac{666+666+666666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777+777777+7}{7} = \frac{888+888+888888+8}{8} = \frac{999+999+999999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{335} &:= \frac{111+111+111+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+222+222+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+333+333+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+444+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+555+555+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+666+666+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777+777+7+7}{7} = \frac{888+888+888+8+8}{8} = \frac{999+999+999+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1335} &:= \frac{111+111+1111+1+1}{1} = \frac{222+222+2222+2+2}{2} = \frac{333+333+3333+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+4444+4+4}{4} = \frac{555+555+5555+5+5}{5} = \frac{666+666+6666+6+6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{777 + 777 + 7777 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 8888 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 9999 + 9 + 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11335} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 11111 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 22222 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 33333 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 44444 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 55555 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 66666 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 77777 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 88888 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 99999 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111335} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 111111 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222222 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333333 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444444 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555555 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666666 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777777 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888888 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999999 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{336} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1336} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 1111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 2222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 3333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 4444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 5555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 6666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 7777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 8888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 9999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11336} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 11111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 22222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 33333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 44444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 55555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 66666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 77777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 88888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 99999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111336} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 111111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{337} := \frac{(111 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (4+4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (5+5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (6+6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (7+7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (8+8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (9+9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3337} &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (1+1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (2+2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (3+3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (4+4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (5+5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (6+6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (7+7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (8+8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (9+9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33337} &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (1+1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (2+2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (3+3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (4+4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (5+5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (6+6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (7+7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (8+8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (9+9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333337} &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (1+1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (2+2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (3+3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (4+4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (5+5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (6+6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (7+7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (8+8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (9+9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{338} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (1+1+1) + (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (2+2+2) + (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (3+3+3) + (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (4+4+4) + (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (5+5+5) + (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (6+6+6) + (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (7+7+7) + (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (8+8+8) + (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (9+9+9) + (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3338} &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (1+1+1) + (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (2+2+2) + (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (3+3+3) + (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (4+4+4) + (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (5+5+5) + (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (6+6+6) + (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (7+7+7) + (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (8+8+8) + (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (9+9+9) + (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33338} &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (1+1+1) + (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (2+2+2) + (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (3+3+3) + (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (4+4+4) + (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (5+5+5) + (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (6+6+6) + (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (7+7+7) + (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (8+8+8) + (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (9+9+9) + (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333338} &:= \frac{(111111 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{339} &:= \frac{(111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3339} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33339} &:= \frac{(11111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333339} &:= \frac{(111111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{340} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1340} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11340} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111340} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{341} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3441} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1) \times 111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2) \times 222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3) \times 333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4) \times 444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5) \times 555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6) \times 666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7) \times 777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8) \times 888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9) \times 999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{34441} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1) \times 1111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2) \times 2222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3) \times 3333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4) \times 4444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5) \times 5555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6) \times 6666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7) \times 7777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8) \times 8888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9) \times 9999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{344441} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1) \times 11111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2) \times 22222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3) \times 33333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4) \times 44444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5) \times 55555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6) \times 66666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7) \times 77777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8) \times 88888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9) \times 99999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{342} := \frac{(111 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3342} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33342} &:= \frac{(11111 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333342} &:= \frac{(111111 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{343} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1343} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 666 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 999 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11343} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 666 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 999 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111343} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 666 + 66 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 999 + 99 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{344} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 111 + 11}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222 + 22}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333 + 33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444 + 44}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555 + 55}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666 + 66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777 + 77}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888 + 88}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999 + 99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1344} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 111 + 11}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 222 + 22}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 333 + 33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 444 + 44}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 555 + 55}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 666 + 66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 777 + 77}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 888 + 88}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 999 + 99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{11344} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 111 + 11}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 222 + 22}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 333 + 33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 444 + 44}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 555 + 55}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 666 + 66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 777 + 77}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 888 + 88}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 999 + 99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111344} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 111 + 11}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 222 + 22}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 333 + 33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 444 + 44}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 555 + 55}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 666 + 66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 777 + 77}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 888 + 88}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 999 + 99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{345} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1345} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11345} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111345} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{346} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1346} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11346} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111346} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{347} := \frac{(111 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (4+4+4) + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (5+5+5) + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (6+6+6) + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (7+7+7) + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (8+8+8) + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (9+9+9) + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3347} &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (1+1+1) + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (2+2+2) + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (3+3+3) + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (4+4+4) + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (5+5+5) + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (6+6+6) + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (7+7+7) + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (8+8+8) + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (9+9+9) + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33347} &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (1+1+1) + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (2+2+2) + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (3+3+3) + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (4+4+4) + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (5+5+5) + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (6+6+6) + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (7+7+7) + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (8+8+8) + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (9+9+9) + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333347} &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (1+1+1) + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (2+2+2) + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (3+3+3) + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (4+4+4) + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (5+5+5) + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (6+6+6) + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (7+7+7) + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (8+8+8) + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (9+9+9) + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{348} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (1+1+1) + (11+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (2+2+2) + (22+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (3+3+3) + (33+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (4+4+4) + (44+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (5+5+5) + (55+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (6+6+6) + (66+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (7+7+7) + (77+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (8+8+8) + (88+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (9+9+9) + (99+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3348} &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (1+1+1) + (11+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (2+2+2) + (22+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (3+3+3) + (33+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (4+4+4) + (44+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (5+5+5) + (55+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (6+6+6) + (66+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (7+7+7) + (77+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (8+8+8) + (88+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (9+9+9) + (99+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33348} &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (1+1+1) + (11+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (2+2+2) + (22+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (3+3+3) + (33+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (4+4+4) + (44+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (5+5+5) + (55+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (6+6+6) + (66+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (7+7+7) + (77+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (8+8+8) + (88+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (9+9+9) + (99+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{333348} &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (1+1+1) + (11+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (2+2+2) + (22+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (3+3+3) + (33+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (4+4+4) + (44+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (5+5+5) + (55+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (6+6+6) + (66+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (7+7+7) + (77+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (8+8+8) + (88+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (9+9+9) + (99+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{349} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (1+1+1) + (11+1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (2+2+2) + (22+2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (3+3+3) + (33+3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (4+4+4) + (44+4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (5+5+5) + (55+5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (6+6+6) + (66+6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (7+7+7) + (77+7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (8+8+8) + (88+8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (9+9+9) + (99+9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3349} &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (1+1+1) + (11+1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (2+2+2) + (22+2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (3+3+3) + (33+3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (4+4+4) + (44+4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (5+5+5) + (55+5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (6+6+6) + (66+6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (7+7+7) + (77+7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (8+8+8) + (88+8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (9+9+9) + (99+9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{33349} &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (1+1+1) + (11+1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (2+2+2) + (22+2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (3+3+3) + (33+3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (4+4+4) + (44+4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (5+5+5) + (55+5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (6+6+6) + (66+6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (7+7+7) + (77+7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (8+8+8) + (88+8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (9+9+9) + (99+9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{333349} &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (1+1+1) + (11+1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (2+2+2) + (22+2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (3+3+3) + (33+3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (4+4+4) + (44+4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (5+5+5) + (55+5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (6+6+6) + (66+6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (7+7+7) + (77+7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (8+8+8) + (88+8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (9+9+9) + (99+9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{350} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + (111-1-1-1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + (222-2-2-2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + (333-3-3-3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + (444-4-4-4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + (555-5-5-5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + (666-6-6-6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + (777-7-7-7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + (888-8-8-8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + (999-9-9-9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1350} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + (1111-1-1-1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + (2222-2-2-2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + (3333-3-3-3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + (4444-4-4-4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + (5555-5-5-5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + (6666-6-6-6) \times 6}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + (7777-7-7-7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + (8888-8-8-8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + (9999-9-9-9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11350} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + (11111-1-1-1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + (22222-2-2-2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + (33333-3-3-3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + (44444-4-4-4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + (55555-5-5-5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + (66666-6-6-6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + (77777-7-7-7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + (88888-8-8-8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + (99999-9-9-9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111350} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + (111111-1-1-1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + (222222-2-2-2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + (333333-3-3-3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + (444444-4-4-4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + (555555-5-5-5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + (666666-6-6-6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + (777777-7-7-7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + (888888-8-8-8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + (999999-9-9-9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{351} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + (111-1-1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + (222-2-2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + (333-3-3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + (444-4-4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + (555-5-5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + (666-6-6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + (777-7-7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + (888-8-8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + (999-9-9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1351} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + (1111-1-1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + (2222-2-2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + (3333-3-3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + (4444-4-4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + (5555-5-5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + (6666-6-6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + (7777-7-7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + (8888-8-8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + (9999-9-9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11351} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + (11111-1-1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + (22222-2-2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + (33333-3-3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + (44444-4-4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + (55555-5-5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + (66666-6-6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + (77777-7-7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + (88888-8-8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + (99999-9-9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111351} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + (111111-1-1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + (222222-2-2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + (333333-3-3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + (444444-4-4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + (555555-5-5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + (666666-6-6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + (777777-7-7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + (888888-8-8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + (999999-9-9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{352} := \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + (111-1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + (222-2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + (333-3) \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + (444-4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + (555-5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + (666-6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + (777-7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + (888-8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + (999-9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1352} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + (1111-1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + (2222-2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + (3333-3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + (4444-4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + (5555-5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + (6666-6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + (7777-7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + (8888-8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + (9999-9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11352} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + (11111-1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + (22222-2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + (33333-3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + (44444-4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + (55555-5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + (66666-6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + (77777-7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + (88888-8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + (99999-9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111352} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + (111111-1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + (222222-2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + (333333-3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + (444444-4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + (555555-5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + (666666-6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + (777777-7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + (888888-8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + (999999-9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{353} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + 111 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + 222 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + 333 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + 444 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + 555 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + 666 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + 777 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + 888 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + 999 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1353} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + 1111 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + 2222 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + 3333 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + 4444 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + 5555 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + 6666 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + 7777 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + 8888 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + 9999 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11353} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + 11111 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + 22222 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + 33333 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + 44444 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + 55555 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + 66666 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + 77777 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + 88888 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + 99999 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111353} &:= \frac{(11+11) \times 11 + 111111 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times 22 + 222222 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times 33 + 333333 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44) \times 44 + 444444 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times 55 + 555555 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times 66 + 666666 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77) \times 77 + 777777 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times 88 + 888888 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times 99 + 999999 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{354} &:= \frac{111+111+111+11+11-1}{1} = \frac{222+222+222+22+22-2}{2} = \frac{333+333+333+33+33-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444+444+444+44+44-4}{4} = \frac{555+555+555+55+55-5}{5} = \frac{666+666+666+66+66-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777+777+777+77+77-7}{7} = \frac{888+888+888+88+88-8}{8} = \frac{999+999+999+99+99-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1354} &:= \frac{1111+111+111+11+11-1}{1} = \frac{2222+222+222+22+22-2}{2} = \frac{3333+333+333+33+33-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+444+444+44+44-4}{4} = \frac{5555+555+555+55+55-5}{5} = \frac{6666+666+666+66+66-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777+777+777+77+77-7}{7} = \frac{8888+888+888+88+88-8}{8} = \frac{9999+999+999+99+99-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{11354} &:= \frac{11111+111+111+11+11-1}{1} = \frac{22222+222+222+22+22-2}{2} = \frac{33333+333+333+33+33-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444+444+444+44+44-4}{4} = \frac{55555+555+555+55+55-5}{5} = \frac{66666+666+666+66+66-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777+777+777+77+77-7}{7} = \frac{88888+888+888+88+88-8}{8} = \frac{99999+999+999+99+99-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111354} &:= \frac{111111+111+111+11+11-1}{1} = \frac{222222+222+222+22+22-2}{2} = \frac{333333+333+333+33+33-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+444+444+44+44-4}{4} = \frac{555555+555+555+55+55-5}{5} = \frac{666666+666+666+66+66-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+777+777+77+77-7}{7} = \frac{888888+888+888+88+88-8}{8} = \frac{999999+999+999+99+99-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{355} &:= \frac{111+111+111+11+11}{1} = \frac{222+222+222+22+22}{2} = \frac{333+333+333+33+33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444+444+444+44+44}{4} = \frac{555+555+555+55+55}{5} = \frac{666+666+666+66+66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777+777+777+77+77}{7} = \frac{888+888+888+88+88}{8} = \frac{999+999+999+99+99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1355} &:= \frac{1111+111+111+11+11}{4} = \frac{2222+222+222+22+22}{5} = \frac{3333+333+333+33+33}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+444+444+44+44}{4} = \frac{5555+555+555+55+55}{5} = \frac{6666+666+666+66+66}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 99}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11355} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 11}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 22}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 44}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 55}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111355} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 11}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 22}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 44}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 55}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{356} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1356} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11356} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111356} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{357} := \frac{(111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 111 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 222 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 333 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 444 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 555 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 666 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 777 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 888 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 999 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1357} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1111 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2222 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3333 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4444 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5555 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6666 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7777 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8888 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9999 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11357} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 11111 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 22222 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 33333 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 44444 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 55555 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 66666 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 77777 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 88888 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 99999 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111357} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 111111 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 222222 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 333333 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 444444 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 555555 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 666666 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 777777 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 888888 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 999999 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{358} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + (111 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + (222 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + (333 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + (444 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + (555 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + (666 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + (777 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + (888 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + (999 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1358} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + (1111 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + (2222 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + (3333 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + (4444 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + (5555 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + (6666 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + (7777 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + (8888 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + (9999 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11358} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + (11111 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + (22222 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + (33333 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + (44444 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + (55555 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + (66666 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + (77777 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + (88888 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + (99999 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111358} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + (111111 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + (222222 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + (333333 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + (444444 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + (555555 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + (666666 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + (777777 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + (888888 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + (999999 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{359} &:= \frac{1111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{370359} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{370370359} &:= \frac{1111111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{370370370359} &:= \frac{1111111111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{360} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3360} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33360} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333360} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{361} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3361} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33361} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333361} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{362} := \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3662} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times 111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times 222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times 333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times 444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times 555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times 666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times 777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times 888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times 999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{36662} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times 1111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times 2222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times 3333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times 4444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times 5555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times 6666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times 7777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times 8888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times 9999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{366662} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times 11111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times 22222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times 33333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times 44444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times 55555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times 66666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times 77777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times 88888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times 99999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{363} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3663} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times 111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times 222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times 333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times 444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times 555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times 666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times 777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times 888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times 999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{36663} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times 1111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times 2222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times 3333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times 4444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times 5555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times 6666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times 7777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times 8888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times 9999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{366663} &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times 11111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times 22222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times 33333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times 44444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times 55555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times 66666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times 77777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times 88888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times 99999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{364} &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times 11+1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times 22+2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times 33+3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times 44+4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times 55+5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times 66+6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times 77+7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times 88+8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times 99+9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3664} &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times 111+1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times 222+2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times 333+3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times 444+4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times 555+5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times 666+6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times 777+7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times 888+8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times 999+9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{36664} &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times 1111+1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times 2222+2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times 3333+3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times 4444+4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times 5555+5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times 6666+6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times 7777+7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times 8888+8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times 9999+9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{366664} &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times 11111+1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times 22222+2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times 33333+3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times 44444+4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times 55555+5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times 66666+6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times 77777+7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times 88888+8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times 99999+9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{365} &:= \frac{(111+11) \times (1+1+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+22) \times (2+2+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+33) \times (3+3+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+44) \times (4+4+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+55) \times (5+5+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+66) \times (6+6+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+77) \times (7+7+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+88) \times (8+8+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+99) \times (9+9+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3365} &:= \frac{(1111+11) \times (1+1+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22) \times (2+2+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33) \times (3+3+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+44) \times (4+4+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55) \times (5+5+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66) \times (6+6+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33365} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333365} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{366} &:= \frac{(111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3366} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33366} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333366} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{367} := \frac{(111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3367} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33367} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333367} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{368} &:= \frac{(111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3368} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33368} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{333368} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{369} &:= \frac{1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3699} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{36999} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{369999} &:= \frac{1111111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{370} &:= \frac{1111 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} = \frac{4444 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3700} &:= \frac{11111 - 11}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 22}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 33}{3 + 3 + 3} = \frac{44444 - 44}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 55}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 66}{6 + 6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 77}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 88}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 99}{9 + 9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{37000} := \frac{111111 - 111}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 222}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 333}{3 + 3 + 3} = \frac{444444 - 444}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 555}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 666}{6 + 6 + 6}$$

$$:= \frac{777777 - 777}{7+7+7} = \frac{888888 - 888}{8+8+8} = \frac{999999 - 999}{9+9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{370000} &:= \frac{1111111 - 1111}{1+1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 2222}{2+2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 3333}{3+3+3} = \frac{4444444 - 4444}{4+4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 5555}{5+5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 6666}{6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 7777}{7+7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 8888}{8+8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 9999}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{371} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3371} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33371} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333371} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{372} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3372} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33372} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333372} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{373} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3773} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times 111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times 222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times 333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times 444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times 555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times 666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times 777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times 888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times 999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{37773} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times 1111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times 2222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times 3333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times 4444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times 5555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times 6666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times 7777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times 8888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times 9999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{377773} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times 11111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times 22222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times 33333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times 44444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times 55555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times 66666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times 77777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times 88888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times 99999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{374} := \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3774} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times 111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times 222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times 333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times 444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times 555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times 666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times 777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times 888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times 999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{37774} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times 1111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times 2222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times 3333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times 4444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times 5555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times 6666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times 7777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times 8888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times 9999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{377774} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times 11111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times 22222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times 33333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times 44444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times 55555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times 66666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times 77777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times 88888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times 99999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{375} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3775} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times 111 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times 222 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times 333 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times 444 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times 555 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times 666 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times 777 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times 888 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times 999 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{37775} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times 1111 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times 2222 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times 3333 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times 4444 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times 5555 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times 6666 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times 7777 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times 8888 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times 9999 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \color{red}{377775} &:= \frac{(11+11+11+1) \times 11111 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22+2) \times 22222 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33+3) \times 33333 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+44+4) \times 44444 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55+5) \times 55555 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66+6) \times 66666 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+77+7) \times 77777 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88+8) \times 88888 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99+9) \times 99999 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \color{red}{376} &:= \frac{(11+11+11+1) \times 11+1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22+2) \times 22+2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33+3) \times 33+3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+44+4) \times 44+4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55+5) \times 55+5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66+6) \times 66+6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+77+7) \times 77+7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88+8) \times 88+8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99+9) \times 99+9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \color{red}{3776} &:= \frac{(11+11+11+1) \times 111+1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22+2) \times 222+2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33+3) \times 333+3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+44+4) \times 444+4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55+5) \times 555+5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66+6) \times 666+6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+77+7) \times 777+7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88+8) \times 888+8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99+9) \times 999+9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \color{red}{37776} &:= \frac{(11+11+11+1) \times 1111+1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22+2) \times 2222+2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33+3) \times 3333+3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+44+4) \times 4444+4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55+5) \times 5555+5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66+6) \times 6666+6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+77+7) \times 7777+7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88+8) \times 8888+8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99+9) \times 9999+9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \color{red}{377776} &:= \frac{(11+11+11+1) \times 11111+1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22+2) \times 22222+2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33+3) \times 33333+3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+44+4) \times 44444+4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55+5) \times 55555+5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66+6) \times 66666+6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+77+7) \times 77777+7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88+8) \times 88888+8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99+9) \times 99999+9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \color{red}{377} &:= \frac{(11+11+11+1) \times 11+1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22+2) \times 22+2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33+3) \times 33+3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+44+4) \times 44+4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55+5) \times 55+5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66+6) \times 66+6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+77+7) \times 77+7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88+8) \times 88+8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99+9) \times 99+9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \color{red}{3777} &:= \frac{(11+11+11+1) \times 111+1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22+2) \times 222+2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33+3) \times 333+3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+44+4) \times 444+4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55+5) \times 555+5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66+6) \times 666+6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77+77+77+7) \times 777+7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88+8) \times 888+8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99+9) \times 999+9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{37777} &:= \frac{(11+11+11+1) \times 1111+1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22+2) \times 2222+2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33+3) \times 3333+3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44+4) \times 4444+4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55+5) \times 5555+5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66+6) \times 6666+6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77+7) \times 7777+7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88+8) \times 8888+8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99+9) \times 9999+9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{377777} &:= \frac{(11+11+11+1) \times 11111+1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22+2) \times 22222+2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33+3) \times 33333+3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44+4) \times 44444+4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55+5) \times 55555+5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66+6) \times 66666+6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77+7) \times 77777+7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88+8) \times 88888+8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99+9) \times 99999+9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{378} &:= \frac{1111+11+11+1}{1+1+1} = \frac{2222+22+22+2}{2+2+2} = \frac{3333+33+33+3}{3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+44+44+4}{4+4+4} = \frac{5555+55+55+5}{5+5+5} = \frac{6666+66+66+6}{6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+77+77+7}{7+7+7} = \frac{8888+88+88+8}{8+8+8} = \frac{9999+99+99+9}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{370378} &:= \frac{1111111+11+11+1}{1+1+1} = \frac{2222222+22+22+2}{2+2+2} = \frac{3333333+33+33+3}{3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+44+44+4}{4+4+4} = \frac{5555555+55+55+5}{5+5+5} = \frac{6666666+66+66+6}{6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+77+77+7}{7+7+7} = \frac{8888888+88+88+8}{8+8+8} = \frac{9999999+99+99+9}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{370370378} &:= \frac{111111111+11+11+1}{1+1+1} = \frac{222222222+22+22+2}{2+2+2} = \frac{333333333+33+33+3}{3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444444+44+44+4}{4+4+4} = \frac{555555555+55+55+5}{5+5+5} = \frac{666666666+66+66+6}{6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777777+77+77+7}{7+7+7} = \frac{888888888+88+88+8}{8+8+8} = \frac{999999999+99+99+9}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{370370370378} &:= \frac{11111111111+11+11+1}{1+1+1} = \frac{22222222222+22+22+2}{2+2+2} = \frac{33333333333+33+33+3}{3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444444444+44+44+4}{4+4+4} = \frac{55555555555+55+55+5}{5+5+5} = \frac{66666666666+66+66+6}{6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777777777+77+77+7}{7+7+7} = \frac{88888888888+88+88+8}{8+8+8} = \frac{99999999999+99+99+9}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{379} := \frac{1111+1}{1+1+1+1)+1111} 11 = \frac{2222+2}{2+2+2+2)+2222} 22 = \frac{3333+3}{3+3+3+3)+3333} 33$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4+4+4)+4444} 44 = \frac{5555+5}{5+5+5+5)+5555} 55 = \frac{6666+6}{6+6+6+6)+6666} 66 \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7+7+7)+7777} 77 = \frac{8888+8}{8+8+8+8)+8888} 88 = \frac{9999+9}{9+9+9+9)+9999} 99 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{10379} &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1+1+1)+111111} 11 = \frac{2222+2}{2+2+2+2)+222222} 22 = \frac{3333+3}{3+3+3+3)+333333} 33 \\ &:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4+4+4)+444444} 44 = \frac{5555+5}{5+5+5+5)+555555} 55 = \frac{6666+6}{6+6+6+6)+666666} 66 \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7+7+7)+777777} 77 = \frac{8888+8}{8+8+8+8)+888888} 88 = \frac{9999+9}{9+9+9+9)+999999} 99 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1010379} &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1+1+1)+11111111} 11 = \frac{2222+2}{2+2+2+2)+22222222} 22 = \frac{3333+3}{3+3+3+3)+33333333} 33 \\ &:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4+4+4)+44444444} 44 = \frac{5555+5}{5+5+5+5)+55555555} 55 = \frac{6666+6}{6+6+6+6)+66666666} 66 \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7+7+7)+77777777} 77 = \frac{8888+8}{8+8+8+8)+88888888} 88 = \frac{9999+9}{9+9+9+9)+99999999} 99 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{101010379} &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1+1+1)+1111111111} 11 = \frac{2222+2}{2+2+2+2)+2222222222} 22 = \frac{3333+3}{3+3+3+3)+3333333333} 33 \\ &:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4+4+4)+4444444444} 44 = \frac{5555+5}{5+5+5+5)+5555555555} 55 = \frac{6666+6}{6+6+6+6)+6666666666} 66 \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7+7+7)+7777777777} 77 = \frac{8888+8}{8+8+8+8)+8888888888} 88 = \frac{9999+9}{9+9+9+9)+9999999999} 99 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{380} &:= \frac{1111-1}{1+1+1} + \frac{11-1}{1} = \frac{2222-2}{2+2+2} + \frac{22-2}{2} = \frac{3333-3}{3+3+3} + \frac{33-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-4}{4+4+4} + \frac{44-4}{4} = \frac{5555-5}{5+5+5} + \frac{55-5}{5} = \frac{6666-6}{6+6+6} + \frac{66-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-7}{7+7+7} + \frac{77-7}{7} = \frac{8888-8}{8+8+8} + \frac{88-8}{8} = \frac{9999-9}{9+9+9} + \frac{99-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3810} &:= \frac{11111-11}{1+1+1} + \frac{111-1}{1} = \frac{22222-22}{2+2+2} + \frac{222-2}{2} = \frac{33333-33}{3+3+3} + \frac{333-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-44}{4+4+4} + \frac{444-4}{4} = \frac{55555-55}{5+5+5} + \frac{555-5}{5} = \frac{66666-66}{6+6+6} + \frac{666-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-77}{7+7+7} + \frac{777-7}{7} = \frac{88888-88}{8+8+8} + \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{99999-99}{9+9+9} + \frac{999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{38110} &:= \frac{111111-111}{1+1+1} + \frac{1111-1}{1} = \frac{222222-222}{2+2+2} + \frac{2222-2}{2} = \frac{333333-333}{3+3+3} + \frac{3333-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444-444}{4+4+4} + \frac{4444-4}{4} = \frac{555555-555}{5+5+5} + \frac{5555-5}{5} = \frac{666666-666}{6+6+6} + \frac{6666-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-777}{7+7+7} + \frac{7777-7}{7} = \frac{888888-888}{8+8+8} + \frac{8888-8}{8} = \frac{999999-999}{9+9+9} + \frac{9999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{381110} &:= \frac{1111111 - 1111}{1+1+1} + \frac{11111 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 2222}{2+2+2} + \frac{22222 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 3333}{3+3+3} + \frac{33333 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 4444}{4+4+4} + \frac{44444 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 5555}{5+5+5} + \frac{55555 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 6666}{6+6+6} + \frac{66666 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 7777}{7+7+7} + \frac{77777 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 8888}{8+8+8} + \frac{88888 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 9999}{9+9+9} + \frac{99999 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{381} &:= \frac{1111 - 1}{1+1+1} + \frac{11}{1} = \frac{2222 - 2}{2+2+2} + \frac{22}{2} = \frac{3333 - 3}{3+3+3} + \frac{33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 4}{4+4+4} + \frac{44}{4} = \frac{5555 - 5}{5+5+5} + \frac{55}{5} = \frac{6666 - 6}{6+6+6} + \frac{66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 7}{7+7+7} + \frac{77}{7} = \frac{8888 - 8}{8+8+8} + \frac{88}{8} = \frac{9999 - 9}{9+9+9} + \frac{99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3811} &:= \frac{11111 - 11}{1+1+1} + \frac{111}{1} = \frac{22222 - 22}{2+2+2} + \frac{222}{2} = \frac{33333 - 33}{3+3+3} + \frac{333}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 44}{4+4+4} + \frac{444}{4} = \frac{55555 - 55}{5+5+5} + \frac{555}{5} = \frac{66666 - 66}{6+6+6} + \frac{666}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 77}{7+7+7} + \frac{777}{7} = \frac{88888 - 88}{8+8+8} + \frac{888}{8} = \frac{99999 - 99}{9+9+9} + \frac{999}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{38111} &:= \frac{111111 - 111}{1+1+1} + \frac{1111}{1} = \frac{222222 - 222}{2+2+2} + \frac{2222}{2} = \frac{333333 - 333}{3+3+3} + \frac{3333}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 444}{4+4+4} + \frac{4444}{4} = \frac{555555 - 555}{5+5+5} + \frac{5555}{5} = \frac{666666 - 666}{6+6+6} + \frac{6666}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 777}{7+7+7} + \frac{7777}{7} = \frac{888888 - 888}{8+8+8} + \frac{8888}{8} = \frac{999999 - 999}{9+9+9} + \frac{9999}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{381111} &:= \frac{1111111 - 1111}{1+1+1} + \frac{11111}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 2222}{2+2+2} + \frac{22222}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 3333}{3+3+3} + \frac{33333}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 4444}{4+4+4} + \frac{44444}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 5555}{5+5+5} + \frac{55555}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 6666}{6+6+6} + \frac{66666}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 7777}{7+7+7} + \frac{77777}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 8888}{8+8+8} + \frac{88888}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 9999}{9+9+9} + \frac{99999}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{382} &:= \frac{1111 - 1}{1+1+1} + \frac{11+1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 2}{2+2+2} + \frac{22+2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 3}{3+3+3} + \frac{33+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 4}{4+4+4} + \frac{44+4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 5}{5+5+5} + \frac{55+5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 6}{6+6+6} + \frac{66+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 7}{7+7+7} + \frac{77+7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 8}{8+8+8} + \frac{88+8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 9}{9+9+9} + \frac{99+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3812} &:= \frac{11111 - 11}{1+1+1} + \frac{111+1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 22}{2+2+2} + \frac{222+2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 33}{3+3+3} + \frac{333+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 44}{4+4+4} + \frac{444+4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 55}{5+5+5} + \frac{555+5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 66}{6+6+6} + \frac{666+6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777-77}{7+7+7} + \frac{777+7}{7} = \frac{88888-88}{8+8+8} + \frac{888+8}{8} = \frac{99999-99}{9+9+9} + \frac{999+9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{38112} &:= \frac{111111-111}{1+1+1} + \frac{1111+1}{1} = \frac{222222-222}{2+2+2} + \frac{2222+2}{2} = \frac{333333-333}{3+3+3} + \frac{3333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444-444}{4+4+4} + \frac{4444+4}{4} = \frac{555555-555}{5+5+5} + \frac{5555+5}{5} = \frac{666666-666}{6+6+6} + \frac{6666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-777}{7+7+7} + \frac{7777+7}{7} = \frac{888888-888}{8+8+8} + \frac{8888+8}{8} = \frac{999999-999}{9+9+9} + \frac{9999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{381112} &:= \frac{1111111-1111}{1+1+1} + \frac{11111+1}{1} = \frac{2222222-2222}{2+2+2} + \frac{22222+2}{2} = \frac{3333333-3333}{3+3+3} + \frac{33333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444-4444}{4+4+4} + \frac{44444+4}{4} = \frac{5555555-5555}{5+5+5} + \frac{55555+5}{5} = \frac{6666666-6666}{6+6+6} + \frac{66666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777-7777}{7+7+7} + \frac{77777+7}{7} = \frac{8888888-8888}{8+8+8} + \frac{88888+8}{8} = \frac{9999999-9999}{9+9+9} + \frac{99999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{383} &:= \frac{1111-111-111-111-11-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222-222-222-222-22-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333-333-333-333-33-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-444-444-444-44-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555-555-555-555-55-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666-666-666-666-66-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-777-777-777-77-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888-888-888-888-88-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999-999-999-999-99-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5383} &:= \frac{11111-111-111-111-11-1}{1+1} = \frac{22222-222-222-222-22-2}{2+2} = \frac{33333-333-333-333-33-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-444-444-444-44-4}{4+4} = \frac{55555-555-555-555-55-5}{5+5} = \frac{66666-666-666-666-66-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-777-777-777-77-7}{7+7} = \frac{88888-888-888-888-88-8}{8+8} = \frac{99999-999-999-999-99-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55383} &:= \frac{111111-111-111-111-11-1}{1+1} = \frac{222222-222-222-222-22-2}{2+2} = \frac{333333-333-333-333-33-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444-444-444-444-44-4}{4+4} = \frac{555555-555-555-555-55-5}{5+5} = \frac{666666-666-666-666-66-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-777-777-777-77-7}{7+7} = \frac{888888-888-888-888-88-8}{8+8} = \frac{999999-999-999-999-99-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555383} &:= \frac{1111111-111-111-111-11-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222-222-222-222-22-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333-333-333-333-33-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444-444-444-444-44-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555-555-555-555-55-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666-666-666-666-66-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777-777-777-777-77-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888-888-888-888-88-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999-999-999-999-99-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{384} := \frac{(11+11+11-1) \times (11+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22-2) \times (22+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33-3) \times (33+3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3984} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 111 - 1) \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222 - 2) \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333 - 3) \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{39984} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111 + 1111 - 1) \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222 + 2222 - 2) \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333 + 3333 - 3) \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444 + 4444 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555 + 5555 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666 + 6666 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 7777 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 8888 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 9999 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{399984} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 11111 - 1) \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 22222 - 2) \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 33333 - 3) \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 44444 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 55555 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 66666 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 77777 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 88888 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 99999 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{385} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3885} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times 111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times 222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times 333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times 444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times 555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times 666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times 777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times 888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times 999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{38885} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times 1111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times 2222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times 3333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times 4444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times 5555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times 6666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times 7777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times 8888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times 9999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{388885} &:= \frac{(11+11+11+1+1) \times 11111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22+2+2) \times 22222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33+3+3) \times 33333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44+4+4) \times 44444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55+5+5) \times 55555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66+6+6) \times 66666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77+7+7) \times 77777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88+8+8) \times 88888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99+9+9) \times 99999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{386} &:= \frac{(11+11+11+1+1) \times 11+1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22+2+2) \times 22+2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33+3+3) \times 33+3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44+4+4) \times 44+4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55+5+5) \times 55+5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66+6+6) \times 66+6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77+7+7) \times 77+7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88+8+8) \times 88+8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99+9+9) \times 99+9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3886} &:= \frac{(11+11+11+1+1) \times 111+1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22+2+2) \times 222+2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33+3+3) \times 333+3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44+4+4) \times 444+4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55+5+5) \times 555+5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66+6+6) \times 666+6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77+7+7) \times 777+7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88+8+8) \times 888+8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99+9+9) \times 999+9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{38886} &:= \frac{(11+11+11+1+1) \times 1111+1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22+2+2) \times 2222+2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33+3+3) \times 3333+3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44+4+4) \times 4444+4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55+5+5) \times 5555+5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66+6+6) \times 6666+6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77+7+7) \times 7777+7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88+8+8) \times 8888+8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99+9+9) \times 9999+9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{388886} &:= \frac{(11+11+11+1+1) \times 11111+1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22+2+2) \times 22222+2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33+3+3) \times 33333+3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44+4+4) \times 44444+4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55+5+5) \times 55555+5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66+6+6) \times 66666+6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77+7+7) \times 77777+7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88+8+8) \times 88888+8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99+9+9) \times 99999+9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{387} &:= \frac{1111-111-111-111-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222-222-222-222-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333-333-333-333-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-444-444-444-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555-555-555-555-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666-666-666-666-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-777-777-777-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888-888-888-888-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999-999-999-999-9-9-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5387} &:= \frac{11111-111-111-111-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{22222-222-222-222-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{33333-333-333-333-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-444-444-444-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{55555-555-555-555-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{66666-666-666-666-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55387} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555387} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{388} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5388} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55388} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555388} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{389} := \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 111}{1+1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 222}{2+2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 333}{3+3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 444}{4+4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 555}{5+5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 666}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 777}{7+7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 888}{8+8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 999}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5389} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 - 111 - 111}{1+1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 222 - 222}{2+2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 333 - 333}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 444 - 444}{4+4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 555 - 555}{5+5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 666 - 666}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 777 - 777}{7+7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 888 - 888}{8+8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 999 - 999}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55389} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 111 - 111}{1+1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 222 - 222}{2+2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 333 - 333}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 444 - 444}{4+4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 555 - 555}{5+5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 666 - 666}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 777 - 777}{7+7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 888 - 888}{8+8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 999 - 999}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555389} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 111 - 111}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 222 - 222}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 333 - 333}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 444 - 444}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 555 - 555}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 666 - 666}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 777 - 777}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 888 - 888}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 999 - 999}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{390} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 9 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5390} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 9 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55390} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 9 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{555390} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{391} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{5391} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{55391} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{555391} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{392} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{4392} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{44392} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{444392} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{393} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3693} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times (111 + 1) - (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times (222 + 2) - (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times (333 + 3) - (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times (444 + 4) - (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times (555 + 5) - (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times (666 + 6) - (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times (777 + 7) - (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times (888 + 8) - (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times (999 + 9) - (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{36693} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times (1111 + 1) - (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times (2222 + 2) - (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times (3333 + 3) - (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times (4444 + 4) - (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times (5555 + 5) - (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times (6666 + 6) - (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times (7777 + 7) - (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times (8888 + 8) - (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times (9999 + 9) - (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{366693} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times (11111 + 1) - (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times (22222 + 2) - (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times (33333 + 3) - (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times (44444 + 4) - (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times (55555 + 5) - (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times (66666 + 6) - (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times (77777 + 7) - (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times (88888 + 8) - (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times (99999 + 9) - (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 394 &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (11+1) - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (22+2) - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (33+3) - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (44+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (55+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (66+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (77+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (88+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (99+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3694 &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (111+1) - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (222+2) - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (333+3) - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (444+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (555+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (666+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (777+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (888+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (999+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36694 &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (1111+1) - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (2222+2) - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (3333+3) - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (4444+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (5555+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (6666+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (7777+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (8888+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (9999+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 366694 &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (11111+1) - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (22222+2) - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (33333+3) - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (44444+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (55555+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (66666+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (77777+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (88888+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (99999+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 395 &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (11+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (22+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (33+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (44+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (55+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (66+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (77+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (88+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (99+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3695 &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (111+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (222+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (333+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (444+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (555+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (666+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (777+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (888+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (999+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36695 &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (1111+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (2222+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (3333+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (4444+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (5555+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (6666+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (7777+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (8888+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (9999+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 366695 &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (11111+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (22222+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (33333+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (44444+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (55555+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (66666+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (77777+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (88888+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (99999+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 396 &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (11+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (22+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (33+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (44+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (55+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (66+6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (77+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (88+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (99+9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3696 &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (999+9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 36696 &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (1111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (2222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (3333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (4444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (5555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (6666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (7777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (8888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (9999+9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 366696 &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (11111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (22222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (33333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (44444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (55555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (66666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (77777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (88888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (99999+9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 397 &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$3697 := \frac{(11+11+11) \times (111+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (222+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (333+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times (444 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times (555 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times (666 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times (777 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times (888 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times (999 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{36697} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times (1111 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times (2222 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times (3333 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times (4444 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times (5555 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times (6666 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times (7777 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times (8888 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times (9999 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{366697} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times (11111 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times (22222 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times (33333 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times (44444 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times (55555 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times (66666 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times (77777 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times (88888 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times (99999 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{398} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2398} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 11 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22398} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222398} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 399 &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3399 &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33399 &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 333399 &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 400 &:= \frac{(111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4400 &:= \frac{(1111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44400 &:= \frac{(11111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 444400 &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 401 &:= \frac{(111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4401 &:= \frac{(1111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44401 &:= \frac{(11111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 444401 &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 402 &:= \frac{(111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$4402 := \frac{(1111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{44402} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{444402} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{403} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(2222 + 2222) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(3333 + 3333) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(5555 + 5555) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(6666 + 6666) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(8888 + 8888) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(9999 + 9999) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{20403} &:= \frac{(11111 + 1111) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22222 + 2222) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33333 + 3333) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 4444) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55555 + 5555) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66666 + 6666) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 7777) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88888 + 8888) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99999 + 9999) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2020403} &:= \frac{(1111111 + 1111) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(2222222 + 2222) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(3333333 + 3333) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444 + 4444) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(5555555 + 5555) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(6666666 + 6666) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777 + 7777) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(8888888 + 8888) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(9999999 + 9999) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{202020403} &:= \frac{(111111111 + 1111) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(222222222 + 2222) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(333333333 + 3333) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(444444444 + 4444) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(555555555 + 5555) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(666666666 + 6666) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(777777777 + 7777) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(888888888 + 8888) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(999999999 + 9999) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 404 &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1+1+1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2+2+2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3+3+3)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4+4+4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5+5+5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6+6+6)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7+7+7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8+8+8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9+9+9)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 40404 &:= \frac{111111 \times (1+1+1+1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{222222 \times (2+2+2+2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{333333 \times (3+3+3+3)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (4+4+4+4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{555555 \times (5+5+5+5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{666666 \times (6+6+6+6)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (7+7+7+7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{888888 \times (8+8+8+8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{999999 \times (9+9+9+9)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4040404 &:= \frac{11111111 \times (1+1+1+1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{22222222 \times (2+2+2+2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{33333333 \times (3+3+3+3)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (4+4+4+4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{55555555 \times (5+5+5+5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{66666666 \times (6+6+6+6)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 \times (7+7+7+7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{88888888 \times (8+8+8+8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{99999999 \times (9+9+9+9)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 404040404 &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (1+1+1+1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{2222222222 \times (2+2+2+2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{3333333333 \times (3+3+3+3)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (4+4+4+4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{5555555555 \times (5+5+5+5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{6666666666 \times (6+6+6+6)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (7+7+7+7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{8888888888 \times (8+8+8+8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{9999999999 \times (9+9+9+9)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 405 &:= \frac{111 \times 11 - (1+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 22 - (2+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 33 - (3+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44 - (4+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 55 - (5+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 66 - (6+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77 - (7+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 88 - (8+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 99 - (9+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4105 &:= \frac{111 \times 111 - (1+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 222 - (2+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 333 - (3+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 444 - (4+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 555 - (5+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 666 - (6+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 777 - (7+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 888 - (8+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 999 - (9+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41105 &:= \frac{111 \times 1111 - (1+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 2222 - (2+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 3333 - (3+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 4444 - (4+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 5555 - (5+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 6666 - (6+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{777 \times 7777 - (7+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 8888 - (8+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 9999 - (9+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{411105} &:= \frac{111 \times 11111 - (1+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 22222 - (2+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 33333 - (3+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44444 - (4+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 55555 - (5+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 66666 - (6+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77777 - (7+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 88888 - (8+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 99999 - (9+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{406} &:= \frac{111 \times 11 - (1+1+1) \times 1}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 22 - (2+2+2) \times 2}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 33 - (3+3+3) \times 3}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44 - (4+4+4) \times 4}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 55 - (5+5+5) \times 5}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 66 - (6+6+6) \times 6}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77 - (7+7+7) \times 7}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 88 - (8+8+8) \times 8}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 99 - (9+9+9) \times 9}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4106} &:= \frac{111 \times 111 - (1+1+1) \times 1}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 222 - (2+2+2) \times 2}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 333 - (3+3+3) \times 3}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 444 - (4+4+4) \times 4}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 555 - (5+5+5) \times 5}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 666 - (6+6+6) \times 6}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 777 - (7+7+7) \times 7}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 888 - (8+8+8) \times 8}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 999 - (9+9+9) \times 9}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{41106} &:= \frac{111 \times 1111 - (1+1+1) \times 1}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 2222 - (2+2+2) \times 2}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 3333 - (3+3+3) \times 3}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 4444 - (4+4+4) \times 4}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 5555 - (5+5+5) \times 5}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 6666 - (6+6+6) \times 6}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 7777 - (7+7+7) \times 7}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 8888 - (8+8+8) \times 8}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 9999 - (9+9+9) \times 9}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{411106} &:= \frac{111 \times 11111 - (1+1+1) \times 1}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 22222 - (2+2+2) \times 2}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 33333 - (3+3+3) \times 3}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44444 - (4+4+4) \times 4}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 55555 - (5+5+5) \times 5}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 66666 - (6+6+6) \times 6}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77777 - (7+7+7) \times 7}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 88888 - (8+8+8) \times 8}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 99999 - (9+9+9) \times 9}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{407} &:= \frac{111 \times 11}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 22}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 33}{(3+3+3) \times 3} = \frac{444 \times 44}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 55}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 66}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 88}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 99}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4107} := \frac{111 \times 111}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 222}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 333}{(3+3+3) \times 3} = \frac{444 \times 444}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 555}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 666}{(6+6+6) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{777 \times 777}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 888}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 999}{(9+9+9) \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{41107} &:= \frac{111 \times 1111}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 2222}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 3333}{(3+3+3) \times 3} = \frac{444 \times 4444}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 5555}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 6666}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 7777}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 8888}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 9999}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{411107} &:= \frac{111 \times 11111}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 22222}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 33333}{(3+3+3) \times 3} = \frac{444 \times 44444}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 55555}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 66666}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77777}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 88888}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 99999}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{408} &:= \frac{111 \times 11 + (1+1+1) \times 1}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 22 + (2+2+2) \times 2}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 33 + (3+3+3) \times 3}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44 + (4+4+4) \times 4}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 55 + (5+5+5) \times 5}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 66 + (6+6+6) \times 6}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77 + (7+7+7) \times 7}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 88 + (8+8+8) \times 8}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 99 + (9+9+9) \times 9}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4108} &:= \frac{111 \times 111 + (1+1+1) \times 1}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 222 + (2+2+2) \times 2}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 333 + (3+3+3) \times 3}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 444 + (4+4+4) \times 4}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 555 + (5+5+5) \times 5}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 666 + (6+6+6) \times 6}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 777 + (7+7+7) \times 7}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 888 + (8+8+8) \times 8}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 999 + (9+9+9) \times 9}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{41108} &:= \frac{111 \times 1111 + (1+1+1) \times 1}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 2222 + (2+2+2) \times 2}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 3333 + (3+3+3) \times 3}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 4444 + (4+4+4) \times 4}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 5555 + (5+5+5) \times 5}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 6666 + (6+6+6) \times 6}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 7777 + (7+7+7) \times 7}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 8888 + (8+8+8) \times 8}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 9999 + (9+9+9) \times 9}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{411108} &:= \frac{111 \times 11111 + (1+1+1) \times 1}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 22222 + (2+2+2) \times 2}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 33333 + (3+3+3) \times 3}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44444 + (4+4+4) \times 4}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 55555 + (5+5+5) \times 5}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 66666 + (6+6+6) \times 6}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77777 + (7+7+7) \times 7}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 88888 + (8+8+8) \times 8}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 99999 + (9+9+9) \times 9}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{409} &:= \frac{111 \times 11 + (1+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 22 + (2+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 33 + (3+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44 + (4+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 55 + (5+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 66 + (6+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{777 \times 77 + (7+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 88 + (8+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 99 + (9+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4109} &:= \frac{111 \times 111 + (1+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 222 + (2+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 333 + (3+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 444 + (4+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 555 + (5+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 666 + (6+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 777 + (7+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 888 + (8+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 999 + (9+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{41109} &:= \frac{111 \times 1111 + (1+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 2222 + (2+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 3333 + (3+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 4444 + (4+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 5555 + (5+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 6666 + (6+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 7777 + (7+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 8888 + (8+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 9999 + (9+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{411109} &:= \frac{111 \times 11111 + (1+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times 22222 + (2+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times 33333 + (3+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44444 + (4+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times 55555 + (5+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times 66666 + (6+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77777 + (7+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times 88888 + (8+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times 99999 + (9+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{410} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1+1+1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2+2+2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4+4+4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5+5+5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7+7+7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8+8+8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4110} &:= \frac{11111 + 1111 + 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1+1+1} = \frac{22222 + 2222 + 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2+2+2} = \frac{33333 + 3333 + 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 4444 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4+4+4} = \frac{55555 + 5555 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5+5+5} = \frac{66666 + 6666 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 7777 + 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7+7+7} = \frac{88888 + 8888 + 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8+8+8} = \frac{99999 + 9999 + 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{41110} &:= \frac{111111 + 11111 + 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1+1+1} = \frac{222222 + 22222 + 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2+2+2} = \frac{333333 + 33333 + 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44444 + 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4+4+4} = \frac{555555 + 55555 + 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5+5+5} = \frac{666666 + 66666 + 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77777 + 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7+7+7} = \frac{888888 + 88888 + 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8+8+8} = \frac{999999 + 99999 + 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{411110} := \frac{1111111 + 111111 + 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1+1+1} = \frac{2222222 + 222222 + 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2+2+2} = \frac{3333333 + 333333 + 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3+3+3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444444 + 444444 + 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 555555 + 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 666666 + 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 777777 + 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 888888 + 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 999999 + 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

► **411** := $\frac{1111 + 111 + 11}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 22}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 33}{3 + 3 + 3}$
 $\frac{4444 + 444 + 44}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 55}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 66}{6 + 6 + 6}$
 $\frac{7777 + 777 + 77}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 88}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 99}{9 + 9 + 9}$

4111 := $\frac{11111 + 1111 + 111}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 2222 + 222}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 3333 + 333}{3 + 3 + 3}$
 $\frac{44444 + 4444 + 444}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 5555 + 555}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 6666 + 666}{6 + 6 + 6}$
 $\frac{77777 + 7777 + 777}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 8888 + 888}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 9999 + 999}{9 + 9 + 9}$

41111 := $\frac{111111 + 11111 + 1111}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22222 + 2222}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33333 + 3333}{3 + 3 + 3}$
 $\frac{444444 + 44444 + 4444}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55555 + 5555}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66666 + 6666}{6 + 6 + 6}$
 $\frac{777777 + 77777 + 7777}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88888 + 8888}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99999 + 9999}{9 + 9 + 9}$

411111 := $\frac{1111111 + 111111 + 11111}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 222222 + 22222}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 333333 + 33333}{3 + 3 + 3}$
 $\frac{4444444 + 444444 + 44444}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 555555 + 55555}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 666666 + 66666}{6 + 6 + 6}$
 $\frac{7777777 + 777777 + 77777}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 888888 + 88888}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 999999 + 99999}{9 + 9 + 9}$

► **412** := $\frac{1111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3}$
 $\frac{4444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6}$
 $\frac{7777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9}$

4112 := $\frac{11111 + 1111 + 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 2222 + 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 3333 + 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3}$
 $\frac{44444 + 4444 + 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 5555 + 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 6666 + 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6}$
 $\frac{77777 + 7777 + 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 8888 + 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 9999 + 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9}$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{41112} &:= \frac{111111 + 11111 + 1111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22222 + 2222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33333 + 3333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44444 + 4444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55555 + 5555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66666 + 6666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77777 + 7777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88888 + 8888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99999 + 9999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{411112} &:= \frac{1111111 + 111111 + 11111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 222222 + 22222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 333333 + 33333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 444444 + 44444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 555555 + 55555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 666666 + 66666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 777777 + 77777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 888888 + 88888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 999999 + 99999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{413} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) + (111 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) + (222 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) + (333 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) + (444 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) + (555 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) + (666 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) + (777 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + (888 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + (999 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1413} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) + (111 - 1) \times 111}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) + (222 - 2) \times 222}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) + (333 - 3) \times 333}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) + (444 - 4) \times 444}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) + (555 - 5) \times 555}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) + (666 - 6) \times 666}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) + (777 - 7) \times 777}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + (888 - 8) \times 888}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + (999 - 9) \times 999}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11413} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) + (111 - 1) \times 1111}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) + (222 - 2) \times 2222}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) + (333 - 3) \times 3333}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) + (444 - 4) \times 4444}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) + (555 - 5) \times 5555}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) + (666 - 6) \times 6666}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) + (777 - 7) \times 7777}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + (888 - 8) \times 8888}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + (999 - 9) \times 9999}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111413} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) + (111 - 1) \times 11111}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) + (222 - 2) \times 22222}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) + (333 - 3) \times 33333}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) + (444 - 4) \times 44444}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) + (555 - 5) \times 55555}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) + (666 - 6) \times 66666}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) + (777 - 7) \times 77777}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + (888 - 8) \times 88888}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + (999 - 9) \times 99999}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{414} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 111 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 222 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 333 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 444 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 555 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 666 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7+7) + 777 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8+8) + 888 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9+9) + 999 \times 99}{9 \times 99}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30414} &:= \frac{111111 \times (1+1+1) + 111 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{222222 \times (2+2+2) + 222 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{333333 \times (3+3+3) + 333 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (4+4+4) + 444 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{555555 \times (5+5+5) + 555 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{666666 \times (6+6+6) + 666 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (7+7+7) + 777 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{888888 \times (8+8+8) + 888 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{999999 \times (9+9+9) + 999 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3030414} &:= \frac{11111111 \times (1+1+1) + 111 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{22222222 \times (2+2+2) + 222 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{33333333 \times (3+3+3) + 333 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (4+4+4) + 444 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{55555555 \times (5+5+5) + 555 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{66666666 \times (6+6+6) + 666 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 \times (7+7+7) + 777 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{88888888 \times (8+8+8) + 888 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{99999999 \times (9+9+9) + 999 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{303030414} &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (1+1+1) + 111 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222222222 \times (2+2+2) + 222 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333333333 \times (3+3+3) + 333 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (4+4+4) + 444 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555555555 \times (5+5+5) + 555 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666666666 \times (6+6+6) + 666 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (7+7+7) + 777 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888888888 \times (8+8+8) + 888 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999999999 \times (9+9+9) + 999 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{415} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1+1) + (111+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2+2) + (222+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3+3) + (333+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4+4) + (444+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5+5) + (555+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6+6) + (666+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7+7) + (777+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8+8) + (888+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9+9) + (999+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30415} &:= \frac{111111 \times (1+1+1) + (111+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{222222 \times (2+2+2) + (222+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{333333 \times (3+3+3) + (333+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (4+4+4) + (444+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{555555 \times (5+5+5) + (555+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{666666 \times (6+6+6) + (666+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (7+7+7) + (777+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{888888 \times (8+8+8) + (888+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{999999 \times (9+9+9) + (999+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3030415} &:= \frac{11111111 \times (1+1+1) + (111+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{22222222 \times (2+2+2) + (222+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{33333333 \times (3+3+3) + (333+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (4+4+4) + (444+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{55555555 \times (5+5+5) + (555+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{66666666 \times (6+6+6) + (666+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 \times (7+7+7) + (777+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{88888888 \times (8+8+8) + (888+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{99999999 \times (9+9+9) + (999+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{303030415} := \frac{1111111111 \times (1+1+1) + (111+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222222222 \times (2+2+2) + (222+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333333333 \times (3+3+3) + (333+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33}$$

$$:= \frac{4444444444 \times (4+4+4) + (444+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555555555 \times (5+5+5) + (555+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666666666 \times (6+6+6) + (666+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66}$$

$$:= \frac{7777777777 \times (7+7+7) + (777+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888888888 \times (8+8+8) + (888+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999999999 \times (9+9+9) + (999+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99}$$

► **416** := $\frac{111 \times 11 + (11-1-1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 22 + (22-2-2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 33 + (33-3-3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)}$

$$:= \frac{444 \times 44 + (44-4-4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 55 + (55-5-5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 66 + (66-6-6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)}$$

$$:= \frac{777 \times 77 + (77-7-7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times (7+7+7)} = \frac{888 \times 88 + (88-8-8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times (8+8+8)} = \frac{999 \times 99 + (99-9-9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times (9+9+9)}$$

4116 := $\frac{111 \times 111 + (11-1-1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 222 + (22-2-2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 333 + (33-3-3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)}$

$$:= \frac{444 \times 444 + (44-4-4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 555 + (55-5-5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 666 + (66-6-6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)}$$

$$:= \frac{777 \times 777 + (77-7-7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times (7+7+7)} = \frac{888 \times 888 + (88-8-8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times (8+8+8)} = \frac{999 \times 999 + (99-9-9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times (9+9+9)}$$

41116 := $\frac{111 \times 1111 + (11-1-1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 2222 + (22-2-2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 3333 + (33-3-3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)}$

$$:= \frac{444 \times 4444 + (44-4-4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 5555 + (55-5-5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 6666 + (66-6-6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)}$$

$$:= \frac{777 \times 7777 + (77-7-7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times (7+7+7)} = \frac{888 \times 8888 + (88-8-8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times (8+8+8)} = \frac{999 \times 9999 + (99-9-9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times (9+9+9)}$$

411116 := $\frac{111 \times 11111 + (11-1-1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 22222 + (22-2-2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 33333 + (33-3-3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)}$

$$:= \frac{444 \times 44444 + (44-4-4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 55555 + (55-5-5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 66666 + (66-6-6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)}$$

$$:= \frac{777 \times 77777 + (77-7-7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times (7+7+7)} = \frac{888 \times 88888 + (88-8-8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times (8+8+8)} = \frac{999 \times 99999 + (99-9-9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times (9+9+9)}$$

► **417** := $\frac{111 \times 11 + (11-1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 22 + (22-2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 33 + (33-3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)}$

$$:= \frac{444 \times 44 + (44-4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 55 + (55-5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 66 + (66-6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)}$$

$$:= \frac{777 \times 77 + (77-7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times (7+7+7)} = \frac{888 \times 88 + (88-8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times (8+8+8)} = \frac{999 \times 99 + (99-9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times (9+9+9)}$$

4117 := $\frac{111 \times 111 + (11-1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 222 + (22-2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 333 + (33-3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)}$

$$:= \frac{444 \times 444 + (44-4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 555 + (55-5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 666 + (66-6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)}$$

$$:= \frac{777 \times 777 + (77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 888 + (88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 999 + (99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{41117} &:= \frac{111 \times 1111 + (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 2222 + (22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 3333 + (33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 4444 + (44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 5555 + (55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 6666 + (66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 7777 + (77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 8888 + (88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 9999 + (99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{411117} &:= \frac{111 \times 11111 + (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 22222 + (22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 33333 + (33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44444 + (44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 55555 + (55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 66666 + (66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77777 + (77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 88888 + (88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 99999 + (99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{418} &:= \frac{111 \times 11 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 22 + 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 33 + 33 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44 + 44 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 55 + 55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 66 + 66 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77 + 77 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 88 + 88 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 99 + 99 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4118} &:= \frac{111 \times 111 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 222 + 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 333 + 33 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 444 + 44 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 555 + 55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 666 + 66 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 777 + 77 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 888 + 88 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 999 + 99 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{41118} &:= \frac{111 \times 1111 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 2222 + 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 3333 + 33 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 4444 + 44 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 5555 + 55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 6666 + 66 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 7777 + 77 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 8888 + 88 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 9999 + 99 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{411118} &:= \frac{111 \times 11111 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 22222 + 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 33333 + 33 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44444 + 44 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 55555 + 55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 66666 + 66 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77777 + 77 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 88888 + 88 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 99999 + 99 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 419 &:= \frac{111 \times 11 + (11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 22 + (22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 33 + (33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44 + (44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 55 + (55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 66 + (66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77 + (77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 88 + (88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 99 + (99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4119 &:= \frac{111 \times 111 + (11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 222 + (22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 333 + (33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 444 + (44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 555 + (55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 666 + (66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 777 + (77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 888 + (88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 999 + (99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41119 &:= \frac{111 \times 1111 + (11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 2222 + (22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 3333 + (33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 4444 + (44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 5555 + (55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 6666 + (66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 7777 + (77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 8888 + (88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 9999 + (99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 411119 &:= \frac{111 \times 11111 + (11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 22222 + (22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 33333 + (33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44444 + (44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 55555 + (55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 66666 + (66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77777 + (77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 88888 + (88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 99999 + (99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 420 &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2420 &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22420 &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222420} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{421} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2421} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22421} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222421} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{422} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2422} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22422} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222422} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{423} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2423} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22423} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222423} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 424 &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2424 &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22424 &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 222424 &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 425 &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2425 &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22425 &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \color{red}222425 &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \color{red}426 &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \color{red}2426 &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \color{red}22426 &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \color{red}222426 &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \color{red}427 &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2427} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22427} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222427} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{428} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2428} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22428} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222428} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 429 &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times (11+11+11)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (22+22+22)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (33+33+33)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times (44+44+44)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (55+55+55)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times (66+66+66)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times (77+77+77)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (88+88+88)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (99+99+99)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4329 &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times (111+111+111)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (222+222+222)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (333+333+333)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times (444+444+444)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (555+555+555)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times (666+666+666)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times (777+777+777)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (888+888+888)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (999+999+999)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43329 &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times (1111+1111+1111)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (2222+2222+2222)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (3333+3333+3333)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times (4444+4444+4444)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (5555+5555+5555)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times (6666+6666+6666)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times (7777+7777+7777)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (8888+8888+8888)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (9999+9999+9999)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 433329 &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times (11111+11111+11111)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (22222+22222+22222)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (33333+33333+33333)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times (44444+44444+44444)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (55555+55555+55555)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times (66666+66666+66666)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times (77777+77777+77777)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (88888+88888+88888)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (99999+99999+99999)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 430 &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times (11+11+11) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (22+22+22) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (33+33+33) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times (44+44+44) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (55+55+55) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times (66+66+66) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times (77+77+77) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (88+88+88) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (99+99+99) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4330 &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times (111+111+111) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (222+222+222) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (333+333+333) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times (444+444+444) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (555+555+555) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times (666+666+666) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times (777+777+777) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (888+888+888) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (999+999+999) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43330 &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times (1111+1111+1111) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (2222+2222+2222) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (3333+3333+3333) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times (4444+4444+4444) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (5555+5555+5555) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times (6666+6666+6666) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times (7777+7777+7777) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (8888+8888+8888) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (9999+9999+9999) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{433330} &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times (11111+11111+11111) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times (22222+22222+22222) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times (33333+33333+33333) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times (44444+44444+44444) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times (55555+55555+55555) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times (66666+66666+66666) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times (77777+77777+77777) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times (88888+88888+88888) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times (99999+99999+99999) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{431} &:= \frac{111+111+111+111-11-1-1}{1} = \frac{222+222+222+222-22-2-2}{2} = \frac{333+333+333+333-33-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+444+444-44-4-4}{4} = \frac{555+555+555+555-55-5-5}{5} = \frac{666+666+666+666-66-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777+777+777-77-7-7}{7} = \frac{888+888+888+888-88-8-8}{8} = \frac{999+999+999+999-99-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1431} &:= \frac{1111+111+111+111-11-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222+222+222+222-22-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333+333+333+333-33-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+444+444+444-44-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555+555+555+555-55-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666+666+666+666-66-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+777+777+777-77-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888+888+888+888-88-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999+999+999+999-99-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11431} &:= \frac{11111+111+111+111-11-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222+222+222+222-22-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333+333+333+333-33-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+444+444+444-44-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555+555+555+555-55-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666+666+666+666-66-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+777+777+777-77-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888+888+888+888-88-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999+999+999+999-99-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111431} &:= \frac{111111+111+111+111-11-1-1}{1} = \frac{222222+222+222+222-22-2-2}{2} = \frac{333333+333+333+333-33-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+444+444+444-44-4-4}{4} = \frac{555555+555+555+555-55-5-5}{5} = \frac{666666+666+666+666-66-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+777+777+777-77-7-7}{7} = \frac{888888+888+888+888-88-8-8}{8} = \frac{999999+999+999+999-99-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{432} &:= \frac{111+111+111+111-11-1}{1} = \frac{222+222+222+222-22-2}{2} = \frac{333+333+333+333-33-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+444+444+444-44-4}{4} = \frac{555+555+555+555-55-5}{5} = \frac{666+666+666+666-66-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+777+777+777-77-7}{7} = \frac{888+888+888+888-88-8}{8} = \frac{999+999+999+999-99-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{1432} := \frac{1111+111+111+111-11-1}{1} = \frac{2222+222+222+222-22-2}{2} = \frac{3333+333+333+333-33-3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11432} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111432} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{433} &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 111 + 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222 + 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333 + 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444 + 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555 + 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666 + 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777 + 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888 + 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999 + 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1433} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 111 + 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 222 + 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 333 + 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 444 + 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 555 + 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 666 + 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 777 + 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 888 + 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 999 + 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11433} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 111 + 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 222 + 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 333 + 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 444 + 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 555 + 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 666 + 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 777 + 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 888 + 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 999 + 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111433} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 111 + 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 222 + 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 333 + 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 444 + 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 555 + 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 666 + 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 777 + 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 888 + 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 999 + 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 434 &:= \frac{111 + 111 + 111 + 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222 + 222 + 222 + 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333 + 333 + 333 + 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 444 + 444 + 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555 + 555 + 555 + 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666 + 666 + 666 + 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 777 + 777 + 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888 + 888 + 888 + 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999 + 999 + 999 + 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1434 &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 111 + 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 222 + 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 333 + 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 444 + 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 555 + 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 666 + 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 777 + 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 888 + 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 999 + 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 11434 &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 111 + 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 222 + 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 333 + 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 444 + 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 555 + 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 666 + 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 777 + 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 888 + 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 999 + 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 111434 &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 111 + 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 222 + 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 333 + 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 444 + 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 555 + 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 666 + 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 777 + 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 888 + 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 999 + 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 435 &:= \frac{(111 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4435 &:= \frac{(1111 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44435 &:= \frac{(11111 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 444435 &:= \frac{(111111-1-1) \times (1+1+1+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222-2-2) \times (2+2+2+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333-3-3) \times (3+3+3+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444-4-4) \times (4+4+4+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555-5-5) \times (5+5+5+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666-6-6) \times (6+6+6+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777-7-7) \times (7+7+7+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888-8-8) \times (8+8+8+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999-9-9) \times (9+9+9+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 436 &:= \frac{(111-1-1) \times (1+1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222-2-2) \times (2+2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333-3-3) \times (3+3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-4-4) \times (4+4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555-5-5) \times (5+5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666-6-6) \times (6+6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7-7) \times (7+7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888-8-8) \times (8+8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999-9-9) \times (9+9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4436 &:= \frac{(1111-1-1) \times (1+1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222-2-2) \times (2+2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333-3-3) \times (3+3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-4-4) \times (4+4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555-5-5) \times (5+5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666-6-6) \times (6+6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-7-7) \times (7+7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888-8-8) \times (8+8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999-9-9) \times (9+9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44436 &:= \frac{(11111-1-1) \times (1+1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222-2-2) \times (2+2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333-3-3) \times (3+3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-4-4) \times (4+4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555-5-5) \times (5+5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666-6-6) \times (6+6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-7-7) \times (7+7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888-8-8) \times (8+8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999-9-9) \times (9+9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 444436 &:= \frac{(111111-1-1) \times (1+1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222-2-2) \times (2+2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333-3-3) \times (3+3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444-4-4) \times (4+4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555-5-5) \times (5+5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666-6-6) \times (6+6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777-7-7) \times (7+7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888-8-8) \times (8+8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999-9-9) \times (9+9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 437 &:= \frac{1111-11-1-1}{1+1} - \frac{111+1}{1} = \frac{2222-22-2-2}{2+2} - \frac{222+2}{2} = \frac{3333-33-3-3}{3+3} - \frac{333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-44-4-4}{4+4} - \frac{444+4}{4} = \frac{5555-55-5-5}{5+5} - \frac{555+5}{5} = \frac{6666-66-6-6}{6+6} - \frac{666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-77-7-7}{7+7} - \frac{777+7}{7} = \frac{8888-88-8-8}{8+8} - \frac{888+8}{8} = \frac{9999-99-9-9}{9+9} - \frac{999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$5437 := \frac{11111-11-1-1}{1+1} - \frac{111+1}{1} = \frac{22222-22-2-2}{2+2} - \frac{222+2}{2} = \frac{33333-33-3-3}{3+3} - \frac{333+3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{444 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{555 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{666 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{777 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{888 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{999 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55437} &:= \frac{111111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{111 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{222 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{333 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{444 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{555 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{666 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{777 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{888 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{999 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555437} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{111 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{222 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{333 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{444 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{555 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{666 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{777 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{888 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{999 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{438} &:= \frac{1111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{111}{1} = \frac{2222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{222}{2} = \frac{3333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{444}{4} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{555}{5} = \frac{6666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{777}{7} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{888}{8} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4438} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{1111}{1} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{2222}{2} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{3333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{4444}{4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{5555}{5} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{6666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{7777}{7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{8888}{8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{9999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{44438} &:= \frac{111111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{11111}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{22222}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{33333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{44444}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{55555}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{66666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{77777}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{88888}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{99999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{444438} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{111111}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{222222}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{333333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{444444}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{555555}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{666666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{777777}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{888888}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{999999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 439 &:= \frac{1111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{111 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{222 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{444 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{555 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{777 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{888 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5439 &:= \frac{11111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{111 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{222 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{444 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{555 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{777 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{888 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55439 &:= \frac{111111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{111 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{222 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{444 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{555 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{777 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{888 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 555439 &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{111 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{222 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{444 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{555 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{777 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{888 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 440 &:= \frac{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (222 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (333 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (444 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (555 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (666 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (777 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (888 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (999 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4440 &:= \frac{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1111 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2222 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3333 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4444 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5555 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6666 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7777 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8888 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9999 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44440 &:= \frac{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (11111 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (22222 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (33333 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44444 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55555 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66666 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (77777 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (88888 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (99999 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 444440 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times (111111 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times (222222 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times (333333 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times (444444 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times (555555 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times (666666 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times (777777 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times (888888 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times (999999 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 441 &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 1) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 2) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 3) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 4) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 5) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 6) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2441 &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 1) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 2) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 3) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 4) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 5) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 6) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22441 &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 1) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 2) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 3) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 4) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 5) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 6) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 222441 &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 1) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 2) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 3) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 4) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 5) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 6) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 442 &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2442 := \frac{(1111 + 111 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22442} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222442} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{443} &:= \frac{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times 111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times 222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times 333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times 444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times 555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times 666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times 777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times 888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times 999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4443} &:= \frac{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times 1111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times 2222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times 3333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times 4444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times 5555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times 6666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times 7777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times 8888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times 9999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{44443} &:= \frac{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times 11111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times 22222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times 33333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times 44444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times 55555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times 66666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times 77777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times 88888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times 99999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{444443} &:= \frac{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times 111111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times 222222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times 333333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times 444444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times 555555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times 666666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times 777777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times 888888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times 999999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 444 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4444 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 1111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 2222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 3333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 4444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 5555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 6666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 7777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 8888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 9999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44444 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 11111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 22222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 33333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 44444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 55555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 66666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 77777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 88888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 99999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 444444 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 111111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 222222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 333333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 444444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 555555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 666666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 777777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 888888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 999999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 445 &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5445 &:= \frac{11111 - 111 - 111 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 222 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 333 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 444 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 555 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 666 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 777 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 888 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 999 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55445 &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 111 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 222 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 333 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 444 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 555 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 666 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 777 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 888 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 999 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 555445 &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 111 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 222 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 333 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 444 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 555 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 666 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 777 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 888 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 999 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 446 &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2446 &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22446 &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 222446 &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 447 &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$4447 := \frac{(1111 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (4+4+4+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (5+5+5+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (6+6+6+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (7+7+7+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (8+8+8+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (9+9+9+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44447 &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (1+1+1+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (2+2+2+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (3+3+3+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (4+4+4+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (5+5+5+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (6+6+6+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (7+7+7+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (8+8+8+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (9+9+9+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 444447 &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (1+1+1+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (2+2+2+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (3+3+3+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (4+4+4+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (5+5+5+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (6+6+6+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (7+7+7+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (8+8+8+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (9+9+9+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 448 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (1+1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (2+2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (3+3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (4+4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (5+5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (6+6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (7+7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (8+8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (9+9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4448 &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (1+1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (2+2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (3+3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (4+4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (5+5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (6+6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (7+7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (8+8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (9+9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44448 &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (1+1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (2+2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (3+3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (4+4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (5+5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (6+6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (7+7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (8+8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (9+9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 444448 &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (1+1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (2+2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (3+3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (4+4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (5+5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (6+6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (7+7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (8+8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (9+9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 449 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (1+1+1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (2+2+2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (3+3+3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (4+4+4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (5+5+5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (6+6+6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (7+7+7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (8+8+8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (9+9+9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4449 &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (1+1+1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (2+2+2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (3+3+3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (4+4+4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (5+5+5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (6+6+6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (7+7+7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (8+8+8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (9+9+9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44449 &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (1+1+1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (2+2+2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (3+3+3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (4+4+4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (5+5+5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (6+6+6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (7+7+7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (8+8+8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (9+9+9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 444449 &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (1+1+1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (2+2+2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (3+3+3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (4+4+4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (5+5+5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (6+6+6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (7+7+7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (8+8+8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (9+9+9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 450 &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 11}{1+1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 22}{2+2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 33}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 44}{4+4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 55}{5+5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 66}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 77}{7+7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 88}{8+8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 99}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5450 &:= \frac{11111 - 111 - 111 + 11}{1+1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 222 + 22}{2+2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 333 + 33}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 444 + 44}{4+4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 555 + 55}{5+5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 666 + 66}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 777 + 77}{7+7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 888 + 88}{8+8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 999 + 99}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55450 &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 111 + 11}{1+1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 222 + 22}{2+2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 333 + 33}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 444 + 44}{4+4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 555 + 55}{5+5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 666 + 66}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 777 + 77}{7+7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 888 + 88}{8+8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 999 + 99}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 555450 &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 111 + 11}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 222 + 22}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 333 + 33}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 444 + 44}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 555 + 55}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 666 + 66}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 777 + 77}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 888 + 88}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 999 + 99}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 451 &:= \frac{111 + 11 + 1}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 + 22 + 2}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 + 33 + 3}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 44 + 4}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 5}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 6}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 7}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 8}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 9}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4551 &:= \frac{111 + 11 + 1}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 + 22 + 2}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 + 33 + 3}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 44 + 4}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 5}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 6}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 7}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 8}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 9}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45551 &:= \frac{111 + 11 + 1}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 + 22 + 2}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 + 33 + 3}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 44 + 4}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 5}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 6}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 7}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 8}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 9}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 455551 &:= \frac{111 + 11 + 1}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 + 22 + 2}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 + 33 + 3}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 + 44 + 4}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 + 55 + 5}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 + 66 + 6}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 + 77 + 7}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 + 88 + 8}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 + 99 + 9}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 452 &:= \frac{(111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$4452 := \frac{(1111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{44452} &:= \frac{(11111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{444452} &:= \frac{(111111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{453} &:= \frac{111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 11 \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 22 \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 33 \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 44 \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 55 \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 66 \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 77 \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 88 \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 99 \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3453} &:= \frac{1111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 11 \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 22 \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 33 \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 44 \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 55 \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 66 \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 77 \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 88 \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 99 \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33453} &:= \frac{11111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 11 \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{22222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 22 \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{33333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 33 \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 44 \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{55555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 55 \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{66666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 66 \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 77 \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{88888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 88 \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{99999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 99 \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333453} &:= \frac{111111 \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 11 \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{222222 \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 22 \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{333333 \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 33 \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 44 \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{555555 \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 55 \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{666666 \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 66 \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 77 \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{888888 \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 88 \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{999999 \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 99 \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 454 &:= \frac{111 \times (1+1+1) + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{222 \times (2+2+2) + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{333 \times (3+3+3) + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times (4+4+4) + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{555 \times (5+5+5) + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{666 \times (6+6+6) + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times (7+7+7) + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{888 \times (8+8+8) + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{999 \times (9+9+9) + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3454 &:= \frac{1111 \times (1+1+1) + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (2+2+2) + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (3+3+3) + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (4+4+4) + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (5+5+5) + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (6+6+6) + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (7+7+7) + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (8+8+8) + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (9+9+9) + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33454 &:= \frac{11111 \times (1+1+1) + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{22222 \times (2+2+2) + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{33333 \times (3+3+3) + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 \times (4+4+4) + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{55555 \times (5+5+5) + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{66666 \times (6+6+6) + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 \times (7+7+7) + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{88888 \times (8+8+8) + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{99999 \times (9+9+9) + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 333454 &:= \frac{111111 \times (1+1+1) + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{222222 \times (2+2+2) + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{333333 \times (3+3+3) + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (4+4+4) + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{555555 \times (5+5+5) + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{666666 \times (6+6+6) + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (7+7+7) + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{888888 \times (8+8+8) + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{999999 \times (9+9+9) + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 455 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 111 + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 222 + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 333 + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 444 + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 555 + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 666 + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 777 + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 888 + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 999 + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4455 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 1111 + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 2222 + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 3333 + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 4444 + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 5555 + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 6666 + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 7777 + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 8888 + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 9999 + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44455 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 11111 + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 22222 + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 33333 + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 44444 + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 55555 + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 66666 + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 77777 + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 88888 + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 99999 + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 444455 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 111111 + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 222222 + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 333333 + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 444444 + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 555555 + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 666666 + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 777777 + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 888888 + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 999999 + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 456 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 111 + (11+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 222 + (22+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 333 + (33+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 444 + (44+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 555 + (55+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 666 + (66+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 777 + (77+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 888 + (88+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 999 + (99+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4456 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 1111 + (11+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 2222 + (22+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 3333 + (33+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 4444 + (44+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 5555 + (55+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 6666 + (66+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 7777 + (77+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 8888 + (88+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 9999 + (99+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44456 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 11111 + (11+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 22222 + (22+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 33333 + (33+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 44444 + (44+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 55555 + (55+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 66666 + (66+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 77777 + (77+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 88888 + (88+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 99999 + (99+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 444456 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 111111 + (11+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 222222 + (22+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 333333 + (33+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 444444 + (44+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 555555 + (55+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 666666 + (66+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 777777 + (77+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 888888 + (88+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 999999 + (99+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 457 &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 111 + (11+1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 222 + (22+2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 333 + (33+3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 444 + (44+4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 555 + (55+5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 666 + (66+6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 777 + (77+7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 888 + (88+8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 999 + (99+9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$4457 := \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 1111 + (11+1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 2222 + (22+2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 3333 + (33+3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 4444 + (44+4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 5555 + (55+5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 6666 + (66+6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 7777 + (77+7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 8888 + (88+8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 9999 + (99+9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{44457} &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 11111 + (11+1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 22222 + (22+2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 33333 + (33+3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 44444 + (44+4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 55555 + (55+5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 66666 + (66+6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 77777 + (77+7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 88888 + (88+8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 99999 + (99+9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{444457} &:= \frac{(1+1+1+1) \times 111111 + (11+1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2+2+2+2) \times 222222 + (22+2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3+3+3+3) \times 333333 + (33+3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4+4+4+4) \times 444444 + (44+4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5+5+5+5) \times 555555 + (55+5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6+6+6+6) \times 666666 + (66+6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7+7+7+7) \times 777777 + (77+7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8+8+8+8) \times 888888 + (88+8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9+9+9+9) \times 999999 + (99+9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{458} &:= \frac{(111+111+1) \times (11+11) + (11+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(222+222+2) \times (22+22) + (22+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(333+333+3) \times (33+33) + (33+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444+4) \times (44+44) + (44+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(555+555+5) \times (55+55) + (55+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(666+666+6) \times (66+66) + (66+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777+7) \times (77+77) + (77+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(888+888+8) \times (88+88) + (88+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(999+999+9) \times (99+99) + (99+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2458} &:= \frac{(1111+111+1) \times (11+11) + (11+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(2222+222+2) \times (22+22) + (22+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(3333+333+3) \times (33+33) + (33+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+444+4) \times (44+44) + (44+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(5555+555+5) \times (55+55) + (55+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(6666+666+6) \times (66+66) + (66+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+777+7) \times (77+77) + (77+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(8888+888+8) \times (88+88) + (88+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(9999+999+9) \times (99+99) + (99+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22458} &:= \frac{(11111+111+1) \times (11+11) + (11+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22222+222+2) \times (22+22) + (22+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33333+333+3) \times (33+33) + (33+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+444+4) \times (44+44) + (44+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55555+555+5) \times (55+55) + (55+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66666+666+6) \times (66+66) + (66+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+777+7) \times (77+77) + (77+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88888+888+8) \times (88+88) + (88+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99999+999+9) \times (99+99) + (99+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222458} &:= \frac{(111111+111+1) \times (11+11) + (11+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(222222+222+2) \times (22+22) + (22+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(333333+333+3) \times (33+33) + (33+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+444+4) \times (44+44) + (44+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(555555+555+5) \times (55+55) + (55+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(666666+666+6) \times (66+66) + (66+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+777+7) \times (77+77) + (77+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(888888+888+8) \times (88+88) + (88+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(999999+999+9) \times (99+99) + (99+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 459 &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 11} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 22} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 44} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 55} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 77} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 88} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45459 &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 11} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 22} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 44} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 55} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 77} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 88} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4545459 &:= \frac{(11111111 + 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 11} = \frac{(22222222 + 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 22} = \frac{(33333333 + 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44444444 + 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 44} = \frac{(55555555 + 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 55} = \frac{(66666666 + 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77777777 + 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 77} = \frac{(88888888 + 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 88} = \frac{(99999999 + 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 454545459 &:= \frac{(1111111111 + 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 11} = \frac{(2222222222 + 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 22} = \frac{(3333333333 + 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444444 + 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 44} = \frac{(5555555555 + 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 55} = \frac{(6666666666 + 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777777 + 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 77} = \frac{(8888888888 + 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 88} = \frac{(9999999999 + 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 460 &:= \frac{1111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times 11}{(1 + 1) \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times 22}{(2 + 2) \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times 33}{(3 + 3) \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times 44}{(4 + 4) \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times 55}{(5 + 5) \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times 66}{(6 + 6) \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times 77}{(7 + 7) \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times 88}{(8 + 8) \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times 99}{(9 + 9) \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45460 &:= \frac{111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times 11}{(1 + 1) \times 11} = \frac{222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times 22}{(2 + 2) \times 22} = \frac{333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times 33}{(3 + 3) \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times 44}{(4 + 4) \times 44} = \frac{555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times 55}{(5 + 5) \times 55} = \frac{666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times 66}{(6 + 6) \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times 77}{(7 + 7) \times 77} = \frac{888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times 88}{(8 + 8) \times 88} = \frac{999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times 99}{(9 + 9) \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4545460 &:= \frac{11111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times 11}{(1 + 1) \times 11} = \frac{22222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times 22}{(2 + 2) \times 22} = \frac{33333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times 33}{(3 + 3) \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times 44}{(4 + 4) \times 44} = \frac{55555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times 55}{(5 + 5) \times 55} = \frac{66666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times 66}{(6 + 6) \times 66} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times 77}{(7 + 7) \times 77} = \frac{88888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times 88}{(8 + 8) \times 88} = \frac{99999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times 99}{(9 + 9) \times 99}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{454545460} &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times 11}{(1 + 1) \times 11} = \frac{2222222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times 22}{(2 + 2) \times 22} = \frac{3333333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times 33}{(3 + 3) \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times 44}{(4 + 4) \times 44} = \frac{5555555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times 55}{(5 + 5) \times 55} = \frac{6666666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times 66}{(6 + 6) \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times 77}{(7 + 7) \times 77} = \frac{8888888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times 88}{(8 + 8) \times 88} = \frac{9999999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times 99}{(9 + 9) \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{461} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5461} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55461} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555461} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{462} &:= \frac{11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 11 + 11)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (22 + 22 + 22)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (33 + 33 + 33)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44 + 44 + 44)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55 + 55 + 55)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 + 66 + 66)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (77 + 77 + 77)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (88 + 88 + 88)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (99 + 99 + 99)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4662 &:= \frac{11+1+1+1) \times (111+111+111)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{22+2+2+2) \times (222+222+222)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{33+3+3+3) \times (333+333+333)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44+4+4+4) \times (444+444+444)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{55+5+5+5) \times (555+555+555)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{66+6+6+6) \times (666+666+666)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77+7+7+7) \times (777+777+777)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{88+8+8+8) \times (888+888+888)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{99+9+9+9) \times (999+999+999)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46662 &:= \frac{11+1+1+1) \times (1111+1111+1111)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{22+2+2+2) \times (2222+2222+2222)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{33+3+3+3) \times (3333+3333+3333)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44+4+4+4) \times (4444+4444+4444)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{55+5+5+5) \times (5555+5555+5555)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{66+6+6+6) \times (6666+6666+6666)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77+7+7+7) \times (7777+7777+7777)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{88+8+8+8) \times (8888+8888+8888)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{99+9+9+9) \times (9999+9999+9999)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 466662 &:= \frac{11+1+1+1) \times (11111+11111+11111)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{22+2+2+2) \times (22222+22222+22222)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{33+3+3+3) \times (33333+33333+33333)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44+4+4+4) \times (44444+44444+44444)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{55+5+5+5) \times (55555+55555+55555)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{66+6+6+6) \times (66666+66666+66666)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77+7+7+7) \times (77777+77777+77777)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{88+8+8+8) \times (88888+88888+88888)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{99+9+9+9) \times (99999+99999+99999)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 463 &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times (11+11+11) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times (22+22+22) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times (33+33+33) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times (44+44+44) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times (55+55+55) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times (66+66+66) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times (77+77+77) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times (88+88+88) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times (99+99+99) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4663 &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times (111+111+111) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times (222+222+222) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times (333+333+333) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times (444+444+444) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times (555+555+555) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times (666+666+666) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times (777+777+777) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times (888+888+888) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times (999+999+999) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46663 &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times (1111+1111+1111) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times (2222+2222+2222) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times (3333+3333+3333) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times (4444+4444+4444) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times (5555+5555+5555) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times (6666+6666+6666) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times (7777+7777+7777) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times (8888+8888+8888) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times (9999+9999+9999) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 466663 &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times (11111+11111+11111) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times (22222+22222+22222) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times (33333+33333+33333) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times (44444+44444+44444) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times (55555+55555+55555) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times (66666+66666+66666) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times (77777+77777+77777) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times (88888+88888+88888) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times (99999+99999+99999) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 464 &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2464 &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22464 &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 222464 &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 465 &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2465 &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22465 &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{222465} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{466} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2466} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{22466} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{222466} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{467} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{2467} := \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22467} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222467} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{468} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2468} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22468} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222468} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 469 &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2469 &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22469 &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 222469 &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 470 &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2470 &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22470 &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 222470 &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 471 &:= \frac{1111 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{2222 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{3333 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{5555 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{6666 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{8888 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10471 &:= \frac{1111 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} + \frac{111111}{11} = \frac{2222 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} + \frac{222222}{22} = \frac{3333 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} + \frac{333333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} + \frac{444444}{44} = \frac{5555 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} + \frac{555555}{55} = \frac{6666 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} + \frac{666666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} + \frac{777777}{77} = \frac{8888 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} + \frac{888888}{88} = \frac{9999 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} + \frac{999999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1010471 &:= \frac{1111 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} + \frac{11111111}{11} = \frac{2222 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} + \frac{22222222}{22} = \frac{3333 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} + \frac{33333333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} + \frac{44444444}{44} = \frac{5555 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} + \frac{55555555}{55} = \frac{6666 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} + \frac{66666666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} + \frac{77777777}{77} = \frac{8888 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} + \frac{88888888}{88} = \frac{9999 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} + \frac{99999999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 101010471 &:= \frac{1111 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} + \frac{1111111111}{11} = \frac{2222 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} + \frac{2222222222}{22} = \frac{3333 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} + \frac{3333333333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} + \frac{4444444444}{44} = \frac{5555 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} + \frac{5555555555}{55} = \frac{6666 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} + \frac{6666666666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} + \frac{7777777777}{77} = \frac{8888 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} + \frac{8888888888}{88} = \frac{9999 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} + \frac{9999999999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 472 &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2472 &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22472} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222472} &:= \frac{(1111111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{473} &:= \frac{(11 + 11) \times (11 + 11) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22) \times (22 + 22) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33) \times (33 + 33) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44) \times (44 + 44) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55) \times (55 + 55) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66) \times (66 + 66) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77) \times (77 + 77) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88) \times (88 + 88) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99) \times (99 + 99) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4873} &:= \frac{(111 + 111) \times (11 + 11) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222) \times (22 + 22) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333) \times (33 + 33) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444) \times (44 + 44) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555) \times (55 + 55) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666) \times (66 + 66) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777) \times (77 + 77) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888) \times (88 + 88) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999) \times (99 + 99) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{48873} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111) \times (11 + 11) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222) \times (22 + 22) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333) \times (33 + 33) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444) \times (44 + 44) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555) \times (55 + 55) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666) \times (66 + 66) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777) \times (77 + 77) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888) \times (88 + 88) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999) \times (99 + 99) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{488873} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 11) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 22) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 33) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 44) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 55) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 66) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 77) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 88) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 99) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{474} := \frac{(111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\mathbf{2474} := \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\mathbf{22474} := \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\mathbf{222474} := \frac{(1111111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(4444444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{475} := \frac{(111 + 111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1) + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2) + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3) + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4) + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5) + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6) + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7) + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8) + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9) + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\mathbf{2475} := \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1) + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2) + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3) + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4) + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5) + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6) + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7) + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8) + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9) + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\mathbf{22475} := \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1) + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2) + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3) + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4) + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5) + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6) + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7) + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8) + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9) + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{222475} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1) + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2) + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3) + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4) + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5) + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6) + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7) + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8) + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9) + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{476} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 11 + 11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (22 + 22 + 22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (33 + 33 + 33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44 + 44 + 44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55 + 55 + 55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 + 66 + 66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (77 + 77 + 77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (88 + 88 + 88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (99 + 99 + 99 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{4676} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 + 111 + 111 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (222 + 222 + 222 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (333 + 333 + 333 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (444 + 444 + 444 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (555 + 555 + 555 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (666 + 666 + 666 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (777 + 777 + 777 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (888 + 888 + 888 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (999 + 999 + 999 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{46676} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1111 + 1111 + 1111 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2222 + 2222 + 2222 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3333 + 3333 + 3333 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4444 + 4444 + 4444 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5555 + 5555 + 5555 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6666 + 6666 + 6666 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7777 + 7777 + 7777 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8888 + 8888 + 8888 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9999 + 9999 + 9999 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{466676} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (11111 + 11111 + 11111 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (22222 + 22222 + 22222 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (33333 + 33333 + 33333 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44444 + 44444 + 44444 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55555 + 55555 + 55555 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66666 + 66666 + 66666 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (77777 + 77777 + 77777 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (88888 + 88888 + 88888 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (99999 + 99999 + 99999 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{477} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 99}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2477} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 66}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 99}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22477} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222477} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{478} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5478} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55478} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555478} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{479} := \frac{(111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 33}{3 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 66}{6 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 99}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\mathbf{2479} := \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 33}{3 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 66}{6 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 99}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\mathbf{22479} := \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 33}{3 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 66}{6 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 99}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\mathbf{222479} := \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 33}{3 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 66}{6 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 99}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{480} := \frac{(111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\mathbf{2480} := \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\mathbf{22480} := \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 222480 &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 481 &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1) \times 111}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2) \times 222}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3) \times 333}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} = \frac{(44 + 4 + 4) \times 444}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5) \times 555}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6) \times 666}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7) \times 777}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8) \times 888}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9) \times 999}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4181 &:= \frac{(111 + 1 + 1) \times 111}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2 + 2) \times 222}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3 + 3) \times 333}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} = \frac{(444 + 4 + 4) \times 444}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5 + 5) \times 555}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6 + 6) \times 666}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7 + 7) \times 777}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8 + 8) \times 888}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9 + 9) \times 999}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41181 &:= \frac{(1111 + 1 + 1) \times 111}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2 + 2) \times 222}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3 + 3) \times 333}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} = \frac{(4444 + 4 + 4) \times 444}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5 + 5) \times 555}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6 + 6) \times 666}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7 + 7) \times 777}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8 + 8) \times 888}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9 + 9) \times 999}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 411181 &:= \frac{(11111 + 1 + 1) \times 111}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 2 + 2) \times 222}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 3 + 3) \times 333}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} = \frac{(44444 + 4 + 4) \times 444}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 5 + 5) \times 555}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 6 + 6) \times 666}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 7 + 7) \times 777}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 8 + 8) \times 888}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 9 + 9) \times 999}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 482 &:= \frac{(11 + 11) \times (11 + 11) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22) \times (22 + 22) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33) \times (33 + 33) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44) \times (44 + 44) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55) \times (55 + 55) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66) \times (66 + 66) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77) \times (77 + 77) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88) \times (88 + 88) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99) \times (99 + 99) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4882 &:= \frac{(111 + 111) \times (11 + 11) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222) \times (22 + 22) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333) \times (33 + 33) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444) \times (44 + 44) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555) \times (55 + 55) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666) \times (66 + 66) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777) \times (77 + 77) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888) \times (88 + 88) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999) \times (99 + 99) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48882 &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111) \times (11 + 11) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222) \times (22 + 22) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333) \times (33 + 33) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444) \times (44 + 44) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555) \times (55 + 55) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666) \times (66 + 66) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 7777) \times (77 + 77) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888) \times (88 + 88) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999) \times (99 + 99) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 488882 &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 11) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 22) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 33) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 44) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 55) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 66) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 77) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 88) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 99) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 483 &:= \frac{(11 + 11) \times (11 + 11) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22) \times (22 + 22) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33) \times (33 + 33) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44) \times (44 + 44) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55) \times (55 + 55) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66) \times (66 + 66) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77) \times (77 + 77) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88) \times (88 + 88) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99) \times (99 + 99) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4883 &:= \frac{(111 + 111) \times (11 + 11) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222) \times (22 + 22) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333) \times (33 + 33) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444) \times (44 + 44) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555) \times (55 + 55) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666) \times (66 + 66) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777) \times (77 + 77) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888) \times (88 + 88) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999) \times (99 + 99) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48883 &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111) \times (11 + 11) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222) \times (22 + 22) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333) \times (33 + 33) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444) \times (44 + 44) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555) \times (55 + 55) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666) \times (66 + 66) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777) \times (77 + 77) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888) \times (88 + 88) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999) \times (99 + 99) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 488883 &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 11) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 22) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 33) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 44) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 55) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 66) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 77) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 88) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 99) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 484 &:= \frac{(11 + 11) \times (11 + 11)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22) \times (22 + 22)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33) \times (33 + 33)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44) \times (44 + 44)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55) \times (55 + 55)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66) \times (66 + 66)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77) \times (77 + 77)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88) \times (88 + 88)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99) \times (99 + 99)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4884 &:= \frac{(111 + 111) \times (11 + 11)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222) \times (22 + 22)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333) \times (33 + 33)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444) \times (44 + 44)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555) \times (55 + 55)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666) \times (66 + 66)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777) \times (77 + 77)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888) \times (88 + 88)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999) \times (99 + 99)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48884 &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111) \times (11 + 11)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222) \times (22 + 22)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333) \times (33 + 33)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444) \times (44 + 44)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555) \times (55 + 55)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666) \times (66 + 66)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777) \times (77 + 77)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888) \times (88 + 88)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999) \times (99 + 99)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 488884 &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 11)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 22)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 33)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 44)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 55)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 66)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 77)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 88)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 99)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 485 &:= \frac{(11 + 11) \times (11 + 11) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22) \times (22 + 22) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33) \times (33 + 33) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44) \times (44 + 44) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55) \times (55 + 55) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66) \times (66 + 66) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77) \times (77 + 77) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88) \times (88 + 88) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99) \times (99 + 99) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4885 &:= \frac{(111 + 111) \times (11 + 11) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222) \times (22 + 22) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333) \times (33 + 33) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444) \times (44 + 44) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555) \times (55 + 55) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666) \times (66 + 66) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777) \times (77 + 77) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888) \times (88 + 88) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999) \times (99 + 99) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48885 &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111) \times (11 + 11) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222) \times (22 + 22) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333) \times (33 + 33) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444) \times (44 + 44) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555) \times (55 + 55) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666) \times (66 + 66) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777) \times (77 + 77) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888) \times (88 + 88) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999) \times (99 + 99) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 488885 &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 11) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 22) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 33) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 44) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 55) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 66) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 77) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 88) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 99) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 486 &:= \frac{(11+11) \times (11+11) + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times (22+22) + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times (33+33) + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times (44+44) + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times (55+55) + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times (66+66) + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times (77+77) + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times (88+88) + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times (99+99) + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4886 &:= \frac{(111+111) \times (11+11) + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222) \times (22+22) + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333) \times (33+33) + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444) \times (44+44) + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555) \times (55+55) + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666) \times (66+66) + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777) \times (77+77) + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888) \times (88+88) + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999) \times (99+99) + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48886 &:= \frac{(1111+1111) \times (11+11) + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222) \times (22+22) + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333) \times (33+33) + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4444) \times (44+44) + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555) \times (55+55) + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666) \times (66+66) + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7777) \times (77+77) + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8888) \times (88+88) + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9999) \times (99+99) + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 488886 &:= \frac{(11111+11111) \times (11+11) + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22222) \times (22+22) + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33333) \times (33+33) + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+44444) \times (44+44) + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55555) \times (55+55) + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66666) \times (66+66) + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+77777) \times (77+77) + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88888) \times (88+88) + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99999) \times (99+99) + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 487 &:= \frac{(11+11) \times (11+11) + 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22) \times (22+22) + 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33) \times (33+33) + 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44) \times (44+44) + 4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55) \times (55+55) + 5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66) \times (66+66) + 6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77) \times (77+77) + 7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88) \times (88+88) + 8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99) \times (99+99) + 9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4887 &:= \frac{(111+111) \times (11+11) + 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222) \times (22+22) + 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333) \times (33+33) + 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444) \times (44+44) + 4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555) \times (55+55) + 5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666) \times (66+66) + 6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777) \times (77+77) + 7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888) \times (88+88) + 8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999) \times (99+99) + 9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48887 &:= \frac{(1111+1111) \times (11+11) + 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222) \times (22+22) + 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333) \times (33+33) + 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4444) \times (44+44) + 4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555) \times (55+55) + 5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666) \times (66+66) + 6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 7777) \times (77 + 77) + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888) \times (88 + 88) + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999) \times (99 + 99) + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{488887} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 11) + 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 22) + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 33) + 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 44) + 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 55) + 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 66) + 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 77) + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 88) + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 99) + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{488} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5488} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55488} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555488} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{489} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5489} := \frac{11111 - 111 - 11 - 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 22 - 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 33 - 33}{3 + 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 44 - 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 55 - 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 66 - 66}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 77 - 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 88 - 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 99 - 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55489} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 11 - 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 22 - 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 33 - 33}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 44 - 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 55 - 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 66 - 66}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 77 - 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 88 - 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 99 - 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555489} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 11 - 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 22 - 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 33 - 33}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 44 - 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 55 - 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 66 - 66}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 77 - 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 88 - 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 99 - 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{490} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5490} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55490} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555490} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 491 &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5491 &:= \frac{11111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55491 &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 555491 &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 492 &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4492 &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 + 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 + 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 + 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44492 &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 444492 &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 493 &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4993 &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 49993 &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 499993 &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 494 &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5494 &:= \frac{11111 - 111 - 11 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 22 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 33 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 44 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 55 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 66 - 6}{6 + 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 77 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 88 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 99 - 9}{9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55494} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 11 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 22 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 33 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 44 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 55 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 66 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 77 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 88 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 99 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555494} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 11 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 22 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 33 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 44 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 55 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 66 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 77 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 88 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 99 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{495} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5495} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 - 11 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 22 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 33 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 44 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 55 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 66 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 77 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 88 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 99 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55495} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 11 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 22 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 33 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 44 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 55 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 66 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 77 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 88 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 99 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555495} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 11 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 22 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 33 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 44 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 55 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 66 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 77 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 88 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 99 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{496} := \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3+3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5496} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55496} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555496} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{497} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4997} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{49997} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{499997} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{498} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{4998} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{49998} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{499998} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{499} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{4999} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9}{9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{49999} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{499999} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 3 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 4 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 5 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 6 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 9 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{500} &:= \frac{1111 - 111}{1+1} = \frac{2222 - 222}{2+2} = \frac{3333 - 333}{3+3} = \frac{4444 - 444}{4+4} = \frac{5555 - 555}{5+5} = \frac{6666 - 666}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777}{7+7} = \frac{8888 - 888}{8+8} = \frac{9999 - 999}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5000} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111}{1+1} = \frac{22222 - 2222}{2+2} = \frac{33333 - 3333}{3+3} = \frac{44444 - 4444}{4+4} = \frac{55555 - 5555}{5+5} = \frac{66666 - 6666}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777}{7+7} = \frac{88888 - 8888}{8+8} = \frac{99999 - 9999}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{50000} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111}{1+1} = \frac{222222 - 22222}{2+2} = \frac{333333 - 33333}{3+3} = \frac{444444 - 44444}{4+4} = \frac{555555 - 55555}{5+5} = \frac{666666 - 66666}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777}{7+7} = \frac{888888 - 88888}{8+8} = \frac{999999 - 99999}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{500000} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333}{3+3} = \frac{4444444 - 444444}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{501} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222 - 222 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333 - 333 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555 - 555 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666 - 666 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888 - 888 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999 - 999 + 9 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5001} := \frac{11111 - 1111 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 + 3 + 3}{3+3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{50001} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{500001} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{502} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5002} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{50002} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{500002} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 503 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (11-1-1) - 1 \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (22-2-2) - 2 \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (33-3-3) - 3 \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (44-4-4) - 4 \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (55-5-5) - 5 \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (66-6-6) - 6 \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (77-7-7) - 7 \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (88-8-8) - 8 \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (99-9-9) - 9 \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5003 &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (11-1-1) - 1 \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (22-2-2) - 2 \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (33-3-3) - 3 \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (44-4-4) - 4 \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (55-5-5) - 5 \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (66-6-6) - 6 \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (77-7-7) - 7 \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (88-8-8) - 8 \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (99-9-9) - 9 \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 50003 &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (11-1-1) - 1 \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (22-2-2) - 2 \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (33-3-3) - 3 \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (44-4-4) - 4 \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (55-5-5) - 5 \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (66-6-6) - 6 \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (77-7-7) - 7 \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (88-8-8) - 8 \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (99-9-9) - 9 \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 500003 &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (11-1-1) - 1 \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (22-2-2) - 2 \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (33-3-3) - 3 \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (44-4-4) - 4 \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (55-5-5) - 5 \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (66-6-6) - 6 \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (77-7-7) - 7 \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (88-8-8) - 8 \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (99-9-9) - 9 \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 504 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (11-1-1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (22-2-2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (33-3-3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (44-4-4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (55-5-5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (66-6-6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (77-7-7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (88-8-8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (99-9-9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5004 &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (11-1-1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (22-2-2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (33-3-3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (44-4-4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (55-5-5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (66-6-6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (77-7-7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (88-8-8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (99-9-9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 50004 &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (11-1-1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (22-2-2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (33-3-3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (44-4-4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (55-5-5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (66-6-6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (77-7-7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (88-8-8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (99-9-9)}{(9+9) \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{500004} &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (11-1-1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (22-2-2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (33-3-3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (44-4-4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (55-5-5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (66-6-6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (77-7-7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (88-8-8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (99-9-9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{505} &:= \frac{11111-1}{11+11} = \frac{22222-2}{22+22} = \frac{33333-3}{33+33} = \frac{44444-4}{44+44} = \frac{55555-5}{55+55} = \frac{66666-6}{66+66} \\ &:= \frac{77777-7}{77+77} = \frac{88888-8}{88+88} = \frac{99999-9}{99+99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{50505} &:= \frac{1111111-1}{11+11} = \frac{2222222-2}{22+22} = \frac{3333333-3}{33+33} = \frac{4444444-4}{44+44} = \frac{5555555-5}{55+55} = \frac{6666666-6}{66+66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777-7}{77+77} = \frac{8888888-8}{88+88} = \frac{9999999-9}{99+99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5050505} &:= \frac{111111111-1}{11+11} = \frac{222222222-2}{22+22} = \frac{333333333-3}{33+33} = \frac{444444444-4}{44+44} = \frac{555555555-5}{55+55} = \frac{666666666-6}{66+66} \\ &:= \frac{777777777-7}{77+77} = \frac{888888888-8}{88+88} = \frac{999999999-9}{99+99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{505050505} &:= \frac{11111111111-1}{11+11} = \frac{22222222222-2}{22+22} = \frac{33333333333-3}{33+33} = \frac{44444444444-4}{44+44} = \frac{55555555555-5}{55+55} = \frac{66666666666-6}{66+66} \\ &:= \frac{77777777777-7}{77+77} = \frac{88888888888-8}{88+88} = \frac{99999999999-9}{99+99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{506} &:= \frac{1111-111+11+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222-222+22+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333-333+33+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-444+44+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555-555+55+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666-666+66+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-777+77+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888-888+88+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999-999+99+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5506} &:= \frac{11111-111+11+1}{1+1} = \frac{22222-222+22+2}{2+2} = \frac{33333-333+33+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-444+44+4}{4+4} = \frac{55555-555+55+5}{5+5} = \frac{66666-666+66+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-777+77+7}{7+7} = \frac{88888-888+88+8}{8+8} = \frac{99999-999+99+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{55506} := \frac{111111-111+11+1}{1+1} = \frac{222222-222+22+2}{2+2} = \frac{333333-333+33+3}{3+3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444444 - 444 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 555 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 666 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 888 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 999 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555506} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{507} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5507} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55507} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555507} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{508} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5508 &:= \frac{11111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{22222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{33333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{55555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{66666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 55508 &:= \frac{111111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{222222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{333333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{555555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{666666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{888888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{999999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 555508 &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 509 &:= \frac{1111 - 111}{1+1} + \frac{11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222}{2+2} + \frac{22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333}{3+3} + \frac{33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444}{4+4} + \frac{44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555}{5+5} + \frac{55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666}{6+6} + \frac{66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777}{7+7} + \frac{77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888}{8+8} + \frac{88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999}{9+9} + \frac{99 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5109 &:= \frac{11111 - 1111}{1+1} + \frac{111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222}{2+2} + \frac{222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333}{3+3} + \frac{333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 4444}{4+4} + \frac{444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555}{5+5} + \frac{555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666}{6+6} + \frac{666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 7777}{7+7} + \frac{777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888}{8+8} + \frac{888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999}{9+9} + \frac{999 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 51109 &:= \frac{111111 - 11111}{1+1} + \frac{1111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222}{2+2} + \frac{2222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333}{3+3} + \frac{3333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 44444}{4+4} + \frac{4444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555}{5+5} + \frac{5555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666}{6+6} + \frac{6666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 77777}{7+7} + \frac{7777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888}{8+8} + \frac{8888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999}{9+9} + \frac{9999 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 511109 &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111}{1+1} + \frac{11111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222}{2+2} + \frac{22222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333}{3+3} + \frac{33333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444}{4+4} + \frac{44444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555}{5+5} + \frac{55555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666}{6+6} + \frac{66666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777}{7+7} + \frac{77777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888}{8+8} + \frac{88888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999}{9+9} + \frac{99999 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 510 &:= \frac{1111-111}{1+1} + \frac{11-1}{1} = \frac{222-22}{2+2} + \frac{22-2}{2} = \frac{333-33}{3+3} + \frac{33-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444-44}{4+4} + \frac{44-4}{4} = \frac{555-55}{5+5} + \frac{55-5}{5} = \frac{666-66}{6+6} + \frac{66-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777-77}{7+7} + \frac{77-7}{7} = \frac{888-88}{8+8} + \frac{88-8}{8} = \frac{999-99}{9+9} + \frac{99-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5110 &:= \frac{11111-1111}{1+1} + \frac{111-1}{1} = \frac{2222-222}{2+2} + \frac{222-2}{2} = \frac{3333-333}{3+3} + \frac{333-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-444}{4+4} + \frac{444-4}{4} = \frac{5555-555}{5+5} + \frac{555-5}{5} = \frac{6666-666}{6+6} + \frac{666-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-777}{7+7} + \frac{777-7}{7} = \frac{8888-888}{8+8} + \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{9999-999}{9+9} + \frac{999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 51110 &:= \frac{111111-11111}{1+1} + \frac{1111-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2222}{2+2} + \frac{2222-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3333}{3+3} + \frac{3333-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-4444}{4+4} + \frac{4444-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5555}{5+5} + \frac{5555-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6666}{6+6} + \frac{6666-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-7777}{7+7} + \frac{7777-7}{7} = \frac{88888-8888}{8+8} + \frac{8888-8}{8} = \frac{99999-9999}{9+9} + \frac{9999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 511110 &:= \frac{1111111-111111}{1+1} + \frac{11111-1}{1} = \frac{222222-22222}{2+2} + \frac{22222-2}{2} = \frac{333333-33333}{3+3} + \frac{33333-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444-44444}{4+4} + \frac{44444-4}{4} = \frac{555555-55555}{5+5} + \frac{55555-5}{5} = \frac{666666-66666}{6+6} + \frac{66666-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-77777}{7+7} + \frac{77777-7}{7} = \frac{888888-88888}{8+8} + \frac{88888-8}{8} = \frac{999999-99999}{9+9} + \frac{99999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 511 &:= \frac{111-11}{1+1} + \frac{11}{1} = \frac{22-2}{2+2} + \frac{22}{2} = \frac{33-3}{3+3} + \frac{33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44-4}{4+4} + \frac{44}{4} = \frac{55-5}{5+5} + \frac{55}{5} = \frac{66-6}{6+6} + \frac{66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77-7}{7+7} + \frac{77}{7} = \frac{88-8}{8+8} + \frac{88}{8} = \frac{99-9}{9+9} + \frac{99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5111 &:= \frac{1111-111}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1} = \frac{222-222}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2} = \frac{333-333}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444-444}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4} = \frac{555-555}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5} = \frac{666-666}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777-777}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7} = \frac{888-888}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8} = \frac{999-999}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 51111 &:= \frac{11111-1111}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{1} = \frac{2222-2222}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{2} = \frac{3333-3333}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-4444}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{4} = \frac{5555-5555}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{5} = \frac{6666-6666}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{777777 - 77777}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{511111} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111}{1+1} + \frac{11111}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222}{2+2} + \frac{22222}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333}{3+3} + \frac{33333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444}{4+4} + \frac{44444}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555}{5+5} + \frac{55555}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666}{6+6} + \frac{66666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777}{7+7} + \frac{77777}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888}{8+8} + \frac{88888}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999}{9+9} + \frac{99999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{512} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5512} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{22222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{33333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{55555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{66666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55512} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{222222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{333333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{555555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{666666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{888888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{999999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555512} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{513} &:= \frac{1111 - 111}{1+1} + \frac{11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222}{2+2} + \frac{22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333}{3+3} + \frac{33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444}{4+4} + \frac{44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555}{5+5} + \frac{55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666}{6+6} + \frac{66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777}{7+7} + \frac{77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888}{8+8} + \frac{88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999}{9+9} + \frac{99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5113} := \frac{11111 - 1111}{1+1} + \frac{111 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222}{2+2} + \frac{222 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333}{3+3} + \frac{333 + 3 + 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{44444 - 4444}{4+4} + \frac{444 + 4+4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555}{5+5} + \frac{555 + 5+5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666}{6+6} + \frac{666 + 6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777}{7+7} + \frac{777 + 7+7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888}{8+8} + \frac{888 + 8+8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999}{9+9} + \frac{999 + 9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{51113} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111}{1+1} + \frac{1111 + 1+1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222}{2+2} + \frac{2222 + 2+2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333}{3+3} + \frac{3333 + 3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444}{4+4} + \frac{4444 + 4+4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555}{5+5} + \frac{5555 + 5+5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666}{6+6} + \frac{6666 + 6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777}{7+7} + \frac{7777 + 7+7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888}{8+8} + \frac{8888 + 8+8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999}{9+9} + \frac{9999 + 9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{511113} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111}{1+1} + \frac{11111 + 1+1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222}{2+2} + \frac{22222 + 2+2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333}{3+3} + \frac{33333 + 3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444}{4+4} + \frac{44444 + 4+4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555}{5+5} + \frac{55555 + 5+5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666}{6+6} + \frac{66666 + 6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777}{7+7} + \frac{77777 + 7+7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888}{8+8} + \frac{88888 + 8+8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999}{9+9} + \frac{99999 + 9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{514} &:= \frac{1111 - 111}{1+1} + \frac{11 + 1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222}{2+2} + \frac{22 + 2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333}{3+3} + \frac{33 + 3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444}{4+4} + \frac{44 + 4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555}{5+5} + \frac{55 + 5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666}{6+6} + \frac{66 + 6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777}{7+7} + \frac{77 + 7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888}{8+8} + \frac{88 + 8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999}{9+9} + \frac{99 + 9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5114} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111}{1+1} + \frac{111 + 1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222}{2+2} + \frac{222 + 2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333}{3+3} + \frac{333 + 3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444}{4+4} + \frac{444 + 4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555}{5+5} + \frac{555 + 5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666}{6+6} + \frac{666 + 6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777}{7+7} + \frac{777 + 7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888}{8+8} + \frac{888 + 8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999}{9+9} + \frac{999 + 9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{51114} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111}{1+1} + \frac{1111 + 1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222}{2+2} + \frac{2222 + 2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333}{3+3} + \frac{3333 + 3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444}{4+4} + \frac{4444 + 4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555}{5+5} + \frac{5555 + 5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666}{6+6} + \frac{6666 + 6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777}{7+7} + \frac{7777 + 7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888}{8+8} + \frac{8888 + 8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999}{9+9} + \frac{9999 + 9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{511114} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111}{1+1} + \frac{11111 + 1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222}{2+2} + \frac{22222 + 2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333}{3+3} + \frac{33333 + 3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444}{4+4} + \frac{44444 + 4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555}{5+5} + \frac{55555 + 5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666}{6+6} + \frac{66666 + 6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777}{7+7} + \frac{77777 + 7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888}{8+8} + \frac{88888 + 8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999}{9+9} + \frac{99999 + 9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 515 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (11-1-1) + (1+1) \times 11}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (22-2-2) + (2+2) \times 22}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (33-3-3) + (3+3) \times 33}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (44-4-4) + (4+4) \times 44}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (55-5-5) + (5+5) \times 55}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (66-6-6) + (6+6) \times 66}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (77-7-7) + (7+7) \times 77}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (88-8-8) + (8+8) \times 88}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (99-9-9) + (9+9) \times 99}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5015 &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (11-1-1) + (1+1) \times 11}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (22-2-2) + (2+2) \times 22}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (33-3-3) + (3+3) \times 33}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (44-4-4) + (4+4) \times 44}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (55-5-5) + (5+5) \times 55}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (66-6-6) + (6+6) \times 66}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (77-7-7) + (7+7) \times 77}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (88-8-8) + (8+8) \times 88}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (99-9-9) + (9+9) \times 99}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 50015 &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (11-1-1) + (1+1) \times 11}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (22-2-2) + (2+2) \times 22}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (33-3-3) + (3+3) \times 33}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (44-4-4) + (4+4) \times 44}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (55-5-5) + (5+5) \times 55}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (66-6-6) + (6+6) \times 66}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (77-7-7) + (7+7) \times 77}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (88-8-8) + (8+8) \times 88}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (99-9-9) + (9+9) \times 99}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 500015 &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (11-1-1) + (1+1) \times 11}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (22-2-2) + (2+2) \times 22}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (33-3-3) + (3+3) \times 33}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (44-4-4) + (4+4) \times 44}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (55-5-5) + (5+5) \times 55}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (66-6-6) + (6+6) \times 66}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (77-7-7) + (7+7) \times 77}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (88-8-8) + (8+8) \times 88}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (99-9-9) + (9+9) \times 99}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 516 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (11-1-1) + (1+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (22-2-2) + (2+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (33-3-3) + (3+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (44-4-4) + (4+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (55-5-5) + (5+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (66-6-6) + (6+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (77-7-7) + (7+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (88-8-8) + (8+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (99-9-9) + (9+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5016 &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (11-1-1) + (1+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (22-2-2) + (2+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (33-3-3) + (3+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (44-4-4) + (4+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (55-5-5) + (5+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (66-6-6) + (6+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (77-7-7) + (7+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (88-8-8) + (8+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (99-9-9) + (9+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 50016 &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (11-1-1) + (1+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (22-2-2) + (2+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (33-3-3) + (3+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (44-4-4) + (4+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (55-5-5) + (5+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (66-6-6) + (6+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77777 + 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + (7 + 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + (8 + 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + (9 + 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{500016} &:= \frac{(111111 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + (1 + 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + (2 + 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + (3 + 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + (4 + 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + (5 + 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + (6 + 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + (7 + 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + (8 + 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + (9 + 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{517} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5517} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55517} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555517} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{518} &:= \frac{111 \times 11 + 111 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 22 + 222 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 33 + 333 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44 + 444 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 55 + 555 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 66 + 666 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77 + 777 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 88 + 888 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 99 + 999 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1518} &:= \frac{111 \times 11 + 1111 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 22 + 2222 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 33 + 3333 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44 + 4444 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 55 + 5555 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 66 + 6666 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77 + 7777 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times (7+7+7)} = \frac{888 \times 88 + 8888 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times (8+8+8)} = \frac{999 \times 99 + 9999 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times (9+9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11518} &:= \frac{111 \times 11 + 11111 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 22 + 22222 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 33 + 33333 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44 + 44444 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 55 + 55555 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 66 + 66666 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77 + 77777 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times (7+7+7)} = \frac{888 \times 88 + 88888 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times (8+8+8)} = \frac{999 \times 99 + 99999 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times (9+9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111518} &:= \frac{111 \times 11 + 111111 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 22 + 222222 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 33 + 333333 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44 + 444444 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 55 + 555555 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 66 + 666666 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77 + 777777 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times (7+7+7)} = \frac{888 \times 88 + 888888 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times (8+8+8)} = \frac{999 \times 99 + 999999 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times (9+9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{519} &:= \frac{111 \times 11 + (111+1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 22 + (222+2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 33 + (333+3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44 + (444+4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 55 + (555+5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 66 + (666+6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77 + (777+7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times (7+7+7)} = \frac{888 \times 88 + (888+8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times (8+8+8)} = \frac{999 \times 99 + (999+9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times (9+9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1519} &:= \frac{111 \times 11 + (1111+1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 22 + (2222+2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 33 + (3333+3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44 + (4444+4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 55 + (5555+5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 66 + (6666+6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77 + (7777+7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times (7+7+7)} = \frac{888 \times 88 + (8888+8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times (8+8+8)} = \frac{999 \times 99 + (9999+9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times (9+9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11519} &:= \frac{111 \times 11 + (11111+1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 22 + (22222+2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 33 + (33333+3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44 + (44444+4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 55 + (55555+5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 66 + (66666+6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times 77 + (77777+7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times (7+7+7)} = \frac{888 \times 88 + (88888+8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times (8+8+8)} = \frac{999 \times 99 + (99999+9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times (9+9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111519} &:= \frac{111 \times 11 + (111111+1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times (1+1+1)} = \frac{222 \times 22 + (222222+2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times (2+2+2)} = \frac{333 \times 33 + (333333+3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times (3+3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times 44 + (444444+4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times (4+4+4)} = \frac{555 \times 55 + (555555+5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times (5+5+5)} = \frac{666 \times 66 + (666666+6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times (6+6+6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{777 \times 77 + (777777 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 88 + (888888 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 99 + (999999 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}$$

► **520** := $\frac{111 \times 11 + (111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 22 + (222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 33 + (333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}$
 $:= \frac{444 \times 44 + (444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 55 + (555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 66 + (666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}$
 $:= \frac{777 \times 77 + (777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 88 + (888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 99 + (999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}$

5220 := $\frac{111 \times 111 + (1111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 222 + (2222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 333 + (3333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}$
 $:= \frac{444 \times 444 + (4444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 555 + (5555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 666 + (6666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}$
 $:= \frac{777 \times 777 + (7777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 888 + (8888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 999 + (9999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}$

52220 := $\frac{111 \times 1111 + (11111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 2222 + (22222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 3333 + (33333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}$
 $:= \frac{444 \times 4444 + (44444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 5555 + (55555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 6666 + (66666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}$
 $:= \frac{777 \times 7777 + (77777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 8888 + (88888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 9999 + (99999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}$

522220 := $\frac{111 \times 11111 + (111111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222 \times 22222 + (222222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333 \times 33333 + (333333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}$
 $:= \frac{444 \times 44444 + (444444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555 \times 55555 + (555555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666 \times 66666 + (666666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}$
 $:= \frac{777 \times 77777 + (777777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888 \times 88888 + (888888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999 \times 99999 + (999999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}$

► **521** := $\frac{1111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3}$
 $:= \frac{4444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6}$
 $:= \frac{7777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}$

5521 := $\frac{11111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3}$
 $:= \frac{44444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6}$
 $:= \frac{77777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{55521} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{555521} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{522} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{5522} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{55522} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{555522} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{523} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5523} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55523} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555523} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{524} &:= \frac{1111 + 11}{1 + 1} - \frac{111}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 22}{2 + 2} - \frac{222}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 33}{3 + 3} - \frac{333}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44}{4 + 4} - \frac{444}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55}{5 + 5} - \frac{555}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66}{6 + 6} - \frac{666}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77}{7 + 7} - \frac{777}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88}{8 + 8} - \frac{888}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99}{9 + 9} - \frac{999}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5524} &:= \frac{11111 + 11}{1 + 1} - \frac{111}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22}{2 + 2} - \frac{222}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33}{3 + 3} - \frac{333}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44}{4 + 4} - \frac{444}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55}{5 + 5} - \frac{555}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66}{6 + 6} - \frac{666}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77}{7 + 7} - \frac{777}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88}{8 + 8} - \frac{888}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99}{9 + 9} - \frac{999}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55524} &:= \frac{111111 + 11}{1 + 1} - \frac{111}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22}{2 + 2} - \frac{222}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33}{3 + 3} - \frac{333}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44}{4 + 4} - \frac{444}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55}{5 + 5} - \frac{555}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66}{6 + 6} - \frac{666}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77}{7 + 7} - \frac{777}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88}{8 + 8} - \frac{888}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99}{9 + 9} - \frac{999}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{555524} := \frac{1111111 + 11}{1 + 1} - \frac{111}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22}{2 + 2} - \frac{222}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33}{3 + 3} - \frac{333}{3 + 3 + 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444444 + 44}{4 + 4} - \frac{444}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55}{5 + 5} - \frac{555}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66}{6 + 6} - \frac{666}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 77}{7 + 7} - \frac{777}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88}{8 + 8} - \frac{888}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99}{9 + 9} - \frac{999}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 525 &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5525 &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 + 111 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (222 + 222 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (333 + 333 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (444 + 444 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (555 + 555 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (666 + 666 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (777 + 777 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (888 + 888 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (999 + 999 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55525 &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1111 + 1111 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2222 + 2222 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3333 + 3333 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4444 + 4444 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5555 + 5555 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6666 + 6666 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7777 + 7777 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8888 + 8888 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9999 + 9999 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 555525 &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (11111 + 11111 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (22222 + 22222 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (33333 + 33333 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44444 + 44444 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55555 + 55555 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66666 + 66666 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (77777 + 77777 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (88888 + 88888 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (99999 + 99999 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 526 &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (22 + 22 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (33 + 33 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44 + 44 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55 + 55 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66 + 66 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (77 + 77 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (88 + 88 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (99 + 99 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5526 &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 + 111 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (222 + 222 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (333 + 333 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (444 + 444 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (555 + 555 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (666 + 666 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (777 + 777 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (888 + 888 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (999 + 999 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 55526 &:= \frac{(11+11+1+1+1) \times (1111+1111-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2+2+2) \times (2222+2222-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3+3+3) \times (3333+3333-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4+4) \times (4444+4444-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5+5) \times (5555+5555-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6+6) \times (6666+6666-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7+7) \times (7777+7777-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8+8) \times (8888+8888-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9+9) \times (9999+9999-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 555526 &:= \frac{(11+11+1+1+1) \times (11111+11111-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2+2+2) \times (22222+22222-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3+3+3) \times (33333+33333-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+4+4+4) \times (44444+44444-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5+5+5) \times (55555+55555-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6+6+6) \times (66666+66666-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+7+7+7) \times (77777+77777-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8+8+8) \times (88888+88888-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9+9+9) \times (99999+99999-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 527 &:= \frac{(11+11+11+11) \times (11+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22+22) \times (22+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33+33) \times (33+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+44+44) \times (44+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55+55) \times (55+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66+66) \times (66+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+77+77) \times (77+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88+88) \times (88+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99+99) \times (99+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5327 &:= \frac{(111+111+111+111) \times (11+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222+222+222) \times (22+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333+333+333) \times (33+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444+444+444+444) \times (44+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555+555+555) \times (55+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666+666+666) \times (66+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777+777+777+777) \times (77+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888+888+888) \times (88+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999+999+999) \times (99+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53327 &:= \frac{(1111+1111+1111+1111) \times (11+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222+2222+2222) \times (22+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333+3333+3333) \times (33+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444+4444+4444+4444) \times (44+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555+5555+5555) \times (55+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666+6666+6666) \times (66+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777+7777+7777+7777) \times (77+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8888+8888+8888) \times (88+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9999+9999+9999) \times (99+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 533327 &:= \frac{(11111+11111+11111+11111) \times (11+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22222+22222+22222) \times (22+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33333+33333+33333) \times (33+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444+44444+44444+44444) \times (44+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55555+55555+55555) \times (55+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66666+66666+66666) \times (66+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777+77777+77777+77777) \times (77+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88888+88888+88888) \times (88+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99999+99999+99999) \times (99+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 528 &:= \frac{(11+11+11+11) \times (11+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22+22) \times (22+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33+33) \times (33+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44+44+44) \times (44+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55+55) \times (55+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66+66) \times (66+6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77+77+77) \times (77+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88+88) \times (88+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99+99) \times (99+9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{5328} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 111 + 111) \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222 + 222) \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333 + 333) \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444 + 444) \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555 + 555) \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666 + 666) \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777 + 777) \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888 + 888) \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999 + 999) \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{53328} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111 + 1111 + 1111) \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222 + 2222 + 2222) \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333 + 3333 + 3333) \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444 + 4444 + 4444) \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555 + 5555 + 5555) \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666 + 6666 + 6666) \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 7777 + 7777) \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 8888 + 8888) \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 9999 + 9999) \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{533328} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{529} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1) \times (11 + 11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2) \times (22 + 22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3) \times (33 + 33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 99 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{5129} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 1) \times (11 + 11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 2) \times (22 + 22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 3) \times (33 + 33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 4) \times (44 + 44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 5) \times (55 + 55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 6) \times (66 + 66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 7) \times (77 + 77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 8) \times (88 + 88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 9) \times (99 + 99 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{51129} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111 + 1) \times (11 + 11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222 + 2) \times (22 + 22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333 + 3) \times (33 + 33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444 + 4) \times (44 + 44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555 + 5) \times (55 + 55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666 + 6) \times (66 + 66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 7) \times (77 + 77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 8) \times (88 + 88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 9) \times (99 + 99 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{511129} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 1) \times (11 + 11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 2) \times (22 + 22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 3) \times (33 + 33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 4) \times (44 + 44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 5) \times (55 + 55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 6) \times (66 + 66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 7) \times (77 + 77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 8) \times (88 + 88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 9) \times (99 + 99 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 530 &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times (11+11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times (22+22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times (33+33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times (44+44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times (55+55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times (66+66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times (77+77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times (88+88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times (99+99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5130 &:= \frac{(111+111+1) \times (11+11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222+2) \times (22+22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333+3) \times (33+33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444+4) \times (44+44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555+5) \times (55+55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666+6) \times (66+66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777+7) \times (77+77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888+8) \times (88+88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999+9) \times (99+99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 51130 &:= \frac{(1111+1111+1) \times (11+11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222+2) \times (22+22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333+3) \times (33+33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4444+4) \times (44+44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555+5) \times (55+55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666+6) \times (66+66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7777+7) \times (77+77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8888+8) \times (88+88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9999+9) \times (99+99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 511130 &:= \frac{(11111+11111+1) \times (11+11+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22222+2) \times (22+22+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33333+3) \times (33+33+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+44444+4) \times (44+44+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55555+5) \times (55+55+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66666+6) \times (66+66+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+77777+7) \times (77+77+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88888+8) \times (88+88+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99999+9) \times (99+99+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 531 &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times (11+11+1) + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times (22+22+2) + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times (33+33+3) + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times (44+44+4) + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times (55+55+5) + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times (66+66+6) + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times (77+77+7) + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times (88+88+8) + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times (99+99+9) + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5131 &:= \frac{(111+111+1) \times (11+11+1) + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222+2) \times (22+22+2) + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333+3) \times (33+33+3) + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444+4) \times (44+44+4) + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555+5) \times (55+55+5) + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666+6) \times (66+66+6) + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777+7) \times (77+77+7) + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888+8) \times (88+88+8) + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999+9) \times (99+99+9) + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 51131 &:= \frac{(1111+1111+1) \times (11+11+1) + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222+2) \times (22+22+2) + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333+3) \times (33+33+3) + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4444+4) \times (44+44+4) + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555+5) \times (55+55+5) + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666+6) \times (66+66+6) + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 7) \times (77 + 77 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 8) \times (88 + 88 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 9) \times (99 + 99 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{511131} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 1) \times (11 + 11 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 2) \times (22 + 22 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 3) \times (33 + 33 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 4) \times (44 + 44 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 5) \times (55 + 55 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 6) \times (66 + 66 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 7) \times (77 + 77 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 8) \times (88 + 88 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 9) \times (99 + 99 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{532} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 11) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 22) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 33) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 44) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 55) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 66) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4532} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 + 11) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 + 22) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 + 33) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 + 44) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 + 55) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 + 66) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{44532} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 11) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 22) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 33) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 44) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 55) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 66) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{444532} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 11) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 22) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 33) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 44) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 55) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 66) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{533} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5343} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{53443} &:= \frac{(11111 + 1111 + 111) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 2222 + 222) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 3333 + 333) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 4444 + 444) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 5555 + 555) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 6666 + 666) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 7777 + 777) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 8888 + 888) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 9999 + 999) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{534443} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11111 + 1111) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22222 + 2222) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33333 + 3333) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44444 + 4444) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55555 + 5555) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66666 + 6666) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77777 + 7777) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88888 + 8888) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99999 + 9999) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{534} &:= \frac{1111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5434} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55534} &:= \frac{111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555534} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 535 &:= \frac{(111-1-1-1-1) \times (111-1)}{(11+11) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2-2-2-2) \times (222-2)}{(22+22) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3-3-3-3) \times (333-3)}{(33+33) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-4-4-4-4) \times (444-4)}{(44+44) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5-5-5-5) \times (555-5)}{(55+55) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6-6-6-6) \times (666-6)}{(66+66) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7-7-7-7) \times (777-7)}{(77+77) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8-8-8-8) \times (888-8)}{(88+88) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9-9-9-9) \times (999-9)}{(99+99) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5535 &:= \frac{(1111-1-1-1-1) \times (111-1)}{(11+11) \times 1} = \frac{(2222-2-2-2-2) \times (222-2)}{(22+22) \times 2} = \frac{(3333-3-3-3-3) \times (333-3)}{(33+33) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-4-4-4-4) \times (444-4)}{(44+44) \times 4} = \frac{(5555-5-5-5-5) \times (555-5)}{(55+55) \times 5} = \frac{(6666-6-6-6-6) \times (666-6)}{(66+66) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-7-7-7-7) \times (777-7)}{(77+77) \times 7} = \frac{(8888-8-8-8-8) \times (888-8)}{(88+88) \times 8} = \frac{(9999-9-9-9-9) \times (999-9)}{(99+99) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55535 &:= \frac{(11111-1-1-1-1) \times (111-1)}{(11+11) \times 1} = \frac{(22222-2-2-2-2) \times (222-2)}{(22+22) \times 2} = \frac{(33333-3-3-3-3) \times (333-3)}{(33+33) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-4-4-4-4) \times (444-4)}{(44+44) \times 4} = \frac{(55555-5-5-5-5) \times (555-5)}{(55+55) \times 5} = \frac{(66666-6-6-6-6) \times (666-6)}{(66+66) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-7-7-7-7) \times (777-7)}{(77+77) \times 7} = \frac{(88888-8-8-8-8) \times (888-8)}{(88+88) \times 8} = \frac{(99999-9-9-9-9) \times (999-9)}{(99+99) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 555535 &:= \frac{(111111-1-1-1-1) \times (111-1)}{(11+11) \times 1} = \frac{(222222-2-2-2-2) \times (222-2)}{(22+22) \times 2} = \frac{(333333-3-3-3-3) \times (333-3)}{(33+33) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444-4-4-4-4) \times (444-4)}{(44+44) \times 4} = \frac{(555555-5-5-5-5) \times (555-5)}{(55+55) \times 5} = \frac{(666666-6-6-6-6) \times (666-6)}{(66+66) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777-7-7-7-7) \times (777-7)}{(77+77) \times 7} = \frac{(888888-8-8-8-8) \times (888-8)}{(88+88) \times 8} = \frac{(999999-9-9-9-9) \times (999-9)}{(99+99) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 536 &:= \frac{(111+11+11+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+22+22+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+33+33+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+44+44+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+55+55+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+66+66+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+77+77+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+88+88+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+99+99+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4536 &:= \frac{(1111+11+11+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22+22+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33+33+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+44+44+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55+55+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66+66+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+77+77+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+88+88+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+99+99+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$44536 := \frac{(11111+11+11+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22+22+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33+33+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{444536} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{537} &:= \frac{1111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5537} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55537} &:= \frac{111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555537} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{538} &:= \frac{1111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{5538} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{55538} &:= \frac{111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{555538} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{539} &:= \frac{1111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{5539} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{55539} &:= \frac{111111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{555539} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6 + 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9+9}$$

► **540** := $\frac{1111 - 11 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222 - 22 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333 - 33 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3+3}$
 $:= \frac{4444 - 44 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666 - 66 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6+6}$
 $:= \frac{7777 - 77 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9+9}$

5540 := $\frac{11111 - 11 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3+3}$
 $:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6+6}$
 $:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9+9}$

55540 := $\frac{111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3+3}$
 $:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6+6}$
 $:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9+9}$

555540 := $\frac{1111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3+3}$
 $:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6+6}$
 $:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9+9}$

► **541** := $\frac{1111 - 11 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222 - 22 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333 - 33 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3+3}$
 $:= \frac{4444 - 44 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666 - 66 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6+6}$
 $:= \frac{7777 - 77 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9+9}$

5541 := $\frac{11111 - 11 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3+3}$
 $:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6+6}$
 $:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9+9}$

55541 := $\frac{111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3+3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555541} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{542} &:= \frac{1111 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5542} &:= \frac{11111 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55542} &:= \frac{111111 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555542} &:= \frac{1111111 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{543} &:= \frac{1111 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5543 &:= \frac{11111-1}{1+1} - \frac{11+1}{1} = \frac{22222-2}{2+2} - \frac{22+2}{2} = \frac{33333-3}{3+3} - \frac{33+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444-4}{4+4} - \frac{44+4}{4} = \frac{55555-5}{5+5} - \frac{55+5}{5} = \frac{66666-6}{6+6} - \frac{66+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777-7}{7+7} - \frac{77+7}{7} = \frac{88888-8}{8+8} - \frac{88+8}{8} = \frac{99999-9}{9+9} - \frac{99+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 55543 &:= \frac{111111-1}{1+1} - \frac{11+1}{1} = \frac{222222-2}{2+2} - \frac{22+2}{2} = \frac{333333-3}{3+3} - \frac{33+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444-4}{4+4} - \frac{44+4}{4} = \frac{555555-5}{5+5} - \frac{55+5}{5} = \frac{666666-6}{6+6} - \frac{66+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777-7}{7+7} - \frac{77+7}{7} = \frac{888888-8}{8+8} - \frac{88+8}{8} = \frac{999999-9}{9+9} - \frac{99+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 555543 &:= \frac{1111111-1}{1+1} - \frac{11+1}{1} = \frac{2222222-2}{2+2} - \frac{22+2}{2} = \frac{3333333-3}{3+3} - \frac{33+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444-4}{4+4} - \frac{44+4}{4} = \frac{5555555-5}{5+5} - \frac{55+5}{5} = \frac{6666666-6}{6+6} - \frac{66+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777-7}{7+7} - \frac{77+7}{7} = \frac{8888888-8}{8+8} - \frac{88+8}{8} = \frac{9999999-9}{9+9} - \frac{99+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 544 &:= \frac{1111-1}{1+1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{2222-2}{2+2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{3333-3}{3+3} - \frac{33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444-4}{4+4} - \frac{44}{4} = \frac{5555-5}{5+5} - \frac{55}{5} = \frac{6666-6}{6+6} - \frac{66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777-7}{7+7} - \frac{77}{7} = \frac{8888-8}{8+8} - \frac{88}{8} = \frac{9999-9}{9+9} - \frac{99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5544 &:= \frac{11111-1}{1+1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{22222-2}{2+2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{33333-3}{3+3} - \frac{33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444-4}{4+4} - \frac{44}{4} = \frac{55555-5}{5+5} - \frac{55}{5} = \frac{66666-6}{6+6} - \frac{66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777-7}{7+7} - \frac{77}{7} = \frac{88888-8}{8+8} - \frac{88}{8} = \frac{99999-9}{9+9} - \frac{99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 55544 &:= \frac{111111-1}{1+1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{222222-2}{2+2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{333333-3}{3+3} - \frac{33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444-4}{4+4} - \frac{44}{4} = \frac{555555-5}{5+5} - \frac{55}{5} = \frac{666666-6}{6+6} - \frac{66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777-7}{7+7} - \frac{77}{7} = \frac{888888-8}{8+8} - \frac{88}{8} = \frac{999999-9}{9+9} - \frac{99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 555544 &:= \frac{1111111-1}{1+1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{2222222-2}{2+2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{3333333-3}{3+3} - \frac{33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444-4}{4+4} - \frac{44}{4} = \frac{5555555-5}{5+5} - \frac{55}{5} = \frac{6666666-6}{6+6} - \frac{66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777-7}{7+7} - \frac{77}{7} = \frac{8888888-8}{8+8} - \frac{88}{8} = \frac{9999999-9}{9+9} - \frac{99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 545 &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} - \frac{33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4} - \frac{44}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} - \frac{55}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} - \frac{66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7} - \frac{77}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} - \frac{88}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} - \frac{99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5545 &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} - \frac{33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4}{4+4} - \frac{44}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} - \frac{55}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} - \frac{66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} - \frac{77}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} - \frac{88}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} - \frac{99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55545 &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} - \frac{33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} - \frac{44}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} - \frac{55}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} - \frac{66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} - \frac{77}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} - \frac{88}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} - \frac{99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 555545 &:= \frac{1111111+1}{1+1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{2222222+2}{2+2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{3333333+3}{3+3} - \frac{33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+4}{4+4} - \frac{44}{4} = \frac{5555555+5}{5+5} - \frac{55}{5} = \frac{6666666+6}{6+6} - \frac{66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+7}{7+7} - \frac{77}{7} = \frac{8888888+8}{8+8} - \frac{88}{8} = \frac{9999999+9}{9+9} - \frac{99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 546 &:= \frac{1111-11-11+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222-22-22+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333-33-33+3+3+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-44-44+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555-55-55+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666-66-66+6+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-77-77+7+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888-88-88+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999-99-99+9+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5546 &:= \frac{11111-11-11+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{22222-22-22+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{33333-33-33+3+3+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-44-44+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{55555-55-55+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{66666-66-66+6+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-77-77+7+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{88888-88-88+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{99999-99-99+9+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55546 &:= \frac{111111-11-11+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{222222-22-22+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{333333-33-33+3+3+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444-44-44+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{555555-55-55+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{666666-66-66+6+6+6}{6+6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555546} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{547} &:= \frac{1111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5547} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55547} &:= \frac{111111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555547} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{548} &:= \frac{1111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5548} := \frac{11111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3+3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55548} &:= \frac{111111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555548} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{549} &:= \frac{1111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5549} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55549} &:= \frac{111111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555549} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad 550 := \frac{1111-11}{1+1} = \frac{2222-22}{2+2} = \frac{3333-33}{3+3} = \frac{4444-44}{4+4} = \frac{5555-55}{5+5} = \frac{6666-66}{6+6} = \frac{7777-77}{7+7} = \frac{8888-88}{8+8} = \frac{9999-99}{9+9}$$

$$5550 := \frac{11111-11}{1+1} = \frac{22222-22}{2+2} = \frac{33333-33}{3+3} = \frac{44444-44}{4+4} = \frac{55555-55}{5+5} = \frac{66666-66}{6+6} = \frac{77777-77}{7+7} = \frac{88888-88}{8+8} = \frac{99999-99}{9+9}$$

$$55550 := \frac{111111-11}{1+1} = \frac{222222-22}{2+2} = \frac{333333-33}{3+3} = \frac{444444-44}{4+4} = \frac{555555-55}{5+5} = \frac{666666-66}{6+6} = \frac{777777-77}{7+7} = \frac{888888-88}{8+8} = \frac{999999-99}{9+9}$$

$$555550 := \frac{1111111-11}{1+1} = \frac{2222222-22}{2+2} = \frac{3333333-33}{3+3} = \frac{4444444-44}{4+4} = \frac{5555555-55}{5+5} = \frac{6666666-66}{6+6} = \frac{7777777-77}{7+7} = \frac{8888888-88}{8+8} = \frac{9999999-99}{9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 551 &:= \frac{1111-11+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222-22+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333-33+3+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-44+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555-55+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666-66+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-77+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888-88+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999-99+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5551 &:= \frac{11111-11+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{22222-22+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{33333-33+3+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-44+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{55555-55+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{66666-66+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-77+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{88888-88+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{99999-99+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55551 &:= \frac{111111-11+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{222222-22+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{333333-33+3+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444-44+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{555555-55+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{666666-66+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-77+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{888888-88+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{999999-99+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 555551 &:= \frac{1111111-11+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222-22+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333-33+3+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444-44+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555-55+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666-66+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777-77+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888-88+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999-99+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 552 &:= \frac{1111-11+1+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222-22+2+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333-33+3+3+3+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-44+4+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555-55+5+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666-66+6+6+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-77+7+7+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888-88+8+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999-99+9+9+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5552 &:= \frac{11111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55552 &:= \frac{111111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 555552 &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 553 &:= \frac{1111 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5553 &:= \frac{11111 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55553 &:= \frac{111111 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 7}{7 + 7} - \frac{7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 8}{8 + 8} - \frac{8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 9}{9 + 9} - \frac{9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 555553 &:= \frac{1111111 - 1}{1 + 1} - \frac{1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 2}{2 + 2} - \frac{2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 3}{3 + 3} - \frac{3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 4}{4 + 4} - \frac{4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 5}{5 + 5} - \frac{5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 6}{6 + 6} - \frac{6 + 6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777777-7}{7+7} - \frac{7+7}{7} = \frac{8888888-8}{8+8} - \frac{8+8}{8} = \frac{9999999-9}{9+9} - \frac{9+9}{9}$$

► **554** := $\frac{1 \times (1111-1-1-1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{2 \times (2222-2-2-2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{3 \times (3333-3-3-3)}{(3+3) \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{4 \times (4444-4-4-4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{5 \times (5555-5-5-5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{6 \times (6666-6-6-6)}{(6+6) \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{7 \times (7777-7-7-7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{8 \times (8888-8-8-8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{9 \times (9999-9-9-9)}{(9+9) \times 9}$

5554 := $\frac{1 \times (11111-1-1-1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{2 \times (22222-2-2-2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{3 \times (33333-3-3-3)}{(3+3) \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{4 \times (44444-4-4-4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{5 \times (55555-5-5-5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{6 \times (66666-6-6-6)}{(6+6) \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{7 \times (77777-7-7-7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{8 \times (88888-8-8-8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{9 \times (99999-9-9-9)}{(9+9) \times 9}$

55554 := $\frac{1 \times (111111-1-1-1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{2 \times (222222-2-2-2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{3 \times (333333-3-3-3)}{(3+3) \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{4 \times (444444-4-4-4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{5 \times (555555-5-5-5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{6 \times (666666-6-6-6)}{(6+6) \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{7 \times (777777-7-7-7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{8 \times (888888-8-8-8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{9 \times (999999-9-9-9)}{(9+9) \times 9}$

555554 := $\frac{1 \times (1111111-1-1-1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{2 \times (2222222-2-2-2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{3 \times (3333333-3-3-3)}{(3+3) \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{4 \times (4444444-4-4-4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{5 \times (5555555-5-5-5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{6 \times (6666666-6-6-6)}{(6+6) \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{7 \times (7777777-7-7-7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{8 \times (8888888-8-8-8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{9 \times (9999999-9-9-9)}{(9+9) \times 9}$

► **555** := $\frac{1111-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333-3}{3+3} = \frac{4444-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666-6}{6+6} = \frac{7777-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999-9}{9+9}$

5555 := $\frac{11111-1}{1+1} = \frac{22222-2}{2+2} = \frac{33333-3}{3+3} = \frac{44444-4}{4+4} = \frac{55555-5}{5+5} = \frac{66666-6}{6+6} = \frac{77777-7}{7+7} = \frac{88888-8}{8+8} = \frac{99999-9}{9+9}$

55555 := $\frac{111111-1}{1+1} = \frac{222222-2}{2+2} = \frac{333333-3}{3+3} = \frac{444444-4}{4+4} = \frac{555555-5}{5+5} = \frac{666666-6}{6+6} = \frac{777777-7}{7+7} = \frac{888888-8}{8+8} = \frac{999999-9}{9+9}$

555555 := $\frac{1111111-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333-3}{3+3} = \frac{4444444-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666-6}{6+6} = \frac{7777777-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999-9}{9+9}$

$$\blacktriangleright \quad 556 := \frac{1111+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} = \frac{4444+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} = \frac{7777+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9}$$

$$5556 := \frac{11111+1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} = \frac{44444+4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} = \frac{77777+7}{7+7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9}$$

$$55556 := \frac{111111+1}{1+1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} = \frac{444444+4}{4+4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} = \frac{777777+7}{7+7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9}$$

$$555556 := \frac{1111111+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333+3}{3+3} = \frac{4444444+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666+6}{6+6} = \frac{7777777+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999+9}{9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 557 &:= \frac{1111+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+3+3+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666+6+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+9+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5557 &:= \frac{11111+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+3+3+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{66666+6+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{88888+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{99999+9+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55557 &:= \frac{111111+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{222222+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{333333+3+3+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{555555+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{666666+6+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{888888+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{999999+9+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 555557 &:= \frac{1111111+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333+3+3+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+4+4+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555+5+5+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666+6+6+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+7+7+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888+8+8+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999+9+9+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 558 &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1} + \frac{1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} + \frac{2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} + \frac{3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4} + \frac{4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} + \frac{5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} + \frac{6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7} + \frac{7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} + \frac{8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} + \frac{9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5558 &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4}{4+4} + \frac{4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} + \frac{5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} + \frac{6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55558 &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 555558 &:= \frac{1111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{1+1}{1} = \frac{2222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{2+2}{2} = \frac{3333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{4+4}{4} = \frac{5555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{5+5}{5} = \frac{6666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{7+7}{7} = \frac{8888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{8+8}{8} = \frac{9999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 559 &:= \frac{1111+11-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+22-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+33-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+44-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+55-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666+66-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+77-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+88-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+99-9-9-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5559 &:= \frac{11111+11-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+22-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+33-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+44-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+55-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{66666+66-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+77-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{88888+88-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{99999+99-9-9-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55559 &:= \frac{111111+11-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{222222+22-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{333333+33-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{555555+55-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{666666+66-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{888888+88-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{999999+99-9-9-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 555559 &:= \frac{1111111+11-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222+22-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333+33-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+44-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555+55-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666+66-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}$$

► **560** := $\frac{1111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3}$
 $:= \frac{4444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6}$
 $:= \frac{7777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}$

5560 := $\frac{11111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3}$
 $:= \frac{44444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6}$
 $:= \frac{77777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}$

55560 := $\frac{111111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3}$
 $:= \frac{444444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6}$
 $:= \frac{777777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}$

555560 := $\frac{1111111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3}$
 $:= \frac{4444444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6}$
 $:= \frac{7777777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}$

► **561** := $\frac{1111 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 33}{3 + 3} = \frac{4444 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66}{6 + 6} = \frac{7777 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99}{9 + 9}$

5561 := $\frac{11111 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33}{3 + 3} = \frac{44444 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66}{6 + 6} = \frac{77777 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99}{9 + 9}$

55561 := $\frac{111111 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33}{3 + 3} = \frac{444444 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66}{6 + 6} = \frac{777777 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99}{9 + 9}$

555561 := $\frac{1111111 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33}{3 + 3} = \frac{4444444 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66}{6 + 6} = \frac{7777777 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99}{9 + 9}$

► **562** := $\frac{1111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5562} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55562} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555562} &:= \frac{1111111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{563} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5563} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55563} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 555563 &:= \frac{1111111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 564 &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5564 &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 55564 &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 555564 &:= \frac{1111111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 565 &:= \frac{(111 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6565 &:= \frac{(1111 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66565} &:= \frac{(11111 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666565} &:= \frac{(111111 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{566} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5566} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55566} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555566} &:= \frac{1111111 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{567} := \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5567} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55567} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555567} &:= \frac{1111111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{568} &:= \frac{1111 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5568} &:= \frac{11111 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55568} &:= \frac{111111 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{555568} &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{569} &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{5569} &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{55569} &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{555569} &:= \frac{1111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{570} &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{5570} &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6+6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9+9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55570} &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555570} &:= \frac{1111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{571} &:= \frac{1111+11+11+11-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+22+22+22-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+33+33+33-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+44+44+44-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+55+55+55-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666+66+66+66-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+77+77+77-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+88+88+88-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+99+99+99-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5571} &:= \frac{11111+11+11+11-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+22+22+22-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+33+33+33-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+44+44+44-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+55+55+55-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{66666+66+66+66-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+77+77+77-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{88888+88+88+88-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{99999+99+99+99-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55571} &:= \frac{111111+11+11+11-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{222222+22+22+22-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{333333+33+33+33-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44+44+44-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{555555+55+55+55-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{666666+66+66+66-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77+77+77-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{888888+88+88+88-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{999999+99+99+99-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555571} &:= \frac{1111111+11+11+11-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222+22+22+22-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333+33+33+33-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+44+44+44-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555+55+55+55-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666+66+66+66-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+77+77+77-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888+88+88+88-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999+99+99+99-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{572} := \frac{1111+11+11+11}{1+1} = \frac{2222+22+22+22}{2+2} = \frac{3333+33+33+33}{3+3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5572} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55572} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555572} &:= \frac{1111111 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{573} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5573} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55573} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 555573 &:= \frac{1111111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 574 &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1) \times (111 + 1)}{(11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2) \times (222 + 2)}{(22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3) \times (333 + 3)}{(33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4) \times (444 + 4)}{(44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5) \times (555 + 5)}{(55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6) \times (666 + 6)}{(66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7) \times (777 + 7)}{(77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8) \times (888 + 8)}{(88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9) \times (999 + 9)}{(99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5754 &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11) \times (111 + 1)}{(11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22) \times (222 + 2)}{(22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33) \times (333 + 3)}{(33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44) \times (444 + 4)}{(44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55) \times (555 + 5)}{(55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66) \times (666 + 6)}{(66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77) \times (777 + 7)}{(77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88) \times (888 + 8)}{(88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99) \times (999 + 9)}{(99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 57554 &:= \frac{(11111 + 1111 + 111) \times (111 + 1)}{(11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(22222 + 2222 + 222) \times (222 + 2)}{(22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(33333 + 3333 + 333) \times (333 + 3)}{(33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 4444 + 444) \times (444 + 4)}{(44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(55555 + 5555 + 555) \times (555 + 5)}{(55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(66666 + 6666 + 666) \times (666 + 6)}{(66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 7777 + 777) \times (777 + 7)}{(77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(88888 + 8888 + 888) \times (888 + 8)}{(88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(99999 + 9999 + 999) \times (999 + 9)}{(99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 575554 &:= \frac{(111111 + 11111 + 1111) \times (111 + 1)}{(11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(222222 + 22222 + 2222) \times (222 + 2)}{(22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(333333 + 33333 + 3333) \times (333 + 3)}{(33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 44444 + 4444) \times (444 + 4)}{(44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(555555 + 55555 + 5555) \times (555 + 5)}{(55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(666666 + 66666 + 6666) \times (666 + 6)}{(66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 77777 + 7777) \times (777 + 7)}{(77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(888888 + 88888 + 8888) \times (888 + 8)}{(88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(999999 + 99999 + 9999) \times (999 + 9)}{(99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 575 &:= \frac{(111 - 11) \times (11 + 11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (22 + 22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (33 + 33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (44 + 44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (55 + 55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (66 + 66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (77 + 77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (88 + 88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (99 + 99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$5750 := \frac{(1111 - 111) \times (11 + 11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222) \times (22 + 22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333) \times (33 + 33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 - 444) \times (44 + 44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555) \times (55 + 55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666) \times (66 + 66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 777) \times (77 + 77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888) \times (88 + 88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999) \times (99 + 99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{57500} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111) \times (11 + 11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222) \times (22 + 22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333) \times (33 + 33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444) \times (44 + 44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555) \times (55 + 55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666) \times (66 + 66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777) \times (77 + 77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888) \times (88 + 88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999) \times (99 + 99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{575000} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111) \times (11 + 11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222) \times (22 + 22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333) \times (33 + 33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444) \times (44 + 44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555) \times (55 + 55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666) \times (66 + 66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777) \times (77 + 77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888) \times (88 + 88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999) \times (99 + 99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{576} &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5576} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55576} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555576} &:= \frac{1111111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 577 &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5577 &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55577 &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 555577 &:= \frac{1111111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 578 &:= \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5578 &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55578 &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 555578 &:= \frac{1111111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 579 &:= \frac{1111 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{99 + 99 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5579 &:= \frac{11111 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{99 + 99 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 55579 &:= \frac{11111 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{99 + 99 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 555579 &:= \frac{111111 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{99 + 99 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 580 &:= \frac{1111 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5580 &:= \frac{11111 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+99+9+9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55580} &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+33+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+66+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+99+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555580} &:= \frac{1111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+33+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+66+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+99+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{581} &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+33+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+55+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+66+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+99+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5581} &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+33+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+55+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+66+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+99+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55581} &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+33+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+55+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+66+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+99+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555581} &:= \frac{1111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+11+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+22+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+33+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+44+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+55+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+66+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+77+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+88+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+99+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{582} := \frac{1111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+33+3+3+3+3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5582} &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55582} &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555582} &:= \frac{1111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11+11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22+22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33+33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44+44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55+55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66+66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77+77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88+88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99+99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{583} &:= \frac{111+1}{1+1+1+1} + \frac{1111-1}{1+1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2+2+2} + \frac{2222-2}{2+2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3+3+3} + \frac{3333-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444+4}{4+4+4+4} + \frac{4444-4}{4+4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5+5+5} + \frac{5555-5}{5+5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6+6+6} + \frac{6666-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777+7}{7+7+7+7} + \frac{7777-7}{7+7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8+8+8} + \frac{8888-8}{8+8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9+9+9} + \frac{9999-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5583} &:= \frac{111+1}{1+1+1+1} + \frac{11111-1}{1+1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2+2+2} + \frac{22222-2}{2+2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3+3+3} + \frac{33333-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444+4}{4+4+4+4} + \frac{44444-4}{4+4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5+5+5} + \frac{55555-5}{5+5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6+6+6} + \frac{66666-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777+7}{7+7+7+7} + \frac{77777-7}{7+7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8+8+8} + \frac{88888-8}{8+8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9+9+9} + \frac{99999-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55583} &:= \frac{111+1}{1+1+1+1} + \frac{111111-1}{1+1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2+2+2} + \frac{222222-2}{2+2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3+3+3} + \frac{333333-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444+4}{4+4+4+4} + \frac{444444-4}{4+4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5+5+5} + \frac{555555-5}{5+5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6+6+6} + \frac{666666-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777+7}{7+7+7+7} + \frac{777777-7}{7+7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8+8+8} + \frac{888888-8}{8+8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9+9+9} + \frac{999999-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 555583 &:= \frac{111+1}{1+1+1+1} + \frac{1111111-1}{1+1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2+2+2} + \frac{2222222-2}{2+2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3+3+3} + \frac{3333333-3}{3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{444+4}{4+4+4+4} + \frac{4444444-4}{4+4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5+5+5} + \frac{5555555-5}{5+5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6+6+6} + \frac{6666666-6}{6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{777+7}{7+7+7+7} + \frac{7777777-7}{7+7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8+8+8} + \frac{8888888-8}{8+8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9+9+9} + \frac{9999999-9}{9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 584 &:= \frac{111+1}{1+1+1+1} + \frac{1111+1}{1+1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2+2+2} + \frac{2222+2}{2+2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3+3+3} + \frac{3333+3}{3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{444+4}{4+4+4+4} + \frac{4444+4}{4+4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5+5+5} + \frac{5555+5}{5+5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6+6+6} + \frac{6666+6}{6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{777+7}{7+7+7+7} + \frac{7777+7}{7+7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8+8+8} + \frac{8888+8}{8+8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9+9+9} + \frac{9999+9}{9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5584 &:= \frac{111+1}{1+1+1+1} + \frac{11111+1}{1+1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2+2+2} + \frac{22222+2}{2+2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3+3+3} + \frac{33333+3}{3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{444+4}{4+4+4+4} + \frac{44444+4}{4+4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5+5+5} + \frac{55555+5}{5+5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6+6+6} + \frac{66666+6}{6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{777+7}{7+7+7+7} + \frac{77777+7}{7+7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8+8+8} + \frac{88888+8}{8+8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9+9+9} + \frac{99999+9}{9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 55584 &:= \frac{111+1}{1+1+1+1} + \frac{111111+1}{1+1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2+2+2} + \frac{222222+2}{2+2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3+3+3} + \frac{333333+3}{3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{444+4}{4+4+4+4} + \frac{444444+4}{4+4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5+5+5} + \frac{555555+5}{5+5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6+6+6} + \frac{666666+6}{6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{777+7}{7+7+7+7} + \frac{777777+7}{7+7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8+8+8} + \frac{888888+8}{8+8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9+9+9} + \frac{999999+9}{9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 555584 &:= \frac{111+1}{1+1+1+1} + \frac{1111111+1}{1+1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2+2+2} + \frac{2222222+2}{2+2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3+3+3} + \frac{3333333+3}{3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{444+4}{4+4+4+4} + \frac{4444444+4}{4+4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5+5+5} + \frac{5555555+5}{5+5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6+6+6} + \frac{6666666+6}{6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{777+7}{7+7+7+7} + \frac{7777777+7}{7+7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8+8+8} + \frac{8888888+8}{8+8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9+9+9} + \frac{9999999+9}{9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 585 &:= \frac{(111+111+11+1) \times (11-1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(222+222+22+2) \times (22-2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(333+333+33+3) \times (33-3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(444+444+44+4) \times (44-4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(555+555+55+5) \times (55-5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(666+666+66+6) \times (66-6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(777+777+77+7) \times (77-7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(888+888+88+8) \times (88-8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(999+999+99+9) \times (99-9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5585 &:= \frac{(1111+1111+11+1) \times (11-1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(2222+2222+22+2) \times (22-2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(3333+3333+33+3) \times (33-3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444+4444+44+4) \times (44-4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(5555+5555+55+5) \times (55-5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(6666+6666+66+6) \times (66-6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 - 7)}{(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 - 8)}{(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 - 9)}{(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55585} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 11 + 1) \times (11 - 1)}{(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 22 + 2) \times (22 - 2)}{(2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 33 + 3) \times (33 - 3)}{(3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 44 + 4) \times (44 - 4)}{(4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 55 + 5) \times (55 - 5)}{(5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 66 + 6) \times (66 - 6)}{(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 - 7)}{(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 - 8)}{(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 - 9)}{(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555585} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111111 + 11 + 1) \times (11 - 1)}{(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(222222 + 222222 + 22 + 2) \times (22 - 2)}{(2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(333333 + 333333 + 33 + 3) \times (33 - 3)}{(3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444444 + 44 + 4) \times (44 - 4)}{(4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(555555 + 555555 + 55 + 5) \times (55 - 5)}{(5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(666666 + 666666 + 66 + 6) \times (66 - 6)}{(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 - 7)}{(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(888888 + 888888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 - 8)}{(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(999999 + 999999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 - 9)}{(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{586} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1) \times 11 + 111 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2) \times 22 + 222 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3) \times 33 + 333 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4) \times 44 + 444 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5) \times 55 + 555 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6) \times 66 + 666 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7) \times 77 + 777 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8) \times 88 + 888 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9) \times 99 + 999 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5886} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1) \times 111 + 1111 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2) \times 222 + 2222 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3) \times 333 + 3333 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4) \times 444 + 4444 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5) \times 555 + 5555 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6) \times 666 + 6666 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7) \times 777 + 7777 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8) \times 888 + 8888 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9) \times 999 + 9999 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{58886} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1) \times 1111 + 11111 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2) \times 2222 + 22222 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3) \times 3333 + 33333 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4) \times 4444 + 44444 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5) \times 5555 + 55555 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6) \times 6666 + 66666 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7) \times 7777 + 77777 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8) \times 8888 + 88888 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9) \times 9999 + 99999 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{588886} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1) \times 11111 + 111111 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2) \times 22222 + 222222 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3) \times 33333 + 333333 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4) \times 44444 + 444444 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5) \times 55555 + 555555 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6) \times 66666 + 666666 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7) \times 77777 + 777777 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8) \times 88888 + 888888 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9) \times 99999 + 999999 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{587} := \frac{1111 - 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{111}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 - 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{222}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 - 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{333}{3 + 3 + 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 - 44}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4+4+4} = \frac{5555 - 55}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5+5+5} = \frac{6666 - 66}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 77}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7+7+7} = \frac{8888 - 88}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8+8+8} = \frac{9999 - 99}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5587} &:= \frac{11111 - 11}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1+1+1} = \frac{22222 - 22}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2+2+2} = \frac{33333 - 33}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 44}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4+4+4} = \frac{55555 - 55}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5+5+5} = \frac{66666 - 66}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7+7+7} = \frac{88888 - 88}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8+8+8} = \frac{99999 - 99}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555587} &:= \frac{111111 - 11}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1+1+1} = \frac{222222 - 22}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2+2+2} = \frac{333333 - 33}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4+4+4} = \frac{555555 - 55}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5+5+5} = \frac{666666 - 66}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7+7+7} = \frac{888888 - 88}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8+8+8} = \frac{999999 - 99}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5555587} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1+1+1} = \frac{2222222 - 22}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2+2+2} = \frac{3333333 - 33}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 44}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4+4+4} = \frac{5555555 - 55}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5+5+5} = \frac{6666666 - 66}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 77}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7+7+7} = \frac{8888888 - 88}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8+8+8} = \frac{9999999 - 99}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{588} &:= \frac{1111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1+1+1} = \frac{2222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2+2+2} = \frac{3333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4+4+4} = \frac{5555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5+5+5} = \frac{6666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7+7+7} = \frac{8888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8+8+8} = \frac{9999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5588} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1+1+1} = \frac{22222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2+2+2} = \frac{33333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4+4+4} = \frac{55555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5+5+5} = \frac{66666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7+7+7} = \frac{88888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8+8+8} = \frac{99999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55588} &:= \frac{111111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1+1+1} = \frac{222222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2+2+2} = \frac{333333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3+3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4+4+4} = \frac{555555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5+5+5} = \frac{666666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6+6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7+7+7} = \frac{888888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8+8+8} = \frac{999999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9+9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{555588} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{111}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{222}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{333}{3 + 3 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{444}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{555}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{666}{6 + 6 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{777}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{888}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{999}{9 + 9 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{589} &:= \frac{(111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) - 11 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) - 22 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) - 33 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) - 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) - 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) - 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) - 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) - 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) - 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{6589} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) - 11 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) - 22 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) - 33 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) - 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) - 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) - 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) - 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) - 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) - 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{66589} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) - 11 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) - 22 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) - 33 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) - 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) - 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) - 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) - 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) - 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) - 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{666589} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) - 11 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) - 22 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) - 33 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) - 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) - 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) - 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) - 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) - 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) - 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{590} &:= \frac{(111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) - (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) - (22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) - (33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) - (44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) - (55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) - (66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) - (77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) - (88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) - (99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6590} := \frac{(1111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) - (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) - (22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) - (33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) - (44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) - (55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) - (66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) - (77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) - (88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) - (99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66590} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) - (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) - (22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) - (33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) - (44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) - (55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) - (66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) - (77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) - (88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) - (99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666590} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) - (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) - (22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) - (33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) - (44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) - (55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) - (66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) - (77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) - (88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) - (99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{591} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 111 - 1 \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{1 \times (11 + 11 - 1)} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 222 - 2 \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{2 \times (22 + 22 - 2)} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 333 - 3 \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{3 \times (33 + 33 - 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 444 - 4 \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{4 \times (44 + 44 - 4)} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 555 - 5 \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{5 \times (55 + 55 - 5)} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 666 - 6 \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{6 \times (66 + 66 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 777 - 7 \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{7 \times (77 + 77 - 7)} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 888 - 8 \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{8 \times (88 + 88 - 8)} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 999 - 9 \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{9 \times (99 + 99 - 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{592591} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 111111 - 1 \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{1 \times (11 + 11 - 1)} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 222222 - 2 \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{2 \times (22 + 22 - 2)} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 333333 - 3 \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{3 \times (33 + 33 - 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 444444 - 4 \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{4 \times (44 + 44 - 4)} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 555555 - 5 \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{5 \times (55 + 55 - 5)} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 666666 - 6 \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{6 \times (66 + 66 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 777777 - 7 \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{7 \times (77 + 77 - 7)} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 888888 - 8 \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{8 \times (88 + 88 - 8)} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 999999 - 9 \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{9 \times (99 + 99 - 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{592592591} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 111111111 - 1 \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{1 \times (11 + 11 - 1)} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 222222222 - 2 \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{2 \times (22 + 22 - 2)} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 333333333 - 3 \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{3 \times (33 + 33 - 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 444444444 - 4 \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{4 \times (44 + 44 - 4)} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 555555555 - 5 \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{5 \times (55 + 55 - 5)} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 666666666 - 6 \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{6 \times (66 + 66 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 777777777 - 7 \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{7 \times (77 + 77 - 7)} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 888888888 - 8 \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{8 \times (88 + 88 - 8)} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 999999999 - 9 \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{9 \times (99 + 99 - 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{592592592591} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 111111111111 - 1 \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{1 \times (11 + 11 - 1)} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 222222222222 - 2 \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{2 \times (22 + 22 - 2)} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 333333333333 - 3 \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{3 \times (33 + 33 - 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 444444444444 - 4 \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{4 \times (44 + 44 - 4)} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 555555555555 - 5 \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{5 \times (55 + 55 - 5)} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 666666666666 - 6 \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{6 \times (66 + 66 - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 777777777777 - 7 \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{7 \times (77 + 77 - 7)} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 888888888888 - 8 \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{8 \times (88 + 88 - 8)} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 999999999999 - 9 \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{9 \times (99 + 99 - 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 592 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times 111}{(11+11-1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times 222}{(22+22-2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times 333}{(33+33-3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 444}{(44+44-4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times 555}{(55+55-5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times 666}{(66+66-6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 777}{(77+77-7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times 888}{(88+88-8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times 999}{(99+99-9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 592592 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times 111111}{(11+11-1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times 222222}{(22+22-2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times 333333}{(33+33-3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 444444}{(44+44-4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times 555555}{(55+55-5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times 666666}{(66+66-6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 777777}{(77+77-7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times 888888}{(88+88-8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times 999999}{(99+99-9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 592592592 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times 111111111}{(11+11-1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times 222222222}{(22+22-2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times 333333333}{(33+33-3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 444444444}{(44+44-4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times 555555555}{(55+55-5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times 666666666}{(66+66-6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 777777777}{(77+77-7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times 888888888}{(88+88-8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times 999999999}{(99+99-9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 592592592592 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times 111111111111}{(11+11-1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times 222222222222}{(22+22-2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times 333333333333}{(33+33-3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 444444444444}{(44+44-4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times 555555555555}{(55+55-5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times 666666666666}{(66+66-6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 777777777777}{(77+77-7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times 888888888888}{(88+88-8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times 999999999999}{(99+99-9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 593 &:= \frac{(111-1-1) \times 11-1 \times (11+1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2-2) \times 22-2 \times (22+2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3-3) \times 33-3 \times (33+3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-4-4) \times 44-4 \times (44+4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5-5) \times 55-5 \times (55+5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6-6) \times 66-6 \times (66+6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7-7) \times 77-7 \times (77+7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8-8) \times 88-8 \times (88+8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9-9) \times 99-9 \times (99+9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5983 &:= \frac{(1111-11-11) \times 11-1 \times (11+1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222-22-22) \times 22-2 \times (22+2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333-33-33) \times 33-3 \times (33+3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-44-44) \times 44-4 \times (44+4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555-55-55) \times 55-5 \times (55+5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666-66-66) \times 66-6 \times (66+6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-77-77) \times 77-7 \times (77+7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888-88-88) \times 88-8 \times (88+8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999-99-99) \times 99-9 \times (99+9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59883 &:= \frac{(11111-111-111) \times 11-1 \times (11+1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222-222-222) \times 22-2 \times (22+2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333-333-333) \times 33-3 \times (33+3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-444-444) \times 44-4 \times (44+4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555-555-555) \times 55-5 \times (55+5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666-666-666) \times 66-6 \times (66+6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77777 - 777 - 777) \times 77 - 7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 888 - 888) \times 88 - 8 \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 999 - 999) \times 99 - 9 \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{598883} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1111 - 1111) \times 11 - 1 \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2222 - 2222) \times 22 - 2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3333 - 3333) \times 33 - 3 \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 4444 - 4444) \times 44 - 4 \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5555 - 5555) \times 55 - 5 \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6666 - 6666) \times 66 - 6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7777 - 7777) \times 77 - 7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8888 - 8888) \times 88 - 8 \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9999 - 9999) \times 99 - 9 \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{594} &:= \frac{(111 - 1 - 1) \times 11 - 1 \times 11}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2) \times 22 - 2 \times 22}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3) \times 33 - 3 \times 33}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times 44 - 4 \times 44}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times 55 - 5 \times 55}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times 66 - 6 \times 66}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7) \times 77 - 7 \times 77}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8) \times 88 - 8 \times 88}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9) \times 99 - 9 \times 99}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5984} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 - 11) \times 11 - 1 \times 11}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 - 22) \times 22 - 2 \times 22}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 - 33) \times 33 - 3 \times 33}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 - 44) \times 44 - 4 \times 44}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 - 55) \times 55 - 5 \times 55}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 - 66) \times 66 - 6 \times 66}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77 - 77) \times 77 - 7 \times 77}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 - 88) \times 88 - 8 \times 88}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 - 99) \times 99 - 9 \times 99}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{59884} &:= \frac{(11111 - 111 - 111) \times 11 - 1 \times 11}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 222 - 222) \times 22 - 2 \times 22}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 333 - 333) \times 33 - 3 \times 33}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 444 - 444) \times 44 - 4 \times 44}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 555 - 555) \times 55 - 5 \times 55}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 666 - 666) \times 66 - 6 \times 66}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 777 - 777) \times 77 - 7 \times 77}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 888 - 888) \times 88 - 8 \times 88}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 999 - 999) \times 99 - 9 \times 99}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{598884} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1111 - 1111) \times 11 - 1 \times 11}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2222 - 2222) \times 22 - 2 \times 22}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3333 - 3333) \times 33 - 3 \times 33}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 4444 - 4444) \times 44 - 4 \times 44}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5555 - 5555) \times 55 - 5 \times 55}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6666 - 6666) \times 66 - 6 \times 66}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7777 - 7777) \times 77 - 7 \times 77}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8888 - 8888) \times 88 - 8 \times 88}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9999 - 9999) \times 99 - 9 \times 99}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{595} &:= \frac{(111 - 1 - 1) \times 11 - 1 \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2) \times 22 - 2 \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3) \times 33 - 3 \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times 44 - 4 \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times 55 - 5 \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times 66 - 6 \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7) \times 77 - 7 \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8) \times 88 - 8 \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9) \times 99 - 9 \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5985 &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 - 11) \times 11 - 1 \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 - 22) \times 22 - 2 \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 - 33) \times 33 - 3 \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 - 44) \times 44 - 4 \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 - 55) \times 55 - 5 \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 - 66) \times 66 - 6 \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77 - 77) \times 77 - 7 \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 - 88) \times 88 - 8 \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 - 99) \times 99 - 9 \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59885 &:= \frac{(11111 - 111 - 111) \times 11 - 1 \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 222 - 222) \times 22 - 2 \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 333 - 333) \times 33 - 3 \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 444 - 444) \times 44 - 4 \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 555 - 555) \times 55 - 5 \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 666 - 666) \times 66 - 6 \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 777 - 777) \times 77 - 7 \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 888 - 888) \times 88 - 8 \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 999 - 999) \times 99 - 9 \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 598885 &:= \frac{(111111 - 1111 - 1111) \times 11 - 1 \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2222 - 2222) \times 22 - 2 \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3333 - 3333) \times 33 - 3 \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 4444 - 4444) \times 44 - 4 \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5555 - 5555) \times 55 - 5 \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6666 - 6666) \times 66 - 6 \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7777 - 7777) \times 77 - 7 \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8888 - 8888) \times 88 - 8 \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9999 - 9999) \times 99 - 9 \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 596 &:= \frac{1111 \times (11 + 1) - (11 - 1) \times (11 + 11)}{1 \times (11 + 11)} = \frac{2222 \times (22 + 2) - (22 - 2) \times (22 + 22)}{2 \times (22 + 22)} = \frac{3333 \times (33 + 3) - (33 - 3) \times (33 + 33)}{3 \times (33 + 33)} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (44 + 4) - (44 - 4) \times (44 + 44)}{4 \times (44 + 44)} = \frac{5555 \times (55 + 5) - (55 - 5) \times (55 + 55)}{5 \times (55 + 55)} = \frac{6666 \times (66 + 6) - (66 - 6) \times (66 + 66)}{6 \times (66 + 66)} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (77 + 7) - (77 - 7) \times (77 + 77)}{7 \times (77 + 77)} = \frac{8888 \times (88 + 8) - (88 - 8) \times (88 + 88)}{8 \times (88 + 88)} = \frac{9999 \times (99 + 9) - (99 - 9) \times (99 + 99)}{9 \times (99 + 99)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 60596 &:= \frac{111111 \times (11 + 1) - (11 - 1) \times (11 + 11)}{1 \times (11 + 11)} = \frac{222222 \times (22 + 2) - (22 - 2) \times (22 + 22)}{2 \times (22 + 22)} = \frac{333333 \times (33 + 3) - (33 - 3) \times (33 + 33)}{3 \times (33 + 33)} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (44 + 4) - (44 - 4) \times (44 + 44)}{4 \times (44 + 44)} = \frac{555555 \times (55 + 5) - (55 - 5) \times (55 + 55)}{5 \times (55 + 55)} = \frac{666666 \times (66 + 6) - (66 - 6) \times (66 + 66)}{6 \times (66 + 66)} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (77 + 7) - (77 - 7) \times (77 + 77)}{7 \times (77 + 77)} = \frac{888888 \times (88 + 8) - (88 - 8) \times (88 + 88)}{8 \times (88 + 88)} = \frac{999999 \times (99 + 9) - (99 - 9) \times (99 + 99)}{9 \times (99 + 99)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6060596 &:= \frac{11111111 \times (11 + 1) - (11 - 1) \times (11 + 11)}{1 \times (11 + 11)} = \frac{22222222 \times (22 + 2) - (22 - 2) \times (22 + 22)}{2 \times (22 + 22)} = \frac{33333333 \times (33 + 3) - (33 - 3) \times (33 + 33)}{3 \times (33 + 33)} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (44 + 4) - (44 - 4) \times (44 + 44)}{4 \times (44 + 44)} = \frac{55555555 \times (55 + 5) - (55 - 5) \times (55 + 55)}{5 \times (55 + 55)} = \frac{66666666 \times (66 + 6) - (66 - 6) \times (66 + 66)}{6 \times (66 + 66)} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 \times (77 + 7) - (77 - 7) \times (77 + 77)}{7 \times (77 + 77)} = \frac{88888888 \times (88 + 8) - (88 - 8) \times (88 + 88)}{8 \times (88 + 88)} = \frac{99999999 \times (99 + 9) - (99 - 9) \times (99 + 99)}{9 \times (99 + 99)} \end{aligned}$$

$$606060596 := \frac{1111111111 \times (11 + 1) - (11 - 1) \times (11 + 11)}{1 \times (11 + 11)} = \frac{2222222222 \times (22 + 2) - (22 - 2) \times (22 + 22)}{2 \times (22 + 22)} = \frac{3333333333 \times (33 + 3) - (33 - 3) \times (33 + 33)}{3 \times (33 + 33)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (44 + 4) - (44 - 4) \times (44 + 44)}{4 \times (44 + 44)} = \frac{5555555555 \times (55 + 5) - (55 - 5) \times (55 + 55)}{5 \times (55 + 55)} = \frac{6666666666 \times (66 + 6) - (66 - 6) \times (66 + 66)}{6 \times (66 + 66)} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (77 + 7) - (77 - 7) \times (77 + 77)}{7 \times (77 + 77)} = \frac{8888888888 \times (88 + 8) - (88 - 8) \times (88 + 88)}{8 \times (88 + 88)} = \frac{9999999999 \times (99 + 9) - (99 - 9) \times (99 + 99)}{9 \times (99 + 99)} \end{aligned}$$

► **597** := $\frac{(111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

6597 := $\frac{(1111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

66597 := $\frac{(11111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

666597 := $\frac{(111111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

► **598** := $\frac{(111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

6598 := $\frac{(1111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66598} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666598} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{599} &:= \frac{(111 - 1 - 1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5989} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 - 11) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 - 22) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 - 33) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 - 44) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 - 55) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 - 66) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77 - 77) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 - 88) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 - 99) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{59889} &:= \frac{(11111 - 111 - 111) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 222 - 222) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 333 - 333) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 444 - 444) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 555 - 555) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 666 - 666) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 777 - 777) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 888 - 888) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 999 - 999) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{598889} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1111 - 1111) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2222 - 2222) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3333 - 3333) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 4444 - 4444) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5555 - 5555) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6666 - 6666) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7777 - 7777) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8888 - 8888) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9999 - 9999) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{600} &:= \frac{1111+111+1+1}{1+1} - \frac{11+1}{1} = \frac{2222+222+2+2}{2+2} - \frac{22+2}{2} = \frac{3333+333+3+3}{3+3} - \frac{33+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+444+4+4}{4+4} - \frac{44+4}{4} = \frac{5555+555+5+5}{5+5} - \frac{55+5}{5} = \frac{6666+666+6+6}{6+6} - \frac{66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+777+7+7}{7+7} - \frac{77+7}{7} = \frac{8888+888+8+8}{8+8} - \frac{88+8}{8} = \frac{9999+999+9+9}{9+9} - \frac{99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6100} &:= \frac{11111+1111+1+1}{1+1} - \frac{11+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2222+2+2}{2+2} - \frac{22+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3333+3+3}{3+3} - \frac{33+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4444+4+4}{4+4} - \frac{44+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5555+5+5}{5+5} - \frac{55+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6666+6+6}{6+6} - \frac{66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7777+7+7}{7+7} - \frac{77+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8888+8+8}{8+8} - \frac{88+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9999+9+9}{9+9} - \frac{99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{61100} &:= \frac{111111+11111+1+1}{1+1} - \frac{11+1}{1} = \frac{222222+22222+2+2}{2+2} - \frac{22+2}{2} = \frac{333333+33333+3+3}{3+3} - \frac{33+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44444+4+4}{4+4} - \frac{44+4}{4} = \frac{555555+55555+5+5}{5+5} - \frac{55+5}{5} = \frac{666666+66666+6+6}{6+6} - \frac{66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77777+7+7}{7+7} - \frac{77+7}{7} = \frac{888888+88888+8+8}{8+8} - \frac{88+8}{8} = \frac{999999+99999+9+9}{9+9} - \frac{99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{611100} &:= \frac{1111111+111111+1+1}{1+1} - \frac{11+1}{1} = \frac{2222222+222222+2+2}{2+2} - \frac{22+2}{2} = \frac{3333333+333333+3+3}{3+3} - \frac{33+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+444444+4+4}{4+4} - \frac{44+4}{4} = \frac{5555555+555555+5+5}{5+5} - \frac{55+5}{5} = \frac{6666666+666666+6+6}{6+6} - \frac{66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+777777+7+7}{7+7} - \frac{77+7}{7} = \frac{8888888+888888+8+8}{8+8} - \frac{88+8}{8} = \frac{9999999+999999+9+9}{9+9} - \frac{99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{601} &:= \frac{1111+111+1+1}{1+1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{2222+222+2+2}{2+2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{3333+333+3+3}{3+3} - \frac{33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+444+4+4}{4+4} - \frac{44}{4} = \frac{5555+555+5+5}{5+5} - \frac{55}{5} = \frac{6666+666+6+6}{6+6} - \frac{66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+777+7+7}{7+7} - \frac{77}{7} = \frac{8888+888+8+8}{8+8} - \frac{88}{8} = \frac{9999+999+9+9}{9+9} - \frac{99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6101} &:= \frac{11111+1111+1+1}{1+1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{22222+2222+2+2}{2+2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{33333+3333+3+3}{3+3} - \frac{33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4444+4+4}{4+4} - \frac{44}{4} = \frac{55555+5555+5+5}{5+5} - \frac{55}{5} = \frac{66666+6666+6+6}{6+6} - \frac{66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7777+7+7}{7+7} - \frac{77}{7} = \frac{88888+8888+8+8}{8+8} - \frac{88}{8} = \frac{99999+9999+9+9}{9+9} - \frac{99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{61101} &:= \frac{111111+11111+1+1}{1+1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{222222+22222+2+2}{2+2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{333333+33333+3+3}{3+3} - \frac{33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44444+4+4}{4+4} - \frac{44}{4} = \frac{555555+55555+5+5}{5+5} - \frac{55}{5} = \frac{666666+66666+6+6}{6+6} - \frac{66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77777+7+7}{7+7} - \frac{77}{7} = \frac{888888+88888+8+8}{8+8} - \frac{88}{8} = \frac{999999+99999+9+9}{9+9} - \frac{99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{611101} &:= \frac{1111111+111111+1+1}{1+1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{2222222+222222+2+2}{2+2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{3333333+333333+3+3}{3+3} - \frac{33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444+444444+4+4}{4+4} - \frac{44}{4} = \frac{5555555+555555+5+5}{5+5} - \frac{55}{5} = \frac{6666666+666666+6+6}{6+6} - \frac{66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777+777777+7+7}{7+7} - \frac{77}{7} = \frac{8888888+888888+8+8}{8+8} - \frac{88}{8} = \frac{9999999+999999+9+9}{9+9} - \frac{99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{602} &:= \frac{1111+111+1+1}{1+1} - \frac{11-1}{1} = \frac{2222+222+2+2}{2+2} - \frac{22-2}{2} = \frac{3333+333+3+3}{3+3} - \frac{33-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+444+4+4}{4+4} - \frac{44-4}{4} = \frac{5555+555+5+5}{5+5} - \frac{55-5}{5} = \frac{6666+666+6+6}{6+6} - \frac{66-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777+777+7+7}{7+7} - \frac{77-7}{7} = \frac{8888+888+8+8}{8+8} - \frac{88-8}{8} = \frac{9999+999+9+9}{9+9} - \frac{99-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{6102} &:= \frac{11111+1111+1+1}{1+1} - \frac{11-1}{1} = \frac{22222+2222+2+2}{2+2} - \frac{22-2}{2} = \frac{33333+3333+3+3}{3+3} - \frac{33-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444+4444+4+4}{4+4} - \frac{44-4}{4} = \frac{55555+5555+5+5}{5+5} - \frac{55-5}{5} = \frac{66666+6666+6+6}{6+6} - \frac{66-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777+7777+7+7}{7+7} - \frac{77-7}{7} = \frac{88888+8888+8+8}{8+8} - \frac{88-8}{8} = \frac{99999+9999+9+9}{9+9} - \frac{99-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{61102} &:= \frac{111111+11111+1+1}{1+1} - \frac{11-1}{1} = \frac{222222+22222+2+2}{2+2} - \frac{22-2}{2} = \frac{333333+33333+3+3}{3+3} - \frac{33-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+44444+4+4}{4+4} - \frac{44-4}{4} = \frac{555555+55555+5+5}{5+5} - \frac{55-5}{5} = \frac{666666+66666+6+6}{6+6} - \frac{66-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+77777+7+7}{7+7} - \frac{77-7}{7} = \frac{888888+88888+8+8}{8+8} - \frac{88-8}{8} = \frac{999999+99999+9+9}{9+9} - \frac{99-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{611102} &:= \frac{1111111+111111+1+1}{1+1} - \frac{11-1}{1} = \frac{2222222+222222+2+2}{2+2} - \frac{22-2}{2} = \frac{3333333+333333+3+3}{3+3} - \frac{33-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444+444444+4+4}{4+4} - \frac{44-4}{4} = \frac{5555555+555555+5+5}{5+5} - \frac{55-5}{5} = \frac{6666666+666666+6+6}{6+6} - \frac{66-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777+777777+7+7}{7+7} - \frac{77-7}{7} = \frac{8888888+888888+8+8}{8+8} - \frac{88-8}{8} = \frac{9999999+999999+9+9}{9+9} - \frac{99-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{603} &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11 - (1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22 - (2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33 - (3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44 - (4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55 - (5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66 - (6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77 - (7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88 - (8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99 - (9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6103} := \frac{(1111-1) \times 11 - (1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222-2) \times 22 - (2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333-3) \times 33 - (3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 - 4) \times 44 - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5) \times 55 - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6) \times 66 - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7) \times 77 - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8) \times 88 - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9) \times 99 - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{61103} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1) \times 11 - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2) \times 22 - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3) \times 33 - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4) \times 44 - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5) \times 55 - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6) \times 66 - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7) \times 77 - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8) \times 88 - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9) \times 99 - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{611103} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1) \times 11 - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2) \times 22 - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3) \times 33 - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 4) \times 44 - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5) \times 55 - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6) \times 66 - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7) \times 77 - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8) \times 88 - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9) \times 99 - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{604} &:= \frac{(111 - 1) \times 11 - (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times 22 - (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times 33 - (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4) \times 44 - (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5) \times 55 - (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6) \times 66 - (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7) \times 77 - (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8) \times 88 - (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9) \times 99 - (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6104} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1) \times 11 - (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2) \times 22 - (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3) \times 33 - (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 4) \times 44 - (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5) \times 55 - (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6) \times 66 - (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7) \times 77 - (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8) \times 88 - (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9) \times 99 - (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{61104} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1) \times 11 - (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2) \times 22 - (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3) \times 33 - (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4) \times 44 - (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5) \times 55 - (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6) \times 66 - (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7) \times 77 - (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8) \times 88 - (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9) \times 99 - (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{611104} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1) \times 11 - (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2) \times 22 - (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3) \times 33 - (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 4) \times 44 - (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5) \times 55 - (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6) \times 66 - (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7) \times 77 - (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8) \times 88 - (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9) \times 99 - (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 605 &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6105 &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 111}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 222}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 333}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 444}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 555}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 666}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 777}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 888}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 999}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 61105 &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 1111}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 2222}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 3333}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 4444}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 5555}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 6666}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 7777}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 8888}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 9999}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 611105 &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11111}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22222}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33333}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44444}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55555}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66666}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77777}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88888}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99999}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 606 &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11 + (1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22 + (2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33 + (3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44 + (4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55 + (5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66 + (6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77 + (7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88 + (8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99 + (9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6106 &:= \frac{(1111-1) \times 11 + (1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222-2) \times 22 + (2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333-3) \times 33 + (3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-4) \times 44 + (4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555-5) \times 55 + (5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666-6) \times 66 + (6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-7) \times 77 + (7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888-8) \times 88 + (8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999-9) \times 99 + (9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$61106 := \frac{(11111-1) \times 11 + (1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222-2) \times 22 + (2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333-3) \times 33 + (3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44444 - 4) \times 44 + (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5) \times 55 + (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6) \times 66 + (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7) \times 77 + (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8) \times 88 + (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9) \times 99 + (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{611106} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1) \times 11 + (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2) \times 22 + (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3) \times 33 + (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 4) \times 44 + (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5) \times 55 + (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6) \times 66 + (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7) \times 77 + (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8) \times 88 + (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9) \times 99 + (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{607} &:= \frac{(111 - 1) \times 11 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times 22 + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times 33 + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4) \times 44 + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5) \times 55 + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6) \times 66 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7) \times 77 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8) \times 88 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9) \times 99 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6107} &:= \frac{(111 - 1) \times 111 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times 222 + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times 333 + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4) \times 444 + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5) \times 555 + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6) \times 666 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7) \times 777 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8) \times 888 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9) \times 999 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{61107} &:= \frac{(111 - 1) \times 1111 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times 2222 + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times 3333 + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4) \times 4444 + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5) \times 5555 + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6) \times 6666 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7) \times 7777 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8) \times 8888 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9) \times 9999 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{611107} &:= \frac{(111 - 1) \times 11111 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times 22222 + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times 33333 + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4) \times 44444 + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5) \times 55555 + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6) \times 66666 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7) \times 77777 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8) \times 88888 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9) \times 99999 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{608} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777+777-7-7-7-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+888-8-8-8-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+999-9-9-9-9-9-9-9}{9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6108} &:= \frac{11111+1111-1-1-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+2222-2-2-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+3333-3-3-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4444-4-4-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+5555-5-5-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{66666+6666-6-6-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7777-7-7-7-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{88888+8888-8-8-8-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{99999+9999-9-9-9-9-9-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{61108} &:= \frac{111111+11111-1-1-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{222222+22222-2-2-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{333333+33333-3-3-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44444-4-4-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{555555+55555-5-5-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{666666+66666-6-6-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77777-7-7-7-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{888888+88888-8-8-8-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{999999+99999-9-9-9-9-9-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{611108} &:= \frac{1111111+111111-1-1-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222+222222-2-2-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333+333333-3-3-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+444444-4-4-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555+555555-5-5-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666+666666-6-6-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+777777-7-7-7-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888+888888-8-8-8-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999+999999-9-9-9-9-9-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{609} &:= \frac{1111+111-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+222-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+333-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+444-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+555-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666+666-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+777-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+888-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+999-9-9-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6109} &:= \frac{11111+1111-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+2222-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+3333-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4444-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+5555-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{66666+6666-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7777-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{88888+8888-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{99999+9999-9-9-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{61109} &:= \frac{111111+11111-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{222222+22222-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{333333+33333-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44444-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{555555+55555-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{666666+66666-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77777-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{888888+88888-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{999999+99999-9-9-9-9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{611109} := \frac{1111111+111111-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222+222222-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333+333333-3-3-3-3}{3+3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444444 + 444444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 555555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 666666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 777777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 888888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 999999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

► **610** := $\frac{1111 + 111 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3}$
 $\frac{4444 + 444 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6}$
 $\frac{7777 + 777 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}$

6110 := $\frac{11111 + 1111 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 2222 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 3333 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3}$
 $\frac{44444 + 4444 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 5555 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 6666 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6}$
 $\frac{77777 + 7777 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 8888 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 9999 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}$

61110 := $\frac{111111 + 11111 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22222 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33333 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3}$
 $\frac{444444 + 44444 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55555 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66666 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6}$
 $\frac{777777 + 77777 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88888 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99999 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}$

611110 := $\frac{1111111 + 111111 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 222222 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 333333 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3}$
 $\frac{4444444 + 444444 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 555555 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 666666 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6}$
 $\frac{7777777 + 777777 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 888888 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 999999 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}$

► **611** := $\frac{1111 + 111}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 222}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 333}{3 + 3}$
 $\frac{4444 + 444}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 555}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 666}{6 + 6}$
 $\frac{7777 + 777}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 888}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 999}{9 + 9}$

6111 := $\frac{11111 + 1111}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 2222}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 3333}{3 + 3}$
 $\frac{44444 + 4444}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 5555}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 6666}{6 + 6}$
 $\frac{77777 + 7777}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 8888}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 9999}{9 + 9}$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{61111} &:= \frac{111111 + 11111}{1+1} = \frac{222222 + 22222}{2+2} = \frac{333333 + 33333}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44444}{4+4} = \frac{555555 + 55555}{5+5} = \frac{666666 + 66666}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77777}{7+7} = \frac{888888 + 88888}{8+8} = \frac{999999 + 99999}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{611111} &:= \frac{1111111 + 111111}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 + 222222}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 + 333333}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 444444}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 + 555555}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 + 666666}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 777777}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 + 888888}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 + 999999}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{612} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 9 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6112} &:= \frac{11111 + 1111 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{22222 + 2222 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{33333 + 3333 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 4444 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{55555 + 5555 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{66666 + 6666 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 7777 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 + 8888 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 + 9999 + 9 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{61112} &:= \frac{111111 + 11111 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{222222 + 22222 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{333333 + 33333 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44444 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{555555 + 55555 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{666666 + 66666 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77777 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{888888 + 88888 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{999999 + 99999 + 9 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{611112} &:= \frac{1111111 + 111111 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 + 222222 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 + 333333 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 444444 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 + 555555 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 + 666666 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 777777 + 7 + 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 + 888888 + 8 + 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 + 999999 + 9 + 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{613} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6+6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6113} &:= \frac{11111 + 1111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 2222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 3333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 4444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 5555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 6666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 7777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 8888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 9999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{61113} &:= \frac{111111 + 11111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{611113} &:= \frac{1111111 + 111111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 222222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 333333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 444444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 555555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 666666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 777777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 888888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 999999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{614} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 11 - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 22 - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 33 - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 44 - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 55 - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 66 - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 77 - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 88 - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 99 - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6114} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1) \times 11 - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2) \times 22 - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3) \times 33 - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4) \times 44 - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5) \times 55 - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6) \times 66 - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7) \times 77 - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8) \times 88 - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9) \times 99 - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{61114} &:= \frac{(11111 + 1) \times 11 - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 2) \times 22 - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 3) \times 33 - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 4) \times 44 - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 5) \times 55 - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 6) \times 66 - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 7) \times 77 - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 8) \times 88 - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 9) \times 99 - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{611114} := \frac{(111111 + 1) \times 11 - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 2) \times 22 - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 3) \times 33 - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444444 + 4) \times 44 - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 5) \times 55 - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 6) \times 66 - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 7) \times 77 - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 8) \times 88 - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 9) \times 99 - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

► **615** := $\frac{1111 + 11 + 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 22 + 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 33 + 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3}$
 $:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6}$
 $:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}$

5615 := $\frac{11111 + 11 + 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3}$
 $:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6}$
 $:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}$

55615 := $\frac{111111 + 11 + 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3}$
 $:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6}$
 $:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}$

555615 := $\frac{1111111 + 11 + 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22 + 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33 + 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3}$
 $:= \frac{4444444 + 44 + 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55 + 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66 + 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6}$
 $:= \frac{7777777 + 77 + 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 + 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 + 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9}$

► **616** := $\frac{111 + 1) \times 11}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{222 + 2) \times 22}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{333 + 3) \times 33}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{444 + 4) \times 44}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{555 + 5) \times 55}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{666 + 6) \times 66}{(6 + 6) \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{777 + 7) \times 77}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{888 + 8) \times 88}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{999 + 9) \times 99}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$

6216 := $\frac{111 + 1) \times 111}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{222 + 2) \times 222}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{333 + 3) \times 333}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{444 + 4) \times 444}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{555 + 5) \times 555}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{666 + 6) \times 666}{(6 + 6) \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{777 + 7) \times 777}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{888 + 8) \times 888}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{999 + 9) \times 999}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{62216} &:= \frac{111+1 \times 1111}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222+2 \times 2222}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333+3 \times 3333}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444+4 \times 4444}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555+5 \times 5555}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666+6 \times 6666}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777+7 \times 7777}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888+8 \times 8888}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999+9 \times 9999}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{622216} &:= \frac{111+1 \times 11111}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222+2 \times 22222}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333+3 \times 33333}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444+4 \times 44444}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555+5 \times 55555}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666+6 \times 66666}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777+7 \times 77777}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888+8 \times 88888}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999+9 \times 99999}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{617} &:= \frac{1111+11+111+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+22+222+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+33+333+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+44+444+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+55+555+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666+66+666+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+77+777+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+88+888+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+99+999+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5617} &:= \frac{11111+11+111+1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+22+222+2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+33+333+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+44+444+4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+55+555+5}{5+5} = \frac{66666+66+666+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+77+777+7}{7+7} = \frac{88888+88+888+8}{8+8} = \frac{99999+99+999+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55617} &:= \frac{111111+11+111+1}{1+1} = \frac{222222+22+222+2}{2+2} = \frac{333333+33+333+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44+444+4}{4+4} = \frac{555555+55+555+5}{5+5} = \frac{666666+66+666+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77+777+7}{7+7} = \frac{888888+88+888+8}{8+8} = \frac{999999+99+999+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555617} &:= \frac{1111111+11+111+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222+22+222+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333+33+333+3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+44+444+4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555+55+555+5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666+66+666+6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+77+777+7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888+88+888+8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999+99+999+9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{618} := \frac{1111+11+111+1+1+1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+22+222+2+2+2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+33+333+3+3+3}{3+3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 + 44 + 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 55 + 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 66 + 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77 + 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 88 + 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 99 + 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5618} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55618} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555618} &:= \frac{1111111 + 11 + 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22 + 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33 + 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 44 + 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55 + 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66 + 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 77 + 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 + 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 + 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{619} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 11 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 22 + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 33 + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 44 + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 55 + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 66 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 77 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 88 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 99 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6219} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 111 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 222 + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 333 + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 444 + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 555 + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 666 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 777 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 888 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 999 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{62219} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 1111 + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 2222 + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 3333 + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 4444 + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 5555 + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 6666 + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 7777 + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 8888 + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 9999 + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{622219} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times 11111 + (1+1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times 22222 + (2+2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times 33333 + (3+3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 44444 + (4+4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times 55555 + (5+5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times 66666 + (6+6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 77777 + (7+7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times 88888 + (8+8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times 99999 + (9+9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{620} &:= \frac{1111+11+111+11-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+22+222+22-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+33+333+33-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+44+444+44-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+55+555+55-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666+66+666+66-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777+77+777+77-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+88+888+88-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+99+999+99-9-9-9-9}{9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{5620} &:= \frac{11111+11+111+11-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+22+222+22-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+33+333+33-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444+44+444+44-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+55+555+55-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{66666+66+666+66-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777+77+777+77-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{88888+88+888+88-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{99999+99+999+99-9-9-9-9}{9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{55620} &:= \frac{111111+11+111+11-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{222222+22+222+22-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{333333+33+333+33-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+44+444+44-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{555555+55+555+55-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{666666+66+666+66-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+77+777+77-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{888888+88+888+88-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{999999+99+999+99-9-9-9-9}{9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{555620} &:= \frac{1111111+11+111+11-1-1-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222+22+222+22-2-2-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333+33+333+33-3-3-3-3}{3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444+44+444+44-4-4-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555+55+555+55-5-5-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666+66+666+66-6-6-6-6}{6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777+77+777+77-7-7-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888+88+888+88-8-8-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999+99+999+99-9-9-9-9}{9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{621} &:= \frac{1111+11+111+11-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{2222+22+222+22-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{3333+33+333+33-3-3}{3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+44+444+44-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{5555+55+555+55-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{6666+66+666+66-6-6}{6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777+77+777+77-7-7}{7+7} = \frac{8888+88+888+88-8-8}{8+8} = \frac{9999+99+999+99-9-9}{9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{5621} &:= \frac{11111+11+111+11-1-1}{1+1} = \frac{22222+22+222+22-2-2}{2+2} = \frac{33333+33+333+33-3-3}{3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444+44+444+44-4-4}{4+4} = \frac{55555+55+555+55-5-5}{5+5} = \frac{66666+66+666+66-6-6}{6+6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9+9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55621} &:= \frac{111111 + 11 + 111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{222222 + 22 + 222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{333333 + 33 + 333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44 + 444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{555555 + 55 + 555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{666666 + 66 + 666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77 + 777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{888888 + 88 + 888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{999999 + 99 + 999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555621} &:= \frac{1111111 + 11 + 111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1+1} = \frac{2222222 + 22 + 222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2+2} = \frac{3333333 + 33 + 333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3+3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 44 + 444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4+4} = \frac{5555555 + 55 + 555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5+5} = \frac{6666666 + 66 + 666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6+6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 77 + 777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7+7} = \frac{8888888 + 88 + 888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8+8} = \frac{9999999 + 99 + 999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9+9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{622} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 1 + 1}{1+1} + \frac{11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 2 + 2}{2+2} + \frac{22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 3 + 3}{3+3} + \frac{33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 4 + 4}{4+4} + \frac{44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 5 + 5}{5+5} + \frac{55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 6 + 6}{6+6} + \frac{66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 7 + 7}{7+7} + \frac{77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 8 + 8}{8+8} + \frac{88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 9 + 9}{9+9} + \frac{99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6122} &:= \frac{11111 + 1111 + 1 + 1}{1+1} + \frac{11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 2222 + 2 + 2}{2+2} + \frac{22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 3333 + 3 + 3}{3+3} + \frac{33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 4444 + 4 + 4}{4+4} + \frac{44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 5555 + 5 + 5}{5+5} + \frac{55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 6666 + 6 + 6}{6+6} + \frac{66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 7777 + 7 + 7}{7+7} + \frac{77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 8888 + 8 + 8}{8+8} + \frac{88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 9999 + 9 + 9}{9+9} + \frac{99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{61122} &:= \frac{111111 + 11111 + 1 + 1}{1+1} + \frac{11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22222 + 2 + 2}{2+2} + \frac{22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33333 + 3 + 3}{3+3} + \frac{33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44444 + 4 + 4}{4+4} + \frac{44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55555 + 5 + 5}{5+5} + \frac{55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66666 + 6 + 6}{6+6} + \frac{66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77777 + 7 + 7}{7+7} + \frac{77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88888 + 8 + 8}{8+8} + \frac{88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99999 + 9 + 9}{9+9} + \frac{99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{611122} &:= \frac{1111111 + 111111 + 1 + 1}{1+1} + \frac{11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 + 222222 + 2 + 2}{2+2} + \frac{22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 + 333333 + 3 + 3}{3+3} + \frac{33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 444444 + 4 + 4}{4+4} + \frac{44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 + 555555 + 5 + 5}{5+5} + \frac{55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 + 666666 + 6 + 6}{6+6} + \frac{66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 777777 + 7 + 7}{7+7} + \frac{77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 + 888888 + 8 + 8}{8+8} + \frac{88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 + 999999 + 9 + 9}{9+9} + \frac{99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{623} := \frac{1111 + 111 + 1 + 1}{1+1} + \frac{11}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 2 + 2}{2+2} + \frac{22}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 3 + 3}{3+3} + \frac{33}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{77}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{88}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6123} &:= \frac{11111 + 1111 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11}{1} = \frac{22222 + 2222 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22}{2} = \frac{33333 + 3333 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 4444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44}{4} = \frac{55555 + 5555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55}{5} = \frac{66666 + 6666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 7777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{77}{7} = \frac{88888 + 8888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{88}{8} = \frac{99999 + 9999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{61123} &:= \frac{111111 + 11111 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22222 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33333 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{77}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{88}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6111223} &:= \frac{1111111 + 111111 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11}{1} = \frac{2222222 + 222222 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22}{2} = \frac{3333333 + 333333 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 444444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44}{4} = \frac{5555555 + 555555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55}{5} = \frac{6666666 + 666666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 777777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{77}{7} = \frac{8888888 + 888888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{88}{8} = \frac{9999999 + 999999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{624} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 222 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 333 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6124} &:= \frac{11111 + 1111 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 2222 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 3333 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 4444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 5555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 6666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 7777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 8888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 9999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{61124} &:= \frac{111111 + 11111 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22222 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33333 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{611124} &:= \frac{1111111 + 111111 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 + 222222 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 + 333333 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{33 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 + 444444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 + 555555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 + 666666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{66 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 + 777777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 + 888888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 + 999999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{99 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{625} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 11 + (11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 22 + (22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 33 + (33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 44 + (44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 55 + (55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 66 + (66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 77 + (77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 88 + (88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 99 + (99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{6225} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 111 + (11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 222 + (22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 333 + (33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 444 + (44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 555 + (55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 666 + (66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 777 + (77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 888 + (88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 999 + (99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{62225} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 1111 + (11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 2222 + (22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 3333 + (33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 4444 + (44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 5555 + (55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 6666 + (66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 7777 + (77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 8888 + (88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 9999 + (99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{622225} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 11111 + (11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 22222 + (22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 33333 + (33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 44444 + (44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 55555 + (55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 66666 + (66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 77777 + (77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 88888 + (88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 99999 + (99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{626} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 11 + (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 22 + (22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 33 + (33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 44 + (44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 55 + (55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 66 + (66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 77 + (77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 88 + (88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 99 + (99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6226} := \frac{(111 + 1) \times 111 + (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 222 + (22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 333 + (33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 444 + (44-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times 555 + (55-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times 666 + (66-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 777 + (77-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times 888 + (88-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times 999 + (99-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{62226} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times 1111 + (11-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times 2222 + (22-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times 3333 + (33-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 4444 + (44-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times 5555 + (55-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times 6666 + (66-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 7777 + (77-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times 8888 + (88-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times 9999 + (99-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{622226} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times 11111 + (11-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times 22222 + (22-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times 33333 + (33-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 44444 + (44-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times 55555 + (55-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times 66666 + (66-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 77777 + (77-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times 88888 + (88-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times 99999 + (99-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{627} &:= \frac{(111+1+1+1) \times 11}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2+2) \times 22}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3+3) \times 33}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4+4+4) \times 44}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5+5) \times 55}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6+6) \times 66}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7+7+7) \times 77}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8+8) \times 88}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9+9) \times 99}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6127} &:= \frac{(1111+1+1+1) \times 11}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2+2) \times 22}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3+3) \times 33}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4+4+4) \times 44}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5+5+5) \times 55}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6+6+6) \times 66}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7+7+7) \times 77}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8+8) \times 88}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9+9) \times 99}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{61127} &:= \frac{(11111+1+1+1) \times 11}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2+2) \times 22}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3+3) \times 33}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4+4+4) \times 44}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5+5) \times 55}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6+6+6) \times 66}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7+7+7) \times 77}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8+8) \times 88}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9+9) \times 99}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{611127} &:= \frac{(111111+1+1+1) \times 11}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2+2+2) \times 22}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3+3+3) \times 33}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4+4+4) \times 44}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5+5+5) \times 55}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6+6+6) \times 66}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7+7+7) \times 77}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8+8+8) \times 88}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9+9+9) \times 99}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 628 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times 11 + (1+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times 22 + (2+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times 33 + (3+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 44 + (4+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times 55 + (5+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times 66 + (6+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 77 + (7+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times 88 + (8+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times 99 + (9+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6228 &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times 11 + (1+1) \times (111+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times 22 + (2+2) \times (222+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times 33 + (3+3) \times (333+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times 44 + (4+4) \times (444+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times 55 + (5+5) \times (555+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times 66 + (6+6) \times (666+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times 77 + (7+7) \times (777+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times 88 + (8+8) \times (888+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times 99 + (9+9) \times (999+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 62228 &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times 11 + (1+1) \times (1111+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times 22 + (2+2) \times (2222+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times 33 + (3+3) \times (3333+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times 44 + (4+4) \times (4444+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times 55 + (5+5) \times (5555+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times 66 + (6+6) \times (6666+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times 77 + (7+7) \times (7777+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times 88 + (8+8) \times (8888+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times 99 + (9+9) \times (9999+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 622228 &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times 11 + (1+1) \times (11111+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2) \times 22 + (2+2) \times (22222+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3) \times 33 + (3+3) \times (33333+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times 44 + (4+4) \times (44444+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5) \times 55 + (5+5) \times (55555+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6) \times 66 + (6+6) \times (66666+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times 77 + (7+7) \times (77777+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8) \times 88 + (8+8) \times (88888+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9) \times 99 + (9+9) \times (99999+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 629 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times 11 + (1+1) \times (11+1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times 22 + (2+2) \times (22+2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times 33 + (3+3) \times (33+3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 44 + (4+4) \times (44+4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times 55 + (5+5) \times (55+5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times 66 + (6+6) \times (66+6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 77 + (7+7) \times (77+7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times 88 + (8+8) \times (88+8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times 99 + (9+9) \times (99+9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6329 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times 111 + (1+1) \times (111+1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times 222 + (2+2) \times (222+2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times 333 + (3+3) \times (333+3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 444 + (4+4) \times (444+4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times 555 + (5+5) \times (555+5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times 666 + (6+6) \times (666+6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 777 + (7+7) \times (777+7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times 888 + (8+8) \times (888+8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times 999 + (9+9) \times (999+9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$63329 := \frac{(111+1) \times 1111 + (1+1) \times (1111+1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times 2222 + (2+2) \times (2222+2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times 3333 + (3+3) \times (3333+3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 4444 + (4+4) \times (4444+4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times 5555 + (5+5) \times (5555+5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times 6666 + (6+6) \times (6666+6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 7777 + (7+7) \times (7777+7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times 8888 + (8+8) \times (8888+8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times 9999 + (9+9) \times (9999+9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{633329} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times 11111 + (1+1) \times (11111+1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times 22222 + (2+2) \times (22222+2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times 33333 + (3+3) \times (33333+3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times 44444 + (4+4) \times (44444+4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times 55555 + (5+5) \times (55555+5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times 66666 + (6+6) \times (66666+6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times 77777 + (7+7) \times (77777+7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times 88888 + (8+8) \times (88888+8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times 99999 + (9+9) \times (99999+9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{630} &:= \frac{(111+111-11-1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222-22-2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333-33-3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444-44-4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555-55-5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666-66-6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777-77-7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888-88-8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999-99-9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3630} &:= \frac{(1111+111-11-1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+222-22-2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+333-33-3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+444-44-4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+555-55-5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+666-66-6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+777-77-7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+888-88-8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+999-99-9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33630} &:= \frac{(11111+111-11-1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+222-22-2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+333-33-3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+444-44-4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+555-55-5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+666-66-6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+777-77-7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+888-88-8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+999-99-9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333630} &:= \frac{(111111+111-11-1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222+222-22-2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333+333-33-3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+444-44-4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555+555-55-5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666+666-66-6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+777-77-7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888+888-88-8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999+999-99-9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{631} &:= \frac{(111+111-11-1) \times (1+1+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222-22-2) \times (2+2+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333-33-3) \times (3+3+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444-44-4) \times (4+4+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555-55-5) \times (5+5+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666-66-6) \times (6+6+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777-77-7) \times (7+7+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888-88-8) \times (8+8+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999-99-9) \times (9+9+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3631} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33631} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333631} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{632} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3632} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33632} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333632} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

► **633** := $\frac{(111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$

3633 := $\frac{(1111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$

33633 := $\frac{(11111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$

333633 := $\frac{(111111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$

► **634** := $\frac{(111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$

3634 := $\frac{(1111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \color{red}{33634} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \color{red}{333634} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \color{red}{635} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \color{red}{3635} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \color{red}{33635} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \color{red}{333635} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \color{red}{636} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3636} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33636} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333636} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{637} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3637} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33637} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{333637} := \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \text{638} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 11 + (11 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 22 + (22 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 33 + (33 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 44 + (44 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 55 + (55 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 66 + (66 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 77 + (77 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 88 + (88 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 99 + (99 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{6238} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 111 + (11 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 222 + (22 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 333 + (33 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 444 + (44 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 555 + (55 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 666 + (66 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 777 + (77 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 888 + (88 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 999 + (99 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{62238} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 1111 + (11 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 2222 + (22 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 3333 + (33 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 4444 + (44 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 5555 + (55 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 6666 + (66 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 7777 + (77 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 8888 + (88 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 9999 + (99 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{622238} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times 11111 + (11 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times 22222 + (22 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times 33333 + (33 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times 44444 + (44 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times 55555 + (55 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times 66666 + (66 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times 77777 + (77 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times 88888 + (88 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times 99999 + (99 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \text{639} &:= \frac{1111 + 111}{1 + 1} + \frac{111 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 222}{2 + 2} + \frac{222 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 333}{3 + 3} + \frac{333 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444}{4 + 4} + \frac{444 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 555}{5 + 5} + \frac{555 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 666}{6 + 6} + \frac{666 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777}{7 + 7} + \frac{777 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 888}{8 + 8} + \frac{888 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 999}{9 + 9} + \frac{999 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{5639} &:= \frac{11111 + 111}{1 + 1} + \frac{111 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 222}{2 + 2} + \frac{222 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 333}{3 + 3} + \frac{333 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444}{4 + 4} + \frac{444 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 555}{5 + 5} + \frac{555 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 666}{6 + 6} + \frac{666 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777}{7 + 7} + \frac{777 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 888}{8 + 8} + \frac{888 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 999}{9 + 9} + \frac{999 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{55639} &:= \frac{111111+111}{1+1} + \frac{111+1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{222222+222}{2+2} + \frac{222+2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{333333+333}{3+3} + \frac{333+3}{3+3+3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+444}{4+4} + \frac{444+4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{555555+555}{5+5} + \frac{555+5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{666666+666}{6+6} + \frac{666+6}{6+6+6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+777}{7+7} + \frac{777+7}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{888888+888}{8+8} + \frac{888+8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{999999+999}{9+9} + \frac{999+9}{9+9+9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{555639} &:= \frac{1111111+111}{1+1} + \frac{111+1}{1+1+1+1} = \frac{2222222+222}{2+2} + \frac{222+2}{2+2+2+2} = \frac{3333333+333}{3+3} + \frac{333+3}{3+3+3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444+444}{4+4} + \frac{444+4}{4+4+4+4} = \frac{5555555+555}{5+5} + \frac{555+5}{5+5+5+5} = \frac{6666666+666}{6+6} + \frac{666+6}{6+6+6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777+777}{7+7} + \frac{777+7}{7+7+7+7} = \frac{8888888+888}{8+8} + \frac{888+8}{8+8+8+8} = \frac{9999999+999}{9+9} + \frac{999+9}{9+9+9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{640} &:= \frac{1111-11-11-11}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{2222-22-22-22}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{3333-33-33-33}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\
 &:= \frac{4444-44-44-44}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{5555-55-55-55}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{6666-66-66-66}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\
 &:= \frac{7777-77-77-77}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{8888-88-88-88}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999-99-99-99}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{5640} &:= \frac{11111-11-11-11}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{22222-22-22-22}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{33333-33-33-33}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\
 &:= \frac{44444-44-44-44}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{55555-55-55-55}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{66666-66-66-66}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\
 &:= \frac{77777-77-77-77}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{88888-88-88-88}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{99999-99-99-99}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{55640} &:= \frac{111111-11-11-11}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{222222-22-22-22}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{333333-33-33-33}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\
 &:= \frac{444444-44-44-44}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{555555-55-55-55}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{666666-66-66-66}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\
 &:= \frac{777777-77-77-77}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{888888-88-88-88}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{999999-99-99-99}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{555640} &:= \frac{1111111-11-11-11}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{2222222-22-22-22}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{3333333-33-33-33}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444-44-44-44}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{5555555-55-55-55}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{6666666-66-66-66}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777-77-77-77}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{8888888-88-88-88}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999999-99-99-99}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{641} &:= \frac{(111+111+111-11-1) \times (1+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222+222-22-2) \times (2+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333+333-33-3) \times (3+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444+444+444-44-4) \times (4+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555+555-55-5) \times (5+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666+666-66-6) \times (6+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2641} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22641} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222641} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{642} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2642} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22642} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{222642} := \frac{(111111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

► **643** := $\frac{(111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

2643 := $\frac{(1111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

22643 := $\frac{(11111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

222643 := $\frac{(111111 + 111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

► **644** := $\frac{111 \times (11 + 1) - (11 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times (22 + 2) - (22 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times (33 + 3) - (33 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444 \times (44 + 4) - (44 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times (55 + 5) - (55 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times (66 + 6) - (66 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times (77 + 7) - (77 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times (88 + 8) - (88 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times (99 + 9) - (99 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

6644 := $\frac{1111 \times (11 + 1) - (11 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (22 + 2) - (22 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (33 + 3) - (33 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 \times (44 + 4) - (44 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (55 + 5) - (55 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (66 + 6) - (66 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (77 + 7) - (77 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (88 + 8) - (88 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (99 + 9) - (99 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{66644} &:= \frac{11111 \times (11+1) - (11+11) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{22222 \times (22+2) - (22+22) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{33333 \times (33+3) - (33+33) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 \times (44+4) - (44+44) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{55555 \times (55+5) - (55+55) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{66666 \times (66+6) - (66+66) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 \times (77+7) - (77+77) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{88888 \times (88+8) - (88+88) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{99999 \times (99+9) - (99+99) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{666644} &:= \frac{111111 \times (11+1) - (11+11) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222222 \times (22+2) - (22+22) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333333 \times (33+3) - (33+33) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 \times (44+4) - (44+44) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555555 \times (55+5) - (55+55) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666666 \times (66+6) - (66+66) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 \times (77+7) - (77+77) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888888 \times (88+8) - (88+88) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999999 \times (99+9) - (99+99) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{645} &:= \frac{1111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{2222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{3333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{6666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{5645} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{55645} &:= \frac{111111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{555645} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{646} := \frac{1111 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{2222 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{3333 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{6666 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5646} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55646} &:= \frac{111111 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555646} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{647} &:= \frac{1111 + 111 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{111}{(1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{2222 + 222 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{222}{(2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{3333 + 333 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{333}{(3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 444 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{444}{(4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{5555 + 555 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{555}{(5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{6666 + 666 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{666}{(6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 777 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{777}{(7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{8888 + 888 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{888}{(8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{9999 + 999 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{999}{(9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5647} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{111}{(1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{222}{(2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{333}{(3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{444}{(4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{555}{(5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{666}{(6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{777}{(7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{888}{(8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{999}{(9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55647} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{111}{(1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{222222 + 222 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{222}{(2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{333333 + 333 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{333}{(3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{444}{(4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{555555 + 555 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{555}{(5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{666666 + 666 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{666}{(6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{777}{(7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{888888 + 888 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{888}{(8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{999999 + 999 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{999}{(9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 555647 &:= \frac{1111111+111-1-1}{1+1} + \frac{111}{(1+1+1)} = \frac{2222222+222-2-2}{2+2} + \frac{222}{(2+2+2)} = \frac{3333333+333-3-3}{3+3} + \frac{333}{(3+3+3)} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444+444-4-4}{4+4} + \frac{444}{(4+4+4)} = \frac{5555555+555-5-5}{5+5} + \frac{555}{(5+5+5)} = \frac{6666666+666-6-6}{6+6} + \frac{666}{(6+6+6)} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777+777-7-7}{7+7} + \frac{777}{(7+7+7)} = \frac{8888888+888-8-8}{8+8} + \frac{888}{(8+8+8)} = \frac{9999999+999-9-9}{9+9} + \frac{999}{(9+9+9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 648 &:= \frac{1111+111}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1+1+1} = \frac{2222+222}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2+2+2} = \frac{3333+333}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3+3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+444}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4+4+4} = \frac{5555+555}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5+5+5} = \frac{6666+666}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6+6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777+777}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7+7+7} = \frac{8888+888}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8+8+8} = \frac{9999+999}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9+9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5648 &:= \frac{11111+111}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1+1+1} = \frac{22222+222}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2+2+2} = \frac{33333+333}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3+3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444+444}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4+4+4} = \frac{55555+555}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5+5+5} = \frac{66666+666}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6+6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777+777}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7+7+7} = \frac{88888+888}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8+8+8} = \frac{99999+999}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9+9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 55648 &:= \frac{111111+111}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1+1+1} = \frac{222222+222}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2+2+2} = \frac{333333+333}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3+3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+444}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4+4+4} = \frac{555555+555}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5+5+5} = \frac{666666+666}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6+6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+777}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7+7+7} = \frac{888888+888}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8+8+8} = \frac{999999+999}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9+9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 555648 &:= \frac{1111111+111}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1+1+1} = \frac{2222222+222}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2+2+2} = \frac{3333333+333}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3+3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444+444}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4+4+4} = \frac{5555555+555}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5+5+5} = \frac{6666666+666}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6+6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777+777}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7+7+7} = \frac{8888888+888}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8+8+8} = \frac{9999999+999}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9+9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 649 &:= \frac{1111+111+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1+1+1} = \frac{2222+222+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2+2+2} = \frac{3333+333+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3+3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+444+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4+4+4} = \frac{5555+555+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5+5+5} = \frac{6666+666+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6+6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777+777+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7+7+7} = \frac{8888+888+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8+8+8} = \frac{9999+999+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9+9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5649 &:= \frac{11111+111+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1+1+1} = \frac{22222+222+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2+2+2} = \frac{33333+333+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3+3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444+444+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4+4+4} = \frac{55555+555+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5+5+5} = \frac{66666+666+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6+6+6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{777}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{888}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{999}{9 + 9 + 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55649} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{111}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{222}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{333}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{444}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{555}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{666}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{777}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{888}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{999}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555649} &:= \frac{1111111 + 111 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{111}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 222 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{222}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 333 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{333}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{444}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{555}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{666}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{777}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{888}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{999}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{650} &:= \frac{1111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{2222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{3333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{5555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{6666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{8888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5650} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55650} &:= \frac{111111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{222222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{333333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{555555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{666666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{888888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{999999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555650} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{2222222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{3333333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{5555555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{6666666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{8888888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{651} := \frac{1111 - 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{2222 - 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{3333 - 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{3333}{33}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444-44}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{5555-55}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{6666-66}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{7777-77}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{8888-88}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999-99}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5651} &:= \frac{11111-11}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{22222-22}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{33333-33}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{44444-44}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{55555-55}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{66666-66}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{77777-77}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{88888-88}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{99999-99}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55651} &:= \frac{111111-11}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{222222-22}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{333333-33}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{444444-44}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{555555-55}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{666666-66}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{777777-77}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{888888-88}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{999999-99}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555651} &:= \frac{1111111-11}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{2222222-22}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{3333333-33}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{4444444-44}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{5555555-55}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{6666666-66}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777-77}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{8888888-88}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999999-99}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{652} &:= \frac{1111-11+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{2222-22+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{3333-33+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{4444-44+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{5555-55+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{6666-66+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{7777-77+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{8888-88+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999-99+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5652} &:= \frac{11111-11+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{22222-22+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{33333-33+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{44444-44+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{55555-55+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{66666-66+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{77777-77+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{88888-88+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{99999-99+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55652} &:= \frac{111111-11+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{222222-22+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{333333-33+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\ &:= \frac{444444-44+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{555555-55+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{666666-66+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &:= \frac{777777-77+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{888888-88+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{999999-99+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{555652} &:= \frac{1111111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{1111}{11} = \frac{2222222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{2222}{22} = \frac{3333333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{4444}{44} = \frac{5555555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{5555}{55} = \frac{6666666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{7777}{77} = \frac{8888888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{9999}{99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{653} &:= \frac{(111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 + 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 + 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 + 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 + 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 + 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 + 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 + 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 + 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 + 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{6653} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 + 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 + 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 + 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 + 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 + 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 + 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 + 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 + 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 + 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{66653} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 + 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 + 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 + 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 + 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 + 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 + 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 + 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 + 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 + 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{666653} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 + 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 + 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 + 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 + 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 + 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 + 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 + 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 + 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 + 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{654} &:= \frac{(111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6654} := \frac{(1111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66654} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666654} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{655} &:= \frac{111 \times (11 + 1) - 11 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times (22 + 2) - 22 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times (33 + 3) - 33 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times (44 + 4) - 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times (55 + 5) - 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times (66 + 6) - 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times (77 + 7) - 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times (88 + 8) - 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times (99 + 9) - 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6655} &:= \frac{1111 \times (11 + 1) - 11 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (22 + 2) - 22 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (33 + 3) - 33 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (44 + 4) - 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (55 + 5) - 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (66 + 6) - 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (77 + 7) - 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (88 + 8) - 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (99 + 9) - 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66655} &:= \frac{11111 \times (11 + 1) - 11 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{22222 \times (22 + 2) - 22 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{33333 \times (33 + 3) - 33 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 \times (44 + 4) - 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{55555 \times (55 + 5) - 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{66666 \times (66 + 6) - 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 \times (77 + 7) - 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{88888 \times (88 + 8) - 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{99999 \times (99 + 9) - 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666655} &:= \frac{111111 \times (11 + 1) - 11 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{222222 \times (22 + 2) - 22 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{333333 \times (33 + 3) - 33 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (44 + 4) - 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{555555 \times (55 + 5) - 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{666666 \times (66 + 6) - 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (77 + 7) - 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{888888 \times (88 + 8) - 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{999999 \times (99 + 9) - 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{656} & := \frac{111 \times (11+1) - (11-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times (22+2) - (22-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times (33+3) - (33-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{444 \times (44+4) - (44-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times (55+5) - (55-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times (66+6) - (66-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{777 \times (77+7) - (77-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times (88+8) - (88-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times (99+9) - (99-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6656} & := \frac{1111 \times (11+1) - (11-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (22+2) - (22-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (33+3) - (33-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{4444 \times (44+4) - (44-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (55+5) - (55-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (66+6) - (66-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{7777 \times (77+7) - (77-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (88+8) - (88-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (99+9) - (99-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66656} & := \frac{11111 \times (11+1) - (11-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{22222 \times (22+2) - (22-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{33333 \times (33+3) - (33-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{44444 \times (44+4) - (44-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{55555 \times (55+5) - (55-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{66666 \times (66+6) - (66-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{77777 \times (77+7) - (77-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{88888 \times (88+8) - (88-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{99999 \times (99+9) - (99-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666656} & := \frac{111111 \times (11+1) - (11-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222222 \times (22+2) - (22-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333333 \times (33+3) - (33-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{444444 \times (44+4) - (44-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555555 \times (55+5) - (55-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666666 \times (66+6) - (66-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{777777 \times (77+7) - (77-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888888 \times (88+8) - (88-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999999 \times (99+9) - (99-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{657} & := \frac{111 \times (11+1) - (11-1-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times (22+2) - (22-2-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times (33+3) - (33-3-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{444 \times (44+4) - (44-4-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times (55+5) - (55-5-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times (66+6) - (66-6-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{777 \times (77+7) - (77-7-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times (88+8) - (88-8-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times (99+9) - (99-9-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6657} & := \frac{1111 \times (11+1) - (11-1-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (22+2) - (22-2-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (33+3) - (33-3-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{4444 \times (44+4) - (44-4-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (55+5) - (55-5-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (66+6) - (66-6-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{7777 \times (77+7) - (77-7-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (88+8) - (88-8-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (99+9) - (99-9-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{66657} := \frac{11111 \times (11+1) - (11-1-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{22222 \times (22+2) - (22-2-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{33333 \times (33+3) - (33-3-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{44444 \times (44+4) - (44-4-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{55555 \times (55+5) - (55-5-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{66666 \times (66+6) - (66-6-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 \times (77+7) - (77-7-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{88888 \times (88+8) - (88-8-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{99999 \times (99+9) - (99-9-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666657} &:= \frac{111111 \times (11+1) - (11-1-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222222 \times (22+2) - (22-2-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333333 \times (33+3) - (33-3-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (44+4) - (44-4-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555555 \times (55+5) - (55-5-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666666 \times (66+6) - (66-6-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (77+7) - (77-7-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888888 \times (88+8) - (88-8-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999999 \times (99+9) - (99-9-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{658} := \frac{(111+11) \times 11 - (11+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} := \frac{(222+22) \times 22 - (22+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} := \frac{(333+33) \times 33 - (33+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &::= \frac{(444+44) \times 44 - (44+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} := \frac{(555+55) \times 55 - (55+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} := \frac{(666+66) \times 66 - (66+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &::= \frac{(777+77) \times 77 - (77+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} := \frac{(888+88) \times 88 - (88+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+99) \times 99 - (99+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6758} := \frac{(111+11) \times 111 - (11+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} := \frac{(222+22) \times 222 - (22+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} := \frac{(333+33) \times 333 - (33+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &::= \frac{(444+44) \times 444 - (44+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} := \frac{(555+55) \times 555 - (55+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} := \frac{(666+66) \times 666 - (66+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &::= \frac{(777+77) \times 777 - (77+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} := \frac{(888+88) \times 888 - (88+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+99) \times 999 - (99+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{67758} := \frac{(111+11) \times 1111 - (11+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} := \frac{(222+22) \times 2222 - (22+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} := \frac{(333+33) \times 3333 - (33+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &::= \frac{(444+44) \times 4444 - (44+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} := \frac{(555+55) \times 5555 - (55+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} := \frac{(666+66) \times 6666 - (66+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &::= \frac{(777+77) \times 7777 - (77+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} := \frac{(888+88) \times 8888 - (88+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+99) \times 9999 - (99+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{677758} := \frac{(111+11) \times 11111 - (11+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} := \frac{(222+22) \times 22222 - (22+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} := \frac{(333+33) \times 33333 - (33+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &::= \frac{(444+44) \times 44444 - (44+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} := \frac{(555+55) \times 55555 - (55+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} := \frac{(666+66) \times 66666 - (66+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &::= \frac{(777+77) \times 77777 - (77+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} := \frac{(888+88) \times 88888 - (88+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+99) \times 99999 - (99+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 659 &:= \frac{1111-11-1-1}{1+1} + \frac{111-1}{1} := \frac{2222-22-2-2}{2+2} + \frac{222-2}{2} := \frac{3333-33-3-3}{3+3} + \frac{333-3}{3} \\ &::= \frac{4444-44-4-4}{4+4} + \frac{444-4}{4} := \frac{5555-55-5-5}{5+5} + \frac{555-5}{5} := \frac{6666-66-6-6}{6+6} + \frac{666-6}{6} \\ &::= \frac{7777-77-7-7}{7+7} + \frac{777-7}{7} := \frac{8888-88-8-8}{8+8} + \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{9999-99-9-9}{9+9} + \frac{999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5659 &:= \frac{11111-11-1-1}{1+1} + \frac{111-1}{1} := \frac{22222-22-2-2}{2+2} + \frac{222-2}{2} := \frac{33333-33-3-3}{3+3} + \frac{333-3}{3} \\ &::= \frac{44444-44-4-4}{4+4} + \frac{444-4}{4} := \frac{55555-55-5-5}{5+5} + \frac{555-5}{5} := \frac{66666-66-6-6}{6+6} + \frac{666-6}{6} \\ &::= \frac{77777-77-7-7}{7+7} + \frac{777-7}{7} := \frac{88888-88-8-8}{8+8} + \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{99999-99-9-9}{9+9} + \frac{999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55659 &:= \frac{111111-11-1-1}{1+1} + \frac{111-1}{1} := \frac{222222-22-2-2}{2+2} + \frac{222-2}{2} := \frac{333333-33-3-3}{3+3} + \frac{333-3}{3} \\ &::= \frac{444444-44-4-4}{4+4} + \frac{444-4}{4} := \frac{555555-55-5-5}{5+5} + \frac{555-5}{5} := \frac{666666-66-6-6}{6+6} + \frac{666-6}{6} \\ &::= \frac{777777-77-7-7}{7+7} + \frac{777-7}{7} := \frac{888888-88-8-8}{8+8} + \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{999999-99-9-9}{9+9} + \frac{999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 555659 &:= \frac{1111111-11-1-1}{1+1} + \frac{111-1}{1} := \frac{2222222-22-2-2}{2+2} + \frac{222-2}{2} := \frac{3333333-33-3-3}{3+3} + \frac{333-3}{3} \\ &::= \frac{4444444-44-4-4}{4+4} + \frac{444-4}{4} := \frac{5555555-55-5-5}{5+5} + \frac{555-5}{5} := \frac{6666666-66-6-6}{6+6} + \frac{666-6}{6} \\ &::= \frac{7777777-77-7-7}{7+7} + \frac{777-7}{7} := \frac{8888888-88-8-8}{8+8} + \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{9999999-99-9-9}{9+9} + \frac{999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 660 &:= \frac{1111-11}{1+1} + \frac{111-1}{1} := \frac{2222-22}{2+2} + \frac{222-2}{2} := \frac{3333-33}{3+3} + \frac{333-3}{3} \\ &::= \frac{4444-44}{4+4} + \frac{444-4}{4} := \frac{5555-55}{5+5} + \frac{555-5}{5} := \frac{6666-66}{6+6} + \frac{666-6}{6} \\ &::= \frac{7777-77}{7+7} + \frac{777-7}{7} := \frac{8888-88}{8+8} + \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{9999-99}{9+9} + \frac{999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5660 &:= \frac{11111-11}{1+1} + \frac{111-1}{1} := \frac{22222-22}{2+2} + \frac{222-2}{2} := \frac{33333-33}{3+3} + \frac{333-3}{3} \\ &::= \frac{44444-44}{4+4} + \frac{444-4}{4} := \frac{55555-55}{5+5} + \frac{555-5}{5} := \frac{66666-66}{6+6} + \frac{666-6}{6} \\ &::= \frac{77777-77}{7+7} + \frac{777-7}{7} := \frac{88888-88}{8+8} + \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{99999-99}{9+9} + \frac{999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55660 &:= \frac{111111-11}{1+1} + \frac{111-1}{1} := \frac{222222-22}{2+2} + \frac{222-2}{2} := \frac{333333-33}{3+3} + \frac{333-3}{3} \\ &::= \frac{444444-44}{4+4} + \frac{444-4}{4} := \frac{555555-55}{5+5} + \frac{555-5}{5} := \frac{666666-66}{6+6} + \frac{666-6}{6} \\ &::= \frac{777777-77}{7+7} + \frac{777-7}{7} := \frac{888888-88}{8+8} + \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{999999-99}{9+9} + \frac{999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555660} &:= \frac{1111111-11}{1+1} + \frac{111-1}{1} := \frac{222222-22}{2+2} + \frac{222-2}{2} := \frac{333333-33}{3+3} + \frac{333-3}{3} \\ &::= \frac{444444-44}{4+4} + \frac{444-4}{4} := \frac{555555-55}{5+5} + \frac{555-5}{5} := \frac{666666-66}{6+6} + \frac{666-6}{6} \\ &::= \frac{777777-77}{7+7} + \frac{777-7}{7} := \frac{888888-88}{8+8} + \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{999999-99}{9+9} + \frac{999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{661} &:= \frac{1111-11+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{111-1}{1} := \frac{2222-22+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{222-2}{2} := \frac{3333-33+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{333-3}{3} \\ &::= \frac{4444-44+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{444-4}{4} := \frac{5555-55+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{555-5}{5} := \frac{6666-66+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{666-6}{6} \\ &::= \frac{7777-77+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{777-7}{7} := \frac{8888-88+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{9999-99+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{5661} &:= \frac{11111-11+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{111-1}{1} := \frac{22222-22+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{222-2}{2} := \frac{33333-33+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{333-3}{3} \\ &::= \frac{44444-44+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{444-4}{4} := \frac{55555-55+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{555-5}{5} := \frac{66666-66+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{666-6}{6} \\ &::= \frac{77777-77+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{777-7}{7} := \frac{88888-88+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{99999-99+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55661} &:= \frac{111111-11+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{111-1}{1} := \frac{222222-22+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{222-2}{2} := \frac{333333-33+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{333-3}{3} \\ &::= \frac{444444-44+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{444-4}{4} := \frac{555555-55+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{555-5}{5} := \frac{666666-66+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{666-6}{6} \\ &::= \frac{777777-77+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{777-7}{7} := \frac{888888-88+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{999999-99+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{555661} &:= \frac{1111111-11+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{111-1}{1} := \frac{2222222-22+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{222-2}{2} := \frac{3333333-33+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{333-3}{3} \\ &::= \frac{4444444-44+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{444-4}{4} := \frac{5555555-55+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{555-5}{5} := \frac{6666666-66+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{666-6}{6} \\ &::= \frac{7777777-77+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{777-7}{7} := \frac{8888888-88+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{888-8}{8} = \frac{9999999-99+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{999-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{662} &:= \frac{1111+11}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} := \frac{2222+22}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} := \frac{3333+33}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\ &::= \frac{4444+44}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} := \frac{5555+55}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} := \frac{6666+66}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ &::= \frac{7777+77}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} := \frac{8888+88}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999+99}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5662} := \frac{11111+11}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} := \frac{22222+22}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} := \frac{33333+33}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & ::= \frac{44444+44}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} := \frac{55555+55}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} := \frac{66666+66}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ & ::= \frac{77777+77}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} := \frac{88888+88}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{99999+99}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{55662} := \frac{111111+11}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} := \frac{222222+22}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} := \frac{333333+33}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & ::= \frac{444444+44}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} := \frac{555555+55}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} := \frac{666666+66}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ & ::= \frac{777777+77}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} := \frac{888888+88}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{999999+99}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{555662} := \frac{1111111+11}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} := \frac{2222222+22}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} := \frac{3333333+33}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & ::= \frac{4444444+44}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} := \frac{5555555+55}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} := \frac{6666666+66}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ & ::= \frac{7777777+77}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} := \frac{8888888+88}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999999+99}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{663} := \frac{1111+11+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} := \frac{2222+22+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} := \frac{3333+33+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & ::= \frac{4444+44+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} := \frac{5555+55+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} := \frac{6666+66+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ & ::= \frac{7777+77+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} := \frac{8888+88+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999+99+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{5663} := \frac{11111+11+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} := \frac{22222+22+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} := \frac{33333+33+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & ::= \frac{44444+44+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} := \frac{55555+55+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} := \frac{66666+66+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ & ::= \frac{77777+77+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} := \frac{88888+88+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{99999+99+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{55663} := \frac{111111+11+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{11} := \frac{222222+22+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{22} := \frac{333333+33+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{33}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & ::= \frac{444444+44+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{44} := \frac{555555+55+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{55} := \frac{666666+66+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\ & ::= \frac{777777+77+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{77} := \frac{888888+88+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{999999+99+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{555663} &:= \frac{1111111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{1111}{11} := \frac{2222222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{2222}{22} := \frac{3333333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{3333}{33} \\
 &::= \frac{4444444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{4444}{44} := \frac{5555555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{5555}{55} := \frac{6666666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{6666}{66} \\
 &::= \frac{7777777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7} + \frac{7777}{77} := \frac{8888888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8} + \frac{8888}{88} = \frac{9999999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9} + \frac{9999}{99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{664} &:= \frac{111 \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} := \frac{222 \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} := \frac{333 \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &::= \frac{444 \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} := \frac{555 \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} := \frac{666 \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &::= \frac{777 \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} := \frac{888 \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{6664} &:= \frac{1111 \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} := \frac{2222 \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} := \frac{3333 \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &::= \frac{4444 \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} := \frac{5555 \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} := \frac{6666 \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &::= \frac{7777 \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} := \frac{8888 \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{66664} &:= \frac{11111 \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} := \frac{22222 \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} := \frac{33333 \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &::= \frac{44444 \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} := \frac{55555 \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} := \frac{66666 \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &::= \frac{77777 \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} := \frac{88888 \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{99999 \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{666664} &:= \frac{111111 \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} := \frac{222222 \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} := \frac{333333 \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &::= \frac{444444 \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} := \frac{555555 \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} := \frac{666666 \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &::= \frac{777777 \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} := \frac{888888 \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{999999 \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{665} := \frac{111 \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} := \frac{222 \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} := \frac{333 \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} ::= & \frac{444 \times (44+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} := \frac{555 \times (55+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} := \frac{666 \times (66+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ ::= & \frac{777 \times (77+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} := \frac{888 \times (88+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times (99+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6665} := \frac{1111 \times (11+1) - (1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} := \frac{2222 \times (22+2) - (2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} := \frac{3333 \times (33+3) - (3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} ::= & \frac{4444 \times (44+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} := \frac{5555 \times (55+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} := \frac{6666 \times (66+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ ::= & \frac{7777 \times (77+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} := \frac{8888 \times (88+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (99+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{66665} := \frac{11111 \times (11+1) - (1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} := \frac{22222 \times (22+2) - (2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} := \frac{33333 \times (33+3) - (3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} ::= & \frac{44444 \times (44+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} := \frac{55555 \times (55+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} := \frac{66666 \times (66+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ ::= & \frac{77777 \times (77+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} := \frac{88888 \times (88+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{99999 \times (99+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{666665} := \frac{111111 \times (11+1) - (1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} := \frac{222222 \times (22+2) - (2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} := \frac{333333 \times (33+3) - (3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} ::= & \frac{444444 \times (44+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} := \frac{555555 \times (55+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} := \frac{666666 \times (66+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ ::= & \frac{777777 \times (77+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} := \frac{888888 \times (88+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999999 \times (99+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{666} & := \frac{111 \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{444 \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{777 \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6666} & := \frac{1111 \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ & := \frac{4444 \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{7777 \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{66666} := \frac{11111 \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{22222 \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{33333 \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{44444 \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{55555 \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{66666 \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{88888 \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{99999 \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666666} &:= \frac{11111 \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{22222 \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{33333 \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{55555 \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{66666 \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{88888 \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{99999 \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{667} &:= \frac{111 \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6667} &:= \frac{1111 \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66667} &:= \frac{11111 \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{22222 \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{33333 \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{55555 \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{66666 \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{88888 \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{99999 \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666667} &:= \frac{111111 \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{222222 \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{333333 \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{555555 \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{666666 \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{888888 \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{999999 \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{668} &:= \frac{1111 + 1}{1 + 1} + \frac{111 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 2}{2 + 2} + \frac{222 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 3}{3 + 3} + \frac{333 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 4}{4 + 4} + \frac{444 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 5}{5 + 5} + \frac{555 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 6}{6 + 6} + \frac{666 + 6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7} + \frac{777+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} + \frac{888+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} + \frac{999+9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6668} &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66668} &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11111+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22222+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44444+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55555+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77777+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88888+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666668} &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11111+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22222+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44444+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55555+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77777+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88888+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{669} &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1} + \frac{111+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} + \frac{222+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} + \frac{333+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4} + \frac{444+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} + \frac{555+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} + \frac{666+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7} + \frac{777+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} + \frac{888+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} + \frac{999+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6669} &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66669} &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11111+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22222+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33333+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44444+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55555+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66666+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77777+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88888+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99999+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{666669} := \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11111+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22222+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33333+3+3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44444+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55555+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66666+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77777+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88888+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99999+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

► **670** := $\frac{1111+1}{1+1} + \frac{111+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} + \frac{222+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} + \frac{333+3+3+3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4} + \frac{444+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} + \frac{555+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} + \frac{666+6+6+6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7} + \frac{777+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} + \frac{888+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} + \frac{999+9+9+9}{9}$

6670 := $\frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333+3+3+3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{44444+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666+6+6+6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999+9+9+9}{9}$

66670 := $\frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11111+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22222+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33333+3+3+3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{44444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44444+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55555+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66666+6+6+6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77777+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88888+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99999+9+9+9}{9}$

666670 := $\frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{111111+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{222222+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{333333+3+3+3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{444444+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{555555+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{666666+6+6+6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{777777+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{888888+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{999999+9+9+9}{9}$

► **671** := $\frac{(111+11) \times (11+11)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(222+22) \times (22+22)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(333+33) \times (33+33)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)}$
 $:= \frac{(444+44) \times (44+44)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(555+55) \times (55+55)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(666+66) \times (66+66)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)}$
 $:= \frac{(777+77) \times (77+77)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(888+88) \times (88+88)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(999+99) \times (99+99)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)}$

6171 := $\frac{(1111+11) \times (11+11)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(2222+22) \times (22+22)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(3333+33) \times (33+33)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)}$
 $:= \frac{(4444+44) \times (44+44)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(5555+55) \times (55+55)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(6666+66) \times (66+66)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)}$
 $:= \frac{(7777+77) \times (77+77)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(8888+88) \times (88+88)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(9999+99) \times (99+99)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{61171} &:= \frac{(11111+11) \times (11+11)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(22222+22) \times (22+22)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(33333+33) \times (33+33)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444+44) \times (44+44)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(55555+55) \times (55+55)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(66666+66) \times (66+66)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777+77) \times (77+77)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(88888+88) \times (88+88)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(99999+99) \times (99+99)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{611171} &:= \frac{(111111+11) \times (11+11)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(222222+22) \times (22+22)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(333333+33) \times (33+33)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444+44) \times (44+44)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(555555+55) \times (55+55)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(666666+66) \times (66+66)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777+77) \times (77+77)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(888888+88) \times (88+88)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(999999+99) \times (99+99)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{672} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{6672} &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{66672} &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{666672} &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{673} := \frac{(111+1) \times (11+1) + (1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (22+2) + (2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (33+3) + (3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (44+4) + (4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (55+5) + (5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (66+6) + (6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (77+7) + (7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (88+8) + (8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (99+9) + (9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6673} &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (11+1) + (1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (22+2) + (2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (33+3) + (3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (44+4) + (4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (55+5) + (5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (66+6) + (6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (77+7) + (7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (88+8) + (8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (99+9) + (9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66673} &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (11+1) + (1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (22+2) + (2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (33+3) + (3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (44+4) + (4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (55+5) + (5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (66+6) + (6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (77+7) + (7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (88+8) + (8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (99+9) + (9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666673} &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (11+1) + (1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (22+2) + (2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (33+3) + (3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (44+4) + (4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (55+5) + (5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (66+6) + (6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (77+7) + (7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (88+8) + (8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (99+9) + (9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{674} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (11+1) + (1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (22+2) + (2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (33+3) + (3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (44+4) + (4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (55+5) + (5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (66+6) + (6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (77+7) + (7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (88+8) + (8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (99+9) + (9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6674} &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (11+1) + (1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (22+2) + (2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (33+3) + (3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (44+4) + (4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (55+5) + (5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (66+6) + (6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (77+7) + (7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (88+8) + (8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (99+9) + (9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66674} &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (11+1) + (1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (22+2) + (2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (33+3) + (3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (44+4) + (4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (55+5) + (5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (66+6) + (6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (77+7) + (7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (88+8) + (8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (99+9) + (9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{666674} &:= \frac{(111111 + 1) \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 2) \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 3) \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 4) \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 5) \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 6) \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 7) \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 8) \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 9) \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{675} &:= \frac{(11 + 1) \times 111 + (11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2) \times 222 + (22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3) \times 333 + (33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4) \times 444 + (44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5) \times 555 + (55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6) \times 666 + (66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7) \times 777 + (77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8) \times 888 + (88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9) \times 999 + (99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{6675} &:= \frac{(11 + 1) \times 1111 + (11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2) \times 2222 + (22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3) \times 3333 + (33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4) \times 4444 + (44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5) \times 5555 + (55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6) \times 6666 + (66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7) \times 7777 + (77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8) \times 8888 + (88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9) \times 9999 + (99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{66675} &:= \frac{(11 + 1) \times 11111 + (11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2) \times 22222 + (22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3) \times 33333 + (33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4) \times 44444 + (44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5) \times 55555 + (55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6) \times 66666 + (66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7) \times 77777 + (77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8) \times 88888 + (88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9) \times 99999 + (99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{666675} &:= \frac{(11 + 1) \times 111111 + (11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2) \times 222222 + (22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3) \times 333333 + (33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4) \times 444444 + (44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5) \times 555555 + (55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6) \times 666666 + (66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7) \times 777777 + (77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8) \times 888888 + (88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9) \times 999999 + (99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{676} &:= \frac{111 \times (11 + 1) + (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times (22 + 2) + (22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times (33 + 3) + (33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{444 \times (44 + 4) + (44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times (55 + 5) + (55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times (66 + 6) + (66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{777 \times (77 + 7) + (77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times (88 + 8) + (88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times (99 + 9) + (99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6676} := \frac{1111 \times (11 + 1) + (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (22 + 2) + (22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (33 + 3) + (33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 \times (44 + 4) + (44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (55 + 5) + (55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (66 + 6) + (66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (77 + 7) + (77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (88 + 8) + (88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (99 + 9) + (99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66676} &:= \frac{11111 \times (11 + 1) + (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{22222 \times (22 + 2) + (22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{33333 \times (33 + 3) + (33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 \times (44 + 4) + (44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{55555 \times (55 + 5) + (55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{66666 \times (66 + 6) + (66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 \times (77 + 7) + (77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{88888 \times (88 + 8) + (88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{99999 \times (99 + 9) + (99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666676} &:= \frac{111111 \times (11 + 1) + (11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{222222 \times (22 + 2) + (22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{333333 \times (33 + 3) + (33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (44 + 4) + (44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{555555 \times (55 + 5) + (55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{666666 \times (66 + 6) + (66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (77 + 7) + (77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{888888 \times (88 + 8) + (88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{999999 \times (99 + 9) + (99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{677} &:= \frac{111 \times (11 + 1) + 11 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{222 \times (22 + 2) + 22 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{333 \times (33 + 3) + 33 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444 \times (44 + 4) + 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{555 \times (55 + 5) + 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{666 \times (66 + 6) + 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777 \times (77 + 7) + 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{888 \times (88 + 8) + 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{999 \times (99 + 9) + 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6677} &:= \frac{1111 \times (11 + 1) + 11 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{2222 \times (22 + 2) + 22 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{3333 \times (33 + 3) + 33 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (44 + 4) + 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{5555 \times (55 + 5) + 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{6666 \times (66 + 6) + 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (77 + 7) + 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{8888 \times (88 + 8) + 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{9999 \times (99 + 9) + 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66677} &:= \frac{11111 \times (11 + 1) + 11 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{22222 \times (22 + 2) + 22 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{33333 \times (33 + 3) + 33 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 \times (44 + 4) + 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{55555 \times (55 + 5) + 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{66666 \times (66 + 6) + 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 \times (77 + 7) + 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{88888 \times (88 + 8) + 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{99999 \times (99 + 9) + 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666677} &:= \frac{111111 \times (11 + 1) + 11 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{222222 \times (22 + 2) + 22 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{333333 \times (33 + 3) + 33 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (44 + 4) + 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{555555 \times (55 + 5) + 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{666666 \times (66 + 6) + 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (77 + 7) + 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{888888 \times (88 + 8) + 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{999999 \times (99 + 9) + 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 678 &:= \frac{(111+1+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6678 &:= \frac{(1111+1+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 66678 &:= \frac{(11111+1+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 666678 &:= \frac{(111111+1+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 679 &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1} + \frac{111+11+1}{1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2} + \frac{222+22+2}{2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3} + \frac{333+33+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444+4}{4+4} + \frac{444+44+4}{4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5} + \frac{555+55+5}{5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6} + \frac{666+66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777+7}{7+7} + \frac{777+77+7}{7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8} + \frac{888+88+8}{8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9} + \frac{999+99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6679 &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111+11+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222+22+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333+33+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444+44+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555+55+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666+66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777+77+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888+88+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999+99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$66679 := \frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11111+11+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22222+22+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33333+33+3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44444+44+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55555+55+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66666+66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77777+77+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88888+88+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99999+99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666679} &:= \frac{1111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{111111+11+1}{1} = \frac{2222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{222222+22+2}{2} = \frac{3333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{333333+33+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{444444+44+4}{4} = \frac{5555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{555555+55+5}{5} = \frac{6666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{666666+66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{777777+77+7}{7} = \frac{8888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{888888+88+8}{8} = \frac{9999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{999999+99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{680} &:= \frac{1111+1}{1+1} + \frac{111+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2}{2+2} + \frac{222+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3}{3+3} + \frac{333+33+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+4}{4+4} + \frac{444+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5}{5+5} + \frac{555+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6}{6+6} + \frac{666+66+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+7}{7+7} + \frac{777+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8}{8+8} + \frac{888+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9}{9+9} + \frac{999+99+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6680} &:= \frac{11111+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333+33+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666+66+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999+99+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66680} &:= \frac{111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{11111+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{22222+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{33333+33+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{44444+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{55555+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{66666+66+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{77777+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{88888+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{99999+99+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666680} &:= \frac{1111111+1}{1+1} + \frac{111111+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222222+2}{2+2} + \frac{222222+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333333+3}{3+3} + \frac{333333+33+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+4}{4+4} + \frac{444444+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555555+5}{5+5} + \frac{555555+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666666+6}{6+6} + \frac{666666+66+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+7}{7+7} + \frac{777777+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888888+8}{8+8} + \frac{888888+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999999+9}{9+9} + \frac{999999+99+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{681} &:= \frac{(111+11) \times 11 + (11-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+22) \times 22 + (22-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+33) \times 33 + (33-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+44) \times 44 + (44-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+55) \times 55 + (55-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+66) \times 66 + (66-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+77) \times 77 + (77-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+88) \times 88 + (88-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+99) \times 99 + (99-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{6181} &:= \frac{(1111+11) \times 11 + (11-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22) \times 22 + (22-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33) \times 33 + (33-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444+44) \times 44 + (44-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55) \times 55 + (55-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66) \times 66 + (66-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777+77) \times 77 + (77-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+88) \times 88 + (88-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+99) \times 99 + (99-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{61181} &:= \frac{(11111+11) \times 11 + (11-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22) \times 22 + (22-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33) \times 33 + (33-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444+44) \times 44 + (44-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55) \times 55 + (55-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66) \times 66 + (66-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777+77) \times 77 + (77-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88) \times 88 + (88-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99) \times 99 + (99-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{611181} &:= \frac{(111111+11) \times 11 + (11-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222+22) \times 22 + (22-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333+33) \times 33 + (33-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444+44) \times 44 + (44-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555+55) \times 55 + (55-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666+66) \times 66 + (66-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777+77) \times 77 + (77-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888+88) \times 88 + (88-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999+99) \times 99 + (99-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{682} &:= \frac{(111+11) \times 11 + 11 \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+22) \times 22 + 22 \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+33) \times 33 + 33 \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444+44) \times 44 + 44 \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+55) \times 55 + 55 \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+66) \times 66 + 66 \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777+77) \times 77 + 77 \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+88) \times 88 + 88 \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+99) \times 99 + 99 \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{6182} &:= \frac{(1111+11) \times 11 + 11 \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22) \times 22 + 22 \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33) \times 33 + 33 \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444+44) \times 44 + 44 \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55) \times 55 + 55 \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66) \times 66 + 66 \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777+77) \times 77 + 77 \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+88) \times 88 + 88 \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+99) \times 99 + 99 \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{61182} &:= \frac{(11111+11) \times 11 + 11 \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22) \times 22 + 22 \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33) \times 33 + 33 \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444+44) \times 44 + 44 \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55) \times 55 + 55 \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66) \times 66 + 66 \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777+77) \times 77 + 77 \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88) \times 88 + 88 \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99) \times 99 + 99 \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{611182} := \frac{(111111+11) \times 11 + 11 \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222+22) \times 22 + 22 \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333+33) \times 33 + 33 \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times 44 + 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times 55 + 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times 66 + 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6}$$

$$:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times 77 + 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times 88 + 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times 99 + 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$$

► **683** := $\frac{1111 + 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{111 + 11}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{222 + 22}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{333 + 33}{3}$

$$:= \frac{4444 + 44}{4 + 4} + \frac{444 + 44}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55}{5 + 5} + \frac{555 + 55}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66}{6 + 6} + \frac{666 + 66}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 + 77}{7 + 7} + \frac{777 + 77}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88}{8 + 8} + \frac{888 + 88}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99}{9 + 9} + \frac{999 + 99}{9}$$

6683 := $\frac{11111 + 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{1111 + 11}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{2222 + 22}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{3333 + 33}{3}$

$$:= \frac{44444 + 44}{4 + 4} + \frac{4444 + 44}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55}{5 + 5} + \frac{5555 + 55}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66}{6 + 6} + \frac{6666 + 66}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 + 77}{7 + 7} + \frac{7777 + 77}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88}{8 + 8} + \frac{8888 + 88}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99}{9 + 9} + \frac{9999 + 99}{9}$$

66683 := $\frac{111111 + 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{11111 + 11}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{22222 + 22}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{33333 + 33}{3}$

$$:= \frac{444444 + 44}{4 + 4} + \frac{44444 + 44}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55}{5 + 5} + \frac{55555 + 55}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66}{6 + 6} + \frac{66666 + 66}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{777777 + 77}{7 + 7} + \frac{77777 + 77}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88}{8 + 8} + \frac{88888 + 88}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99}{9 + 9} + \frac{99999 + 99}{9}$$

666683 := $\frac{1111111 + 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{111111 + 11}{1} = \frac{2222222 + 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{222222 + 22}{2} = \frac{3333333 + 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{333333 + 33}{3}$

$$:= \frac{4444444 + 44}{4 + 4} + \frac{444444 + 44}{4} = \frac{5555555 + 55}{5 + 5} + \frac{555555 + 55}{5} = \frac{6666666 + 66}{6 + 6} + \frac{666666 + 66}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{7777777 + 77}{7 + 7} + \frac{777777 + 77}{7} = \frac{8888888 + 88}{8 + 8} + \frac{888888 + 88}{8} = \frac{9999999 + 99}{9 + 9} + \frac{999999 + 99}{9}$$

► **684** := $\frac{1111 + 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{333 + 33 + 3}{3}$

$$:= \frac{4444 + 44}{4 + 4} + \frac{444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55}{5 + 5} + \frac{555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66}{6 + 6} + \frac{666 + 66 + 6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 + 77}{7 + 7} + \frac{777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88}{8 + 8} + \frac{888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99}{9 + 9} + \frac{999 + 99 + 9}{9}$$

6684 := $\frac{11111 + 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{1111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{2222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{3333 + 33 + 3}{3}$

$$:= \frac{44444 + 44}{4 + 4} + \frac{4444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55}{5 + 5} + \frac{5555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66}{6 + 6} + \frac{6666 + 66 + 6}{6}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 + 77}{7 + 7} + \frac{7777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88}{8 + 8} + \frac{8888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99}{9 + 9} + \frac{9999 + 99 + 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{66684} &:= \frac{111111+11}{1+1} + \frac{11111+11+1}{1} = \frac{222222+22}{2+2} + \frac{22222+22+2}{2} = \frac{333333+33}{3+3} + \frac{33333+33+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+44}{4+4} + \frac{44444+44+4}{4} = \frac{555555+55}{5+5} + \frac{55555+55+5}{5} = \frac{666666+66}{6+6} + \frac{66666+66+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+77}{7+7} + \frac{77777+77+7}{7} = \frac{888888+88}{8+8} + \frac{88888+88+8}{8} = \frac{999999+99}{9+9} + \frac{99999+99+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{666684} &:= \frac{1111111+11}{1+1} + \frac{111111+11+1}{1} = \frac{2222222+22}{2+2} + \frac{222222+22+2}{2} = \frac{3333333+33}{3+3} + \frac{333333+33+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444+44}{4+4} + \frac{444444+44+4}{4} = \frac{5555555+55}{5+5} + \frac{555555+55+5}{5} = \frac{6666666+66}{6+6} + \frac{666666+66+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777+77}{7+7} + \frac{777777+77+7}{7} = \frac{8888888+88}{8+8} + \frac{888888+88+8}{8} = \frac{9999999+99}{9+9} + \frac{999999+99+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{685} &:= \frac{1111+11}{1+1} + \frac{111+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222+22}{2+2} + \frac{222+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333+33}{3+3} + \frac{333+33+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+44}{4+4} + \frac{444+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555+55}{5+5} + \frac{555+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666+66}{6+6} + \frac{666+66+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777+77}{7+7} + \frac{777+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888+88}{8+8} + \frac{888+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999+99}{9+9} + \frac{999+99+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{6685} &:= \frac{11111+11}{1+1} + \frac{1111+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222+22}{2+2} + \frac{2222+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333+33}{3+3} + \frac{3333+33+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444+44}{4+4} + \frac{4444+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555+55}{5+5} + \frac{5555+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666+66}{6+6} + \frac{6666+66+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777+77}{7+7} + \frac{7777+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888+88}{8+8} + \frac{8888+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999+99}{9+9} + \frac{9999+99+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{66685} &:= \frac{111111+11}{1+1} + \frac{11111+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222+22}{2+2} + \frac{22222+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333+33}{3+3} + \frac{33333+33+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+44}{4+4} + \frac{44444+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555+55}{5+5} + \frac{55555+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666+66}{6+6} + \frac{66666+66+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+77}{7+7} + \frac{77777+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888+88}{8+8} + \frac{88888+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999+99}{9+9} + \frac{99999+99+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{666685} &:= \frac{1111111+11}{1+1} + \frac{111111+11+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222222+22}{2+2} + \frac{222222+22+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333333+33}{3+3} + \frac{333333+33+3+3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444+44}{4+4} + \frac{444444+44+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555555+55}{5+5} + \frac{555555+55+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666666+66}{6+6} + \frac{666666+66+6+6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777+77}{7+7} + \frac{777777+77+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888888+88}{8+8} + \frac{888888+88+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999999+99}{9+9} + \frac{999999+99+9+9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{686} &:= \frac{(111+111+111+11-1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222+222+22-2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333+333+33-3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444+444+444+44-4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555+555+55-5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666+666+66-6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2686} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22686} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222686} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{687} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2687} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22687} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{222687} := \frac{(111111 + 111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{688} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2688} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22688} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222688} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{689} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2689} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{22689} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{222689} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{690} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2690} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{22690} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{222690} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{691} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2691} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22691} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222691} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{692} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2692} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22692} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{222692} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 111 + 11 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 222 + 22 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 333 + 33 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 444 + 44 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 555 + 55 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 666 + 66 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 777 + 77 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 888 + 88 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 999 + 99 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{693} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6993} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 111) \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222) \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333) \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444) \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555) \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666) \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777) \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888) \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999) \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{69993} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111 + 1111) \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222 + 2222) \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333 + 3333) \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444 + 4444) \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555 + 5555) \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666 + 6666) \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 7777) \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 8888) \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 9999) \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{699993} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{694} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times (11 + 11 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times (22 + 22 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times (33 + 33 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times (44 + 44 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times (55 + 55 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times (66 + 66 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 77 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 88 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 99 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6994} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 111) \times (11 + 11 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222) \times (22 + 22 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333) \times (33 + 33 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444) \times (44 + 44 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555) \times (55 + 55 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666) \times (66 + 66 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777) \times (77 + 77 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888) \times (88 + 88 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999) \times (99 + 99 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{69994} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111 + 1111) \times (11 + 11 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222 + 2222) \times (22 + 22 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333 + 3333) \times (33 + 33 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444 + 4444) \times (44 + 44 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555 + 5555) \times (55 + 55 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666 + 6666) \times (66 + 66 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 7777) \times (77 + 77 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 8888) \times (88 + 88 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 9999) \times (99 + 99 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{699994} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 11 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 22 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 33 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 44 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 55 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 66 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 77 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 88 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 99 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{695} &:= \frac{1111 + 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44}{4 + 4} + \frac{444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55}{5 + 5} + \frac{555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66}{6 + 6} + \frac{666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77}{7 + 7} + \frac{777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88}{8 + 8} + \frac{888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99}{9 + 9} + \frac{999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6695} &:= \frac{11111 + 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44}{4 + 4} + \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55}{5 + 5} + \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66}{6 + 6} + \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77}{7 + 7} + \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88}{8 + 8} + \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99}{9 + 9} + \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66695} &:= \frac{111111 + 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44}{4 + 4} + \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55}{5 + 5} + \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66}{6 + 6} + \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77}{7 + 7} + \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88}{8 + 8} + \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99}{9 + 9} + \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666695} &:= \frac{1111111 + 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 + 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 + 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 44}{4 + 4} + \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 + 55}{5 + 5} + \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 + 66}{6 + 6} + \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 77}{7 + 7} + \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 + 88}{8 + 8} + \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 + 99}{9 + 9} + \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{696} := \frac{(111 + 111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3696} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33696} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333696} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11 - 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22 - 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33 - 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44 - 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55 - 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66 - 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77 - 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88 - 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99 - 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{697} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3697} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33697} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333697} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{698} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3698} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33698} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333698} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{699} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3699} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33699} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333699} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{700} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3700} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33700} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333700} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{701} := \frac{(111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3701} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33701} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333701} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{702} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3702} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33702} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333702} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{703} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3703} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33703} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333703} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{704} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3704} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33704} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{333704} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 + 11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 + 22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 + 33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 + 44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 + 55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 + 66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 + 77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 + 88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 + 99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{705} &:= \frac{1111 + 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{111 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{222 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{333 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 44}{4 + 4} + \frac{444 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4} = \frac{5555 + 55}{5 + 5} + \frac{555 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5} = \frac{6666 + 66}{6 + 6} + \frac{666 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 77}{7 + 7} + \frac{777 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{8888 + 88}{8 + 8} + \frac{888 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{9999 + 99}{9 + 9} + \frac{999 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6705} &:= \frac{11111 + 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{1111 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1} = \frac{22222 + 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{2222 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2} = \frac{33333 + 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{3333 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44}{4 + 4} + \frac{4444 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4} = \frac{55555 + 55}{5 + 5} + \frac{5555 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5} = \frac{66666 + 66}{6 + 6} + \frac{6666 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77}{7 + 7} + \frac{7777 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{88888 + 88}{8 + 8} + \frac{8888 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{99999 + 99}{9 + 9} + \frac{9999 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66705} &:= \frac{111111 + 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1} = \frac{222222 + 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2} = \frac{333333 + 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 44}{4 + 4} + \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4} = \frac{555555 + 55}{5 + 5} + \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5} = \frac{666666 + 66}{6 + 6} + \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 77}{7 + 7} + \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{888888 + 88}{8 + 8} + \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{999999 + 99}{9 + 9} + \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666705} &:= \frac{1111111 + 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{111111 + 11 + 11 + 11}{1} = \frac{2222222 + 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{222222 + 22 + 22 + 22}{2} = \frac{3333333 + 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{333333 + 33 + 33 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 44}{4 + 4} + \frac{444444 + 44 + 44 + 44}{4} = \frac{5555555 + 55}{5 + 5} + \frac{555555 + 55 + 55 + 55}{5} = \frac{6666666 + 66}{6 + 6} + \frac{666666 + 66 + 66 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 77}{7 + 7} + \frac{777777 + 77 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{8888888 + 88}{8 + 8} + \frac{888888 + 88 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{9999999 + 99}{9 + 9} + \frac{999999 + 99 + 99 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{706} := \frac{1111 + 11}{1 + 1} + \frac{111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 + 22}{2 + 2} + \frac{222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 + 33}{3 + 3} + \frac{333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444+44}{4+4} + \frac{444+44+44+44+4}{4} = \frac{5555+55}{5+5} + \frac{555+55+55+55+5}{5} = \frac{6666+66}{6+6} + \frac{666+66+66+66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+77}{7+7} + \frac{777+77+77+77+7}{7} = \frac{8888+88}{8+8} + \frac{888+88+88+88+8}{8} = \frac{9999+99}{9+9} + \frac{999+99+99+99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6706} &:= \frac{11111+11}{1+1} + \frac{1111+11+11+11+1}{1} = \frac{22222+22}{2+2} + \frac{2222+22+22+22+2}{2} = \frac{33333+33}{3+3} + \frac{3333+33+33+33+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+44}{4+4} + \frac{4444+44+44+44+4}{4} = \frac{55555+55}{5+5} + \frac{5555+55+55+55+5}{5} = \frac{66666+66}{6+6} + \frac{6666+66+66+66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+77}{7+7} + \frac{7777+77+77+77+7}{7} = \frac{88888+88}{8+8} + \frac{8888+88+88+88+8}{8} = \frac{99999+99}{9+9} + \frac{9999+99+99+99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66706} &:= \frac{111111+11}{1+1} + \frac{11111+11+11+11+1}{1} = \frac{222222+22}{2+2} + \frac{22222+22+22+22+2}{2} = \frac{333333+33}{3+3} + \frac{33333+33+33+33+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44}{4+4} + \frac{44444+44+44+44+4}{4} = \frac{555555+55}{5+5} + \frac{55555+55+55+55+5}{5} = \frac{666666+66}{6+6} + \frac{66666+66+66+66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77}{7+7} + \frac{77777+77+77+77+7}{7} = \frac{888888+88}{8+8} + \frac{88888+88+88+88+8}{8} = \frac{999999+99}{9+9} + \frac{99999+99+99+99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666706} &:= \frac{1111111+11}{1+1} + \frac{111111+11+11+11+1}{1} = \frac{2222222+22}{2+2} + \frac{222222+22+22+22+2}{2} = \frac{3333333+33}{3+3} + \frac{333333+33+33+33+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+44}{4+4} + \frac{444444+44+44+44+4}{4} = \frac{5555555+55}{5+5} + \frac{555555+55+55+55+5}{5} = \frac{6666666+66}{6+6} + \frac{666666+66+66+66+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+77}{7+7} + \frac{777777+77+77+77+7}{7} = \frac{8888888+88}{8+8} + \frac{888888+88+88+88+8}{8} = \frac{9999999+99}{9+9} + \frac{999999+99+99+99+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{707} &:= \frac{11+1+1+1) \times 1111}{(11 \times (1+1))} = \frac{22+2+2+2) \times 2222}{(22 \times (2+2))} = \frac{33+3+3+3) \times 3333}{(33 \times (3+3))} \\ &:= \frac{44+4+4+4) \times 4444}{(44 \times (4+4))} = \frac{55+5+5+5) \times 5555}{(55 \times (5+5))} = \frac{66+6+6+6) \times 6666}{(66 \times (6+6))} \\ &:= \frac{77+7+7+7) \times 7777}{(77 \times (7+7))} = \frac{88+8+8+8) \times 8888}{(88 \times (8+8))} = \frac{99+9+9+9) \times 9999}{(99 \times (9+9))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{70707} &:= \frac{11+1+1+1) \times 111111}{(11 \times (1+1))} = \frac{22+2+2+2) \times 222222}{(22 \times (2+2))} = \frac{33+3+3+3) \times 333333}{(33 \times (3+3))} \\ &:= \frac{44+4+4+4) \times 444444}{(44 \times (4+4))} = \frac{55+5+5+5) \times 555555}{(55 \times (5+5))} = \frac{66+6+6+6) \times 666666}{(66 \times (6+6))} \\ &:= \frac{77+7+7+7) \times 777777}{(77 \times (7+7))} = \frac{88+8+8+8) \times 888888}{(88 \times (8+8))} = \frac{99+9+9+9) \times 999999}{(99 \times (9+9))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7070707} &:= \frac{11+1+1+1) \times 11111111}{(11 \times (1+1))} = \frac{22+2+2+2) \times 22222222}{(22 \times (2+2))} = \frac{33+3+3+3) \times 33333333}{(33 \times (3+3))} \\ &:= \frac{44+4+4+4) \times 44444444}{(44 \times (4+4))} = \frac{55+5+5+5) \times 55555555}{(55 \times (5+5))} = \frac{66+6+6+6) \times 66666666}{(66 \times (6+6))} \\ &:= \frac{77+7+7+7) \times 77777777}{(77 \times (7+7))} = \frac{88+8+8+8) \times 88888888}{(88 \times (8+8))} = \frac{99+9+9+9) \times 99999999}{(99 \times (9+9))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 707070707 &:= \frac{11+1+1+1 \times 1111111111}{(11 \times (1+1))} = \frac{22+2+2+2 \times 2222222222}{(22 \times (2+2))} = \frac{33+3+3+3 \times 3333333333}{(33 \times (3+3))} \\
 &:= \frac{44+4+4+4 \times 4444444444}{(44 \times (4+4))} = \frac{55+5+5+5 \times 5555555555}{(55 \times (5+5))} = \frac{66+6+6+6 \times 6666666666}{(66 \times (6+6))} \\
 &:= \frac{77+7+7+7 \times 7777777777}{(77 \times (7+7))} = \frac{88+8+8+8 \times 8888888888}{(88 \times (8+8))} = \frac{99+9+9+9 \times 9999999999}{(99 \times (9+9))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 708 &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 1111 + 11 \times (1+1)}{11 \times (1+1)} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 2222 + 22 \times (2+2)}{22 \times (2+2)} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 3333 + 33 \times (3+3)}{33 \times (3+3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 4444 + 44 \times (4+4)}{44 \times (4+4)} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 5555 + 55 \times (5+5)}{55 \times (5+5)} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 6666 + 66 \times (6+6)}{66 \times (6+6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 7777 + 77 \times (7+7)}{77 \times (7+7)} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 8888 + 88 \times (8+8)}{88 \times (8+8)} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 9999 + 99 \times (9+9)}{99 \times (9+9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 70708 &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 111111 + 11 \times (1+1)}{11 \times (1+1)} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 222222 + 22 \times (2+2)}{22 \times (2+2)} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 333333 + 33 \times (3+3)}{33 \times (3+3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 444444 + 44 \times (4+4)}{44 \times (4+4)} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 555555 + 55 \times (5+5)}{55 \times (5+5)} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 666666 + 66 \times (6+6)}{66 \times (6+6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 777777 + 77 \times (7+7)}{77 \times (7+7)} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 888888 + 88 \times (8+8)}{88 \times (8+8)} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 999999 + 99 \times (9+9)}{99 \times (9+9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7070708 &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 11111111 + 11 \times (1+1)}{11 \times (1+1)} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 22222222 + 22 \times (2+2)}{22 \times (2+2)} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 33333333 + 33 \times (3+3)}{33 \times (3+3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 44444444 + 44 \times (4+4)}{44 \times (4+4)} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 55555555 + 55 \times (5+5)}{55 \times (5+5)} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 66666666 + 66 \times (6+6)}{66 \times (6+6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 77777777 + 77 \times (7+7)}{77 \times (7+7)} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 88888888 + 88 \times (8+8)}{88 \times (8+8)} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 99999999 + 99 \times (9+9)}{99 \times (9+9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 707070708 &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1) \times 1111111111 + 11 \times (1+1)}{11 \times (1+1)} = \frac{(22+2+2+2) \times 2222222222 + 22 \times (2+2)}{22 \times (2+2)} = \frac{(33+3+3+3) \times 3333333333 + 33 \times (3+3)}{33 \times (3+3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4) \times 4444444444 + 44 \times (4+4)}{44 \times (4+4)} = \frac{(55+5+5+5) \times 5555555555 + 55 \times (5+5)}{55 \times (5+5)} = \frac{(66+6+6+6) \times 6666666666 + 66 \times (6+6)}{66 \times (6+6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7) \times 7777777777 + 77 \times (7+7)}{77 \times (7+7)} = \frac{(88+8+8+8) \times 8888888888 + 88 \times (8+8)}{88 \times (8+8)} = \frac{(99+9+9+9) \times 9999999999 + 99 \times (9+9)}{99 \times (9+9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 709 &:= \frac{(111-11) \times (11+1) + (111-1-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-22) \times (22+2) + (222-2-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-33) \times (33+3) + (333-3-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444-44) \times (44+4) + (444-4-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-55) \times (55+5) + (555-5-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-66) \times (66+6) + (666-6-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777-77) \times (77+7) + (777-7-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-88) \times (88+8) + (888-8-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-99) \times (99+9) + (999-9-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$6709 := \frac{(1111-11) \times (11+1) + (111-1-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222-22) \times (22+2) + (222-2-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333-33) \times (33+3) + (333-3-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) + (444 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) + (555 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) + (666 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) + (777 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) + (888 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) + (999 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66709} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) + (111 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) + (222 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) + (333 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) + (444 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) + (555 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) + (666 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) + (777 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) + (888 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) + (999 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666709} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) + (111 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) + (222 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) + (333 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) + (444 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) + (555 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) + (666 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) + (777 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) + (888 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) + (999 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{710} &:= \frac{(111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) + (111 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) + (222 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) + (333 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) + (444 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) + (555 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) + (666 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) + (777 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) + (888 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) + (999 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6710} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) + (111 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) + (222 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) + (333 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) + (444 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) + (555 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) + (666 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) + (777 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) + (888 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) + (999 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66710} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) + (111 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) + (222 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) + (333 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) + (444 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) + (555 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) + (666 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) + (777 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) + (888 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) + (999 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666710} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (11 + 1) + (111 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (22 + 2) + (222 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (33 + 3) + (333 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (44 + 4) + (444 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (55 + 5) + (555 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (66 + 6) + (666 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (77 + 7) + (777 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (88 + 8) + (888 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (99 + 9) + (999 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 711 &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8711 &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 88711 &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 888711 &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 712 &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8712 &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 88712 &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77777 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888712} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{713} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8713} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88713} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888713} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{714} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{8714} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{88714} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{888714} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{715} &:= \frac{(111 - 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7215} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{72215} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 - 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{722215} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777777 - 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$$

► **716** := $\frac{(111 - 1) \times 11 + 111 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times 22 + 222 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times 33 + 333 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(444 - 4) \times 44 + 444 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5) \times 55 + 555 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6) \times 66 + 666 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(777 - 7) \times 77 + 777 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8) \times 88 + 888 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9) \times 99 + 999 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$

1716 := $\frac{(111 - 1) \times 11 + 1111 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times 22 + 2222 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times 33 + 3333 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(444 - 4) \times 44 + 4444 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5) \times 55 + 5555 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6) \times 66 + 6666 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(777 - 7) \times 77 + 7777 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8) \times 88 + 8888 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9) \times 99 + 9999 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$

11716 := $\frac{(111 - 1) \times 11 + 11111 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times 22 + 22222 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times 33 + 33333 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(444 - 4) \times 44 + 44444 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5) \times 55 + 55555 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6) \times 66 + 66666 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(777 - 7) \times 77 + 77777 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8) \times 88 + 88888 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9) \times 99 + 99999 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$

111716 := $\frac{(111 - 1) \times 11 + 111111 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times 22 + 222222 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times 33 + 333333 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(444 - 4) \times 44 + 444444 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5) \times 55 + 555555 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6) \times 66 + 666666 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(777 - 7) \times 77 + 777777 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8) \times 88 + 888888 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9) \times 99 + 999999 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$

► **717** := $\frac{(111 - 1) \times 11 + (111 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times 22 + (222 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times 33 + (333 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(444 - 4) \times 44 + (444 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5) \times 55 + (555 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6) \times 66 + (666 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(777 - 7) \times 77 + (777 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8) \times 88 + (888 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9) \times 99 + (999 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$

1717 := $\frac{(111 - 1) \times 11 + (1111 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times 22 + (2222 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times 33 + (3333 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(444 - 4) \times 44 + (4444 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5) \times 55 + (5555 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6) \times 66 + (6666 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(777 - 7) \times 77 + (7777 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8) \times 88 + (8888 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9) \times 99 + (9999 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 11717 &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11 + (11111+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22 + (22222+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33 + (33333+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44 + (44444+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55 + (55555+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66 + (66666+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77 + (77777+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88 + (88888+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99 + (99999+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 111717 &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11 + (111111+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22 + (222222+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33 + (333333+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44 + (444444+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55 + (555555+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66 + (666666+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77 + (777777+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88 + (888888+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99 + (999999+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 718 &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11 + (111+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22 + (222+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33 + (333+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44 + (444+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55 + (555+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66 + (666+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77 + (777+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88 + (888+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99 + (999+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1718 &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11 + (1111+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22 + (2222+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33 + (3333+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44 + (4444+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55 + (5555+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66 + (6666+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77 + (7777+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88 + (8888+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99 + (9999+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 11718 &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11 + (11111+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22 + (22222+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33 + (33333+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44 + (44444+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55 + (55555+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66 + (66666+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77 + (77777+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88 + (88888+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99 + (99999+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 111718 &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11 + (111111+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22 + (222222+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33 + (333333+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44 + (444444+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55 + (555555+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66 + (666666+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77 + (777777+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88 + (888888+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99 + (999999+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 719 &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11 + (111+1+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22 + (222+2+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33 + (333+3+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44 + (444+4+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55 + (555+5+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66 + (666+6+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77 + (777+7+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88 + (888+8+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99 + (999+9+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1719} &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11 + (1111+1+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22 + (2222+2+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33 + (3333+3+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44 + (4444+4+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55 + (5555+5+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66 + (6666+6+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77 + (7777+7+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88 + (8888+8+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99 + (9999+9+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11719} &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11 + (11111+1+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22 + (22222+2+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33 + (33333+3+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44 + (44444+4+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55 + (55555+5+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66 + (66666+6+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77 + (77777+7+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88 + (88888+8+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99 + (99999+9+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111719} &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11 + (111111+1+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22 + (222222+2+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33 + (333333+3+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44 + (444444+4+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55 + (555555+5+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66 + (666666+6+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77 + (777777+7+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88 + (888888+8+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99 + (999999+9+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{720} &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times 111 - (1+1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times 222 - (2+2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times 333 - (3+3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times 444 - (4+4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times 555 - (5+5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times 666 - (6+6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times 777 - (7+7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times 888 - (8+8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times 999 - (9+9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7220} &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times 1111 - (1+1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times 2222 - (2+2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times 3333 - (3+3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times 4444 - (4+4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times 5555 - (5+5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times 6666 - (6+6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times 7777 - (7+7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times 8888 - (8+8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times 9999 - (9+9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{72220} &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times 11111 - (1+1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times 22222 - (2+2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times 33333 - (3+3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times 44444 - (4+4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times 55555 - (5+5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times 66666 - (6+6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times 77777 - (7+7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times 88888 - (8+8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times 99999 - (9+9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 722220 &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times 111111 - (1+1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times 222222 - (2+2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times 333333 - (3+3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times 444444 - (4+4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times 555555 - (5+5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times 666666 - (6+6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times 777777 - (7+7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times 888888 - (8+8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times 999999 - (9+9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 721 &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times 111 - 1 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times 222 - 2 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times 333 - 3 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times 444 - 4 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times 555 - 5 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times 666 - 6 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times 777 - 7 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times 888 - 8 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times 999 - 9 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7221 &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times 1111 - 1 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times 2222 - 2 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times 3333 - 3 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times 4444 - 4 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times 5555 - 5 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times 6666 - 6 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times 7777 - 7 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times 8888 - 8 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times 9999 - 9 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 72221 &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times 11111 - 1 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times 22222 - 2 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times 33333 - 3 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times 44444 - 4 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times 55555 - 5 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times 66666 - 6 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times 77777 - 7 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times 88888 - 8 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times 99999 - 9 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 722221 &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times 111111 - 1 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times 222222 - 2 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times 333333 - 3 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times 444444 - 4 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times 555555 - 5 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times 666666 - 6 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times 777777 - 7 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times 888888 - 8 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times 999999 - 9 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 722 &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times 111 + 1 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times 222 + 2 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times 333 + 3 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times 444 + 4 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times 555 + 5 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times 666 + 6 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times 777 + 7 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times 888 + 8 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times 999 + 9 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$7222 := \frac{(11+1+1) \times 1111 + 1 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times 2222 + 2 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times 3333 + 3 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times 4444 + 4 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times 5555 + 5 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times 6666 + 6 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times 7777 + 7 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times 8888 + 8 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times 9999 + 9 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{72222} &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times 11111 + 1 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times 22222 + 2 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times 33333 + 3 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times 44444 + 4 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times 55555 + 5 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times 66666 + 6 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times 77777 + 7 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times 88888 + 8 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times 99999 + 9 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{722222} &:= \frac{(11+1+1) \times 111111 + 1 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2) \times 222222 + 2 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3) \times 333333 + 3 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4) \times 444444 + 4 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5) \times 555555 + 5 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6) \times 666666 + 6 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7) \times 777777 + 7 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8) \times 888888 + 8 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9) \times 999999 + 9 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{723} &:= \frac{1111+111+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{111}{1} = \frac{2222+222+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{222}{2} = \frac{3333+333+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+444+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{444}{4} = \frac{5555+555+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{555}{5} = \frac{6666+666+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+777+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{777}{7} = \frac{8888+888+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{888}{8} = \frac{9999+999+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7223} &:= \frac{11111+1111+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111}{1} = \frac{22222+2222+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222}{2} = \frac{33333+3333+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4444+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444}{4} = \frac{55555+5555+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555}{5} = \frac{66666+6666+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7777+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777}{7} = \frac{88888+8888+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888}{8} = \frac{99999+9999+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{72223} &:= \frac{111111+11111+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{11111}{1} = \frac{222222+22222+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{22222}{2} = \frac{333333+33333+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{33333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44444+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{44444}{4} = \frac{555555+55555+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{55555}{5} = \frac{666666+66666+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{66666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77777+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{77777}{7} = \frac{888888+88888+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{88888}{8} = \frac{999999+99999+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{99999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{722223} &:= \frac{1111111+111111+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{111111}{1} = \frac{2222222+222222+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{222222}{2} = \frac{3333333+333333+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{333333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+444444+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{444444}{4} = \frac{5555555+555555+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{555555}{5} = \frac{6666666+666666+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{666666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+777777+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{777777}{7} = \frac{8888888+888888+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{888888}{8} = \frac{9999999+999999+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{999999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 724 &:= \frac{1111+111+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{111+1}{1} = \frac{222+222+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{222+2}{2} = \frac{333+333+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444+444+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{444+4}{4} = \frac{555+555+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{555+5}{5} = \frac{666+666+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777+777+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{777+7}{7} = \frac{888+888+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{888+8}{8} = \frac{999+999+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7224 &:= \frac{11111+1111+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{1111+1}{1} = \frac{2222+2222+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{2222+2}{2} = \frac{3333+3333+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{3333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444+4444+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{4444+4}{4} = \frac{5555+5555+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{5555+5}{5} = \frac{6666+6666+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{6666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7777+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{7777+7}{7} = \frac{8888+8888+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{8888+8}{8} = \frac{9999+9999+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{9999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 72224 &:= \frac{111111+11111+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{11111+1}{1} = \frac{22222+22222+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{22222+2}{2} = \frac{33333+33333+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{33333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444+44444+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{44444+4}{4} = \frac{55555+55555+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{55555+5}{5} = \frac{66666+66666+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{66666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777+77777+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{77777+7}{7} = \frac{88888+88888+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{88888+8}{8} = \frac{99999+99999+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{99999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 722224 &:= \frac{1111111+111111+1+1}{1+1} + \frac{111111+1}{1} = \frac{222222+222222+2+2}{2+2} + \frac{222222+2}{2} = \frac{333333+333333+3+3}{3+3} + \frac{333333+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444+444444+4+4}{4+4} + \frac{444444+4}{4} = \frac{555555+555555+5+5}{5+5} + \frac{555555+5}{5} = \frac{666666+666666+6+6}{6+6} + \frac{666666+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+777777+7+7}{7+7} + \frac{777777+7}{7} = \frac{888888+888888+8+8}{8+8} + \frac{888888+8}{8} = \frac{999999+999999+9+9}{9+9} + \frac{999999+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 725 &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (11+11) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (22+22) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (33+33) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (44+44) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (55+55) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (66+66) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (77+77) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (88+88) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (99+99) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7325 &:= \frac{(111+111+111) \times (11+11) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222+222) \times (22+22) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333+333) \times (33+33) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444+444) \times (44+44) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555+555) \times (55+55) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666+666) \times (66+66) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777+777) \times (77+77) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888+888) \times (88+88) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999+999) \times (99+99) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 73325 &:= \frac{(1111+1111+1111) \times (11+11) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222+2222) \times (22+22) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333+3333) \times (33+33) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4444+4444) \times (44+44) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555+5555) \times (55+55) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666+6666) \times (66+66) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7777+7777) \times (77+77) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8888+8888) \times (88+88) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9999+9999) \times (99+99) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{733325} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 11) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 22) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 33) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 44) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 55) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 66) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 77) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 88) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 99) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{726} &:= \frac{(11 + 1) \times 11 \times 11}{(1 + 1) \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2) \times 22 \times 22}{(2 + 2) \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3) \times 33 \times 33}{(3 + 3) \times 3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4) \times 44 \times 44}{(4 + 4) \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5) \times 55 \times 55}{(5 + 5) \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6) \times 66 \times 66}{(6 + 6) \times 6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7) \times 77 \times 77}{(7 + 7) \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8) \times 88 \times 88}{(8 + 8) \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9) \times 99 \times 99}{(9 + 9) \times 9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7326} &:= \frac{(11 + 1) \times 11 \times 111}{(1 + 1) \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2) \times 22 \times 222}{(2 + 2) \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3) \times 33 \times 333}{(3 + 3) \times 3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4) \times 44 \times 444}{(4 + 4) \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5) \times 55 \times 555}{(5 + 5) \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6) \times 66 \times 666}{(6 + 6) \times 6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7) \times 77 \times 777}{(7 + 7) \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8) \times 88 \times 888}{(8 + 8) \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9) \times 99 \times 999}{(9 + 9) \times 9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{73326} &:= \frac{(11 + 1) \times 11 \times 1111}{(1 + 1) \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2) \times 22 \times 2222}{(2 + 2) \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3) \times 33 \times 3333}{(3 + 3) \times 3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4) \times 44 \times 4444}{(4 + 4) \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5) \times 55 \times 5555}{(5 + 5) \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6) \times 66 \times 6666}{(6 + 6) \times 6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7) \times 77 \times 7777}{(7 + 7) \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8) \times 88 \times 8888}{(8 + 8) \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9) \times 99 \times 9999}{(9 + 9) \times 9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{733326} &:= \frac{(11 + 1) \times 11 \times 11111}{(1 + 1) \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2) \times 22 \times 22222}{(2 + 2) \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3) \times 33 \times 33333}{(3 + 3) \times 3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 4) \times 44 \times 44444}{(4 + 4) \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5) \times 55 \times 55555}{(5 + 5) \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6) \times 66 \times 66666}{(6 + 6) \times 6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 7) \times 77 \times 77777}{(7 + 7) \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8) \times 88 \times 88888}{(8 + 8) \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9) \times 99 \times 99999}{(9 + 9) \times 9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{727} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times (11 + 11) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times (22 + 22) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times (33 + 33) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times (44 + 44) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times (55 + 55) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times (66 + 66) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 77) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 88) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 99) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{7327} := \frac{(111 + 111 + 111) \times (11 + 11) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222) \times (22 + 22) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333) \times (33 + 33) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444) \times (44 + 44) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555) \times (55 + 55) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666) \times (66 + 66) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777) \times (77 + 77) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888) \times (88 + 88) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999) \times (99 + 99) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{73327} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111 + 1111) \times (11 + 11) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222 + 2222) \times (22 + 22) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333 + 3333) \times (33 + 33) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444 + 4444) \times (44 + 44) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555 + 5555) \times (55 + 55) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666 + 6666) \times (66 + 66) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 7777) \times (77 + 77) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 8888) \times (88 + 88) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 9999) \times (99 + 99) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{733327} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 11) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 22) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 33) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 44) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 55) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 66) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 77) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 88) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 99) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{728} &:= \frac{(111 + 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7228} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{72228} &:= \frac{(11111 + 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{722228} &:= \frac{(111111 + 1) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 2) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 3) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 729 &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (11+1+1) + (1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (22+2+2) + (2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (33+3+3) + (3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (44+4+4) + (4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (55+5+5) + (5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (66+6+6) + (6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (77+7+7) + (7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (88+8+8) + (8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (99+9+9) + (9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7229 &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (11+1+1) + (1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (22+2+2) + (2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (33+3+3) + (3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (44+4+4) + (4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (55+5+5) + (5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (66+6+6) + (6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (77+7+7) + (7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (88+8+8) + (8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (99+9+9) + (9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 72229 &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (11+1+1) + (1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (22+2+2) + (2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (33+3+3) + (3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (44+4+4) + (4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (55+5+5) + (5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (66+6+6) + (6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (77+7+7) + (7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (88+8+8) + (8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (99+9+9) + (9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 722229 &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (11+1+1) + (1+1) \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (22+2+2) + (2+2) \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (33+3+3) + (3+3) \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (44+4+4) + (4+4) \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (55+5+5) + (5+5) \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (66+6+6) + (6+6) \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (77+7+7) + (7+7) \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (88+8+8) + (8+8) \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (99+9+9) + (9+9) \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 730 &:= \frac{(111+11) \times (11+1) - (1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+22) \times (22+2) - (2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+33) \times (33+3) - (3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+44) \times (44+4) - (4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+55) \times (55+5) - (5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+66) \times (66+6) - (6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+77) \times (77+7) - (7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+88) \times (88+8) - (8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+99) \times (99+9) - (9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6730 &:= \frac{(1111+11) \times (11+1) - (1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22) \times (22+2) - (2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33) \times (33+3) - (3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+44) \times (44+4) - (4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55) \times (55+5) - (5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66) \times (66+6) - (6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+77) \times (77+7) - (7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+88) \times (88+8) - (8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+99) \times (99+9) - (9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$66730 := \frac{(11111+11) \times (11+1) - (1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22) \times (22+2) - (2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33) \times (33+3) - (3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666730} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{731} &:= \frac{(111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6731} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66731} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666731} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{732} &:= \frac{(111 + 11) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6732} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66732} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666732} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{733} &:= \frac{(111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6733} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66733} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666733} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{734} &:= \frac{(111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6734} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66734} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666734} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{735} &:= \frac{(111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6735} := \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66735} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666735} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{736} &:= \frac{1111 + 1111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 2222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 3333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 4444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 5555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 6666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 7777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 8888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 9999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{370736} &:= \frac{1111111 + 1111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 2222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 3333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 4444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 5555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 6666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 7777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 8888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 9999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{370370736} &:= \frac{111111111 + 1111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{222222222 + 2222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{333333333 + 3333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444444 + 4444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{555555555 + 5555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{666666666 + 6666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777777 + 7777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{888888888 + 8888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{999999999 + 9999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{370370370736} &:= \frac{11111111111 + 1111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{22222222222 + 2222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{33333333333 + 3333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444444444 + 4444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{55555555555 + 5555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{66666666666 + 6666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777777777 + 7777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888888888 + 8888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999999999 + 9999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 737 &:= \frac{1111 + 1111 - 11}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 2222 - 22}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 3333 - 33}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 4444 - 44}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 5555 - 55}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 6666 - 66}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 7777 - 77}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 8888 - 88}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 9999 - 99}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 370737 &:= \frac{1111111 + 1111 - 11}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 2222 - 22}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 3333 - 33}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 4444 - 44}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 5555 - 55}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 6666 - 66}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 7777 - 77}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 8888 - 88}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 9999 - 99}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 370370737 &:= \frac{1111111111 + 1111 - 11}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222222 + 2222 - 22}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333333 + 3333 - 33}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 + 4444 - 44}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555555 + 5555 - 55}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666666 + 6666 - 66}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 + 7777 - 77}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888888 + 8888 - 88}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999999 + 9999 - 99}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 370370370737 &:= \frac{1111111111111 + 1111 - 11}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222222222 + 2222 - 22}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333333333 + 3333 - 33}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444444 + 4444 - 44}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555555555 + 5555 - 55}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666666666 + 6666 - 66}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777777 + 7777 - 77}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888888888 + 8888 - 88}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999999999 + 9999 - 99}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 738 &:= \frac{(1111 - 1) \times (1 + 1) - (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2) \times (2 + 2) - (2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3) \times (3 + 3) - (3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 4) \times (4 + 4) - (4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5) \times (5 + 5) - (5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6) \times (6 + 6) - (6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7) \times (7 + 7) - (7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8) \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9) \times (9 + 9) - (9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 740738 &:= \frac{(1111111 - 1) \times (1 + 1) - (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222 - 2) \times (2 + 2) - (2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333 - 3) \times (3 + 3) - (3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444 - 4) \times (4 + 4) - (4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555 - 5) \times (5 + 5) - (5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666 - 6) \times (6 + 6) - (6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777 - 7) \times (7 + 7) - (7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888 - 8) \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999 - 9) \times (9 + 9) - (9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 740740738 &:= \frac{(1111111111 - 1) \times (1 + 1) - (1 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222222 - 2) \times (2 + 2) - (2 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333333 - 3) \times (3 + 3) - (3 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444444 - 4) \times (4 + 4) - (4 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555555 - 5) \times (5 + 5) - (5 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666666 - 6) \times (6 + 6) - (6 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777777 - 7) \times (7 + 7) - (7 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888888 - 8) \times (8 + 8) - (8 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999999 - 9) \times (9 + 9) - (9 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{740740740738} &:= \frac{(1111111111111 - 1) \times (1+1) - (1+1+1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222222222 - 2) \times (2+2) - (2+2+2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333333333 - 3) \times (3+3) - (3+3+3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444444444444 - 4) \times (4+4) - (4+4+4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555555555 - 5) \times (5+5) - (5+5+5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666666666 - 6) \times (6+6) - (6+6+6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777777777777 - 7) \times (7+7) - (7+7+7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888888888 - 8) \times (8+8) - (8+8+8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999999999 - 9) \times (9+9) - (9+9+9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{739} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1) \times (1+1) - (1+1+1) \times 1}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2) \times (2+2) - (2+2+2) \times 2}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3) \times (3+3) - (3+3+3) \times 3}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 4) \times (4+4) - (4+4+4) \times 4}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5) \times (5+5) - (5+5+5) \times 5}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6) \times (6+6) - (6+6+6) \times 6}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 7) \times (7+7) - (7+7+7) \times 7}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8) \times (8+8) - (8+8+8) \times 8}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9) \times (9+9) - (9+9+9) \times 9}{(9+9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{740739} &:= \frac{(1111111 - 1) \times (1+1) - (1+1+1) \times 1}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222 - 2) \times (2+2) - (2+2+2) \times 2}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333 - 3) \times (3+3) - (3+3+3) \times 3}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444444 - 4) \times (4+4) - (4+4+4) \times 4}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555 - 5) \times (5+5) - (5+5+5) \times 5}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666 - 6) \times (6+6) - (6+6+6) \times 6}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777777 - 7) \times (7+7) - (7+7+7) \times 7}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888 - 8) \times (8+8) - (8+8+8) \times 8}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999 - 9) \times (9+9) - (9+9+9) \times 9}{(9+9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{740740739} &:= \frac{(11111111111 - 1) \times (1+1) - (1+1+1) \times 1}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222222 - 2) \times (2+2) - (2+2+2) \times 2}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333333 - 3) \times (3+3) - (3+3+3) \times 3}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444444444 - 4) \times (4+4) - (4+4+4) \times 4}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555555 - 5) \times (5+5) - (5+5+5) \times 5}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666666 - 6) \times (6+6) - (6+6+6) \times 6}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777777777 - 7) \times (7+7) - (7+7+7) \times 7}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888888 - 8) \times (8+8) - (8+8+8) \times 8}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999999 - 9) \times (9+9) - (9+9+9) \times 9}{(9+9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{740740740739} &:= \frac{(1111111111111 - 1) \times (1+1) - (1+1+1) \times 1}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222222222 - 2) \times (2+2) - (2+2+2) \times 2}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333333333 - 3) \times (3+3) - (3+3+3) \times 3}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444444444444 - 4) \times (4+4) - (4+4+4) \times 4}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555555555 - 5) \times (5+5) - (5+5+5) \times 5}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666666666 - 6) \times (6+6) - (6+6+6) \times 6}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777777777777 - 7) \times (7+7) - (7+7+7) \times 7}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888888888 - 8) \times (8+8) - (8+8+8) \times 8}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999999999 - 9) \times (9+9) - (9+9+9) \times 9}{(9+9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{740} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{740740} &:= \frac{(1111111 - 1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222 - 2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333 - 3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444444 - 4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555 - 5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666 - 6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777777 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{740740740} &:= \frac{(1111111111 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222222 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333333 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444444 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555555 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666666 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777777 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888888 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999999 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{740740740740} &:= \frac{(1111111111111 - 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222222222 - 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333333333 - 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444444444 - 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555555555 - 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666666666 - 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777777777 - 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888888888 - 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999999999 - 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{741} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1) \times (1 + 1) + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2) \times (2 + 2) + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3) \times (3 + 3) + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 4) \times (4 + 4) + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5) \times (5 + 5) + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6) \times (6 + 6) + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7) \times (7 + 7) + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8) \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9) \times (9 + 9) + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{740741} &:= \frac{(1111111 - 1) \times (1 + 1) + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222 - 2) \times (2 + 2) + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333 - 3) \times (3 + 3) + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444 - 4) \times (4 + 4) + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555 - 5) \times (5 + 5) + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666 - 6) \times (6 + 6) + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777 - 7) \times (7 + 7) + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888 - 8) \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999 - 9) \times (9 + 9) + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{740740741} &:= \frac{(1111111111 - 1) \times (1 + 1) + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222222 - 2) \times (2 + 2) + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333333 - 3) \times (3 + 3) + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444444 - 4) \times (4 + 4) + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555555 - 5) \times (5 + 5) + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666666 - 6) \times (6 + 6) + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777777 - 7) \times (7 + 7) + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888888 - 8) \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999999 - 9) \times (9 + 9) + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{740740740741} &:= \frac{(1111111111111 - 1) \times (1 + 1) + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222222222 - 2) \times (2 + 2) + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333333333 - 3) \times (3 + 3) + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444444444 - 4) \times (4 + 4) + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555555555 - 5) \times (5 + 5) + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666666666 - 6) \times (6 + 6) + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777777777 - 7) \times (7 + 7) + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888888888 - 8) \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999999999 - 9) \times (9 + 9) + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 742 &:= \frac{(1111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 740742 &:= \frac{(1111111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 740740742 &:= \frac{(111111111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 740740740742 &:= \frac{(11111111111 + 1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222222222 + 2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333333333 + 3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444444444 + 4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555555555 + 5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666666666 + 6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777777777 + 7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888888888 + 8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999999999 + 9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 743 &:= \frac{(111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + 11 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + 22 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + 33 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6743 &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + 11 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + 22 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + 33 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 66743 &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + 11 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + 22 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + 33 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666743} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + 11 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + 22 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + 33 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + 44 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + 55 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + 66 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + 77 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + 88 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + 99 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{744} &:= \frac{1111 + 1111 + 11 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 2222 + 22 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 3333 + 33 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 4444 + 44 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 5555 + 55 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 6666 + 66 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 7777 + 77 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 8888 + 88 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 9999 + 99 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7444} &:= \frac{11111 + 11111 + 111 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22222 + 222 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33333 + 333 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44444 + 444 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55555 + 555 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66666 + 666 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77777 + 777 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88888 + 888 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99999 + 999 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{74444} &:= \frac{111111 + 111111 + 1111 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 222222 + 2222 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 333333 + 3333 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444444 + 4444 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 555555 + 5555 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 666666 + 6666 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777777 + 7777 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 888888 + 8888 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 999999 + 9999 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{744444} &:= \frac{1111111 + 1111111 + 11111 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 2222222 + 22222 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 3333333 + 33333 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 4444444 + 44444 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 5555555 + 55555 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 6666666 + 66666 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 7777777 + 77777 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 8888888 + 88888 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 9999999 + 99999 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{745} &:= \frac{1111 + 1111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 2222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 3333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 4444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 5555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 6666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 7777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 8888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 9999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{7445} := \frac{11111 + 11111 + 111 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22222 + 222 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33333 + 333 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{44444 + 44444 + 444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55555 + 555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66666 + 666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77777 + 777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88888 + 888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99999 + 999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{74445} &:= \frac{111111 + 111111 + 1111 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 222222 + 2222 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 333333 + 3333 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444444 + 4444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 555555 + 5555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 666666 + 6666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777777 + 7777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 888888 + 8888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 999999 + 9999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{744445} &:= \frac{1111111 + 1111111 + 11111 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 2222222 + 22222 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 3333333 + 33333 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 4444444 + 44444 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 5555555 + 55555 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 6666666 + 66666 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 7777777 + 77777 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 8888888 + 88888 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 9999999 + 99999 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{746} &:= \frac{1111 + 1111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 2222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 3333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 4444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 5555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 6666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 7777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 8888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 9999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7446} &:= \frac{11111 + 11111 + 111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22222 + 222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33333 + 333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44444 + 444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55555 + 555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66666 + 666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77777 + 777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88888 + 888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99999 + 999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{74446} &:= \frac{111111 + 111111 + 1111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 222222 + 2222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 333333 + 3333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444444 + 4444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 555555 + 5555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 666666 + 6666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777777 + 7777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 888888 + 8888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 999999 + 9999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{744446} &:= \frac{1111111 + 1111111 + 11111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 2222222 + 22222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 3333333 + 33333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 4444444 + 44444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 5555555 + 55555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 6666666 + 66666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 7777777 + 77777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 8888888 + 88888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 9999999 + 99999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 747 &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (11+11+1) - (11+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (22+22+2) - (22+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (33+33+3) - (33+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (44+44+4) - (44+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (55+55+5) - (55+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (66+66+6) - (66+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (77+77+7) - (77+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (88+88+8) - (88+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (99+99+9) - (99+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7647 &:= \frac{(111+111+111) \times (11+11+1) - (11+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222+222) \times (22+22+2) - (22+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333+333) \times (33+33+3) - (33+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444+444) \times (44+44+4) - (44+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555+555) \times (55+55+5) - (55+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666+666) \times (66+66+6) - (66+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777+777) \times (77+77+7) - (77+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888+888) \times (88+88+8) - (88+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999+999) \times (99+99+9) - (99+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 76647 &:= \frac{(1111+1111+1111) \times (11+11+1) - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222+2222) \times (22+22+2) - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333+3333) \times (33+33+3) - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4444+4444) \times (44+44+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555+5555) \times (55+55+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666+6666) \times (66+66+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7777+7777) \times (77+77+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8888+8888) \times (88+88+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9999+9999) \times (99+99+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 766647 &:= \frac{(11111+11111+11111) \times (11+11+1) - (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22222+22222) \times (22+22+2) - (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33333+33333) \times (33+33+3) - (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+44444+44444) \times (44+44+4) - (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55555+55555) \times (55+55+5) - (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66666+66666) \times (66+66+6) - (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+77777+77777) \times (77+77+7) - (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88888+88888) \times (88+88+8) - (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99999+99999) \times (99+99+9) - (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 748 &:= \frac{(1111+11) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+44) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+77) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+88) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+99) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 740748 &:= \frac{(1111111+11) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222+22) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333+33) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444+44) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555+55) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666+66) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777+77) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888+88) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999+99) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7407407488 &:= \frac{(111111111+11) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222222+22) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333333+33) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444444+44) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555555+55) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666666+66) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777777+77) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888888+88) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999999+99) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{740740740748} &:= \frac{(111111111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{749} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{740749} &:= \frac{(1111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7407407489} &:= \frac{(1111111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{740740740749} &:= \frac{(111111111111 + 11) \times (1 + 1) + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222222222 + 22) \times (2 + 2) + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333333333 + 33) \times (3 + 3) + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444444444 + 44) \times (4 + 4) + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555555555 + 55) \times (5 + 5) + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666666666 + 66) \times (6 + 6) + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777777777 + 77) \times (7 + 7) + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888888888 + 88) \times (8 + 8) + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999999999 + 99) \times (9 + 9) + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{750} &:= \frac{(1111 - 111) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(2222 - 222) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(3333 - 333) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 444) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(5555 - 555) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(6666 - 666) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 777) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(8888 - 888) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(9999 - 999) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7500} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(22222 - 2222) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(33333 - 3333) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(55555 - 5555) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(66666 - 6666) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77777 - 7777) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(88888 - 8888) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(99999 - 9999) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{75000} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(222222 - 22222) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(333333 - 33333) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(555555 - 55555) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(666666 - 66666) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(888888 - 88888) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(999999 - 99999) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{750000} &:= \frac{(1111111 - 111111) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(2222222 - 222222) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(3333333 - 333333) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444 - 444444) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(5555555 - 555555) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(6666666 - 666666) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777 - 777777) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(8888888 - 888888) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(9999999 - 999999) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{751} &:= \frac{1111 + 1111 + 11 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 2222 + 22 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 3333 + 33 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 + 4444 + 44 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 5555 + 55 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 6666 + 66 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 7777 + 77 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 8888 + 88 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 9999 + 99 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7451} &:= \frac{11111 + 11111 + 111 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22222 + 222 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33333 + 333 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44444 + 444 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55555 + 555 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66666 + 666 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77777 + 777 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88888 + 888 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99999 + 999 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{74451} &:= \frac{111111 + 111111 + 1111 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 222222 + 2222 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 333333 + 3333 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444444 + 4444 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 555555 + 5555 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 666666 + 6666 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777777 + 7777 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 888888 + 8888 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 999999 + 9999 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{744451} &:= \frac{1111111 + 1111111 + 11111 + 11 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 2222222 + 22222 + 22 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 3333333 + 33333 + 33 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 4444444 + 44444 + 44 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 5555555 + 55555 + 55 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 6666666 + 66666 + 66 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 7777777 + 77777 + 77 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 8888888 + 88888 + 88 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 9999999 + 99999 + 99 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{752} := \frac{1111 + 1111 + 11 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222 + 2222 + 22 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333 + 3333 + 33 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 + 4444 + 44 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555 + 5555 + 55 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666 + 6666 + 66 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 + 7777 + 77 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888 + 8888 + 88 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999 + 9999 + 99 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7452} &:= \frac{11111 + 11111 + 111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22222 + 222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33333 + 333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44444 + 444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55555 + 555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66666 + 666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77777 + 777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88888 + 888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99999 + 999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{74452} &:= \frac{111111 + 111111 + 1111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 222222 + 2222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 333333 + 3333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 444444 + 4444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 555555 + 5555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 666666 + 6666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 777777 + 7777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 888888 + 8888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 999999 + 9999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{744452} &:= \frac{1111111 + 1111111 + 11111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1 + 1 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 2222222 + 22222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2 + 2 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 3333333 + 33333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3 + 3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 4444444 + 44444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4 + 4 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 5555555 + 55555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5 + 5 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 6666666 + 66666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6 + 6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 7777777 + 77777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7 + 7 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 8888888 + 88888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8 + 8 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 9999999 + 99999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9 + 9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{753} &:= \frac{1111 \times (11 + 1) + 111 \times (1 + 1)}{(11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{2222 \times (22 + 2) + 222 \times (2 + 2)}{(22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{3333 \times (33 + 3) + 333 \times (3 + 3)}{(33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (44 + 4) + 444 \times (4 + 4)}{(44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{5555 \times (55 + 5) + 555 \times (5 + 5)}{(55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{6666 \times (66 + 6) + 666 \times (6 + 6)}{(66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (77 + 7) + 777 \times (7 + 7)}{(77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{8888 \times (88 + 8) + 888 \times (8 + 8)}{(88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{9999 \times (99 + 9) + 999 \times (9 + 9)}{(99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{740753} &:= \frac{1111111 \times (11 + 1) + 111 \times (1 + 1)}{(11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{2222222 \times (22 + 2) + 222 \times (2 + 2)}{(22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{3333333 \times (33 + 3) + 333 \times (3 + 3)}{(33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 \times (44 + 4) + 444 \times (4 + 4)}{(44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{5555555 \times (55 + 5) + 555 \times (5 + 5)}{(55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{6666666 \times (66 + 6) + 666 \times (6 + 6)}{(66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 \times (77 + 7) + 777 \times (7 + 7)}{(77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{8888888 \times (88 + 8) + 888 \times (8 + 8)}{(88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{9999999 \times (99 + 9) + 999 \times (9 + 9)}{(99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{740740753} &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (11 + 1) + 111 \times (1 + 1)}{(11 - 1 - 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{2222222222 \times (22 + 2) + 222 \times (2 + 2)}{(22 - 2 - 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{3333333333 \times (33 + 3) + 333 \times (3 + 3)}{(33 - 3 - 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (44 + 4) + 444 \times (4 + 4)}{(44 - 4 - 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{5555555555 \times (55 + 5) + 555 \times (5 + 5)}{(55 - 5 - 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{6666666666 \times (66 + 6) + 666 \times (6 + 6)}{(66 - 6 - 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (77 + 7) + 777 \times (7 + 7)}{(77 - 7 - 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{8888888888 \times (88 + 8) + 888 \times (8 + 8)}{(88 - 8 - 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{9999999999 \times (99 + 9) + 999 \times (9 + 9)}{(99 - 9 - 9) \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{740740740753} &:= \frac{1111111111111 \times (11+1) + 111 \times (1+1)}{(11-1-1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{2222222222222 \times (22+2) + 222 \times (2+2)}{(22-2-2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{3333333333333 \times (33+3) + 333 \times (3+3)}{(33-3-3) \times (3+3)} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444444444 \times (44+4) + 444 \times (4+4)}{(44-4-4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{5555555555555 \times (55+5) + 555 \times (5+5)}{(55-5-5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{6666666666666 \times (66+6) + 666 \times (6+6)}{(66-6-6) \times (6+6)} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777777777 \times (77+7) + 777 \times (7+7)}{(77-7-7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{8888888888888 \times (88+8) + 888 \times (8+8)}{(88-8-8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{9999999999999 \times (99+9) + 999 \times (9+9)}{(99-9-9) \times (9+9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{754} &:= \frac{(1111+11+11-1-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22+22-2-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33+33-3-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444+44+44-4-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55+55-5-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66+66-6-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777+77+77-7-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+88+88-8-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+99+99-9-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7554} &:= \frac{(11111+111+111-1-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+222+222-2-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+333+333-3-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444+444+444-4-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+555+555-5-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+666+666-6-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777+777+777-7-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+888+888-8-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+999+999-9-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{75554} &:= \frac{(111111+1111+1111-1-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2222+2222-2-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3333+3333-3-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444+4444+4444-4-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5555+5555-5-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6666+6666-6-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777+7777+7777-7-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8888+8888-8-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9999+9999-9-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{755554} &:= \frac{(1111111+11111+11111-1-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222+22222+22222-2-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333+33333+33333-3-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444444+44444+44444-4-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555+55555+55555-5-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666+66666+66666-6-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777777+77777+77777-7-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888+88888+88888-8-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999+99999+99999-9-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{755} &:= \frac{(11+11-1) \times (11+1) \times (1+1+1) - 1 \times 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22-2) \times (22+2) \times (2+2+2) - 2 \times 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33-3) \times (33+3) \times (3+3+3) - 3 \times 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44-4) \times (44+4) \times (4+4+4) - 4 \times 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55-5) \times (55+5) \times (5+5+5) - 5 \times 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66-6) \times (66+6) \times (6+6+6) - 6 \times 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77-7) \times (77+7) \times (7+7+7) - 7 \times 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88-8) \times (88+8) \times (8+8+8) - 8 \times 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99-9) \times (99+9) \times (9+9+9) - 9 \times 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7955} &:= \frac{(111+111-1) \times (11+1) \times (1+1+1) - 1 \times 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222-2) \times (22+2) \times (2+2+2) - 2 \times 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333-3) \times (33+3) \times (3+3+3) - 3 \times 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444+444-4) \times (44+4) \times (4+4+4) - 4 \times 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555-5) \times (55+5) \times (5+5+5) - 5 \times 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666-6) \times (66+6) \times (6+6+6) - 6 \times 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777+777-7) \times (77+7) \times (7+7+7) - 7 \times 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888-8) \times (88+8) \times (8+8+8) - 8 \times 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999-9) \times (99+9) \times (9+9+9) - 9 \times 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{79955} &:= \frac{(1111+1111-1) \times (11+1) \times (1+1+1) - 1 \times 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222-2) \times (22+2) \times (2+2+2) - 2 \times 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333-3) \times (33+3) \times (3+3+3) - 3 \times 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4444-4) \times (44+4) \times (4+4+4) - 4 \times 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555-5) \times (55+5) \times (5+5+5) - 5 \times 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666-6) \times (66+6) \times (6+6+6) - 6 \times 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7777-7) \times (77+7) \times (7+7+7) - 7 \times 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8888-8) \times (88+8) \times (8+8+8) - 8 \times 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9999-9) \times (99+9) \times (9+9+9) - 9 \times 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{799955} &:= \frac{(11111+11111-1) \times (11+1) \times (1+1+1) - 1 \times 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22222-2) \times (22+2) \times (2+2+2) - 2 \times 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33333-3) \times (33+3) \times (3+3+3) - 3 \times 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+44444-4) \times (44+4) \times (4+4+4) - 4 \times 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55555-5) \times (55+5) \times (5+5+5) - 5 \times 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66666-6) \times (66+6) \times (6+6+6) - 6 \times 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+77777-7) \times (77+7) \times (7+7+7) - 7 \times 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88888-8) \times (88+8) \times (8+8+8) - 8 \times 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99999-9) \times (99+9) \times (9+9+9) - 9 \times 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{756} &:= \frac{(11+11-1) \times (11+1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22-2) \times (22+2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33-3) \times (33+3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44-4) \times (44+4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55-5) \times (55+5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66-6) \times (66+6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77-7) \times (77+7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88-8) \times (88+8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99-9) \times (99+9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7956} &:= \frac{(111+111-1) \times (11+1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222-2) \times (22+2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333-3) \times (33+3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444-4) \times (44+4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555-5) \times (55+5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666-6) \times (66+6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777-7) \times (77+7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888-8) \times (88+8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999-9) \times (99+9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{79956} &:= \frac{(1111+1111-1) \times (11+1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222-2) \times (22+2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333-3) \times (33+3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4444-4) \times (44+4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555-5) \times (55+5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666-6) \times (66+6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7777-7) \times (77+7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8888-8) \times (88+8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9999-9) \times (99+9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{799956} &:= \frac{(11111+11111-1) \times (11+1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22222-2) \times (22+2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33333-3) \times (33+3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+44444-4) \times (44+4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55555-5) \times (55+5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66666-6) \times (66+6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+77777-7) \times (77+7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88888-8) \times (88+8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99999-9) \times (99+9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{757} := \frac{(11-1-1) \times 111 - (11+11) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times 222 - (22+22) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times 333 - (33+33) \times 33}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times 444 - (44+44) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times 555 - (55+55) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times 666 - (66+66) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times 777 - (77+77) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times 888 - (88+88) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times 999 - (99+99) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9757} &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times 1111 - (11+11) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times 2222 - (22+22) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times 3333 - (33+33) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times 4444 - (44+44) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times 5555 - (55+55) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times 6666 - (66+66) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times 7777 - (77+77) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times 8888 - (88+88) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times 9999 - (99+99) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99757} &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times 11111 - (11+11) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times 22222 - (22+22) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times 33333 - (33+33) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times 44444 - (44+44) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times 55555 - (55+55) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times 66666 - (66+66) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times 77777 - (77+77) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times 88888 - (88+88) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times 99999 - (99+99) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999757} &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times 111111 - (11+11) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times 222222 - (22+22) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times 333333 - (33+33) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times 444444 - (44+44) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times 555555 - (55+55) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times 666666 - (66+66) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times 777777 - (77+77) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times 888888 - (88+88) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times 999999 - (99+99) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{758} &:= \frac{(11+11+11) \times (11+11+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+22) \times (22+22+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+33) \times (33+33+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+44) \times (44+44+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+55) \times (55+55+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+66) \times (66+66+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+77) \times (77+77+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+88) \times (88+88+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+99) \times (99+99+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7658} &:= \frac{(111+111+111) \times (11+11+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222+222) \times (22+22+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333+333) \times (33+33+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444+444) \times (44+44+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555+555) \times (55+55+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666+666) \times (66+66+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777+777) \times (77+77+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888+888) \times (88+88+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999+999) \times (99+99+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{76658} &:= \frac{(1111+1111+1111) \times (11+11+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222+2222) \times (22+22+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333+3333) \times (33+33+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4444+4444) \times (44+44+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555+5555) \times (55+55+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666+6666) \times (66+66+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7777+7777) \times (77+77+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8888+8888) \times (88+88+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9999+9999) \times (99+99+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{766658} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 11 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 22 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 33 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 44 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 55 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 66 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 77 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 88 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 99 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{759} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times (11 + 11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times (22 + 22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times (33 + 33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times (44 + 44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times (55 + 55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times (66 + 66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 99 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7659} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 111) \times (11 + 11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222) \times (22 + 22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333) \times (33 + 33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444) \times (44 + 44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555) \times (55 + 55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666) \times (66 + 66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777) \times (77 + 77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888) \times (88 + 88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999) \times (99 + 99 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{76659} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111 + 1111) \times (11 + 11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222 + 2222) \times (22 + 22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333 + 3333) \times (33 + 33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444 + 4444) \times (44 + 44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555 + 5555) \times (55 + 55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666 + 6666) \times (66 + 66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 7777) \times (77 + 77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 8888) \times (88 + 88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 9999) \times (99 + 99 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{766659} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 11 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 22 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 33 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 44 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 55 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 66 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 77 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 88 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 99 + 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{760} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times (11 + 11 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times (22 + 22 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times (33 + 33 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times (44 + 44 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times (55 + 55 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times (66 + 66 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 77 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 88 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 99 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7660} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 111) \times (11 + 11 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222) \times (22 + 22 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333) \times (33 + 33 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444) \times (44 + 44 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555) \times (55 + 55 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666) \times (66 + 66 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777) \times (77 + 77 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888) \times (88 + 88 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999) \times (99 + 99 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{76660} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111 + 1111) \times (11 + 11 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222 + 2222) \times (22 + 22 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333 + 3333) \times (33 + 33 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444 + 4444) \times (44 + 44 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555 + 5555) \times (55 + 55 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666 + 6666) \times (66 + 66 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 7777) \times (77 + 77 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 8888) \times (88 + 88 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 9999) \times (99 + 99 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{766660} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 11 + 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 22 + 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 33 + 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 44 + 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 55 + 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 66 + 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 77 + 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 88 + 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 99 + 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{761} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11) \times (11 + 11 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22) \times (22 + 22 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33) \times (33 + 33 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44) \times (44 + 44 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55) \times (55 + 55 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66) \times (66 + 66 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 77 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 88 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 99 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7661} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 111) \times (11 + 11 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222) \times (22 + 22 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333) \times (33 + 33 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444) \times (44 + 44 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555) \times (55 + 55 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666) \times (66 + 66 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777) \times (77 + 77 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888) \times (88 + 88 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999) \times (99 + 99 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{76661} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111 + 1111) \times (11 + 11 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222 + 2222) \times (22 + 22 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333 + 3333) \times (33 + 33 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444 + 4444) \times (44 + 44 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555 + 5555) \times (55 + 55 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666 + 6666) \times (66 + 66 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 7777) \times (77 + 77 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 8888) \times (88 + 88 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 9999) \times (99 + 99 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{766661} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 11111) \times (11 + 11 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 22222) \times (22 + 22 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 33333) \times (33 + 33 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 44444) \times (44 + 44 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 55555) \times (55 + 55 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 66666) \times (66 + 66 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 77777) \times (77 + 77 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 88888) \times (88 + 88 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 99999) \times (99 + 99 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{762} &:= \frac{(111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777-7-7) \times (77-7-7-7-7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888-8-8) \times (88-8-8-8-8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999-9-9) \times (99-9-9-9-9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7762} &:= \frac{(1111-1-1) \times (11-1-1-1-1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222-2-2) \times (22-2-2-2-2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333-3-3) \times (33-3-3-3-3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-4-4) \times (44-4-4-4-4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555-5-5) \times (55-5-5-5-5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666-6-6) \times (66-6-6-6-6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-7-7) \times (77-7-7-7-7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888-8-8) \times (88-8-8-8-8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999-9-9) \times (99-9-9-9-9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{77762} &:= \frac{(11111-1-1) \times (11-1-1-1-1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222-2-2) \times (22-2-2-2-2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333-3-3) \times (33-3-3-3-3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-4-4) \times (44-4-4-4-4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555-5-5) \times (55-5-5-5-5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666-6-6) \times (66-6-6-6-6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-7-7) \times (77-7-7-7-7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888-8-8) \times (88-8-8-8-8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999-9-9) \times (99-9-9-9-9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{777762} &:= \frac{(111111-1-1) \times (11-1-1-1-1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222-2-2) \times (22-2-2-2-2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333-3-3) \times (33-3-3-3-3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444-4-4) \times (44-4-4-4-4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555-5-5) \times (55-5-5-5-5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666-6-6) \times (66-6-6-6-6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777-7-7) \times (77-7-7-7-7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888-8-8) \times (88-8-8-8-8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999-9-9) \times (99-9-9-9-9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{763} &:= \frac{(111-1-1) \times (11+1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2-2) \times (22+2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3-3) \times (33+3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-4-4) \times (44+4+4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5-5) \times (55+5+5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6-6) \times (66+6+6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7-7) \times (77+7+7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8-8) \times (88+8+8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9-9) \times (99+9+9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7763} &:= \frac{(1111-1-1) \times (11+1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222-2-2) \times (22+2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333-3-3) \times (33+3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-4-4) \times (44+4+4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555-5-5) \times (55+5+5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666-6-6) \times (66+6+6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-7-7) \times (77+7+7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888-8-8) \times (88+8+8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999-9-9) \times (99+9+9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{77763} &:= \frac{(11111-1-1) \times (11+1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222-2-2) \times (22+2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333-3-3) \times (33+3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-4-4) \times (44+4+4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555-5-5) \times (55+5+5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666-6-6) \times (66+6+6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-7-7) \times (77+7+7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888-8-8) \times (88+8+8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999-9-9) \times (99+9+9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{777763} := \frac{(111111-1-1) \times (11+1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222-2-2) \times (22+2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333-3-3) \times (33+3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

► **764** := $\frac{(111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

7764 := $\frac{(1111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

77764 := $\frac{(11111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

777764 := $\frac{(111111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

► **765** := $\frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 111 - (11 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 222 - (22 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 333 - (33 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 444 - (44 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 555 - (55 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 666 - (66 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 777 - (77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 888 - (88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 999 - (99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

7765 := $\frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 1111 - (11 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 2222 - (22 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 3333 - (33 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 4444 - (44 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 5555 - (55 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 6666 - (66 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 7777 - (77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 8888 - (88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 9999 - (99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{77765} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times 11111 - (11+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times 22222 - (22+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times 33333 - (33+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times 44444 - (44+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times 55555 - (55+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times 66666 - (66+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times 77777 - (77+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times 88888 - (88+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times 99999 - (99+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{777765} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times 111111 - (11+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times 222222 - (22+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times 333333 - (33+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times 444444 - (44+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times 555555 - (55+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times 666666 - (66+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times 777777 - (77+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times 888888 - (88+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times 999999 - (99+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{766} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 999 - 99 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9766} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 999 - 99 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{99766} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 999 - 99 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{999766} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 999 - 99 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{767} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 111 - 11 \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 222 - 22 \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 333 - 33 \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 444 - 44 \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 555 - 55 \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 666 - 66 \times 66}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 777 - 77 \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 888 - 88 \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 999 - 99 \times 99}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7667} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111 - 111 \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222 - 222 \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333 - 333 \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444 - 444 \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555 - 555 \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666 - 666 \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777 - 777 \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888 - 888 \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999 - 999 \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{76667} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 11111 - 1111 \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 22222 - 2222 \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 33333 - 3333 \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 44444 - 4444 \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 55555 - 5555 \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 66666 - 6666 \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 77777 - 7777 \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 88888 - 8888 \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 99999 - 9999 \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{766667} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 111111 - 11111 \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 222222 - 22222 \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 333333 - 33333 \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 444444 - 44444 \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 555555 - 55555 \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 666666 - 66666 \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 777777 - 77777 \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 888888 - 88888 \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 999999 - 99999 \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{768} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9768} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99768} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{999768} := \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 333 - 33 + 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 769 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7769 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (1111 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (2222 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (3333 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (4444 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (5555 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (6666 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (7777 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (8888 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (9999 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 77769 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11111 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22222 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33333 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44444 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55555 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66666 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77777 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88888 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99999 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 777769 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111111 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222222 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333333 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444444 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555555 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666666 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777777 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888888 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999999 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 770 &:= \frac{(11 + 11 - 1) \times (111 - 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 - 2) \times (222 - 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 - 3) \times (333 - 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 - 4) \times (444 - 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 - 5) \times (555 - 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 - 6) \times (666 - 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 - 7) \times (777 - 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 - 8) \times (888 - 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 - 9) \times (999 - 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7770 &:= \frac{(11 + 11 - 1) \times (1111 - 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22 - 2) \times (2222 - 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33 - 3) \times (3333 - 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 - 4) \times (4444 - 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55 - 5) \times (5555 - 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66 - 6) \times (6666 - 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 - 7) \times (7777 - 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88 - 8) \times (8888 - 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99 - 9) \times (9999 - 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 77770 &:= \frac{(11+11-1) \times (11111-1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+22-2) \times (22222-2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+33-3) \times (33333-3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44-4) \times (44444-4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+55-5) \times (55555-5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+66-6) \times (66666-6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77-7) \times (77777-7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+88-8) \times (88888-8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+99-9) \times (99999-9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 777770 &:= \frac{(11+11-1) \times (111111-1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+22-2) \times (222222-2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+33-3) \times (333333-3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+44-4) \times (444444-4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+55-5) \times (555555-5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+66-6) \times (666666-6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+77-7) \times (777777-7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+88-8) \times (888888-8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+99-9) \times (999999-9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 771 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (111-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (222-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (333-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (444-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (555-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (666-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (777-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (888-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (999-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7771 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (1111-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (2222-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (3333-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (4444-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (5555-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (6666-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (7777-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (8888-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (9999-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 77771 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (11111-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (22222-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (33333-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (44444-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (55555-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (66666-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (77777-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (88888-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (99999-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 777771 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (111111-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (222222-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (333333-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (444444-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (555555-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (666666-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (777777-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (888888-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (999999-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 772 := \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (111-1) + (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (222-2) + (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (333-3) + (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (444-4) + (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (555-5) + (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (666-6) + (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (777-7) + (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (888-8) + (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (999-9) + (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7772} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (1111-1) + (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (2222-2) + (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (3333-3) + (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (4444-4) + (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (5555-5) + (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (6666-6) + (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (7777-7) + (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (8888-8) + (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (9999-9) + (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{77772} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (11111-1) + (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (22222-2) + (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (33333-3) + (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (44444-4) + (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (55555-5) + (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (66666-6) + (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (77777-7) + (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (88888-8) + (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (99999-9) + (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{777772} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (111111-1) + (1+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (222222-2) + (2+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (333333-3) + (3+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (444444-4) + (4+4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (555555-5) + (5+5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (666666-6) + (6+6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (777777-7) + (7+7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (888888-8) + (8+8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (999999-9) + (9+9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{773} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (111+1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (222+2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (333+3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (444+4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (555+5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (666+6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (777+7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (888+8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (999+9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7773} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (1111+1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (2222+2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (3333+3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (4444+4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (5555+5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (6666+6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (7777+7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (8888+8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (9999+9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{77773} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (11111+1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (22222+2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (33333+3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (44444+4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (55555+5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (66666+6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (77777+7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (88888+8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (99999+9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 777773 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (111111+1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (222222+2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (333333+3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (444444+4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (555555+5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (666666+6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (777777+7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (888888+8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (999999+9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 774 &:= \frac{1111+1111+111-11}{1+1+1} = \frac{2222+2222+222-22}{2+2+2} = \frac{3333+3333+333-33}{3+3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444+4444+444-44}{4+4+4} = \frac{5555+5555+555-55}{5+5+5} = \frac{6666+6666+666-66}{6+6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777+7777+777-77}{7+7+7} = \frac{8888+8888+888-88}{8+8+8} = \frac{9999+9999+999-99}{9+9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7774 &:= \frac{11111+11111+1111-11}{1+1+1} = \frac{22222+22222+2222-22}{2+2+2} = \frac{33333+33333+3333-33}{3+3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444+44444+4444-44}{4+4+4} = \frac{55555+55555+5555-55}{5+5+5} = \frac{66666+66666+6666-66}{6+6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777+77777+7777-77}{7+7+7} = \frac{88888+88888+8888-88}{8+8+8} = \frac{99999+99999+9999-99}{9+9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 77774 &:= \frac{111111+111111+11111-11}{1+1+1} = \frac{222222+222222+22222-22}{2+2+2} = \frac{333333+333333+33333-33}{3+3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444+444444+44444-44}{4+4+4} = \frac{555555+555555+55555-55}{5+5+5} = \frac{666666+666666+66666-66}{6+6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777+777777+77777-77}{7+7+7} = \frac{888888+888888+88888-88}{8+8+8} = \frac{999999+999999+99999-99}{9+9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 777774 &:= \frac{1111111+1111111+111111-11}{1+1+1} = \frac{2222222+2222222+222222-22}{2+2+2} = \frac{3333333+3333333+333333-33}{3+3+3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444+4444444+444444-44}{4+4+4} = \frac{5555555+5555555+555555-55}{5+5+5} = \frac{6666666+6666666+666666-66}{6+6+6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777+7777777+777777-77}{7+7+7} = \frac{8888888+8888888+888888-88}{8+8+8} = \frac{9999999+9999999+999999-99}{9+9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 775 &:= \frac{1111-111-111-111-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222-222-222-222-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333-333-333-333-3-3-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444-444-444-444-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555-555-555-555-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666-666-666-666-6-6-6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777-777-777-777-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888-888-888-888-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999-999-999-999-9-9-9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 10775 &:= \frac{11111-111-111-111-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222-222-222-222-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333-333-333-333-3-3-3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444-444-444-444-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555-555-555-555-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666-666-666-666-6-6-6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{110775} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1110775} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{776} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7776} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 1111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 2222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 3333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 4444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 5555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 6666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 7777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 8888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 9999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{77776} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{777776} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 111111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 222222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 333333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 444444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 555555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 666666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 777777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 888888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 999999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{777} := \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 333}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times 444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times 555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times 666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times 777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times 888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times 999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7777} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times 1111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times 2222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times 3333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times 4444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times 5555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times 6666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times 7777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times 8888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times 9999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{77777} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times 11111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times 22222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times 33333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times 44444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times 55555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times 66666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times 77777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times 88888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times 99999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{777777} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times 111111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times 222222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times 333333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times 444444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times 555555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times 666666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times 777777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times 888888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times 999999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{778} &:= \frac{1111-111-111-111}{1} = \frac{2222-222-222-222}{2} = \frac{3333-333-333-333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-444-444-444}{4} = \frac{5555-555-555-555}{5} = \frac{6666-666-666-666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-777-777-777}{7} = \frac{8888-888-888-888}{8} = \frac{9999-999-999-999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{10778} &:= \frac{11111-111-111-111}{1} = \frac{22222-222-222-222}{2} = \frac{33333-333-333-333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-444-444-444}{4} = \frac{55555-555-555-555}{5} = \frac{66666-666-666-666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-777-777-777}{7} = \frac{88888-888-888-888}{8} = \frac{99999-999-999-999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{110778} &:= \frac{111111-111-111-111}{1} = \frac{222222-222-222-222}{2} = \frac{333333-333-333-333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444-444-444-444}{4} = \frac{555555-555-555-555}{5} = \frac{666666-666-666-666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-777-777-777}{7} = \frac{888888-888-888-888}{8} = \frac{999999-999-999-999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1110778} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 111 - 111}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 222 - 222}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 333 - 333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 444 - 444}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 555 - 555}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 666 - 666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 777 - 777}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 888 - 888}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 999 - 999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{779} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{10779} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{110779} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1110779} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{780} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{10780} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{110780} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1110780} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{781} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{10781} &:= \frac{11111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{110781} &:= \frac{111111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1110781} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{782} := \frac{(111 + 11) \times 11 + 111 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times 22 + 222 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times 33 + 333 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times 44 + 444 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times 55 + 555 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times 66 + 666 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times 77 + 777 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times 88 + 888 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times 99 + 999 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1782} &:= \frac{(111 + 11) \times 11 + 1111 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times 22 + 2222 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times 33 + 3333 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times 44 + 4444 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times 55 + 5555 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times 66 + 6666 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times 77 + 7777 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times 88 + 8888 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times 99 + 9999 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11782} &:= \frac{(111 + 11) \times 11 + 11111 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times 22 + 22222 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times 33 + 33333 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times 44 + 44444 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times 55 + 55555 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times 66 + 66666 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times 77 + 77777 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times 88 + 88888 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times 99 + 99999 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111782} &:= \frac{(111 + 11) \times 11 + 111111 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times 22 + 222222 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times 33 + 333333 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times 44 + 444444 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times 55 + 555555 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times 66 + 666666 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times 77 + 777777 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times 88 + 888888 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times 99 + 999999 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{783} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7783} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (1111 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (2222 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (3333 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (4444 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (5555 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (6666 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (7777 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (8888 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (9999 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{77783} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11111 + 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22222 + 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33333 + 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44444 + 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55555 + 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66666 + 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77777 + 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88888 + 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99999 + 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 777783 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (111111+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (222222+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (333333+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (444444+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (555555+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (666666+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (777777+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (888888+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (999999+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 784 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (999+9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7784 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (1111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (2222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (3333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (4444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (5555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (6666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (7777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (8888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (9999+9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 77784 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (11111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (22222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (33333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (44444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (55555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (66666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (77777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (88888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (99999+9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 777784 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (111111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (222222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (333333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (444444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (555555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (666666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (777777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (888888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (999999+9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 785 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (111+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (222+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (333+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (444+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (555+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (666+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (777+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (888+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (999+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7785 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (1111+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (2222+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (3333+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (4444+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (5555+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (6666+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (7777+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (8888+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (9999+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{77785} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (11111+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (22222+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (33333+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (44444+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (55555+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (66666+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (77777+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (88888+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (99999+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{777785} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times (111111+1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times (222222+2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times (333333+3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times (444444+4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times (555555+5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times (666666+6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times (777777+7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times (888888+8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times (999999+9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{786} &:= \frac{1111-111-111-111+11-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222-222-222-222+22-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333-333-333-333+33-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-444-444-444+44-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555-555-555-555+55-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666-666-666-666+66-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-777-777-777+77-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888-888-888-888+88-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999-999-999-999+99-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9786} &:= \frac{11111-1111-111-111+11-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2222-222-222+22-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3333-333-333+33-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-4444-444-444+44-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5555-555-555+55-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6666-666-666+66-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-7777-777-777+77-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888-8888-888-888+88-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999-9999-999-999+99-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99786} &:= \frac{111111-11111-111-111+11-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{222222-22222-222-222+22-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{333333-33333-333-333+33-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444-44444-444-444+44-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{555555-55555-555-555+55-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{666666-66666-666-666+66-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-77777-777-777+77-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{888888-88888-888-888+88-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{999999-99999-999-999+99-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999786} &:= \frac{1111111-111111-111-111+11-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222222-222222-222-222+22-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333333-333333-333-333+33-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444-444444-444-444+44-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555555-555555-555-555+55-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666666-666666-666-666+66-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777-777777-777-777+77-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888888-888888-888-888+88-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999999-999999-999-999+99-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{787} := \frac{1111-111-111-111+11-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222-222-222-222+22-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333-333-333-333+33-3-3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9787} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99787} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999787} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{788} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9788} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 666 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 999 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99788} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 666 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 999 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{999788} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 666 + 66 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 999 + 99 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{789} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 11}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 22}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 44}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 55}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 77}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 88}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9789} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 111 + 11}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 222 + 22}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 333 + 33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 444 + 44}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 555 + 55}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 666 + 66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 777 + 77}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 888 + 88}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 999 + 99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{99789} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 111 + 11}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 222 + 22}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 333 + 33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 444 + 44}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 555 + 55}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 666 + 66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 777 + 77}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 888 + 88}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 999 + 99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{999789} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 111 + 11}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 222 + 22}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 333 + 33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 444 + 44}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 555 + 55}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 666 + 66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 777 + 77}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 888 + 88}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 999 + 99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{790} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9790} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99790} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999790} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{791} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7791} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (1111 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (2222 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (3333 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (4444 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (5555 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (6666 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (7777 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (8888 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (9999 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{77791} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11111 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22222 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33333 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44444 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55555 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66666 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77777 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88888 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99999 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{777791} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111111 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222222 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333333 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444444 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555555 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666666 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777777 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888888 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999999 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{792} := \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9792} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99792} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999792} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{793} &:= \frac{(111 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7293} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{72293} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{722293} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{794} &:= \frac{(111 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7294} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{72294} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{722294} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{795} &:= \frac{(111 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{7295} := \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{72295} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{722295} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{796} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 1111 - 11 \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 2222 - 22 \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 3333 - 33 \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 4444 - 44 \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 5555 - 55 \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 6666 - 66 \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 7777 - 77 \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 8888 - 88 \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 9999 - 99 \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{80796} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 111111 - 11 \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 222222 - 22 \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 333333 - 33 \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 444444 - 44 \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 555555 - 55 \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 666666 - 66 \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 777777 - 77 \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 888888 - 88 \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 999999 - 99 \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8080796} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11111111 - 11 \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22222222 - 22 \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33333333 - 33 \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44444444 - 44 \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55555555 - 55 \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66666666 - 66 \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77777777 - 77 \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88888888 - 88 \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99999999 - 99 \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{808080796} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 1111111111 - 11 \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 2222222222 - 22 \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 3333333333 - 33 \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 4444444444 - 44 \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 5555555555 - 55 \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 6666666666 - 66 \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 7777777777 - 77 \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 8888888888 - 88 \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 9999999999 - 99 \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 797 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111 - 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222 - 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333 - 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444 - 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555 - 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666 - 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777 - 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888 - 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999 - 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 80797 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 111111 - 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 222222 - 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 333333 - 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 444444 - 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 555555 - 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 666666 - 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 777777 - 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 888888 - 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 999999 - 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8080797 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 11111111 - 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 22222222 - 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 33333333 - 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 44444444 - 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 55555555 - 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 66666666 - 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 77777777 - 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 88888888 - 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 99999999 - 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 808080797 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111111111 - 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222222222 - 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333333333 - 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444444444 - 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555555555 - 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666666666 - 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777777777 - 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888888888 - 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999999999 - 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 798 &:= \frac{(111+11+11) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+22+22) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+33+33) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+44+44) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+55+55) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+66+66) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+77+77) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+88+88) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+99+99) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6798 &:= \frac{(1111+11+11) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22+22) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33+33) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+44+44) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55+55) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66+66) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+77+77) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+88+88) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+99+99) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 66798 &:= \frac{(11111+11+11) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22+22) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33+33) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+44+44) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55+55) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66+66) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666798} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 11) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 22) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 33) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 44) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 55) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 66) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{799} &:= \frac{(111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8799} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88799} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888799} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{800} &:= \frac{(111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8800} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88800} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888800} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{801} &:= \frac{(111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8801} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88801} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888801} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 802 &:= \frac{(111-11) \times (11-1-1-1) + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222-22) \times (22-2-2-2) + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333-33) \times (33-3-3-3) + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-44) \times (44-4-4-4) + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555-55) \times (55-5-5-5) + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666-66) \times (66-6-6-6) + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-77) \times (77-7-7-7) + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888-88) \times (88-8-8-8) + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999-99) \times (99-9-9-9) + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8802 &:= \frac{(1111-11) \times (11-1-1-1) + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222-22) \times (22-2-2-2) + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333-33) \times (33-3-3-3) + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-44) \times (44-4-4-4) + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555-55) \times (55-5-5-5) + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666-66) \times (66-6-6-6) + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-77) \times (77-7-7-7) + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888-88) \times (88-8-8-8) + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999-99) \times (99-9-9-9) + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 88802 &:= \frac{(11111-11) \times (11-1-1-1) + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222-22) \times (22-2-2-2) + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333-33) \times (33-3-3-3) + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-44) \times (44-4-4-4) + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555-55) \times (55-5-5-5) + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666-66) \times (66-6-6-6) + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-77) \times (77-7-7-7) + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888-88) \times (88-8-8-8) + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999-99) \times (99-9-9-9) + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 888802 &:= \frac{(111111-11) \times (11-1-1-1) + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222-22) \times (22-2-2-2) + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333-33) \times (33-3-3-3) + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444-44) \times (44-4-4-4) + 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555-55) \times (55-5-5-5) + 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666-66) \times (66-6-6-6) + 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777-77) \times (77-7-7-7) + 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888-88) \times (88-8-8-8) + 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999-99) \times (99-9-9-9) + 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 803 &:= \frac{(111-11) \times (11-1-1-1) + 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222-22) \times (22-2-2-2) + 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333-33) \times (33-3-3-3) + 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-44) \times (44-4-4-4) + 4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555-55) \times (55-5-5-5) + 5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666-66) \times (66-6-6-6) + 6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-77) \times (77-7-7-7) + 7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888-88) \times (88-8-8-8) + 8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999-99) \times (99-9-9-9) + 9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8803 &:= \frac{(1111-11) \times (11-1-1-1) + 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222-22) \times (22-2-2-2) + 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333-33) \times (33-3-3-3) + 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-44) \times (44-4-4-4) + 4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555-55) \times (55-5-5-5) + 5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666-66) \times (66-6-6-6) + 6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-77) \times (77-7-7-7) + 7 \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888-88) \times (88-8-8-8) + 8 \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999-99) \times (99-9-9-9) + 9 \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 88803 &:= \frac{(11111-11) \times (11-1-1-1) + 1 \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222-22) \times (22-2-2-2) + 2 \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333-33) \times (33-3-3-3) + 3 \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-44) \times (44-4-4-4) + 4 \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555-55) \times (55-5-5-5) + 5 \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666-66) \times (66-6-6-6) + 6 \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888803} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{804} &:= \frac{(111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8804} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88804} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888804} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{805} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 1111 - (1 + 1 + 1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 2222 - (2 + 2 + 2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 3333 - (3 + 3 + 3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 4444 - (4 + 4 + 4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 5555 - (5 + 5 + 5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 6666 - (6 + 6 + 6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 7777 - (7 + 7 + 7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 8888 - (8 + 8 + 8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 9999 - (9 + 9 + 9) \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{80805} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 111111 - (1 + 1 + 1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 222222 - (2 + 2 + 2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 333333 - (3 + 3 + 3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 444444 - (4 + 4 + 4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 555555 - (5 + 5 + 5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 666666 - (6 + 6 + 6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 777777 - (7+7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 888888 - (8+8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 999999 - (9+9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8080805} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 11111111 - (1+1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 22222222 - (2+2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 33333333 - (3+3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 44444444 - (4+4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 55555555 - (5+5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 66666666 - (6+6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 77777777 - (7+7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 88888888 - (8+8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 99999999 - (9+9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{808080805} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111111111 - (1+1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222222222 - (2+2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333333333 - (3+3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444444444 - (4+4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555555555 - (5+5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666666666 - (6+6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777777777 - (7+7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888888888 - (8+8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999999999 - (9+9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{806} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111 - (1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222 - (2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333 - (3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444 - (4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555 - (5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666 - (6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777 - (7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888 - (8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999 - (9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{80806} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 111111 - (1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 222222 - (2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 333333 - (3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 444444 - (4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 555555 - (5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 666666 - (6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 777777 - (7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 888888 - (8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 999999 - (9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8080806} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 11111111 - (1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 22222222 - (2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 33333333 - (3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 44444444 - (4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 55555555 - (5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 66666666 - (6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 77777777 - (7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 88888888 - (8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 99999999 - (9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{808080806} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111111111 - (1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222222222 - (2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333333333 - (3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444444444 - (4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555555555 - (5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666666666 - (6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777777777 - (7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888888888 - (8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999999999 - (9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{807} := \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111 - 1 \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222 - 2 \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333 - 3 \times 33}{33 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444 - 4 \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555 - 5 \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666 - 6 \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777 - 7 \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888 - 8 \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999 - 9 \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{80807} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 111111 - 1 \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 222222 - 2 \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 333333 - 3 \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 444444 - 4 \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 555555 - 5 \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 666666 - 6 \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 777777 - 7 \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 888888 - 8 \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 999999 - 9 \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8080807} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 11111111 - 1 \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 22222222 - 2 \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 33333333 - 3 \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 44444444 - 4 \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 55555555 - 5 \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 66666666 - 6 \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 77777777 - 7 \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 88888888 - 8 \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 99999999 - 9 \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{808080807} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111111111 - 1 \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222222222 - 2 \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333333333 - 3 \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444444444 - 4 \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555555555 - 5 \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666666666 - 6 \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777777777 - 7 \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888888888 - 8 \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999999999 - 9 \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{808} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{80808} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 111111}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 222222}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 333333}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 444444}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 555555}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 666666}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 777777}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 888888}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 999999}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8080808} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 11111111}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 22222222}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 33333333}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 44444444}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 55555555}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 66666666}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 77777777}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 88888888}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 99999999}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 808080808 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111111111}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222222222}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333333333}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444444444}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555555555}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666666666}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777777777}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888888888}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999999999}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 809 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111 + 1 \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222 + 2 \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333 + 3 \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444 + 4 \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555 + 5 \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666 + 6 \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777 + 7 \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888 + 8 \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999 + 9 \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 80809 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 111111 + 1 \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 222222 + 2 \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 333333 + 3 \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 444444 + 4 \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 555555 + 5 \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 666666 + 6 \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 777777 + 7 \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 888888 + 8 \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 999999 + 9 \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8080809 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 11111111 + 1 \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 22222222 + 2 \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 33333333 + 3 \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 44444444 + 4 \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 55555555 + 5 \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 66666666 + 6 \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 77777777 + 7 \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 88888888 + 8 \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 99999999 + 9 \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 808080809 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111111111 + 1 \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222222222 + 2 \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333333333 + 3 \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444444444 + 4 \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555555555 + 5 \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666666666 + 6 \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777777777 + 7 \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888888888 + 8 \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999999999 + 9 \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 810 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111 + (1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222 + (2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333 + (3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444 + (4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555 + (5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666 + (6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777 + (7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888 + (8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999 + (9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 80810 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 111111 + (1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 222222 + (2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 333333 + (3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 444444 + (4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 555555 + (5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 666666 + (6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 777777 + (7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 888888 + (8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 999999 + (9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8080810} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 11111111 + (1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 22222222 + (2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 33333333 + (3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 44444444 + (4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 55555555 + (5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 66666666 + (6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 77777777 + (7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 88888888 + (8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 99999999 + (9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{808080810} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111111111 + (1+1) \times 11}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222222222 + (2+2) \times 22}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333333333 + (3+3) \times 33}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444444444 + (4+4) \times 44}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555555555 + (5+5) \times 55}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666666666 + (6+6) \times 66}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777777777 + (7+7) \times 77}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888888888 + (8+8) \times 88}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999999999 + (9+9) \times 99}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{811} &:= \frac{(111-11) \times (11-1-1-1) + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222-22) \times (22-2-2-2) + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333-33) \times (33-3-3-3) + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-44) \times (44-4-4-4) + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555-55) \times (55-5-5-5) + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666-66) \times (66-6-6-6) + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-77) \times (77-7-7-7) + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888-88) \times (88-8-8-8) + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999-99) \times (99-9-9-9) + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8811} &:= \frac{(1111-11) \times (11-1-1-1) + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222-22) \times (22-2-2-2) + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333-33) \times (33-3-3-3) + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-44) \times (44-4-4-4) + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555-55) \times (55-5-5-5) + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666-66) \times (66-6-6-6) + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-77) \times (77-7-7-7) + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888-88) \times (88-8-8-8) + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999-99) \times (99-9-9-9) + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88811} &:= \frac{(11111-11) \times (11-1-1-1) + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222-22) \times (22-2-2-2) + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333-33) \times (33-3-3-3) + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-44) \times (44-4-4-4) + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555-55) \times (55-5-5-5) + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666-66) \times (66-6-6-6) + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-77) \times (77-7-7-7) + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888-88) \times (88-8-8-8) + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999-99) \times (99-9-9-9) + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888811} &:= \frac{(111111-11) \times (11-1-1-1) + 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222-22) \times (22-2-2-2) + 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333-33) \times (33-3-3-3) + 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444-44) \times (44-4-4-4) + 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555-55) \times (55-5-5-5) + 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666-66) \times (66-6-6-6) + 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777-77) \times (77-7-7-7) + 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888-88) \times (88-8-8-8) + 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999-99) \times (99-9-9-9) + 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{812} := \frac{(111-11) \times (11-1-1-1) + (11+1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222-22) \times (22-2-2-2) + (22+2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333-33) \times (33-3-3-3) + (33+3) \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + (44 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + (55 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + (66 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + (77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + (88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + (99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8812} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + (11 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + (22 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + (33 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + (44 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + (55 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + (66 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + (77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + (88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + (99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88812} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + (11 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + (22 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + (33 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + (44 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + (55 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + (66 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + (77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + (88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + (99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888812} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + (11 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + (22 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + (33 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + (44 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + (55 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + (66 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + (77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + (88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + (99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{813} &:= \frac{(11 + 11) \times 111 - (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22) \times 222 - (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33) \times 333 - (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44) \times 444 - (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55) \times 555 - (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66) \times 666 - (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77) \times 777 - (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88) \times 888 - (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99) \times 999 - (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8213} &:= \frac{(111 + 111) \times 111 - (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222) \times 222 - (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333) \times 333 - (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444) \times 444 - (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555) \times 555 - (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666) \times 666 - (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777) \times 777 - (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888) \times 888 - (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999) \times 999 - (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{82213} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111) \times 111 - (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222) \times 222 - (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333) \times 333 - (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444) \times 444 - (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555) \times 555 - (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666) \times 666 - (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777) \times 777 - (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888) \times 888 - (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999) \times 999 - (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{822213} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111) \times 111 - (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222) \times 222 - (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333) \times 333 - (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444) \times 444 - (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555) \times 555 - (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666) \times 666 - (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777) \times 777 - (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888) \times 888 - (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999) \times 999 - (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{814} &:= \frac{(11 + 11) \times 111}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22) \times 222}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33) \times 333}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44) \times 444}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55) \times 555}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66) \times 666}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77) \times 777}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88) \times 888}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99) \times 999}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{8214} &:= \frac{(111 + 111) \times 111}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222) \times 222}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333) \times 333}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444) \times 444}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555) \times 555}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666) \times 666}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 777) \times 777}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888) \times 888}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999) \times 999}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{82214} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111) \times 111}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222) \times 222}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333) \times 333}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444) \times 444}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555) \times 555}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666) \times 666}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777) \times 777}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888) \times 888}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999) \times 999}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{822214} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111) \times 111}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222) \times 222}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333) \times 333}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444) \times 444}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555) \times 555}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666) \times 666}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777) \times 777}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888) \times 888}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999) \times 999}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{815} &:= \frac{(11 + 11) \times 111 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 22) \times 222 + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 33) \times 333 + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44) \times 444 + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 55) \times 555 + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 66) \times 666 + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77) \times 777 + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 88) \times 888 + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 99) \times 999 + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{8215} := \frac{(111 + 111) \times 111 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222) \times 222 + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333) \times 333 + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 + 444) \times 444 + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555) \times 555 + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666) \times 666 + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777) \times 777 + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888) \times 888 + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999) \times 999 + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{82215} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111) \times 111 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2222) \times 222 + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3333) \times 333 + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444) \times 444 + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5555) \times 555 + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6666) \times 666 + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777) \times 777 + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888) \times 888 + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999) \times 999 + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{822215} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111) \times 111 + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222) \times 222 + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333) \times 333 + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444) \times 444 + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555) \times 555 + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666) \times 666 + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777) \times 777 + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888) \times 888 + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999) \times 999 + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{816} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (1111 + 11)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (2222 + 22)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (3333 + 33)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (4444 + 44)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (5555 + 55)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (6666 + 66)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (7777 + 77)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (8888 + 88)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (9999 + 99)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{80816} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111111 + 11)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222222 + 22)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333333 + 33)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444444 + 44)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555555 + 55)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666666 + 66)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777777 + 77)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888888 + 88)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999999 + 99)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8080816} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11111111 + 11)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22222222 + 22)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33333333 + 33)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44444444 + 44)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55555555 + 55)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66666666 + 66)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77777777 + 77)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88888888 + 88)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99999999 + 99)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{808080816} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (1111111111 + 11)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (2222222222 + 22)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (3333333333 + 33)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (4444444444 + 44)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (5555555555 + 55)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (6666666666 + 66)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (7777777777 + 77)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (8888888888 + 88)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (9999999999 + 99)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 817 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111 + (11-1-1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222 + (22-2-2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333 + (33-3-3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444 + (44-4-4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555 + (55-5-5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666 + (66-6-6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777 + (77-7-7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888 + (88-8-8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999 + (99-9-9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 80817 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 111111 + (11-1-1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 222222 + (22-2-2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 333333 + (33-3-3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 444444 + (44-4-4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 555555 + (55-5-5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 666666 + (66-6-6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 777777 + (77-7-7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 888888 + (88-8-8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 999999 + (99-9-9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8080817 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 11111111 + (11-1-1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 22222222 + (22-2-2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 33333333 + (33-3-3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 44444444 + (44-4-4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 55555555 + (55-5-5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 66666666 + (66-6-6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 77777777 + (77-7-7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 88888888 + (88-8-8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 99999999 + (99-9-9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 808080817 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111111111 + (11-1-1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222222222 + (22-2-2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333333333 + (33-3-3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444444444 + (44-4-4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555555555 + (55-5-5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666666666 + (66-6-6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777777777 + (77-7-7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888888888 + (88-8-8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999999999 + (99-9-9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 818 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111 + (11-1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222 + (22-2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333 + (33-3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444 + (44-4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555 + (55-5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666 + (66-6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777 + (77-7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888 + (88-8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999 + (99-9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 80818 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 111111 + (11-1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 222222 + (22-2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 333333 + (33-3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 444444 + (44-4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 555555 + (55-5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 666666 + (66-6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 777777 + (77-7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 888888 + (88-8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 999999 + (99-9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8080818 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 11111111 + (11-1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 22222222 + (22-2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 33333333 + (33-3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 44444444 + (44-4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 55555555 + (55-5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 66666666 + (66-6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 77777777 + (77-7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 88888888 + (88-8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 99999999 + (99-9) \times 99}{9 \times 99}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{808080818} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111111111 + (11-1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222222222 + (22-2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333333333 + (33-3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444444444 + (44-4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555555555 + (55-5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666666666 + (66-6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777777777 + (77-7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888888888 + (88-8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999999999 + (99-9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{819} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111 + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222 + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333 + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444 + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555 + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666 + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777 + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888 + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999 + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{80819} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 111111 + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 222222 + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 333333 + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 444444 + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 555555 + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 666666 + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 777777 + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 888888 + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 999999 + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8080819} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 11111111 + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 22222222 + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 33333333 + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 44444444 + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 55555555 + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 66666666 + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 77777777 + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 88888888 + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 99999999 + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{808080819} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111111111 + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222222222 + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333333333 + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444444444 + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555555555 + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666666666 + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777777777 + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888888888 + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999999999 + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{820} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111 + (11+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222 + (22+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333 + (33+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444 + (44+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555 + (55+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666 + (66+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777 + (77+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888 + (88+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999 + (99+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 80820 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 111111 + (11+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 222222 + (22+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 333333 + (33+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 444444 + (44+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 555555 + (55+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 666666 + (66+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 777777 + (77+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 888888 + (88+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 999999 + (99+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8080820 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 11111111 + (11+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 22222222 + (22+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 33333333 + (33+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 44444444 + (44+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 55555555 + (55+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 66666666 + (66+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 77777777 + (77+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 88888888 + (88+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 99999999 + (99+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 808080820 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111111111 + (11+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222222222 + (22+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333333333 + (33+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444444444 + (44+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555555555 + (55+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666666666 + (66+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777777777 + (77+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888888888 + (88+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999999999 + (99+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 821 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111 + (11+1+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222 + (22+2+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333 + (33+3+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444 + (44+4+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555 + (55+5+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666 + (66+6+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777 + (77+7+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888 + (88+8+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999 + (99+9+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 80821 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 111111 + (11+1+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 222222 + (22+2+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 333333 + (33+3+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 444444 + (44+4+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 555555 + (55+5+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 666666 + (66+6+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 777777 + (77+7+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 888888 + (88+8+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 999999 + (99+9+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8080821 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 11111111 + (11+1+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 22222222 + (22+2+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 33333333 + (33+3+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 44444444 + (44+4+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 55555555 + (55+5+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 66666666 + (66+6+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 77777777 + (77+7+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 88888888 + (88+8+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 99999999 + (99+9+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 808080821 &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times 1111111111 + (11+1+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times 2222222222 + (22+2+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times 3333333333 + (33+3+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times 4444444444 + (44+4+4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times 5555555555 + (55+5+5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times 6666666666 + (66+6+6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times 7777777777 + (77+7+7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times 8888888888 + (88+8+8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times 9999999999 + (99+9+9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{822} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8222} &:= \frac{(11111 + 1111 + 111) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 2222 + 222) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 3333 + 333) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 4444 + 444) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 5555 + 555) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 6666 + 666) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 7777 + 777) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 8888 + 888) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 9999 + 999) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{82222} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11111 + 1111) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22222 + 2222) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33333 + 3333) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44444 + 4444) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55555 + 5555) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66666 + 6666) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77777 + 7777) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88888 + 8888) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99999 + 9999) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{822222} &:= \frac{(1111111 + 111111 + 11111) \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222 + 222222 + 22222) \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333 + 333333 + 33333) \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444 + 444444 + 44444) \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555 + 555555 + 55555) \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666 + 666666 + 66666) \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777 + 777777 + 77777) \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888 + 888888 + 88888) \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999 + 999999 + 99999) \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{823} &:= \frac{(111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + (11 + 11 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + (22 + 22 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + (33 + 33 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + (44 + 44 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + (55 + 55 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + (66 + 66 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + (77 + 77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + (88 + 88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + (99 + 99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8823} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + (11 + 11 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + (22 + 22 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + (33 + 33 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + (44 + 44 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + (55 + 55 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + (66 + 66 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + (77 + 77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + (88 + 88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + (99 + 99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88823} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + (11 + 11 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + (22 + 22 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + (33 + 33 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + (44 + 44 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + (55 + 55 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + (66 + 66 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + (77 + 77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + (88 + 88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + (99 + 99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 888823 &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + (11 + 11 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + (22 + 22 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + (33 + 33 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + (44 + 44 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + (55 + 55 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + (66 + 66 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + (77 + 77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + (88 + 88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + (99 + 99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 824 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (1111 + 11 + 11)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (2222 + 22 + 22)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (3333 + 33 + 33)}{33 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (4444 + 44 + 44)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (5555 + 55 + 55)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (6666 + 66 + 66)}{66 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (7777 + 77 + 77)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (8888 + 88 + 88)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (9999 + 99 + 99)}{99 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 80824 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111111 + 11 + 11)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222222 + 22 + 22)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333333 + 33 + 33)}{33 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444444 + 44 + 44)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555555 + 55 + 55)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666666 + 66 + 66)}{66 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777777 + 77 + 77)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888888 + 88 + 88)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999999 + 99 + 99)}{99 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8080824 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11111111 + 11 + 11)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22222222 + 22 + 22)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33333333 + 33 + 33)}{33 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44444444 + 44 + 44)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55555555 + 55 + 55)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66666666 + 66 + 66)}{66 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77777777 + 77 + 77)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88888888 + 88 + 88)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99999999 + 99 + 99)}{99 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 808080824 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (1111111111 + 11 + 11)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (2222222222 + 22 + 22)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (3333333333 + 33 + 33)}{33 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (4444444444 + 44 + 44)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (5555555555 + 55 + 55)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (6666666666 + 66 + 66)}{66 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (7777777777 + 77 + 77)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (8888888888 + 88 + 88)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (9999999999 + 99 + 99)}{99 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 825 &:= \frac{(1111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(2222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(3333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$8325 := \frac{(11111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{83325} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{833325} &:= \frac{(1111111 - 11) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(2222222 - 22) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(3333333 - 33) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444 - 44) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(5555555 - 55) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(6666666 - 66) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777 - 77) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(8888888 - 88) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(9999999 - 99) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{826} &:= \frac{11111 + 1}{11 + 1} - \frac{1111 - 11}{11} = \frac{2222 + 2}{22 + 2} - \frac{2222 - 22}{22} = \frac{3333 + 3}{33 + 3} - \frac{3333 - 33}{33} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 4}{44 + 4} - \frac{4444 - 44}{44} = \frac{55555 + 5}{55 + 5} - \frac{5555 - 55}{55} = \frac{66666 + 6}{66 + 6} - \frac{6666 - 66}{66} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 7}{77 + 7} - \frac{7777 - 77}{77} = \frac{88888 + 8}{88 + 8} - \frac{8888 - 88}{88} = \frac{99999 + 9}{99 + 9} - \frac{9999 - 99}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925826} &:= \frac{11111111 + 1}{11 + 1} - \frac{1111 - 11}{11} = \frac{2222222 + 2}{22 + 2} - \frac{2222 - 22}{22} = \frac{3333333 + 3}{33 + 3} - \frac{3333 - 33}{33} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 + 4}{44 + 4} - \frac{4444 - 44}{44} = \frac{5555555 + 5}{55 + 5} - \frac{5555 - 55}{55} = \frac{6666666 + 6}{66 + 6} - \frac{6666 - 66}{66} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 + 7}{77 + 7} - \frac{7777 - 77}{77} = \frac{8888888 + 8}{88 + 8} - \frac{8888 - 88}{88} = \frac{9999999 + 9}{99 + 9} - \frac{9999 - 99}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925826} &:= \frac{1111111111 + 1}{11 + 1} - \frac{1111 - 11}{11} = \frac{222222222 + 2}{22 + 2} - \frac{2222 - 22}{22} = \frac{333333333 + 3}{33 + 3} - \frac{3333 - 33}{33} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 + 4}{44 + 4} - \frac{4444 - 44}{44} = \frac{555555555 + 5}{55 + 5} - \frac{5555 - 55}{55} = \frac{666666666 + 6}{66 + 6} - \frac{6666 - 66}{66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 + 7}{77 + 7} - \frac{7777 - 77}{77} = \frac{888888888 + 8}{88 + 8} - \frac{8888 - 88}{88} = \frac{999999999 + 9}{99 + 9} - \frac{9999 - 99}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925925826} &:= \frac{111111111111 + 1}{11 + 1} - \frac{1111 - 11}{11} = \frac{22222222222 + 2}{22 + 2} - \frac{2222 - 22}{22} = \frac{33333333333 + 3}{33 + 3} - \frac{3333 - 33}{33} \\ &:= \frac{444444444444 + 4}{44 + 4} - \frac{4444 - 44}{44} = \frac{55555555555 + 5}{55 + 5} - \frac{5555 - 55}{55} = \frac{66666666666 + 6}{66 + 6} - \frac{6666 - 66}{66} \\ &:= \frac{777777777777 + 7}{77 + 7} - \frac{7777 - 77}{77} = \frac{88888888888 + 8}{88 + 8} - \frac{8888 - 88}{88} = \frac{99999999999 + 9}{99 + 9} - \frac{9999 - 99}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{827} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 111 - 11 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 222 - 22 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 333 - 33 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 444 - 44 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 555 - 55 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 666 - 66 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 777 - 77 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 888 - 88 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 999 - 99 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8327} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 1111 - 11 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 2222 - 22 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 3333 - 33 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 4444 - 44 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 5555 - 55 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 6666 - 66 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 7777 - 77 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 8888 - 88 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 9999 - 99 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{83327} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 11111 - 11 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 22222 - 22 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 33333 - 33 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 44444 - 44 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 55555 - 55 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 66666 - 66 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 77777 - 77 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 88888 - 88 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 99999 - 99 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{833327} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 111111 - 11 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 222222 - 22 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 333333 - 33 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 444444 - 44 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 555555 - 55 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 666666 - 66 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 777777 - 77 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 888888 - 88 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 999999 - 99 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{828} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times (11+1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times (22+2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times (33+3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times (44+4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times (55+5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times (66+6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times (77+7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times (88+8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times (99+9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8028} &:= \frac{(111+111+1) \times (11+1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+222+2) \times (22+2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+333+3) \times (33+3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444+4) \times (44+4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+555+5) \times (55+5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+666+6) \times (66+6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777+7) \times (77+7) \times (7+7+7)}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+888+8) \times (88+8) \times (8+8+8)}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+999+9) \times (99+9) \times (9+9+9)}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{80028} &:= \frac{(1111+1111+1) \times (11+1) \times (1+1+1)}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222+2) \times (22+2) \times (2+2+2)}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333+3) \times (33+3) \times (3+3+3)}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4444+4) \times (44+4) \times (4+4+4)}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555+5) \times (55+5) \times (5+5+5)}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666+6) \times (66+6) \times (6+6+6)}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 7) \times (77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 8) \times (88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 9) \times (99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{800028} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 1) \times (11 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 2) \times (22 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 3) \times (33 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 4) \times (44 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 5) \times (55 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 6) \times (66 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 7) \times (77 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 8) \times (88 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 9) \times (99 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{829} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 1111 + (11 + 11 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 2222 + (22 + 22 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 3333 + (33 + 33 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 4444 + (44 + 44 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 5555 + (55 + 55 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 6666 + (66 + 66 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 7777 + (77 + 77 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 8888 + (88 + 88 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 9999 + (99 + 99 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{80829} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 111111 + (11 + 11 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 222222 + (22 + 22 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 333333 + (33 + 33 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 444444 + (44 + 44 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 555555 + (55 + 55 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 666666 + (66 + 66 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 777777 + (77 + 77 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 888888 + (88 + 88 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 999999 + (99 + 99 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8080829} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11111111 + (11 + 11 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22222222 + (22 + 22 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33333333 + (33 + 33 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44444444 + (44 + 44 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55555555 + (55 + 55 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66666666 + (66 + 66 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77777777 + (77 + 77 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88888888 + (88 + 88 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99999999 + (99 + 99 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{808080829} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 1111111111 + (11 + 11 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 2222222222 + (22 + 22 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 3333333333 + (33 + 33 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 4444444444 + (44 + 44 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 5555555555 + (55 + 55 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 6666666666 + (66 + 66 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 7777777777 + (77 + 77 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 8888888888 + (88 + 88 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 9999999999 + (99 + 99 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{830} &:= \frac{((11 + 1) \times (11 + 1) + 11 \times (1 + 1)) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1 \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{((22 + 2) \times (22 + 2) + 22 \times (2 + 2)) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2 \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{((33 + 3) \times (33 + 3) + 33 \times (3 + 3)) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3 \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{((44 + 4) \times (44 + 4) + 44 \times (4 + 4)) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{((55 + 5) \times (55 + 5) + 55 \times (5 + 5)) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{((66 + 6) \times (66 + 6) + 66 \times (6 + 6)) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6 \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{((77 + 7) \times (77 + 7) + 77 \times (7 + 7)) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{((88 + 8) \times (88 + 8) + 88 \times (8 + 8)) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8 \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{((99 + 9) \times (99 + 9) + 99 \times (9 + 9)) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9 \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{6830} := \frac{((111 + 1) \times (11 + 1) + 11 \times (1 + 1)) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1 \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{((222 + 2) \times (22 + 2) + 22 \times (2 + 2)) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2 \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{((333 + 3) \times (33 + 3) + 33 \times (3 + 3)) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3 \times (3 + 3)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((444+4) \times (44+4) + 44 \times (4+4)) \times (44-4)}{4 \times 4 \times (4+4)} = \frac{((555+5) \times (55+5) + 55 \times (5+5)) \times (55-5)}{5 \times 5 \times (5+5)} = \frac{((666+6) \times (66+6) + 66 \times (6+6)) \times (66-6)}{6 \times 6 \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{((777+7) \times (77+7) + 77 \times (7+7)) \times (77-7)}{7 \times 7 \times (7+7)} = \frac{((888+8) \times (88+8) + 88 \times (8+8)) \times (88-8)}{8 \times 8 \times (8+8)} = \frac{((999+9) \times (99+9) + 99 \times (9+9)) \times (99-9)}{9 \times 9 \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66830} &:= \frac{((1111+1) \times (11+1) + 11 \times (1+1)) \times (11-1)}{1 \times 1 \times (1+1)} = \frac{((2222+2) \times (22+2) + 22 \times (2+2)) \times (22-2)}{2 \times 2 \times (2+2)} = \frac{((3333+3) \times (33+3) + 33 \times (3+3)) \times (33-3)}{3 \times 3 \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{((4444+4) \times (44+4) + 44 \times (4+4)) \times (44-4)}{4 \times 4 \times (4+4)} = \frac{((5555+5) \times (55+5) + 55 \times (5+5)) \times (55-5)}{5 \times 5 \times (5+5)} = \frac{((6666+6) \times (66+6) + 66 \times (6+6)) \times (66-6)}{6 \times 6 \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{((7777+7) \times (77+7) + 77 \times (7+7)) \times (77-7)}{7 \times 7 \times (7+7)} = \frac{((8888+8) \times (88+8) + 88 \times (8+8)) \times (88-8)}{8 \times 8 \times (8+8)} = \frac{((9999+9) \times (99+9) + 99 \times (9+9)) \times (99-9)}{9 \times 9 \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666830} &:= \frac{((11111+1) \times (11+1) + 11 \times (1+1)) \times (11-1)}{1 \times 1 \times (1+1)} = \frac{((22222+2) \times (22+2) + 22 \times (2+2)) \times (22-2)}{2 \times 2 \times (2+2)} = \frac{((33333+3) \times (33+3) + 33 \times (3+3)) \times (33-3)}{3 \times 3 \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{((44444+4) \times (44+4) + 44 \times (4+4)) \times (44-4)}{4 \times 4 \times (4+4)} = \frac{((55555+5) \times (55+5) + 55 \times (5+5)) \times (55-5)}{5 \times 5 \times (5+5)} = \frac{((66666+6) \times (66+6) + 66 \times (6+6)) \times (66-6)}{6 \times 6 \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{((77777+7) \times (77+7) + 77 \times (7+7)) \times (77-7)}{7 \times 7 \times (7+7)} = \frac{((88888+8) \times (88+8) + 88 \times (8+8)) \times (88-8)}{8 \times 8 \times (8+8)} = \frac{((99999+9) \times (99+9) + 99 \times (9+9)) \times (99-9)}{9 \times 9 \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{831} &:= \frac{(1111-1-1-1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(2222-2-2-2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(3333-3-3-3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-4-4-4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(5555-5-5-5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(6666-6-6-6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-7-7-7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(8888-8-8-8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(9999-9-9-9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8331} &:= \frac{(11111-1-1-1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(22222-2-2-2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(33333-3-3-3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-4-4-4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(55555-5-5-5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(66666-6-6-6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-7-7-7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(88888-8-8-8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(99999-9-9-9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{83331} &:= \frac{(111111-1-1-1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(222222-2-2-2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(333333-3-3-3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444444-4-4-4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(555555-5-5-5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(666666-6-6-6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777777-7-7-7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(888888-8-8-8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(999999-9-9-9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{833331} &:= \frac{(1111111-1-1-1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(2222222-2-2-2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(3333333-3-3-3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444-4-4-4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(5555555-5-5-5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(6666666-6-6-6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777-7-7-7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(8888888-8-8-8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(9999999-9-9-9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 832 &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 111 - 1 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 222 - 2 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 333 - 3 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 444 - 4 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 555 - 5 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 666 - 6 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 777 - 7 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 888 - 8 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 999 - 9 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8332 &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 1111 - 1 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 2222 - 2 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 3333 - 3 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 4444 - 4 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 5555 - 5 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 6666 - 6 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 7777 - 7 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 8888 - 8 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 9999 - 9 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 83332 &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 11111 - 1 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 22222 - 2 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 33333 - 3 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 44444 - 4 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 55555 - 5 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 66666 - 6 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 77777 - 7 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 88888 - 8 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 99999 - 9 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 833332 &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 111111 - 1 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 222222 - 2 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 333333 - 3 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 444444 - 4 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 555555 - 5 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 666666 - 6 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 777777 - 7 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 888888 - 8 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 999999 - 9 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 833 &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 111 + 1 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 222 + 2 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 333 + 3 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 444 + 4 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 555 + 5 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 666 + 6 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 777 + 7 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 888 + 8 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 999 + 9 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8333 &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 1111 + 1 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 2222 + 2 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 3333 + 3 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 4444 + 4 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 5555 + 5 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 6666 + 6 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 7777 + 7 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 8888 + 8 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 9999 + 9 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$83333 := \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 11111 + 1 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 22222 + 2 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 33333 + 3 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 44444 + 4 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 55555 + 5 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 66666 + 6 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 77777 + 7 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 88888 + 8 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 99999 + 9 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{833333} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 111111 + 1 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 222222 + 2 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 333333 + 3 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 444444 + 4 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 555555 + 5 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 666666 + 6 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 777777 + 7 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 888888 + 8 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 999999 + 9 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{834} &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8334} &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{83334} &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{833334} &:= \frac{(1111111+1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1) \times (1+1)} = \frac{(2222222+2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2) \times (2+2)} = \frac{(3333333+3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3) \times (3+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444+4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4) \times (4+4)} = \frac{(5555555+5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5) \times (5+5)} = \frac{(6666666+6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6) \times (6+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777+7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7) \times (7+7)} = \frac{(8888888+8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8) \times (8+8)} = \frac{(9999999+9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9) \times (9+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{835} &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times (11+1)}{1 \times (11+1)} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times (22+2)}{2 \times (22+2)} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times (33+3)}{3 \times (33+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (44-4-4) + 4 \times (44+4)}{4 \times (44+4)} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (55-5-5) + 5 \times (55+5)}{5 \times (55+5)} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (66-6-6) + 6 \times (66+6)}{6 \times (66+6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (77-7-7) + 7 \times (77+7)}{7 \times (77+7)} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (88-8-8) + 8 \times (88+8)}{8 \times (88+8)} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (99-9-9) + 9 \times (99+9)}{9 \times (99+9)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8335} &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times (11+1)}{1 \times (11+1)} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times (22+2)}{2 \times (22+2)} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times (33+3)}{3 \times (33+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (44-4-4) + 4 \times (44+4)}{4 \times (44+4)} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (55-5-5) + 5 \times (55+5)}{5 \times (55+5)} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (66-6-6) + 6 \times (66+6)}{6 \times (66+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (77-7-7) + 7 \times (77+7)}{7 \times (77+7)} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (88-8-8) + 8 \times (88+8)}{8 \times (88+8)} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (99-9-9) + 9 \times (99+9)}{9 \times (99+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{83335} &:= \frac{(111111+1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times (11+1)}{1 \times (11+1)} = \frac{(222222+2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times (22+2)}{2 \times (22+2)} = \frac{(333333+3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times (33+3)}{3 \times (33+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4) \times (44-4-4) + 4 \times (44+4)}{4 \times (44+4)} = \frac{(555555+5) \times (55-5-5) + 5 \times (55+5)}{5 \times (55+5)} = \frac{(666666+6) \times (66-6-6) + 6 \times (66+6)}{6 \times (66+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7) \times (77-7-7) + 7 \times (77+7)}{7 \times (77+7)} = \frac{(888888+8) \times (88-8-8) + 8 \times (88+8)}{8 \times (88+8)} = \frac{(999999+9) \times (99-9-9) + 9 \times (99+9)}{9 \times (99+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{833335} &:= \frac{(1111111+1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times (11+1)}{1 \times (11+1)} = \frac{(2222222+2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times (22+2)}{2 \times (22+2)} = \frac{(3333333+3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times (33+3)}{3 \times (33+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444+4) \times (44-4-4) + 4 \times (44+4)}{4 \times (44+4)} = \frac{(5555555+5) \times (55-5-5) + 5 \times (55+5)}{5 \times (55+5)} = \frac{(6666666+6) \times (66-6-6) + 6 \times (66+6)}{6 \times (66+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777+7) \times (77-7-7) + 7 \times (77+7)}{7 \times (77+7)} = \frac{(8888888+8) \times (88-8-8) + 8 \times (88+8)}{8 \times (88+8)} = \frac{(9999999+9) \times (99-9-9) + 9 \times (99+9)}{9 \times (99+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{836} &:= \frac{(111+1+1+1) \times (11+11)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2+2) \times (22+22)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3+3) \times (33+33)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4+4+4) \times (44+44)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5+5) \times (55+55)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6+6) \times (66+66)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7+7+7) \times (77+77)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8+8) \times (88+88)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9+9) \times (99+99)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8436} &:= \frac{(111+1+1+1) \times (111+111)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2+2) \times (222+222)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3+3) \times (333+333)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4+4+4) \times (444+444)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5+5) \times (555+555)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6+6) \times (666+666)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7+7+7) \times (777+777)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8+8) \times (888+888)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9+9) \times (999+999)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{84436} &:= \frac{(111+1+1+1) \times (1111+1111)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2+2) \times (2222+2222)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3+3) \times (3333+3333)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4+4+4) \times (4444+4444)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5+5) \times (5555+5555)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6+6) \times (6666+6666)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7+7+7) \times (7777+7777)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8+8) \times (8888+8888)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9+9) \times (9999+9999)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 844436 &:= \frac{(111+1+1+1) \times (11111+11111)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2+2) \times (22222+22222)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3+3) \times (33333+33333)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444+4+4+4) \times (44444+44444)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5+5) \times (55555+55555)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6+6) \times (66666+66666)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777+7+7+7) \times (77777+77777)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8+8) \times (88888+88888)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9+9) \times (99999+99999)}{(9+9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 837 &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11 + (111+111+11-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22 + (222+222+22-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33 + (333+333+33-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44 + (444+444+44-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55 + (555+555+55-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66 + (666+666+66-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77 + (777+777+77-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88 + (888+888+88-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99 + (999+999+99-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2837 &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11 + (1111+1111+11-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22 + (2222+2222+22-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33 + (3333+3333+33-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44 + (4444+4444+44-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55 + (5555+5555+55-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66 + (6666+6666+66-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77 + (7777+7777+77-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88 + (8888+8888+88-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99 + (9999+9999+99-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22837 &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11 + (11111+11111+11-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22 + (22222+22222+22-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33 + (33333+33333+33-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44 + (44444+44444+44-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55 + (55555+55555+55-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66 + (66666+66666+66-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77 + (77777+77777+77-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88 + (88888+88888+88-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99 + (99999+99999+99-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 222837 &:= \frac{(111-1) \times 11 + (111111+111111+11-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222-2) \times 22 + (222222+222222+22-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333-3) \times 33 + (333333+333333+33-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444-4) \times 44 + (444444+444444+44-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times 55 + (555555+555555+55-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times 66 + (666666+666666+66-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777-7) \times 77 + (777777+777777+77-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times 88 + (888888+888888+88-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times 99 + (999999+999999+99-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 838 &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 111 + 11 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 222 + 22 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 333 + 33 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 444 + 44 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 555 + 55 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 666 + 66 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 777 + 77 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 888 + 88 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 999 + 99 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8338 &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 1111 + 11 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 2222 + 22 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 3333 + 33 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 4444 + 44 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 5555 + 55 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 6666 + 66 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 7777 + 77 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 8888 + 88 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 9999 + 99 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{83338} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 11111 + 11 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 22222 + 22 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 33333 + 33 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 44444 + 44 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 55555 + 55 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 66666 + 66 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 77777 + 77 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 88888 + 88 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 99999 + 99 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{833338} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times 111111 + 11 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times 222222 + 22 \times 2}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times 333333 + 33 \times 3}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times 444444 + 44 \times 4}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times 555555 + 55 \times 5}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times 666666 + 66 \times 6}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times 777777 + 77 \times 7}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times 888888 + 88 \times 8}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times 999999 + 99 \times 9}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{839} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (11+1+1) + 111 \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (22+2+2) + 222 \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (33+3+3) + 333 \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (44+4+4) + 444 \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (55+5+5) + 555 \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (66+6+6) + 666 \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (77+7+7) + 777 \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (88+8+8) + 888 \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (99+9+9) + 999 \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1839} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (11+1+1) + 1111 \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (22+2+2) + 2222 \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (33+3+3) + 3333 \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (44+4+4) + 4444 \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (55+5+5) + 5555 \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (66+6+6) + 6666 \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (77+7+7) + 7777 \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (88+8+8) + 8888 \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (99+9+9) + 9999 \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11839} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (11+1+1) + 11111 \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (22+2+2) + 22222 \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (33+3+3) + 33333 \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (44+4+4) + 44444 \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (55+5+5) + 55555 \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (66+6+6) + 66666 \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (77+7+7) + 77777 \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (88+8+8) + 88888 \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (99+9+9) + 99999 \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{111839} &:= \frac{(111+1) \times (11+1+1) + 111111 \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+2) \times (22+2+2) + 222222 \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+3) \times (33+3+3) + 333333 \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4) \times (44+4+4) + 444444 \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+5) \times (55+5+5) + 555555 \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+6) \times (66+6+6) + 666666 \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7) \times (77+7+7) + 777777 \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+8) \times (88+8+8) + 888888 \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+9) \times (99+9+9) + 999999 \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{840} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7840} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (111 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (222 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (333 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (444 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (555 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (666 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (777 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (888 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (999 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{77840} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (1111 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (2222 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (3333 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (4444 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (5555 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (6666 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (7777 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (8888 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (9999 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{777840} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11 - 1) \times (11111 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22 - 2) \times (22222 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33 - 3) \times (33333 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44 - 4) \times (44444 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55 - 5) \times (55555 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66 - 6) \times (66666 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77 - 7) \times (77777 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88 - 8) \times (88888 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99 - 9) \times (99999 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad \mathbf{841} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (111 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (222 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (333 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (444 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (555 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (666 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (777 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (888 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (999 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8341} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (1111 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (2222 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (3333 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (4444 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (5555 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (6666 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7) \times (7777 + 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8) \times (8888 + 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9) \times (9999 + 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{83341} &:= \frac{(11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) \times (11111 + 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2) \times (22222 + 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3) \times (33333 + 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4) \times (44444 + 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5) \times (55555 + 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6) \times (66666 + 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times (77777+7) + 7 \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times (88888+8) + 8 \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times (99999+9) + 9 \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{833341} &:= \frac{(11+1+1+1+1) \times (111111+1) + 1 \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+2+2+2+2) \times (222222+2) + 2 \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+3+3+3+3) \times (333333+3) + 3 \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+4+4+4+4) \times (444444+4) + 4 \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+5+5+5+5) \times (555555+5) + 5 \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+6+6+6+6) \times (666666+6) + 6 \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+7+7+7+7) \times (777777+7) + 7 \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+8+8+8+8) \times (888888+8) + 8 \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+9+9+9+9) \times (999999+9) + 9 \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{842} &:= \frac{(111+11) \times (11+1) + (111-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+22) \times (22+2) + (222-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+33) \times (33+3) + (333-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+44) \times (44+4) + (444-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+55) \times (55+5) + (555-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+66) \times (66+6) + (666-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+77) \times (77+7) + (777-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+88) \times (88+8) + (888-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+99) \times (99+9) + (999-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6842} &:= \frac{(1111+11) \times (11+1) + (111-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+22) \times (22+2) + (222-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+33) \times (33+3) + (333-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+44) \times (44+4) + (444-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+55) \times (55+5) + (555-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+66) \times (66+6) + (666-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+77) \times (77+7) + (777-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+88) \times (88+8) + (888-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+99) \times (99+9) + (999-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66842} &:= \frac{(11111+11) \times (11+1) + (111-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22) \times (22+2) + (222-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33) \times (33+3) + (333-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+44) \times (44+4) + (444-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55) \times (55+5) + (555-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66) \times (66+6) + (666-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+77) \times (77+7) + (777-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88) \times (88+8) + (888-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99) \times (99+9) + (999-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666842} &:= \frac{(111111+11) \times (11+1) + (111-1) \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222+22) \times (22+2) + (222-2) \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333+33) \times (33+3) + (333-3) \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+44) \times (44+4) + (444-4) \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555+55) \times (55+5) + (555-5) \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666+66) \times (66+6) + (666-6) \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+77) \times (77+7) + (777-7) \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888+88) \times (88+8) + (888-8) \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999+99) \times (99+9) + (999-9) \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{843} &:= \frac{(111+11) \times (11+1) + 111 \times (1+1)}{(1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+22) \times (22+2) + 222 \times (2+2)}{(2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+33) \times (33+3) + 333 \times (3+3)}{(3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+44) \times (44+4) + 444 \times (4+4)}{(4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+55) \times (55+5) + 555 \times (5+5)}{(5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+66) \times (66+6) + 666 \times (6+6)}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+77) \times (77+7) + 777 \times (7+7)}{(7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+88) \times (88+8) + 888 \times (8+8)}{(8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+99) \times (99+9) + 999 \times (9+9)}{(9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6843} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + 111 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + 222 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + 333 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + 444 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + 555 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + 666 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + 777 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + 888 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + 999 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{66843} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + 111 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + 222 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + 333 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + 444 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + 555 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + 666 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + 777 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + 888 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + 999 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{666843} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (11 + 1) + 111 \times (1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (22 + 2) + 222 \times (2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (33 + 3) + 333 \times (3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (44 + 4) + 444 \times (4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (55 + 5) + 555 \times (5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (66 + 6) + 666 \times (6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (77 + 7) + 777 \times (7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (88 + 8) + 888 \times (8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (99 + 9) + 999 \times (9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{844} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 11) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 22) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 33) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 44) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 55) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 66) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 77) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 88) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 99) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4844} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 11) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 22) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 33) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 44) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 55) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 66) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 77) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 88) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 99) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{44844} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 11) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 22) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 33) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 44) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 55) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 66) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 77) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 88) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 99) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{444844} := \frac{(111111 + 111 - 11) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 22) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 33) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 44) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 55) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 66) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 77) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 88) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 99) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{845} &:= \frac{((11 + 1) \times 11 - 1 \times (1 + 1)) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1 \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{((22 + 2) \times 22 - 2 \times (2 + 2)) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2 \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{((33 + 3) \times 33 - 3 \times (3 + 3)) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3 \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{((44 + 4) \times 44 - 4 \times (4 + 4)) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{((55 + 5) \times 55 - 5 \times (5 + 5)) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{((66 + 6) \times 66 - 6 \times (6 + 6)) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6 \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{((77 + 7) \times 77 - 7 \times (7 + 7)) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{((88 + 8) \times 88 - 8 \times (8 + 8)) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8 \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{((99 + 9) \times 99 - 9 \times (9 + 9)) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9 \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8645} &:= \frac{((11 + 1) \times 111 - 1 \times (1 + 1)) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1 \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{((22 + 2) \times 222 - 2 \times (2 + 2)) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2 \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{((33 + 3) \times 333 - 3 \times (3 + 3)) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3 \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{((44 + 4) \times 444 - 4 \times (4 + 4)) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{((55 + 5) \times 555 - 5 \times (5 + 5)) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{((66 + 6) \times 666 - 6 \times (6 + 6)) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6 \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{((77 + 7) \times 777 - 7 \times (7 + 7)) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{((88 + 8) \times 888 - 8 \times (8 + 8)) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8 \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{((99 + 9) \times 999 - 9 \times (9 + 9)) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9 \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{86645} &:= \frac{((11 + 1) \times 1111 - 1 \times (1 + 1)) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1 \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{((22 + 2) \times 2222 - 2 \times (2 + 2)) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2 \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{((33 + 3) \times 3333 - 3 \times (3 + 3)) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3 \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{((44 + 4) \times 4444 - 4 \times (4 + 4)) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{((55 + 5) \times 5555 - 5 \times (5 + 5)) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{((66 + 6) \times 6666 - 6 \times (6 + 6)) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6 \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{((77 + 7) \times 7777 - 7 \times (7 + 7)) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{((88 + 8) \times 8888 - 8 \times (8 + 8)) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8 \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{((99 + 9) \times 9999 - 9 \times (9 + 9)) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9 \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{866645} &:= \frac{((11 + 1) \times 11111 - 1 \times (1 + 1)) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1 \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{((22 + 2) \times 22222 - 2 \times (2 + 2)) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2 \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{((33 + 3) \times 33333 - 3 \times (3 + 3)) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3 \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{((44 + 4) \times 44444 - 4 \times (4 + 4)) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4 \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{((55 + 5) \times 55555 - 5 \times (5 + 5)) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5 \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{((66 + 6) \times 66666 - 6 \times (6 + 6)) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6 \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{((77 + 7) \times 77777 - 7 \times (7 + 7)) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7 \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{((88 + 8) \times 88888 - 8 \times (8 + 8)) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8 \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{((99 + 9) \times 99999 - 9 \times (9 + 9)) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9 \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{846} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11 \times 11 - 1 \times 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22 \times 22 - 2 \times 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33 \times 33 - 3 \times 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44 \times 44 - 4 \times 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55 \times 55 - 5 \times 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66 \times 66 - 6 \times 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77 \times 77 - 7 \times 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88 \times 88 - 8 \times 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99 \times 99 - 9 \times 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8546} &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 111 \times 11 - 1 \times 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 222 \times 22 - 2 \times 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 333 \times 33 - 3 \times 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 444 \times 44 - 4 \times 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 555 \times 55 - 5 \times 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 666 \times 66 - 6 \times 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 777 \times 77 - 7 \times 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 888 \times 88 - 8 \times 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 999 \times 99 - 9 \times 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{85546} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times 1111 \times 11-1 \times 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times 2222 \times 22-2 \times 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times 3333 \times 33-3 \times 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times 4444 \times 44-4 \times 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times 5555 \times 55-5 \times 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times 6666 \times 66-6 \times 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times 7777 \times 77-7 \times 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times 8888 \times 88-8 \times 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times 9999 \times 99-9 \times 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{855546} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times 11111 \times 11-1 \times 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times 22222 \times 22-2 \times 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times 33333 \times 33-3 \times 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times 44444 \times 44-4 \times 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times 55555 \times 55-5 \times 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times 66666 \times 66-6 \times 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times 77777 \times 77-7 \times 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times 88888 \times 88-8 \times 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times 99999 \times 99-9 \times 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{847} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times 11 \times 11}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times 22 \times 22}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times 33 \times 33}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times 44 \times 44}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times 55 \times 55}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times 66 \times 66}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times 77 \times 77}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times 88 \times 88}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times 99 \times 99}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8547} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times 111 \times 11}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times 222 \times 22}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times 333 \times 33}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times 444 \times 44}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times 555 \times 55}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times 666 \times 66}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times 777 \times 77}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times 888 \times 88}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times 999 \times 99}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{85547} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times 1111 \times 11}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times 2222 \times 22}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times 3333 \times 33}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times 4444 \times 44}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times 5555 \times 55}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times 6666 \times 66}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times 7777 \times 77}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times 8888 \times 88}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times 9999 \times 99}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{855547} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times 11111 \times 11}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times 22222 \times 22}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times 33333 \times 33}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times 44444 \times 44}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times 55555 \times 55}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times 66666 \times 66}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times 77777 \times 77}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times 88888 \times 88}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times 99999 \times 99}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{848} := \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times 11 \times 11 + 1 \times 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times 22 \times 22 + 2 \times 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times 33 \times 33 + 3 \times 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times 44 \times 44 + 4 \times 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times 55 \times 55 + 5 \times 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times 66 \times 66 + 6 \times 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times 77 \times 77 + 7 \times 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times 88 \times 88 + 8 \times 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times 99 \times 99 + 9 \times 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8548} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times 111 \times 11 + 1 \times 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times 222 \times 22 + 2 \times 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times 333 \times 33 + 3 \times 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times 444 \times 44 + 4 \times 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times 555 \times 55 + 5 \times 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times 666 \times 66 + 6 \times 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times 777 \times 77 + 7 \times 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times 888 \times 88 + 8 \times 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times 999 \times 99 + 9 \times 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{85548} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times 1111 \times 11 + 1 \times 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times 2222 \times 22 + 2 \times 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times 3333 \times 33 + 3 \times 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times 4444 \times 44 + 4 \times 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times 5555 \times 55 + 5 \times 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times 6666 \times 66 + 6 \times 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times 7777 \times 77 + 7 \times 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times 8888 \times 88 + 8 \times 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times 9999 \times 99 + 9 \times 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{855548} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1-1) \times 11111 \times 11 + 1 \times 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2-2) \times 22222 \times 22 + 2 \times 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3-3) \times 33333 \times 33 + 3 \times 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4-4) \times 44444 \times 44 + 4 \times 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5-5) \times 55555 \times 55 + 5 \times 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6-6) \times 66666 \times 66 + 6 \times 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7-7) \times 77777 \times 77 + 7 \times 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8-8) \times 88888 \times 88 + 8 \times 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9-9) \times 99999 \times 99 + 9 \times 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{849} &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 111 - (1+1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 222 - (2+2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 333 - (3+3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 444 - (4+4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 555 - (5+5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 666 - (6+6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 777 - (7+7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 888 - (8+8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 999 - (9+9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8249} &:= \frac{(111+111+1) \times 111 - (1+1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+222+2) \times 222 - (2+2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+333+3) \times 333 - (3+3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444+4) \times 444 - (4+4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+555+5) \times 555 - (5+5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+666+6) \times 666 - (6+6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777+7) \times 777 - (7+7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+888+8) \times 888 - (8+8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+999+9) \times 999 - (9+9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{82249} &:= \frac{(1111+1111+1) \times 111 - (1+1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222+2) \times 222 - (2+2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333+3) \times 333 - (3+3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4444+4) \times 444 - (4+4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555+5) \times 555 - (5+5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666+6) \times 666 - (6+6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7777+7) \times 777 - (7+7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8888+8) \times 888 - (8+8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9999+9) \times 999 - (9+9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{822249} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 1) \times 111 - (1 + 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 2) \times 222 - (2 + 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 3) \times 333 - (3 + 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 4) \times 444 - (4 + 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 5) \times 555 - (5 + 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 6) \times 666 - (6 + 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 7) \times 777 - (7 + 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 8) \times 888 - (8 + 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 9) \times 999 - (9 + 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{850} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1) \times 111 - 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2) \times 222 - 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3) \times 333 - 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4) \times 444 - 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5) \times 555 - 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6) \times 666 - 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7) \times 777 - 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8) \times 888 - 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9) \times 999 - 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{8250} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 1) \times 111 - 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 2) \times 222 - 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 3) \times 333 - 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 4) \times 444 - 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 5) \times 555 - 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 6) \times 666 - 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 7) \times 777 - 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 8) \times 888 - 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 9) \times 999 - 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{82250} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111 + 1) \times 111 - 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(2222 + 2222 + 2) \times 222 - 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(3333 + 3333 + 3) \times 333 - 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444 + 4) \times 444 - 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(5555 + 5555 + 5) \times 555 - 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(6666 + 6666 + 6) \times 666 - 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 7) \times 777 - 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 8) \times 888 - 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 9) \times 999 - 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{822250} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 1) \times 111 - 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 2) \times 222 - 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 3) \times 333 - 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 4) \times 444 - 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 5) \times 555 - 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 6) \times 666 - 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 7) \times 777 - 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 8) \times 888 - 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 9) \times 999 - 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{851} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1) \times 111}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2) \times 222}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3) \times 333}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4) \times 444}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5) \times 555}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6) \times 666}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7) \times 777}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8) \times 888}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9) \times 999}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{8251} := \frac{(111 + 111 + 1) \times 111}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 2) \times 222}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 3) \times 333}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 4) \times 444}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 5) \times 555}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 6) \times 666}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 7) \times 777}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 8) \times 888}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 9) \times 999}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{82251} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111 + 1) \times 111}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(2222 + 2222 + 2) \times 222}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(3333 + 3333 + 3) \times 333}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444 + 4) \times 444}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(5555 + 5555 + 5) \times 555}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(6666 + 6666 + 6) \times 666}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 7) \times 777}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 8) \times 888}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 9) \times 999}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{822251} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 1) \times 111}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 2) \times 222}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 3) \times 333}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 4) \times 444}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 5) \times 555}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 6) \times 666}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 7) \times 777}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 8) \times 888}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 9) \times 999}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{852} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1) \times 111 + 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2) \times 222 + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3) \times 333 + 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4) \times 444 + 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5) \times 555 + 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6) \times 666 + 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7) \times 777 + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8) \times 888 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9) \times 999 + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8252} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 1) \times 111 + 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 2) \times 222 + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 3) \times 333 + 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 4) \times 444 + 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 5) \times 555 + 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 6) \times 666 + 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 7) \times 777 + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 8) \times 888 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 9) \times 999 + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{82252} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111 + 1) \times 111 + 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(2222 + 2222 + 2) \times 222 + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(3333 + 3333 + 3) \times 333 + 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444 + 4) \times 444 + 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(5555 + 5555 + 5) \times 555 + 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(6666 + 6666 + 6) \times 666 + 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 7) \times 777 + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 8) \times 888 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 9) \times 999 + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{822252} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 1) \times 111 + 1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 2) \times 222 + 2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 3) \times 333 + 3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 4) \times 444 + 4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 5) \times 555 + 5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 6) \times 666 + 6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 7) \times 777 + 7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 8) \times 888 + 8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 9) \times 999 + 9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 853 &:= \frac{(11+11+1) \times 111 + (1+1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22+22+2) \times 222 + (2+2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33+33+3) \times 333 + (3+3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44+44+4) \times 444 + (4+4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55+55+5) \times 555 + (5+5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66+66+6) \times 666 + (6+6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77+77+7) \times 777 + (7+7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88+88+8) \times 888 + (8+8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99+99+9) \times 999 + (9+9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8253 &:= \frac{(111+111+1) \times 111 + (1+1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(222+222+2) \times 222 + (2+2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(333+333+3) \times 333 + (3+3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+444+4) \times 444 + (4+4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(555+555+5) \times 555 + (5+5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(666+666+6) \times 666 + (6+6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+777+7) \times 777 + (7+7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(888+888+8) \times 888 + (8+8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(999+999+9) \times 999 + (9+9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 82253 &:= \frac{(1111+1111+1) \times 111 + (1+1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2222+2) \times 222 + (2+2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3333+3) \times 333 + (3+3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4444+4) \times 444 + (4+4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5555+5) \times 555 + (5+5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6666+6) \times 666 + (6+6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7777+7) \times 777 + (7+7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8888+8) \times 888 + (8+8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9999+9) \times 999 + (9+9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 822253 &:= \frac{(11111+11111+1) \times 111 + (1+1) \times (1+1+1)}{(1+1+1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222+22222+2) \times 222 + (2+2) \times (2+2+2)}{(2+2+2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333+33333+3) \times 333 + (3+3) \times (3+3+3)}{(3+3+3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+44444+4) \times 444 + (4+4) \times (4+4+4)}{(4+4+4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555+55555+5) \times 555 + (5+5) \times (5+5+5)}{(5+5+5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666+66666+6) \times 666 + (6+6) \times (6+6+6)}{(6+6+6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+77777+7) \times 777 + (7+7) \times (7+7+7)}{(7+7+7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888+88888+8) \times 888 + (8+8) \times (8+8+8)}{(8+8+8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999+99999+9) \times 999 + (9+9) \times (9+9+9)}{(9+9+9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 854 &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9854 &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$99854 := \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999854} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{855} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9855} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99855} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999855} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{856} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9856} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99856} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999856} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{857} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9657} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times 111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times 222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times 333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times 444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times 555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times 666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times 777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times 888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times 999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{86657} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times 1111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times 2222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times 3333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times 4444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times 5555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times 6666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times 7777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times 8888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times 9999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{866657} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times 11111 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times 22222 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times 33333 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times 44444 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times 55555 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times 66666 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times 77777 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times 88888 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times 99999 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 858 &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9658 &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times 111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times 222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times 333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times 444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times 555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times 666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times 777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times 888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times 999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 86658 &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times 1111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times 2222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times 3333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times 4444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times 5555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times 6666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times 7777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times 8888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times 9999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 866658 &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times 11111}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times 22222}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times 33333}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times 44444}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times 55555}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times 66666}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times 77777}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times 88888}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times 99999}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 859 &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8659 &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times 111 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times 222 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times 333 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times 444 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times 555 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times 666 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times 777 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times 888 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times 999 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 86659 &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times 1111 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times 2222 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times 3333 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times 4444 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times 5555 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times 6666 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times 7777 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times 8888 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times 9999 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{866659} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times 11111 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times 22222 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times 33333 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times 44444 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times 55555 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times 66666 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times 77777 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times 88888 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times 99999 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{860} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222 - 2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333 - 3)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444 - 4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555 - 5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666 - 6)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777 - 7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888 - 8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999 - 9)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9860} &:= \frac{(1111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222 - 2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333 - 3)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444 - 4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555 - 5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666 - 6)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777 - 7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888 - 8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999 - 9)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99860} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222 - 2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333 - 3)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444 - 4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555 - 5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666 - 6)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777 - 7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888 - 8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999 - 9)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999860} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222 - 2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333 - 3)}{33 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444 - 4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555 - 5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666 - 6)}{66 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777 - 7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888 - 8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999 - 9)}{99 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{861} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2) \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3) \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7861} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 + 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 + 2) \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 + 3) \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{77861} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 2) \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 3) \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{777861} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 2) \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 3) \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{862} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 1) \times 111 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 2) \times 222 + 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 3) \times 333 + 33 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 4) \times 444 + 44 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 5) \times 555 + 55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 6) \times 666 + 66 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 7) \times 777 + 77 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 8) \times 888 + 88 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 9) \times 999 + 99 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8262} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 1) \times 111 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 2) \times 222 + 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 3) \times 333 + 33 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 4) \times 444 + 44 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 5) \times 555 + 55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 6) \times 666 + 66 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 7) \times 777 + 77 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 8) \times 888 + 88 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 9) \times 999 + 99 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{82262} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111 + 1) \times 111 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(2222 + 2222 + 2) \times 222 + 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(3333 + 3333 + 3) \times 333 + 33 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444 + 4) \times 444 + 44 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(5555 + 5555 + 5) \times 555 + 55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(6666 + 6666 + 6) \times 666 + 66 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 7) \times 777 + 77 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 8) \times 888 + 88 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 9) \times 999 + 99 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{822262} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 1) \times 111 + 11 \times (1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times (1 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 2) \times 222 + 22 \times (2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times (2 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 3) \times 333 + 33 \times (3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times (3 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 4) \times 444 + 44 \times (4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times (4 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 5) \times 555 + 55 \times (5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times (5 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 6) \times 666 + 66 \times (6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times (6 + 6 + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 7) \times 777 + 77 \times (7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times (7 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 8) \times 888 + 88 \times (8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times (8 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 9) \times 999 + 99 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times (9 + 9 + 9)}$$

► **863** := $\frac{(11 + 1) \times (11 + 1) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times 1 \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2) \times (22 + 2) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times 2 \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3) \times (33 + 3) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times 3 \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3 \times 3}$
 := $\frac{(44 + 4) \times (44 + 4) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times 4 \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5) \times (55 + 5) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times 5 \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6) \times (66 + 6) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times 6 \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6 \times 6}$
 := $\frac{(77 + 7) \times (77 + 7) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times 7 \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8) \times (88 + 8) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times 8 \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9) \times (99 + 9) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times 9 \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9 \times 9}$

8063 := $\frac{(111 + 1) \times (11 + 1) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times 1 \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times (22 + 2) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times 2 \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times (33 + 3) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times 3 \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3 \times 3}$
 := $\frac{(444 + 4) \times (44 + 4) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times 4 \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times (55 + 5) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times 5 \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times (66 + 6) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times 6 \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6 \times 6}$
 := $\frac{(777 + 7) \times (77 + 7) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times 7 \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times (88 + 8) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times 8 \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times (99 + 9) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times 9 \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9 \times 9}$

80063 := $\frac{(1111 + 1) \times (11 + 1) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times 1 \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2) \times (22 + 2) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times 2 \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3) \times (33 + 3) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times 3 \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3 \times 3}$
 := $\frac{(4444 + 4) \times (44 + 4) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times 4 \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5) \times (55 + 5) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times 5 \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6) \times (66 + 6) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times 6 \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6 \times 6}$
 := $\frac{(7777 + 7) \times (77 + 7) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times 7 \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8) \times (88 + 8) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times 8 \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9) \times (99 + 9) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times 9 \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9 \times 9}$

800063 := $\frac{(11111 + 1) \times (11 + 1) \times (11 + 1) - (1 + 1) \times 1 \times 1}{(1 + 1) \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 2) \times (22 + 2) \times (22 + 2) - (2 + 2) \times 2 \times 2}{(2 + 2) \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 3) \times (33 + 3) \times (33 + 3) - (3 + 3) \times 3 \times 3}{(3 + 3) \times 3 \times 3}$
 := $\frac{(44444 + 4) \times (44 + 4) \times (44 + 4) - (4 + 4) \times 4 \times 4}{(4 + 4) \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 5) \times (55 + 5) \times (55 + 5) - (5 + 5) \times 5 \times 5}{(5 + 5) \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 6) \times (66 + 6) \times (66 + 6) - (6 + 6) \times 6 \times 6}{(6 + 6) \times 6 \times 6}$
 := $\frac{(77777 + 7) \times (77 + 7) \times (77 + 7) - (7 + 7) \times 7 \times 7}{(7 + 7) \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 8) \times (88 + 8) \times (88 + 8) - (8 + 8) \times 8 \times 8}{(8 + 8) \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 9) \times (99 + 9) \times (99 + 9) - (9 + 9) \times 9 \times 9}{(9 + 9) \times 9 \times 9}$

► **864** := $\frac{(11 + 1) \times (11 + 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 + 2) \times (22 + 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 + 3) \times (33 + 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3 \times 3}$
 := $\frac{(44 + 4) \times (44 + 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 + 5) \times (55 + 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 + 6) \times (66 + 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6 \times 6}$
 := $\frac{(77 + 7) \times (77 + 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 + 8) \times (88 + 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 + 9) \times (99 + 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9 \times 9}$

8064 := $\frac{(111 + 1) \times (11 + 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2) \times (22 + 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3) \times (33 + 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3 \times 3}$
 := $\frac{(444 + 4) \times (44 + 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5) \times (55 + 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6) \times (66 + 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6 \times 6}$
 := $\frac{(777 + 7) \times (77 + 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8) \times (88 + 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9) \times (99 + 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9 \times 9}$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{80064} &:= \frac{(1111+1) \times (11+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2) \times (22+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3) \times (33+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4) \times (44+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5) \times (55+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6) \times (66+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7) \times (77+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8) \times (88+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9) \times (99+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{800064} &:= \frac{(11111+1) \times (11+1) \times (11+1)}{(1+1) \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2) \times (22+2) \times (22+2)}{(2+2) \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3) \times (33+3) \times (33+3)}{(3+3) \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4) \times (44+4) \times (44+4)}{(4+4) \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5) \times (55+5) \times (55+5)}{(5+5) \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6) \times (66+6) \times (66+6)}{(6+6) \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7) \times (77+7) \times (77+7)}{(7+7) \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8) \times (88+8) \times (88+8)}{(8+8) \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9) \times (99+9) \times (99+9)}{(9+9) \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{865} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9865} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99865} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999865} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{866} := \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9866} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99866} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999866} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{867} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9867} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99867} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999867} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{868} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9868} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99868} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999868} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{869} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9869} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99869} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999869} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{870} &:= \frac{(111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8870} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88870} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888870} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{871} := \frac{(111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8871} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88871} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888871} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{872} &:= \frac{(111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8872} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88872} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{888872} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{873} &:= \frac{(111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{8873} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{88873} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{888873} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{874} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9874} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99874} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999874} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{875} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9875} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99875} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999875} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{876} := \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9876} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99876} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999876} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{877} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9877} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99877} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999877} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{878} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9878} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99878} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999878} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{879} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9879} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 99 + 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99879} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999879} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{880} &:= \frac{(111 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8880} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88880} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888880} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{881} := \frac{(111 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444-4) \times (44-4-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555-5) \times (55-5-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666-6) \times (66-6-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7) \times (77-7-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888-8) \times (88-8-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999-9) \times (99-9-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8881} &:= \frac{(1111-1) \times (11-1-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222-2) \times (22-2-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333-3) \times (33-3-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-4) \times (44-4-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555-5) \times (55-5-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666-6) \times (66-6-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-7) \times (77-7-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888-8) \times (88-8-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999-9) \times (99-9-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88881} &:= \frac{(11111-1) \times (11-1-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222-2) \times (22-2-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333-3) \times (33-3-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-4) \times (44-4-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555-5) \times (55-5-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666-6) \times (66-6-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-7) \times (77-7-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888-8) \times (88-8-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999-9) \times (99-9-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888881} &:= \frac{(111111-1) \times (11-1-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222-2) \times (22-2-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333-3) \times (33-3-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444-4) \times (44-4-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555-5) \times (55-5-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666-6) \times (66-6-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777-7) \times (77-7-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888-8) \times (88-8-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999-9) \times (99-9-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{882} &:= \frac{1111-111-111-11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{2222-222-222-22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{3333-333-333-33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-444-444-44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{5555-555-555-55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{6666-666-666-66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-777-777-77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{8888-888-888-88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{9999-999-999-99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9882} &:= \frac{11111-1111-111-11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{22222-2222-222-22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{33333-3333-333-33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-4444-444-44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{55555-5555-555-55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{66666-6666-666-66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-7777-777-77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{88888-8888-888-88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{99999-9999-999-99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99882} &:= \frac{111111-11111-111-11+1+1+1+1}{1} = \frac{222222-22222-222-22+2+2+2+2}{2} = \frac{333333-33333-333-33+3+3+3+3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444-44444-444-44+4+4+4+4}{4} = \frac{555555-55555-555-55+5+5+5+5}{5} = \frac{666666-66666-666-66+6+6+6+6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-77777-777-77+7+7+7+7}{7} = \frac{888888-88888-888-88+8+8+8+8}{8} = \frac{999999-99999-999-99+9+9+9+9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 999882 &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 883 &:= \frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1) + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222 - 2) + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333 - 3) + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444 - 4) + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555 - 5) + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666 - 6) + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777 - 7) + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888 - 8) + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999 - 9) + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8583 &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 11) \times (111 - 1) + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 22) \times (222 - 2) + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 33) \times (333 - 3) + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 44) \times (444 - 4) + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 55) \times (555 - 5) + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 66) \times (666 - 6) + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 77) \times (777 - 7) + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 88) \times (888 - 8) + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 99) \times (999 - 9) + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 85583 &:= \frac{(1111 - 111 - 111 - 111) \times (111 - 1) + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 222 - 222) \times (222 - 2) + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 333 - 333) \times (333 - 3) + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 444 - 444) \times (444 - 4) + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 555 - 555) \times (555 - 5) + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 666 - 666) \times (666 - 6) + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 777 - 777) \times (777 - 7) + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 888 - 888) \times (888 - 8) + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 999 - 999) \times (999 - 9) + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 855583 &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1111 - 1111) \times (111 - 1) + (1 + 1 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2222 - 2222) \times (222 - 2) + (2 + 2 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3333 - 3333) \times (333 - 3) + (3 + 3 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4444 - 4444) \times (444 - 4) + (4 + 4 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5555 - 5555) \times (555 - 5) + (5 + 5 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6666 - 6666) \times (666 - 6) + (6 + 6 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7777 - 7777) \times (777 - 7) + (7 + 7 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8888 - 8888) \times (888 - 8) + (8 + 8 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9999 - 9999) \times (999 - 9) + (9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 884 &:= \frac{(111 + 111 - 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222 - 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333 - 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 777 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4884 &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 - 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 - 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 - 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{44884} &:= \frac{(11111 + 111 - 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 222 - 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 333 - 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 444 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 555 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 666 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 777 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 888 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 999 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{444884} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111 - 1) \times (11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222 - 2) \times (22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333 - 3) \times (33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 444 - 4) \times (44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555 - 5) \times (55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666 - 6) \times (66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 777 - 7) \times (77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888 - 8) \times (88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999 - 9) \times (99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{885} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9885} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{99885} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{999885} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{886} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{4} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{5} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9886} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99886} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999886} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{887} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9887} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99887} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{999887} := \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 3 - 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

► **888** := $\frac{1111 - 111 - 111 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 - 3}{3}$
 $\frac{4444 - 444 - 444 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 - 6}{6}$
 $\frac{7777 - 777 - 777 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 - 9}{9}$

9888 := $\frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 - 3}{3}$
 $\frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 - 6}{6}$
 $\frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 - 9}{9}$

99888 := $\frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 - 3}{3}$
 $\frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 - 6}{6}$
 $\frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 - 9}{9}$

999888 := $\frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 - 3}{3}$
 $\frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 - 6}{6}$
 $\frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 - 9}{9}$

► **889** := $\frac{1111 - 111 - 111}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333}{3}$
 $\frac{4444 - 444 - 444}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666}{6}$
 $\frac{7777 - 777 - 777}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999}{9}$

9889 := $\frac{11111 - 1111 - 111}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333}{3}$
 $\frac{44444 - 4444 - 444}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666}{6}$
 $\frac{77777 - 7777 - 777}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999}{9}$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99889} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999889} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{890} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9890} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99890} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999890} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{891} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 6 + 6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 9 + 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9891} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99891} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999891} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{892} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9892} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99892} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{999892} := \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

► **893** := $\frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9}$

9893 := $\frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9}$

99893 := $\frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9}$

999893 := $\frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9}$

► **894** := $\frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111 + 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222 + 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333 + 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444 + 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555 + 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666 + 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777 + 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888 + 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999 + 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$

8894 := $\frac{(11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (1111 + 1) - 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (2222 + 2) - 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (3333 + 3) - 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (4444 + 4) - 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (5555 + 5) - 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (6666 + 6) - 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (7777 + 7) - 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (8888 + 8) - 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (9999 + 9) - 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88894} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times (11111+1) - 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times (22222+2) - 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times (33333+3) - 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times (44444+4) - 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times (55555+5) - 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times (66666+6) - 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times (77777+7) - 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times (88888+8) - 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times (99999+9) - 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888894} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times (111111+1) - 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times (222222+2) - 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times (333333+3) - 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times (444444+4) - 4 \times (4+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times (555555+5) - 5 \times (5+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times (666666+6) - 6 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times (777777+7) - 7 \times (7+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times (888888+8) - 8 \times (8+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times (999999+9) - 9 \times (9+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{895} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times (111+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times (222+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times (333+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times (444+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times (555+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times (666+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times (777+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times (888+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times (999+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8895} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times (1111+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times (2222+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times (3333+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times (4444+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times (5555+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times (6666+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times (7777+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times (8888+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times (9999+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88895} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times (11111+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times (22222+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times (33333+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times (44444+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times (55555+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times (66666+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times (77777+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times (88888+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times (99999+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888895} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times (111111+1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times (222222+2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times (333333+3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times (444444+4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times (555555+5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times (666666+6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times (777777+7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times (888888+8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times (999999+9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{896} := \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times (111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times (222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times (333+3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times (444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times (555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times (666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times (777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times (888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times (999+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8896} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times (1111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times (2222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times (3333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times (4444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times (5555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times (6666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times (7777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times (8888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times (9999+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88896} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times (11111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times (22222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times (33333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times (44444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times (55555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times (66666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times (77777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times (88888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times (99999+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888896} &:= \frac{(11-1-1-1) \times (111111+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2-2) \times (222222+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3-3) \times (333333+3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4-4) \times (444444+4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5-5) \times (555555+5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6-6) \times (666666+6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7-7) \times (777777+7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8-8) \times (888888+8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9-9) \times (999999+9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{897} &:= \frac{1111-111-111+11-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222-222-222+22-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333-333-333+33-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-444-444+44-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555-555-555+55-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666-666-666+66-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-777-777+77-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888-888-888+88-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999-999-999+99-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9897} &:= \frac{11111-1111-111+11-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2222-222+22-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3333-333+33-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-4444-444+44-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5555-555+55-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6666-666+66-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-7777-777+77-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888-8888-888+88-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999-9999-999+99-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99897} &:= \frac{111111-11111-111+11-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{222222-22222-222+22-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{333333-33333-333+33-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444-44444-444+44-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{555555-55555-555+55-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{666666-66666-666+66-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-77777-777+77-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{888888-88888-888+88-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{999999-99999-999+99-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{999897} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 + 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 + 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 + 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 + 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 + 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 + 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 + 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 + 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{898} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9898} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{99898} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{999898} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 + 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 + 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 + 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 + 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 + 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 + 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 + 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 + 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 + 99 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{899} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 66 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 99 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9899} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 + 66 - 6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 + 99 - 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99899} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999899} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{900} &:= \frac{(111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9900} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99900} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999900} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{901} := \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9901} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99901} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999901} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{902} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9902} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99902} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999902} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{903} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9903} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99903} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999903} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{904} &:= \frac{(111 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8904} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777+7+7) \times (77-7-7-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8) \times (88-8-8-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9) \times (99-9-9-9)}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88904} &:= \frac{(11111+1+1) \times (11-1-1-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2) \times (22-2-2-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3) \times (33-3-3-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4+4) \times (44-4-4-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5) \times (55-5-5-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6+6) \times (66-6-6-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7+7) \times (77-7-7-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8) \times (88-8-8-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9) \times (99-9-9-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888904} &:= \frac{(111111+1+1) \times (11-1-1-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2+2) \times (22-2-2-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3+3) \times (33-3-3-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4+4) \times (44-4-4-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5+5) \times (55-5-5-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6+6) \times (66-6-6-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7+7) \times (77-7-7-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8+8) \times (88-8-8-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9+9) \times (99-9-9-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{905} &:= \frac{(111+1+1) \times (11-1-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222+2+2) \times (22-2-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333+3+3) \times (33-3-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444+4+4) \times (44-4-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555+5+5) \times (55-5-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666+6+6) \times (66-6-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777+7+7) \times (77-7-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888+8+8) \times (88-8-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999+9+9) \times (99-9-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8905} &:= \frac{(1111+1+1) \times (11-1-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222+2+2) \times (22-2-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333+3+3) \times (33-3-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+4+4) \times (44-4-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555+5+5) \times (55-5-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666+6+6) \times (66-6-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+7+7) \times (77-7-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888+8+8) \times (88-8-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999+9+9) \times (99-9-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88905} &:= \frac{(11111+1+1) \times (11-1-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222+2+2) \times (22-2-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333+3+3) \times (33-3-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444+4+4) \times (44-4-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555+5+5) \times (55-5-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666+6+6) \times (66-6-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777+7+7) \times (77-7-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888+8+8) \times (88-8-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999+9+9) \times (99-9-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888905} &:= \frac{(111111+1+1) \times (11-1-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222+2+2) \times (22-2-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333+3+3) \times (33-3-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444+4+4) \times (44-4-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555+5+5) \times (55-5-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666+6+6) \times (66-6-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777+7+7) \times (77-7-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888+8+8) \times (88-8-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999+9+9) \times (99-9-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{906} := \frac{1111 \times (11-1-1) - (1+1+1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (22-2-2) - (2+2+2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (33-3-3) - (3+3+3) \times 33}{3 \times 33}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) - (4 + 4 + 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) - (5 + 5 + 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) - (6 + 6 + 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) - (7 + 7 + 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) - (8 + 8 + 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) - (9 + 9 + 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{90906} &:= \frac{111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) - (1 + 1 + 1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) - (2 + 2 + 2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) - (3 + 3 + 3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) - (4 + 4 + 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) - (5 + 5 + 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) - (6 + 6 + 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) - (7 + 7 + 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) - (8 + 8 + 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) - (9 + 9 + 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9090906} &:= \frac{11111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) - (1 + 1 + 1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{22222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) - (2 + 2 + 2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{33333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) - (3 + 3 + 3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) - (4 + 4 + 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{55555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) - (5 + 5 + 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{66666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) - (6 + 6 + 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) - (7 + 7 + 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{88888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) - (8 + 8 + 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{99999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) - (9 + 9 + 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{909090906} &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) - (1 + 1 + 1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) - (2 + 2 + 2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) - (3 + 3 + 3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) - (4 + 4 + 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) - (5 + 5 + 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) - (6 + 6 + 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) - (7 + 7 + 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) - (8 + 8 + 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) - (9 + 9 + 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{907} &:= \frac{1111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) - (1 + 1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) - (2 + 2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) - (3 + 3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) - (4 + 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) - (5 + 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) - (6 + 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) - (7 + 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) - (8 + 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) - (9 + 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{90907} &:= \frac{111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) - (1 + 1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) - (2 + 2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) - (3 + 3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) - (4 + 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) - (5 + 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) - (6 + 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) - (7 + 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) - (8 + 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) - (9 + 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9090907} &:= \frac{11111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) - (1 + 1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{22222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) - (2 + 2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{33333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) - (3 + 3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) - (4 + 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{55555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) - (5 + 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{66666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) - (6 + 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) - (7 + 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{88888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) - (8 + 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{99999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) - (9 + 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{909090907} &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) - (1 + 1) \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) - (2 + 2) \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) - (3 + 3) \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) - (4 + 4) \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) - (5 + 5) \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) - (6 + 6) \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) - (7 + 7) \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) - (8 + 8) \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) - (9 + 9) \times 99}{9 \times 99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{908} &:= \frac{1111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{90908} &:= \frac{111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9090908} &:= \frac{11111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{22222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{33333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\
 &:= \frac{44444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{55555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{66666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\
 &:= \frac{77777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{88888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{99999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{909090908} &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 99}{9 \times 99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{909} &:= \frac{1111 \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 33} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 66} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{90909} &:= \frac{111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 11} = \frac{222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 22} = \frac{333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 33} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 44} = \frac{555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 55} = \frac{666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 66}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 77} = \frac{888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 88} = \frac{999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 99}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9090909} &:= \frac{11111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 11} = \frac{22222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 22} = \frac{33333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 44} = \frac{55555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 55} = \frac{66666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 77} = \frac{88888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 88} = \frac{99999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{909090909} &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{910} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9910} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99910} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999910} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 + 11 + 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 + 22 + 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 + 33 + 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 + 44 + 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 + 55 + 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 + 66 + 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 + 77 + 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 + 88 + 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 + 99 + 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{911} := \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 11}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 22}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 33}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 44}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 55}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9911} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 + 11 + 11}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 + 22 + 22}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 + 33 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 + 44 + 44}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 + 55 + 55}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 + 66 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 + 99 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99911} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 + 11 + 11}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 + 22 + 22}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 + 33 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 + 44 + 44}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 + 55 + 55}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 + 66 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 + 99 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999911} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 + 11 + 11}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 + 22 + 22}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 + 33 + 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 + 44 + 44}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 + 55 + 55}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 + 66 + 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 + 77 + 77}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 + 88 + 88}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 + 99 + 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{912} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9912} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99912} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{999912} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{913} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9913} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{99913} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{999913} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{914} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9914} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99914} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999914} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{915} &:= \frac{11111 + 1}{11 + 1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{22222 + 2}{22 + 2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{33333 + 3}{33 + 3} - \frac{33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 4}{44 + 4} - \frac{44}{44} = \frac{55555 + 5}{55 + 5} - \frac{55}{55} = \frac{66666 + 6}{66 + 6} - \frac{66}{66} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 7}{77 + 7} - \frac{77}{77} = \frac{88888 + 8}{88 + 8} - \frac{88}{88} = \frac{99999 + 9}{99 + 9} - \frac{99}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925915} &:= \frac{11111111 + 1}{11 + 1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{22222222 + 2}{22 + 2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{33333333 + 3}{33 + 3} - \frac{33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 + 4}{44 + 4} - \frac{44}{44} = \frac{55555555 + 5}{55 + 5} - \frac{55}{55} = \frac{66666666 + 6}{66 + 6} - \frac{66}{66} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 + 7}{77 + 7} - \frac{77}{77} = \frac{88888888 + 8}{88 + 8} - \frac{88}{88} = \frac{99999999 + 9}{99 + 9} - \frac{99}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925915} &:= \frac{1111111111 + 1}{11 + 1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{2222222222 + 2}{22 + 2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{3333333333 + 3}{33 + 3} - \frac{33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 + 4}{44 + 4} - \frac{44}{44} = \frac{5555555555 + 5}{55 + 5} - \frac{55}{55} = \frac{6666666666 + 6}{66 + 6} - \frac{66}{66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 + 7}{77 + 7} - \frac{77}{77} = \frac{8888888888 + 8}{88 + 8} - \frac{88}{88} = \frac{9999999999 + 9}{99 + 9} - \frac{99}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925925915} &:= \frac{1111111111111 + 1}{11 + 1} - \frac{11}{1} = \frac{2222222222222 + 2}{22 + 2} - \frac{22}{2} = \frac{3333333333333 + 3}{33 + 3} - \frac{33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444444 + 4}{44 + 4} - \frac{44}{44} = \frac{5555555555555 + 5}{55 + 5} - \frac{55}{55} = \frac{6666666666666 + 6}{66 + 6} - \frac{66}{66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777777 + 7}{77 + 7} - \frac{77}{77} = \frac{8888888888888 + 8}{88 + 8} - \frac{88}{88} = \frac{9999999999999 + 9}{99 + 9} - \frac{99}{99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{916} := \frac{11111 + 1}{11 + 1} - \frac{11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 + 2}{22 + 2} - \frac{22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 + 3}{33 + 3} - \frac{33 - 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{44444+4}{44+4} - \frac{44-4}{4} = \frac{55555+5}{55+5} - \frac{55-5}{5} = \frac{66666+6}{66+6} - \frac{66-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777+7}{77+7} - \frac{77-7}{7} = \frac{88888+8}{88+8} - \frac{88-8}{8} = \frac{99999+9}{99+9} - \frac{99-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925916} &:= \frac{11111111+1}{11+1} - \frac{11-1}{1} = \frac{2222222+2}{22+2} - \frac{22-2}{2} = \frac{3333333+3}{33+3} - \frac{33-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444444+4}{44+4} - \frac{44-4}{4} = \frac{5555555+5}{55+5} - \frac{55-5}{5} = \frac{6666666+6}{66+6} - \frac{66-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777+7}{77+7} - \frac{77-7}{7} = \frac{8888888+8}{88+8} - \frac{88-8}{8} = \frac{9999999+9}{99+9} - \frac{99-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925916} &:= \frac{1111111111+1}{11+1} - \frac{11-1}{1} = \frac{22222222+2}{22+2} - \frac{22-2}{2} = \frac{33333333+3}{33+3} - \frac{33-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444+4}{44+4} - \frac{44-4}{4} = \frac{55555555+5}{55+5} - \frac{55-5}{5} = \frac{66666666+6}{66+6} - \frac{66-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777777+7}{77+7} - \frac{77-7}{7} = \frac{88888888+8}{88+8} - \frac{88-8}{8} = \frac{99999999+9}{99+9} - \frac{99-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925925916} &:= \frac{111111111111+1}{11+1} - \frac{11-1}{1} = \frac{2222222222+2}{22+2} - \frac{22-2}{2} = \frac{3333333333+3}{33+3} - \frac{33-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444444444+4}{44+4} - \frac{44-4}{4} = \frac{5555555555+5}{55+5} - \frac{55-5}{5} = \frac{6666666666+6}{66+6} - \frac{66-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777+7}{77+7} - \frac{77-7}{7} = \frac{8888888888+8}{88+8} - \frac{88-8}{8} = \frac{9999999999+9}{99+9} - \frac{99-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{917} &:= \frac{(111-11+1+1) \times (11-1-1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222-22+2+2) \times (22-2-2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333-33+3+3) \times (33-3-3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-44+4+4) \times (44-4-4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555-55+5+5) \times (55-5-5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666-66+6+6) \times (66-6-6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-77+7+7) \times (77-7-7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888-88+8+8) \times (88-8-8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999-99+9+9) \times (99-9-9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9917} &:= \frac{(1111-11+1+1) \times (11-1-1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222-22+2+2) \times (22-2-2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333-33+3+3) \times (33-3-3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-44+4+4) \times (44-4-4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555-55+5+5) \times (55-5-5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666-66+6+6) \times (66-6-6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-77+7+7) \times (77-7-7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888-88+8+8) \times (88-8-8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999-99+9+9) \times (99-9-9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99917} &:= \frac{(11111-11+1+1) \times (11-1-1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222-22+2+2) \times (22-2-2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333-33+3+3) \times (33-3-3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-44+4+4) \times (44-4-4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555-55+5+5) \times (55-5-5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666-66+6+6) \times (66-6-6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-77+7+7) \times (77-7-7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888-88+8+8) \times (88-8-8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999-99+9+9) \times (99-9-9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{999917} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{918} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9918} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{99918} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{999918} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{919} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9919} &:= \frac{(1111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99919} &:= \frac{(11111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999919} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11 + 1 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22 + 2 + 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33 + 3 + 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44 + 4 + 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55 + 5 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66 + 6 + 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77 + 7 + 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88 + 8 + 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99 + 9 + 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{920} &:= \frac{1111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{90920} &:= \frac{111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9090920} &:= \frac{11111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{22222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{33333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{55555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{66666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{88888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{99999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{909090920} &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{921} := \frac{1111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 33}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{90921} &:= \frac{111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 11} = \frac{222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 22} = \frac{333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 44} = \frac{555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 55} = \frac{666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 77} = \frac{888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 88} = \frac{999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9090921} &:= \frac{11111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 11} = \frac{22222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 22} = \frac{33333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 44} = \frac{55555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 55} = \frac{66666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 77} = \frac{88888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 88} = \frac{99999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{909090921} &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times (11 + 1)}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times (22 + 2)}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times (33 + 3)}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times (44 + 4)}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times (55 + 5)}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times (66 + 6)}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times (77 + 7)}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times (88 + 8)}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times (99 + 9)}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{922} &:= \frac{1111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{4444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{7777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{90922} &:= \frac{111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 11} = \frac{222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 22} = \frac{333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 44} = \frac{555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 55} = \frac{666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 77} = \frac{888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 88} = \frac{999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9090922} &:= \frac{11111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 11} = \frac{22222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 22} = \frac{33333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 44} = \frac{55555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 55} = \frac{66666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 77} = \frac{88888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 88} = \frac{99999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{909090922} &:= \frac{1111111111 \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 11} = \frac{2222222222 \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 22} = \frac{3333333333 \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 33} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444444 \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 44} = \frac{5555555555 \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 55} = \frac{6666666666 \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 66} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777777 \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 77} = \frac{8888888888 \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 88} = \frac{9999999999 \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{923} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{33 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{66 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{99 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{925923} &:= \frac{111111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{222222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{333333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{33 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{555555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{666666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{66 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{888888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{999999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{99 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{925925923} &:= \frac{11111111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{33 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{66 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{99 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{925925925923} &:= \frac{11111111111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222222222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333333333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{33 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444444444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555555555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666666666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{66 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777777777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888888888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999999999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{99 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{924} &:= \frac{11111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{33 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{66 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{99 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{925924} &:= \frac{11111111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{33 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{66 + 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{99 + 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925924} &:= \frac{11111111111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222222222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333333333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444444444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555555555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666666666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777777777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888888888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999999999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925925924} &:= \frac{1111111111111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{2222222222222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{3333333333333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{5555555555555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{6666666666666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{8888888888888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{9999999999999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{925} &:= \frac{11111 - 11}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 22}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 33}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 44}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 55}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 66}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 88}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 99}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925} &:= \frac{11111111 - 11}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222222 - 22}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333333 - 33}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 - 44}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555555 - 55}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666666 - 66}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 - 77}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888888 - 88}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999999 - 99}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925925} &:= \frac{11111111111 - 11}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222222222 - 22}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333333333 - 33}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444444444 - 44}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555555555 - 55}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666666666 - 66}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777777777 - 77}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888888888 - 88}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999999999 - 99}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925925925} &:= \frac{1111111111111 - 11}{11 + 1} = \frac{2222222222222 - 22}{22 + 2} = \frac{3333333333333 - 33}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444444 - 44}{44 + 4} = \frac{5555555555555 - 55}{55 + 5} = \frac{6666666666666 - 66}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777777 - 77}{77 + 7} = \frac{8888888888888 - 88}{88 + 8} = \frac{9999999999999 - 99}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{926} := \frac{11111 + 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 3}{33 + 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{44444 + 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925926} &:= \frac{11111111 + 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222222 + 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333333 + 3}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 + 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555555 + 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666666 + 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 + 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888888 + 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999999 + 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925926} &:= \frac{1111111111 + 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{2222222222 + 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{3333333333 + 3}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 + 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{5555555555 + 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{6666666666 + 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 + 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{8888888888 + 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{9999999999 + 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925925926} &:= \frac{1111111111111 + 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{2222222222222 + 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{3333333333333 + 3}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444444 + 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{5555555555555 + 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{6666666666666 + 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777777 + 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{8888888888888 + 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{9999999999999 + 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{927} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925927} &:= \frac{11111111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925927} &:= \frac{1111111111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{2222222222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{3333333333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{5555555555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{6666666666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{8888888888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{9999999999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{925925925927} &:= \frac{11111111111111 + 11 + 1 + 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{2222222222222 + 22 + 2 + 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{3333333333333 + 33 + 3 + 3}{33 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444444444 + 44 + 4 + 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{5555555555555 + 55 + 5 + 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{6666666666666 + 66 + 6 + 6}{66 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777777777 + 77 + 7 + 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{8888888888888 + 88 + 8 + 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{9999999999999 + 99 + 9 + 9}{99 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{928} &:= \frac{11111 + 11 + 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 22 + 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 33 + 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{33 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 + 44 + 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 55 + 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 66 + 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{66 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 + 77 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 88 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 99 + 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{99 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9278} &:= \frac{111111 + 111 + 111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 222 + 222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 333 + 333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{33 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 + 444 + 444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 555 + 555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 666 + 666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{66 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 + 777 + 777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 888 + 888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 999 + 999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{99 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{92778} &:= \frac{1111111 + 1111 + 1111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 2222 + 2222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 3333 + 3333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{33 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 + 4444 + 4444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 5555 + 5555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 6666 + 6666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{66 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 + 7777 + 7777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 8888 + 8888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 9999 + 9999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{99 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{927778} &:= \frac{11111111 + 11111 + 11111 + 1 + 1 + 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222222 + 22222 + 22222 + 2 + 2 + 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333333 + 33333 + 33333 + 3 + 3 + 3}{33 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444444 + 44444 + 44444 + 4 + 4 + 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555555 + 55555 + 55555 + 5 + 5 + 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666666 + 66666 + 66666 + 6 + 6 + 6}{66 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777777 + 77777 + 77777 + 7 + 7 + 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888888 + 88888 + 88888 + 8 + 8 + 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999999 + 99999 + 99999 + 9 + 9 + 9}{99 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{929} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(2222 + 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(3333 + 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(5555 + 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(6666 + 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(8888 + 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(9999 + 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{90929} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(222222 + 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(333333 + 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(555555 + 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(666666 + 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777777 + 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(888888 + 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(999999 + 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9090929} &:= \frac{(11111111 + 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(22222222 + 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(33333333 + 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44444444 + 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(55555555 + 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(66666666 + 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77777777 + 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(88888888 + 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(99999999 + 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{909090929} &:= \frac{(1111111111 + 11) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 11 \times 11}{1 \times 11} = \frac{(2222222222 + 22) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 22 \times 22}{2 \times 22} = \frac{(3333333333 + 33) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 33 \times 33}{3 \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444444 + 44) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 44 \times 44}{4 \times 44} = \frac{(5555555555 + 55) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 55 \times 55}{5 \times 55} = \frac{(6666666666 + 66) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 66 \times 66}{6 \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777777 + 77) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 77 \times 77}{7 \times 77} = \frac{(8888888888 + 88) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 88 \times 88}{8 \times 88} = \frac{(9999999999 + 99) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 99 \times 99}{9 \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{930} &:= \frac{11111 - 11}{11 + 1} + \frac{11 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222 - 22}{22 + 2} + \frac{22 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333 - 33}{33 + 3} + \frac{33 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 44}{44 + 4} + \frac{44 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555 - 55}{55 + 5} + \frac{55 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666 - 66}{66 + 6} + \frac{66 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 77}{77 + 7} + \frac{77 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888 - 88}{88 + 8} + \frac{88 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999 - 99}{99 + 9} + \frac{99 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925930} &:= \frac{11111111 - 11}{11 + 1} + \frac{11 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22222222 - 22}{22 + 2} + \frac{22 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33333333 - 33}{33 + 3} + \frac{33 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 - 44}{44 + 4} + \frac{44 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55555555 - 55}{55 + 5} + \frac{55 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66666666 - 66}{66 + 6} + \frac{66 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 - 77}{77 + 7} + \frac{77 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88888888 - 88}{88 + 8} + \frac{88 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99999999 - 99}{99 + 9} + \frac{99 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925930} &:= \frac{1111111111 - 11}{11 + 1} + \frac{11 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{2222222222 - 22}{22 + 2} + \frac{22 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{3333333333 - 33}{33 + 3} + \frac{33 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 - 44}{44 + 4} + \frac{44 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{5555555555 - 55}{55 + 5} + \frac{55 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{6666666666 - 66}{66 + 6} + \frac{66 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 - 77}{77 + 7} + \frac{77 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{8888888888 - 88}{88 + 8} + \frac{88 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{9999999999 - 99}{99 + 9} + \frac{99 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925925930} &:= \frac{111111111111 - 11}{11 + 1} + \frac{11 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222222222222 - 22}{22 + 2} + \frac{22 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333333333333 - 33}{33 + 3} + \frac{33 - 3}{3 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444444444 - 44}{44 + 4} + \frac{44 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555555555555 - 55}{55 + 5} + \frac{55 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666666666666 - 66}{66 + 6} + \frac{66 - 6}{6 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777777777 - 77}{77 + 7} + \frac{77 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888888888888 - 88}{88 + 8} + \frac{88 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999999999999 - 99}{99 + 9} + \frac{99 - 9}{9 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{931} := \frac{(111 + 11 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{7931} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{77931} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{777931} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 11) \times (11 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 22) \times (22 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 33) \times (33 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 44) \times (44 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 55) \times (55 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 66) \times (66 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 77) \times (77 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 88) \times (88 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 99) \times (99 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{932} &:= \frac{(111 \times (1 + 1) + 11 \times 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 \times (2 + 2) + 22 \times 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 \times (3 + 3) + 33 \times 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 \times (4 + 4) + 44 \times 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 \times (5 + 5) + 55 \times 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 \times (6 + 6) + 66 \times 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 \times (7 + 7) + 77 \times 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 \times (8 + 8) + 88 \times 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 \times (9 + 9) + 99 \times 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8932} &:= \frac{(1111 \times (1 + 1) + 11 \times 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 \times (2 + 2) + 22 \times 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 \times (3 + 3) + 33 \times 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 \times (4 + 4) + 44 \times 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 \times (5 + 5) + 55 \times 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 \times (6 + 6) + 66 \times 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 \times (7 + 7) + 77 \times 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 \times (8 + 8) + 88 \times 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 \times (9 + 9) + 99 \times 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88932} &:= \frac{(11111 \times (1 + 1) + 11 \times 1) \times (1 + 1 + 1 + 1)}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 \times (2 + 2) + 22 \times 2) \times (2 + 2 + 2 + 2)}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 \times (3 + 3) + 33 \times 3) \times (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 \times (4 + 4) + 44 \times 4) \times (4 + 4 + 4 + 4)}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 \times (5 + 5) + 55 \times 5) \times (5 + 5 + 5 + 5)}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 \times (6 + 6) + 66 \times 6) \times (6 + 6 + 6 + 6)}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 \times (7 + 7) + 77 \times 7) \times (7 + 7 + 7 + 7)}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 \times (8 + 8) + 88 \times 8) \times (8 + 8 + 8 + 8)}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 \times (9 + 9) + 99 \times 9) \times (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888932} &:= \frac{(111111 \times (1+1) + 11 \times 1) \times (1+1+1+1)}{1 \times 1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 \times (2+2) + 22 \times 2) \times (2+2+2+2)}{2 \times 2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 \times (3+3) + 33 \times 3) \times (3+3+3+3)}{3 \times 3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 \times (4+4) + 44 \times 4) \times (4+4+4+4)}{4 \times 4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 \times (5+5) + 55 \times 5) \times (5+5+5+5)}{5 \times 5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 \times (6+6) + 66 \times 6) \times (6+6+6+6)}{6 \times 6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 \times (7+7) + 77 \times 7) \times (7+7+7+7)}{7 \times 7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 \times (8+8) + 88 \times 8) \times (8+8+8+8)}{8 \times 8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 \times (9+9) + 99 \times 9) \times (9+9+9+9)}{9 \times 9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{933} &:= \frac{(1111+11) \times (11-1) - (11+1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times (11+1)} = \frac{(2222+22) \times (22-2) - (22+2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times (22+2)} = \frac{(3333+33) \times (33-3) - (33+3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times (33+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+44) \times (44-4) - (44+4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times (44+4)} = \frac{(5555+55) \times (55-5) - (55+5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times (55+5)} = \frac{(6666+66) \times (66-6) - (66+6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times (66+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+77) \times (77-7) - (77+7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times (77+7)} = \frac{(8888+88) \times (88-8) - (88+8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times (88+8)} = \frac{(9999+99) \times (99-9) - (99+9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times (99+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925933} &:= \frac{(1111111+11) \times (11-1) - (11+1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times (11+1)} = \frac{(2222222+22) \times (22-2) - (22+2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times (22+2)} = \frac{(3333333+33) \times (33-3) - (33+3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times (33+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444+44) \times (44-4) - (44+4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times (44+4)} = \frac{(5555555+55) \times (55-5) - (55+5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times (55+5)} = \frac{(6666666+66) \times (66-6) - (66+6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times (66+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777+77) \times (77-7) - (77+7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times (77+7)} = \frac{(8888888+88) \times (88-8) - (88+8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times (88+8)} = \frac{(9999999+99) \times (99-9) - (99+9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times (99+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925933} &:= \frac{(111111111+11) \times (11-1) - (11+1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times (11+1)} = \frac{(222222222+22) \times (22-2) - (22+2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times (22+2)} = \frac{(333333333+33) \times (33-3) - (33+3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times (33+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444444444+44) \times (44-4) - (44+4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times (44+4)} = \frac{(555555555+55) \times (55-5) - (55+5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times (55+5)} = \frac{(666666666+66) \times (66-6) - (66+6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times (66+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777777777+77) \times (77-7) - (77+7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times (77+7)} = \frac{(888888888+88) \times (88-8) - (88+8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times (88+8)} = \frac{(999999999+99) \times (99-9) - (99+9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times (99+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925925933} &:= \frac{(11111111111+11) \times (11-1) - (11+1) \times (1+1)}{1 \times (11+1)} = \frac{(22222222222+22) \times (22-2) - (22+2) \times (2+2)}{2 \times (22+2)} = \frac{(33333333333+33) \times (33-3) - (33+3) \times (3+3)}{3 \times (33+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(44444444444+44) \times (44-4) - (44+4) \times (4+4)}{4 \times (44+4)} = \frac{(55555555555+55) \times (55-5) - (55+5) \times (5+5)}{5 \times (55+5)} = \frac{(66666666666+66) \times (66-6) - (66+6) \times (6+6)}{6 \times (66+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(77777777777+77) \times (77-7) - (77+7) \times (7+7)}{7 \times (77+7)} = \frac{(88888888888+88) \times (88-8) - (88+8) \times (8+8)}{8 \times (88+8)} = \frac{(99999999999+99) \times (99-9) - (99+9) \times (9+9)}{9 \times (99+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{934} &:= \frac{(1111+11) \times (11-1) - (11+1) \times 1}{1 \times (11+1)} = \frac{(2222+22) \times (22-2) - (22+2) \times 2}{2 \times (22+2)} = \frac{(3333+33) \times (33-3) - (33+3) \times 3}{3 \times (33+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444+44) \times (44-4) - (44+4) \times 4}{4 \times (44+4)} = \frac{(5555+55) \times (55-5) - (55+5) \times 5}{5 \times (55+5)} = \frac{(6666+66) \times (66-6) - (66+6) \times 6}{6 \times (66+6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777+77) \times (77-7) - (77+7) \times 7}{7 \times (77+7)} = \frac{(8888+88) \times (88-8) - (88+8) \times 8}{8 \times (88+8)} = \frac{(9999+99) \times (99-9) - (99+9) \times 9}{9 \times (99+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925934} &:= \frac{(1111111+11) \times (11-1) - (11+1) \times 1}{1 \times (11+1)} = \frac{(2222222+22) \times (22-2) - (22+2) \times 2}{2 \times (22+2)} = \frac{(3333333+33) \times (33-3) - (33+3) \times 3}{3 \times (33+3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444+44) \times (44-4) - (44+4) \times 4}{4 \times (44+4)} = \frac{(5555555+55) \times (55-5) - (55+5) \times 5}{5 \times (55+5)} = \frac{(6666666+66) \times (66-6) - (66+6) \times 6}{6 \times (66+6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777777 + 77) \times (77 - 7) - (77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times (77 + 7)} = \frac{(8888888 + 88) \times (88 - 8) - (88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times (88 + 8)} = \frac{(9999999 + 99) \times (99 - 9) - (99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times (99 + 9)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925934} &:= \frac{(1111111111 + 11) \times (11 - 1) - (11 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times (11 + 1)} = \frac{(2222222222 + 22) \times (22 - 2) - (22 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times (22 + 2)} = \frac{(3333333333 + 33) \times (33 - 3) - (33 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times (33 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444444 + 44) \times (44 - 4) - (44 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times (44 + 4)} = \frac{(5555555555 + 55) \times (55 - 5) - (55 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times (55 + 5)} = \frac{(6666666666 + 66) \times (66 - 6) - (66 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times (66 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777777 + 77) \times (77 - 7) - (77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times (77 + 7)} = \frac{(8888888888 + 88) \times (88 - 8) - (88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times (88 + 8)} = \frac{(9999999999 + 99) \times (99 - 9) - (99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times (99 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925925934} &:= \frac{(1111111111111 + 11) \times (11 - 1) - (11 + 1) \times 1}{1 \times (11 + 1)} = \frac{(2222222222222 + 22) \times (22 - 2) - (22 + 2) \times 2}{2 \times (22 + 2)} = \frac{(3333333333333 + 33) \times (33 - 3) - (33 + 3) \times 3}{3 \times (33 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444444444 + 44) \times (44 - 4) - (44 + 4) \times 4}{4 \times (44 + 4)} = \frac{(5555555555555 + 55) \times (55 - 5) - (55 + 5) \times 5}{5 \times (55 + 5)} = \frac{(6666666666666 + 66) \times (66 - 6) - (66 + 6) \times 6}{6 \times (66 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777777777 + 77) \times (77 - 7) - (77 + 7) \times 7}{7 \times (77 + 7)} = \frac{(8888888888888 + 88) \times (88 - 8) - (88 + 8) \times 8}{8 \times (88 + 8)} = \frac{(9999999999999 + 99) \times (99 - 9) - (99 + 9) \times 9}{9 \times (99 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{935} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 - 1 - 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 222 - 2 - 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 333 - 3 - 3}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 - 4 - 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 555 - 5 - 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 666 - 6 - 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 - 7 - 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 888 - 8 - 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 999 - 9 - 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925935} &:= \frac{111111111 + 111 - 1 - 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{222222222 + 222 - 2 - 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{333333333 + 333 - 3 - 3}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444444 + 444 - 4 - 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{555555555 + 555 - 5 - 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{666666666 + 666 - 6 - 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777777 + 777 - 7 - 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{888888888 + 888 - 8 - 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{999999999 + 999 - 9 - 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925935} &:= \frac{11111111111 + 111 - 1 - 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222222222 + 222 - 2 - 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333333333 + 333 - 3 - 3}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444444444 + 444 - 4 - 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555555555 + 555 - 5 - 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666666666 + 666 - 6 - 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777777777 + 777 - 7 - 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888888888 + 888 - 8 - 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999999999 + 999 - 9 - 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925925935} &:= \frac{1111111111111 + 111 - 1 - 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{2222222222222 + 222 - 2 - 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{3333333333333 + 333 - 3 - 3}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444444 + 444 - 4 - 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{5555555555555 + 555 - 5 - 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{6666666666666 + 666 - 6 - 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777777 + 777 - 7 - 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{8888888888888 + 888 - 8 - 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{9999999999999 + 999 - 9 - 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{936} := \frac{11111 + 111 + 11 - 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 22 - 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 33 - 3}{33 + 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 44 - 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 55 - 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 66 - 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 77 - 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 88 - 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 99 - 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9361} &:= \frac{111111 + 1111 + 111 - 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{222222 + 2222 + 222 - 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{333333 + 3333 + 333 - 3}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 + 4444 + 444 - 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{555555 + 5555 + 555 - 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{666666 + 6666 + 666 - 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 + 7777 + 777 - 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{888888 + 8888 + 888 - 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{999999 + 9999 + 999 - 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{93611} &:= \frac{1111111 + 11111 + 1111 - 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{2222222 + 22222 + 2222 - 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{3333333 + 33333 + 3333 - 3}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 + 44444 + 4444 - 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{5555555 + 55555 + 5555 - 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{6666666 + 66666 + 6666 - 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 + 77777 + 7777 - 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{8888888 + 88888 + 8888 - 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{9999999 + 99999 + 9999 - 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{936111} &:= \frac{11111111 + 111111 + 11111 - 1}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222222 + 222222 + 22222 - 2}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333333 + 333333 + 33333 - 3}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 + 444444 + 44444 - 4}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555555 + 555555 + 55555 - 5}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666666 + 666666 + 66666 - 6}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 + 777777 + 77777 - 7}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888888 + 888888 + 88888 - 8}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999999 + 999999 + 99999 - 9}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{937} &:= \frac{11111 + 111 + 11 + 11}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222 + 222 + 22 + 22}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333 + 333 + 33 + 33}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 + 444 + 44 + 44}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555 + 555 + 55 + 55}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666 + 666 + 66 + 66}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 + 777 + 77 + 77}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888 + 888 + 88 + 88}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999 + 999 + 99 + 99}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925937} &:= \frac{11111111 + 111 + 11 + 11}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222222 + 222 + 22 + 22}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333333 + 333 + 33 + 33}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{44444444 + 444 + 44 + 44}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555555 + 555 + 55 + 55}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666666 + 666 + 66 + 66}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{77777777 + 777 + 77 + 77}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888888 + 888 + 88 + 88}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999999 + 999 + 99 + 99}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{925925937} &:= \frac{1111111111 + 111 + 11 + 11}{11 + 1} = \frac{2222222222 + 222 + 22 + 22}{22 + 2} = \frac{3333333333 + 333 + 33 + 33}{33 + 3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444444 + 444 + 44 + 44}{44 + 4} = \frac{5555555555 + 555 + 55 + 55}{55 + 5} = \frac{6666666666 + 666 + 66 + 66}{66 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777777 + 777 + 77 + 77}{77 + 7} = \frac{8888888888 + 888 + 88 + 88}{88 + 8} = \frac{9999999999 + 999 + 99 + 99}{99 + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{925925925937} &:= \frac{11111111111111 + 111 + 11 + 11}{11 + 1} = \frac{22222222222222 + 222 + 22 + 22}{22 + 2} = \frac{33333333333333 + 333 + 33 + 33}{33 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444444444444 + 444 + 44 + 44}{44 + 4} = \frac{55555555555555 + 555 + 55 + 55}{55 + 5} = \frac{66666666666666 + 666 + 66 + 66}{66 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777777777777 + 777 + 77 + 77}{77 + 7} = \frac{88888888888888 + 888 + 88 + 88}{88 + 8} = \frac{99999999999999 + 999 + 99 + 99}{99 + 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{938} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7938} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{77938} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{777938} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times (11 + 11 - 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times (22 + 22 - 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times (33 + 33 - 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 44 - 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 55 - 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 66 - 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 77 - 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 88 - 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 99 - 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{939} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9939} &:= \frac{(1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99939} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999939} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) - 11 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) - 22 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) - 33 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) - 44 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) - 55 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) - 66 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) - 77 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) - 88 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) - 99 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{940} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times (11 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(2222 + 222) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(3333 + 333) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times (33 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times (44 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(5555 + 555) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times (55 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(6666 + 666) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(8888 + 888) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times (88 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(9999 + 999) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times (99 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9400} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111) \times (111 - 11)}{1 \times (11 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(2222 + 222) \times (222 - 22)}{2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(3333 + 333) \times (333 - 33)}{3 \times (33 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444) \times (444 - 44)}{4 \times (44 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(5555 + 555) \times (555 - 55)}{5 \times (55 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(6666 + 666) \times (666 - 66)}{6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777) \times (777 - 77)}{7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(8888 + 888) \times (888 - 88)}{8 \times (88 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(9999 + 999) \times (999 - 99)}{9 \times (99 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{94000} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111) \times (1111 - 111)}{1 \times (11 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(2222 + 222) \times (2222 - 222)}{2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(3333 + 333) \times (3333 - 333)}{3 \times (33 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444) \times (4444 - 444)}{4 \times (44 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(5555 + 555) \times (5555 - 555)}{5 \times (55 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(6666 + 666) \times (6666 - 666)}{6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777) \times (7777 - 777)}{7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(8888 + 888) \times (8888 - 888)}{8 \times (88 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(9999 + 999) \times (9999 - 999)}{9 \times (99 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{940000} &:= \frac{(1111 + 111) \times (11111 - 1111)}{1 \times (11 + 1 + 1)} = \frac{(2222 + 222) \times (22222 - 2222)}{2 \times (22 + 2 + 2)} = \frac{(3333 + 333) \times (33333 - 3333)}{3 \times (33 + 3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444) \times (44444 - 4444)}{4 \times (44 + 4 + 4)} = \frac{(5555 + 555) \times (55555 - 5555)}{5 \times (55 + 5 + 5)} = \frac{(6666 + 666) \times (66666 - 6666)}{6 \times (66 + 6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777) \times (77777 - 7777)}{7 \times (77 + 7 + 7)} = \frac{(8888 + 888) \times (88888 - 8888)}{8 \times (88 + 8 + 8)} = \frac{(9999 + 999) \times (99999 - 9999)}{9 \times (99 + 9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{941} := \frac{(1111 + 1) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{(11 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 2) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{(22 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 3) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{(33 + 3 + 3) \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 + 4) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{(44 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 5) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{(55 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 6) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{(66 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{(77 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 8) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{(88 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 9) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{(99 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{94111} &:= \frac{(111111 + 111) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{(11 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{(22 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{(33 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 444) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{(44 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{(55 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{(66 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 777) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{(77 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{(88 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{(99 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9411111} &:= \frac{(11111111 + 11111) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{(11 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222222 + 22222) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{(22 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333333 + 33333) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{(33 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444444 + 44444) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{(44 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555555 + 55555) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{(55 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666666 + 66666) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{(66 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777777 + 77777) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{(77 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888888 + 88888) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{(88 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999999 + 99999) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{(99 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{941111111} &:= \frac{(1111111111 + 1111111) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{(11 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222222 + 2222222) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{(22 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333333 + 3333333) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{(33 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444444444 + 4444444) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{(44 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555555 + 5555555) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{(55 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666666 + 6666666) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{(66 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777777 + 7777777) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{(77 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888888 + 8888888) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{(88 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999999 + 9999999) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{(99 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{942} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1) \times (111 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (11 + 1)}{11 \times (11 + 1)} = \frac{(2222 - 2) \times (222 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (22 + 2)}{22 \times (22 + 2)} = \frac{(3333 - 3) \times (333 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (33 + 3)}{33 \times (33 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 4) \times (444 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (44 + 4)}{44 \times (44 + 4)} = \frac{(5555 - 5) \times (555 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (55 + 5)}{55 \times (55 + 5)} = \frac{(6666 - 6) \times (666 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (66 + 6)}{66 \times (66 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7) \times (777 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (77 + 7)}{77 \times (77 + 7)} = \frac{(8888 - 8) \times (888 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (88 + 8)}{88 \times (88 + 8)} = \frac{(9999 - 9) \times (999 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (99 + 9)}{99 \times (99 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{94182} &:= \frac{(111111 - 111) \times (111 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (11 + 1)}{11 \times (11 + 1)} = \frac{(222222 - 222) \times (222 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (22 + 2)}{22 \times (22 + 2)} = \frac{(333333 - 333) \times (333 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (33 + 3)}{33 \times (33 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 444) \times (444 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (44 + 4)}{44 \times (44 + 4)} = \frac{(555555 - 555) \times (555 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (55 + 5)}{55 \times (55 + 5)} = \frac{(666666 - 666) \times (666 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (66 + 6)}{66 \times (66 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 777) \times (777 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (77 + 7)}{77 \times (77 + 7)} = \frac{(888888 - 888) \times (888 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (88 + 8)}{88 \times (88 + 8)} = \frac{(999999 - 999) \times (999 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (99 + 9)}{99 \times (99 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9418182} &:= \frac{(11111111 - 11111) \times (111 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (11 + 1)}{11 \times (11 + 1)} = \frac{(22222222 - 22222) \times (222 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (22 + 2)}{22 \times (22 + 2)} = \frac{(33333333 - 33333) \times (333 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (33 + 3)}{33 \times (33 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(44444444 - 44444) \times (444 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (44 + 4)}{44 \times (44 + 4)} = \frac{(55555555 - 55555) \times (555 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (55 + 5)}{55 \times (55 + 5)} = \frac{(66666666 - 66666) \times (666 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (66 + 6)}{66 \times (66 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(77777777 - 77777) \times (777 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (77 + 7)}{77 \times (77 + 7)} = \frac{(88888888 - 88888) \times (888 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (88 + 8)}{88 \times (88 + 8)} = \frac{(99999999 - 99999) \times (999 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (99 + 9)}{99 \times (99 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{941818182} := \frac{(1111111111 - 1111111) \times (111 + 1) + (1 + 1) \times (11 + 1)}{11 \times (11 + 1)} = \frac{(2222222222 - 2222222) \times (222 + 2) + (2 + 2) \times (22 + 2)}{22 \times (22 + 2)} = \frac{(3333333333 - 3333333) \times (333 + 3) + (3 + 3) \times (33 + 3)}{33 \times (33 + 3)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444444444 - 4444444) \times (444 + 4) + (4 + 4) \times (44 + 4)}{44 \times (44 + 4)} = \frac{(5555555555 - 5555555) \times (555 + 5) + (5 + 5) \times (55 + 5)}{55 \times (55 + 5)} = \frac{(6666666666 - 6666666) \times (666 + 6) + (6 + 6) \times (66 + 6)}{66 \times (66 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777777777 - 7777777) \times (777 + 7) + (7 + 7) \times (77 + 7)}{77 \times (77 + 7)} = \frac{(8888888888 - 8888888) \times (888 + 8) + (8 + 8) \times (88 + 8)}{88 \times (88 + 8)} = \frac{(9999999999 - 9999999) \times (999 + 9) + (9 + 9) \times (99 + 9)}{99 \times (99 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 943 &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1) \times (11 + 11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2) \times (22 + 22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3) \times (33 + 33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4) \times (44 + 44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5) \times (55 + 55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6) \times (66 + 66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 + 77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 + 88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 + 99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9453 &:= \frac{(1111 + 111 + 11) \times (11 + 11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 222 + 22) \times (22 + 22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 333 + 33) \times (33 + 33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 444 + 44) \times (44 + 44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 555 + 55) \times (55 + 55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 666 + 66) \times (66 + 66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 777 + 77) \times (77 + 77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 888 + 88) \times (88 + 88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 999 + 99) \times (99 + 99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 94553 &:= \frac{(11111 + 1111 + 111) \times (11 + 11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 2222 + 222) \times (22 + 22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 3333 + 333) \times (33 + 33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 4444 + 444) \times (44 + 44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 5555 + 555) \times (55 + 55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 6666 + 666) \times (66 + 66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 7777 + 777) \times (77 + 77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 8888 + 888) \times (88 + 88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 9999 + 999) \times (99 + 99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 945553 &:= \frac{(111111 + 11111 + 1111) \times (11 + 11 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22222 + 2222) \times (22 + 22 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33333 + 3333) \times (33 + 33 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44444 + 4444) \times (44 + 44 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55555 + 5555) \times (55 + 55 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66666 + 6666) \times (66 + 66 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77777 + 7777) \times (77 + 77 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88888 + 8888) \times (88 + 88 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99999 + 9999) \times (99 + 99 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \quad 944 &:= \frac{(11111 - 111) \times (1 + 1) - (111 + 1) \times 11}{(1 + 1) \times 11} = \frac{(22222 - 222) \times (2 + 2) - (222 + 2) \times 22}{(2 + 2) \times 22} = \frac{(33333 - 333) \times (3 + 3) - (333 + 3) \times 33}{(3 + 3) \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 444) \times (4 + 4) - (444 + 4) \times 44}{(4 + 4) \times 44} = \frac{(55555 - 555) \times (5 + 5) - (555 + 5) \times 55}{(5 + 5) \times 55} = \frac{(66666 - 666) \times (6 + 6) - (666 + 6) \times 66}{(6 + 6) \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 777) \times (7 + 7) - (777 + 7) \times 77}{(7 + 7) \times 77} = \frac{(88888 - 888) \times (8 + 8) - (888 + 8) \times 88}{(8 + 8) \times 88} = \frac{(99999 - 999) \times (9 + 9) - (999 + 9) \times 99}{(9 + 9) \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9944 &:= \frac{(111111 - 1111) \times (1 + 1) - (111 + 1) \times 11}{(1 + 1) \times 11} = \frac{(222222 - 2222) \times (2 + 2) - (222 + 2) \times 22}{(2 + 2) \times 22} = \frac{(333333 - 3333) \times (3 + 3) - (333 + 3) \times 33}{(3 + 3) \times 33} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 4444) \times (4 + 4) - (444 + 4) \times 44}{(4 + 4) \times 44} = \frac{(555555 - 5555) \times (5 + 5) - (555 + 5) \times 55}{(5 + 5) \times 55} = \frac{(666666 - 6666) \times (6 + 6) - (666 + 6) \times 66}{(6 + 6) \times 66} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7777) \times (7 + 7) - (777 + 7) \times 77}{(7 + 7) \times 77} = \frac{(888888 - 8888) \times (8 + 8) - (888 + 8) \times 88}{(8 + 8) \times 88} = \frac{(999999 - 9999) \times (9 + 9) - (999 + 9) \times 99}{(9 + 9) \times 99} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99944 &:= \frac{(1111111 - 11111) \times (1+1) - (111+1) \times 11}{(1+1) \times 11} = \frac{(2222222 - 22222) \times (2+2) - (222+2) \times 22}{(2+2) \times 22} = \frac{(3333333 - 33333) \times (3+3) - (333+3) \times 33}{(3+3) \times 33} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444444 - 44444) \times (4+4) - (444+4) \times 44}{(4+4) \times 44} = \frac{(5555555 - 55555) \times (5+5) - (555+5) \times 55}{(5+5) \times 55} = \frac{(6666666 - 66666) \times (6+6) - (666+6) \times 66}{(6+6) \times 66} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777777 - 77777) \times (7+7) - (777+7) \times 77}{(7+7) \times 77} = \frac{(8888888 - 88888) \times (8+8) - (888+8) \times 88}{(8+8) \times 88} = \frac{(9999999 - 99999) \times (9+9) - (999+9) \times 99}{(9+9) \times 99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 999944 &:= \frac{(11111111 - 111111) \times (1+1) - (111+1) \times 11}{(1+1) \times 11} = \frac{(22222222 - 222222) \times (2+2) - (222+2) \times 22}{(2+2) \times 22} = \frac{(33333333 - 333333) \times (3+3) - (333+3) \times 33}{(3+3) \times 33} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444444 - 444444) \times (4+4) - (444+4) \times 44}{(4+4) \times 44} = \frac{(55555555 - 555555) \times (5+5) - (555+5) \times 55}{(5+5) \times 55} = \frac{(66666666 - 666666) \times (6+6) - (666+6) \times 66}{(6+6) \times 66} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777777 - 777777) \times (7+7) - (777+7) \times 77}{(7+7) \times 77} = \frac{(88888888 - 888888) \times (8+8) - (888+8) \times 88}{(8+8) \times 88} = \frac{(99999999 - 999999) \times (9+9) - (999+9) \times 99}{(9+9) \times 99}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 945 &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9745 &:= \frac{(1111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 97745 &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 977745 &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11 - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22 - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33 - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44 - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55 - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66 - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77 - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88 - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99 - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 946 &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9746} &:= \frac{(1111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{97746} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{977746} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{947} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9747} &:= \frac{(1111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{97747} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{977747} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

► **948** := $\frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11 + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22 + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33 + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44 + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55 + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66 + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77 + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88 + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99 + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$

9748 := $\frac{(1111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11 + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22 + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33 + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44 + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55 + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66 + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77 + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88 + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99 + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$

97748 := $\frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11 + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22 + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33 + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44 + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55 + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66 + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77 + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88 + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99 + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$

977748 := $\frac{(111111 - 11111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times 11 + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times 22 + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times 33 + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times 44 + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times 55 + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times 66 + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times 77 + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times 88 + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times 99 + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9}$

► **949** := $\frac{(111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$

9949 := $\frac{(1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$

99949 := $\frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}$

$$:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999949} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{950} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9950} &:= \frac{(1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99950} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999950} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{951} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9951} &:= \frac{(1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99951} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999951} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{952} &:= \frac{(11 + 11 + 11 + 1) \times (111 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(22 + 22 + 22 + 2) \times (222 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(33 + 33 + 33 + 3) \times (333 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(44 + 44 + 44 + 4) \times (444 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(55 + 55 + 55 + 5) \times (555 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(66 + 66 + 66 + 6) \times (666 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(77 + 77 + 77 + 7) \times (777 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(88 + 88 + 88 + 8) \times (888 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(99 + 99 + 99 + 9) \times (999 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9352} &:= \frac{(111 + 111 + 111 + 1) \times (111 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(222 + 222 + 222 + 2) \times (222 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(333 + 333 + 333 + 3) \times (333 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 444 + 444 + 4) \times (444 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(555 + 555 + 555 + 5) \times (555 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(666 + 666 + 666 + 6) \times (666 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 777 + 777 + 7) \times (777 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(888 + 888 + 888 + 8) \times (888 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(999 + 999 + 999 + 9) \times (999 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{93352} &:= \frac{(1111 + 1111 + 1111 + 1) \times (111 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(2222 + 2222 + 2222 + 2) \times (222 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(3333 + 3333 + 3333 + 3) \times (333 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 4444 + 4444 + 4) \times (444 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(5555 + 5555 + 5555 + 5) \times (555 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(6666 + 6666 + 6666 + 6) \times (666 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 7777 + 7777 + 7) \times (777 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(8888 + 8888 + 8888 + 8) \times (888 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(9999 + 9999 + 9999 + 9) \times (999 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{933352} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11111 + 11111 + 1) \times (111 + 1)}{(1 + 1) \times (1 + 1)} = \frac{(22222 + 22222 + 22222 + 2) \times (222 + 2)}{(2 + 2) \times (2 + 2)} = \frac{(33333 + 33333 + 33333 + 3) \times (333 + 3)}{(3 + 3) \times (3 + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44444 + 44444 + 4) \times (444 + 4)}{(4 + 4) \times (4 + 4)} = \frac{(55555 + 55555 + 55555 + 5) \times (555 + 5)}{(5 + 5) \times (5 + 5)} = \frac{(66666 + 66666 + 66666 + 6) \times (666 + 6)}{(6 + 6) \times (6 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77777 + 77777 + 7) \times (777 + 7)}{(7 + 7) \times (7 + 7)} = \frac{(88888 + 88888 + 88888 + 8) \times (888 + 8)}{(8 + 8) \times (8 + 8)} = \frac{(99999 + 99999 + 99999 + 9) \times (999 + 9)}{(9 + 9) \times (9 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{953} := \frac{(111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444-4-4-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555-5-5-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666-6-6-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7-7-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888-8-8-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999-9-9-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9953} &:= \frac{(1111-1-1-1-1-1) \times (11-1-1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222-2-2-2-2-2) \times (22-2-2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333-3-3-3-3-3) \times (33-3-3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-4-4-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555-5-5-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666-6-6-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-7-7-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888-8-8-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999-9-9-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99953} &:= \frac{(11111-1-1-1-1-1) \times (11-1-1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222-2-2-2-2-2) \times (22-2-2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333-3-3-3-3-3) \times (33-3-3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-4-4-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555-5-5-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666-6-6-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-7-7-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888-8-8-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999-9-9-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999953} &:= \frac{(111111-1-1-1-1-1) \times (11-1-1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222-2-2-2-2-2) \times (22-2-2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333-3-3-3-3-3) \times (33-3-3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444-4-4-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555-5-5-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666-6-6-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777-7-7-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888-8-8-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999-9-9-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{954} &:= \frac{(111-1-1-1-1-1) \times (11-1-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222-2-2-2-2-2) \times (22-2-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333-3-3-3-3-3) \times (33-3-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444-4-4-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555-5-5-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666-6-6-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777-7-7-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888-8-8-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999-9-9-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9954} &:= \frac{(1111-1-1-1-1-1) \times (11-1-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222-2-2-2-2-2) \times (22-2-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333-3-3-3-3-3) \times (33-3-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-4-4-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555-5-5-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666-6-6-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-7-7-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888-8-8-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999-9-9-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99954} &:= \frac{(11111-1-1-1-1-1) \times (11-1-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222-2-2-2-2-2) \times (22-2-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333-3-3-3-3-3) \times (33-3-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-4-4-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555-5-5-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666-6-6-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-7-7-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888-8-8-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999-9-9-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{999954} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{955} &:= \frac{(111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9955} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{99955} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{999955} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{956} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9956} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99956} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999956} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{957} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9757} &:= \frac{(1111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{97757} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1111 - 1 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2222 - 2 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3333 - 3 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4444 - 4 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5555 - 5 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6666 - 6 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7777 - 7 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8888 - 8 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9999 - 9 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{977757} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111 - 11111 - 1 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 22222 - 2 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 33333 - 3 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 44444 - 4 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 55555 - 5 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 66666 - 6 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 77777 - 7 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 88888 - 8 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 99999 - 9 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{958} := \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9758} &:= \frac{(1111 - 111 - 111 - 1 - 1) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 222 - 2 - 2) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 333 - 3 - 3) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 444 - 4 - 4) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 555 - 5 - 5) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 666 - 6 - 6) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 777 - 7 - 7) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 888 - 8 - 8) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 999 - 9 - 9) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{97758} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1111 - 1 - 1) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2222 - 2 - 2) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3333 - 3 - 3) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4444 - 4 - 4) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5555 - 5 - 5) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6666 - 6 - 6) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7777 - 7 - 7) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8888 - 8 - 8) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9999 - 9 - 9) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{977758} &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111 - 11111 - 1 - 1) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 22222 - 2 - 2) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 33333 - 3 - 3) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 44444 - 4 - 4) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 55555 - 5 - 5) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 66666 - 6 - 6) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 77777 - 7 - 7) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 88888 - 8 - 8) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 99999 - 9 - 9) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{959} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9959} &:= \frac{(1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99959} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{999959} := \frac{(111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

► **960** := $\frac{(111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

9960 := $\frac{(1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

99960 := $\frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

999960 := $\frac{(111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3)}{3 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

► **961** := $\frac{(111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

9961 := $\frac{(1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99961 &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 999961 &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 962 &:= \frac{(111 + 111) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 222) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 333) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 + 444) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 555) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 666) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 + 777) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 888) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 999) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 962962 &:= \frac{(111111 + 111111) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 222222) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 333333) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444 + 444444) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 555555) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 666666) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777 + 777777) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 888888) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 999999) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 962962962 &:= \frac{(11111111 + 11111111) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(22222222 + 22222222) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(33333333 + 33333333) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444444 + 44444444) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(55555555 + 55555555) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(66666666 + 66666666) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777777 + 77777777) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(88888888 + 88888888) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(99999999 + 99999999) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 962962962962 &:= \frac{(1111111111 + 1111111111) \times (11 + 1 + 1)}{(1 + 1 + 1) \times 1} = \frac{(2222222222 + 2222222222) \times (22 + 2 + 2)}{(2 + 2 + 2) \times 2} = \frac{(3333333333 + 3333333333) \times (33 + 3 + 3)}{(3 + 3 + 3) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444444444 + 4444444444) \times (44 + 4 + 4)}{(4 + 4 + 4) \times 4} = \frac{(5555555555 + 5555555555) \times (55 + 5 + 5)}{(5 + 5 + 5) \times 5} = \frac{(6666666666 + 6666666666) \times (66 + 6 + 6)}{(6 + 6 + 6) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777777777 + 7777777777) \times (77 + 7 + 7)}{(7 + 7 + 7) \times 7} = \frac{(8888888888 + 8888888888) \times (88 + 8 + 8)}{(8 + 8 + 8) \times 8} = \frac{(9999999999 + 9999999999) \times (99 + 9 + 9)}{(9 + 9 + 9) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 963 &:= \frac{(111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9963 &:= \frac{(1111-1-1-1-1) \times (11-1-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222-2-2-2-2) \times (22-2-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333-3-3-3-3) \times (33-3-3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444-4-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555-5-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666-6-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777-7-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888-8-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999-9-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99963 &:= \frac{(11111-1-1-1-1) \times (11-1-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222-2-2-2-2) \times (22-2-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333-3-3-3-3) \times (33-3-3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444-4-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555-5-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666-6-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777-7-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888-8-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999-9-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 999963 &:= \frac{(111111-1-1-1-1) \times (11-1-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222-2-2-2-2) \times (22-2-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333-3-3-3-3) \times (33-3-3)}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444-4-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555-5-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666-6-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6)}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777777-7-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888-8-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999-9-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9)}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright 964 &:= \frac{(111-1-1-1-1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222-2-2-2-2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333-3-3-3-3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444-4-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555-5-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666-6-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(777-7-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888-8-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999-9-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9964 &:= \frac{(1111-1-1-1-1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222-2-2-2-2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333-3-3-3-3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(4444-4-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555-5-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666-6-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(7777-7-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888-8-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999-9-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99964 &:= \frac{(11111-1-1-1-1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222-2-2-2-2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333-3-3-3-3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(44444-4-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555-5-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666-6-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(77777-7-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888-8-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999-9-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 999964 &:= \frac{(111111-1-1-1-1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222-2-2-2-2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333-3-3-3-3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(444444-4-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555-5-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666-6-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

► **965** := $\frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9}$

9965 := $\frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9}$

99965 := $\frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9}$

999965 := $\frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9}$

► **966** := $\frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9}$

9966 := $\frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9}$

99966 := $\frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999966} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{967} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9967} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99967} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999967} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{968} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9768 &:= \frac{(1111 - 111 - 111 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 222 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 333 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 444 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 555 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 666 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 777 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 888 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 999 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 97768 &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1111 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2222 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3333 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4444 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5555 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6666 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7777 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8888 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9999 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 977768 &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111 - 11111 - 1) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 22222 - 2) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 33333 - 3) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 44444 - 4) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 55555 - 5) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 66666 - 6) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 77777 - 7) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 88888 - 8) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 99999 - 9) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 969 &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11 - 1) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22 - 2) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33 - 3) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44 - 4) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55 - 5) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66 - 6) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77 - 7) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88 - 8) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99 - 9) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9769 &:= \frac{(1111 - 111 - 111 - 1) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 222 - 2) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 333 - 3) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 444 - 4) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 555 - 5) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 666 - 6) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 777 - 7) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 888 - 8) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 999 - 9) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 97769 &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1111 - 1) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2222 - 2) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3333 - 3) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4444 - 4) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5555 - 5) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6666 - 6) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7777 - 7) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8888 - 8) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9999 - 9) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 977769 &:= \frac{(111111 - 11111 - 11111 - 1) \times 11 + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 22222 - 2) \times 22 + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 33333 - 3) \times 33 + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 44444 - 4) \times 44 + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 55555 - 5) \times 55 + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 66666 - 6) \times 66 + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 77777 - 7) \times 77 + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 88888 - 8) \times 88 + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 99999 - 9) \times 99 + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

► **970** := $\frac{(111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222 - 2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333 - 3)}{33 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444 - 4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555 - 5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666 - 6)}{66 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777 - 7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888 - 8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999 - 9)}{99 \times 9}$

9970 := $\frac{(1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222 - 2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333 - 3)}{33 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444 - 4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555 - 5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666 - 6)}{66 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777 - 7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888 - 8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999 - 9)}{99 \times 9}$

99970 := $\frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222 - 2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333 - 3)}{33 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444 - 4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555 - 5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666 - 6)}{66 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777 - 7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888 - 8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999 - 9)}{99 \times 9}$

999970 := $\frac{(111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (111 - 1)}{11 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (222 - 2)}{22 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (333 - 3)}{33 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (444 - 4)}{44 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (555 - 5)}{55 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (666 - 6)}{66 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (777 - 7)}{77 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (888 - 8)}{88 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (999 - 9)}{99 \times 9}$

► **971** := $\frac{(111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$

9971 := $\frac{(1111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3}$
 $:= \frac{(4444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6}$
 $:= \frac{(7777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$

$$\begin{aligned} 99971 &:= \frac{(11111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 999971 &:= \frac{(111111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) - 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) - 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) - 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) - 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) - 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) - 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) - 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) - 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) - 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 972 &:= \frac{(111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9972 &:= \frac{(1111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 99972 &:= \frac{(11111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 999972 &:= \frac{(111111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 973 &:= \frac{(111 - 1 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(777-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9973} &:= \frac{(1111-1-1-1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222-2-2-2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333-3-3-3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99973} &:= \frac{(11111-1-1-1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222-2-2-2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333-3-3-3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999973} &:= \frac{(111111-1-1-1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222-2-2-2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333-3-3-3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444-4-4-4) \times (44-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555-5-5-5) \times (55-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666-6-6-6) \times (66-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777-7-7-7) \times (77-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888-8-8-8) \times (88-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999-9-9-9) \times (99-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{974} &:= \frac{1111-111-11-11-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222-222-22-22-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333-333-33-33-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444-444-44-44-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{5555-555-55-55-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{6666-666-66-66-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777-777-77-77-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{8888-888-88-88-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{9999-999-99-99-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9974} &:= \frac{11111-1111-11-11-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{22222-2222-22-22-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{33333-3333-33-33-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444-4444-44-44-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{55555-5555-55-55-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{66666-6666-66-66-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777-7777-77-77-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{88888-8888-88-88-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{99999-9999-99-99-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99974} &:= \frac{111111-11111-11-11-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{222222-22222-22-22-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{333333-33333-33-33-3-3-3-3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444-44444-44-44-4-4-4-4}{4} = \frac{555555-55555-55-55-5-5-5-5}{5} = \frac{666666-66666-66-66-6-6-6-6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777-77777-77-77-7-7-7-7}{7} = \frac{888888-88888-88-88-8-8-8-8}{8} = \frac{999999-99999-99-99-9-9-9-9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{999974} := \frac{1111111-111111-11-11-1-1-1-1}{1} = \frac{2222222-222222-22-22-2-2-2-2}{2} = \frac{3333333-333333-33-33-3-3-3-3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

► **975** := $\frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}$

9975 := $\frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}$

99975 := $\frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}$

999975 := $\frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}$

► **976** := $\frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9}$

9976 := $\frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3}$
 $:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6}$
 $:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9}$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99976} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999976} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{977} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9977} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99977} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999977} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{978} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9978} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99978} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999978} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{979} &:= \frac{(111 - 11 - 11) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 22 - 22) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 33 - 33) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 - 44 - 44) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 55 - 55) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 66 - 66) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 77 - 77) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 88 - 88) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 99 - 99) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9779} &:= \frac{(1111 - 111 - 111) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 222 - 222) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 333 - 333) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 444 - 444) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 555 - 555) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 666 - 666) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 777 - 777) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 888 - 888) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 999 - 999) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{97779} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1111 - 1111) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2222 - 2222) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3333 - 3333) \times 33}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4444 - 4444) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5555 - 5555) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6666 - 6666) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7777 - 7777) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8888 - 8888) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9999 - 9999) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{977779} := \frac{(111111 - 11111 - 11111) \times 11}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 22222 - 22222) \times 22}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 33333 - 33333) \times 33}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444444 - 44444 - 44444) \times 44}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 55555 - 55555) \times 55}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 66666 - 66666) \times 66}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 77777 - 77777) \times 77}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 88888 - 88888) \times 88}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 99999 - 99999) \times 99}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

► **980** := $\frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3}$
 $\frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6}$
 $\frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9}$

9980 := $\frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3}$
 $\frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6}$
 $\frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9}$

99980 := $\frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3}$
 $\frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6}$
 $\frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9}$

999980 := $\frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3}$
 $\frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6}$
 $\frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9}$

► **981** := $\frac{(111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3}$
 $\frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6}$
 $\frac{(777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}$

9981 := $\frac{(1111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3}$
 $\frac{(4444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6}$
 $\frac{(7777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9}$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99981} &:= \frac{(11111-1-1) \times (11-1-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222-2-2) \times (22-2-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333-3-3) \times (33-3-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444-4-4) \times (44-4-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555-5-5) \times (55-5-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666-6-6) \times (66-6-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777-7-7) \times (77-7-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888-8-8) \times (88-8-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999-9-9) \times (99-9-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999981} &:= \frac{(111111-1-1) \times (11-1-1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222-2-2) \times (22-2-2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333-3-3) \times (33-3-3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444-4-4) \times (44-4-4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555-5-5) \times (55-5-5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666-6-6) \times (66-6-6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777-7-7) \times (77-7-7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888-8-8) \times (88-8-8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999-9-9) \times (99-9-9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{982} &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times (111-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times (222-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times (333-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times (444-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times (555-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times (666-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times (777-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times (888-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times (999-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9982} &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times (1111-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times (2222-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times (3333-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times (4444-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times (5555-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times (6666-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times (7777-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times (8888-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times (9999-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99982} &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times (11111-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times (22222-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times (33333-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times (44444-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times (55555-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times (66666-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times (77777-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times (88888-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times (99999-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999982} &:= \frac{(11-1-1) \times (111111-1-1) + 1 \times 1}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22-2-2) \times (222222-2-2) + 2 \times 2}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33-3-3) \times (333333-3-3) + 3 \times 3}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44-4-4) \times (444444-4-4) + 4 \times 4}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55-5-5) \times (555555-5-5) + 5 \times 5}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66-6-6) \times (666666-6-6) + 6 \times 6}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77-7-7) \times (777777-7-7) + 7 \times 7}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88-8-8) \times (888888-8-8) + 8 \times 8}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99-9-9) \times (999999-9-9) + 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{983} := \frac{(111-1-1) \times (11-1-1) + 1 \times (1+1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222-2-2) \times (22-2-2) + 2 \times (2+2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333-3-3) \times (33-3-3) + 3 \times (3+3)}{3 \times 3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9983} &:= \frac{(1111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99983} &:= \frac{(11111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999983} &:= \frac{(111111 - 1 - 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1) + 1 \times (1 + 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 - 2 - 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2) + 2 \times (2 + 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 - 3 - 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3) + 3 \times (3 + 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 - 4 - 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4) + 4 \times (4 + 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 - 5 - 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5) + 5 \times (5 + 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 - 6 - 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6) + 6 \times (6 + 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 - 7 - 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7) + 7 \times (7 + 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 - 8 - 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8) + 8 \times (8 + 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 - 9 - 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9) + 9 \times (9 + 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{984} &:= \frac{(111 + 11 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222 + 22 + 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333 + 33 + 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444 + 44 + 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555 + 55 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666 + 66 + 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{8984} &:= \frac{(1111 + 11 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(2222 + 22 + 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(3333 + 33 + 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(4444 + 44 + 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(5555 + 55 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(6666 + 66 + 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(7777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(8888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(9999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88984} &:= \frac{(11111 + 11 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(22222 + 22 + 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(33333 + 33 + 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(44444 + 44 + 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(55555 + 55 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(66666 + 66 + 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(77777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(88888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(99999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{888984} &:= \frac{(111111 + 11 + 1) \times (11 - 1 - 1 - 1)}{1 \times 1} = \frac{(222222 + 22 + 2) \times (22 - 2 - 2 - 2)}{2 \times 2} = \frac{(333333 + 33 + 3) \times (33 - 3 - 3 - 3)}{3 \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(444444 + 44 + 4) \times (44 - 4 - 4 - 4)}{4 \times 4} = \frac{(555555 + 55 + 5) \times (55 - 5 - 5 - 5)}{5 \times 5} = \frac{(666666 + 66 + 6) \times (66 - 6 - 6 - 6)}{6 \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{(777777 + 77 + 7) \times (77 - 7 - 7 - 7)}{7 \times 7} = \frac{(888888 + 88 + 8) \times (88 - 8 - 8 - 8)}{8 \times 8} = \frac{(999999 + 99 + 9) \times (99 - 9 - 9 - 9)}{9 \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{985} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9985} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99985} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999985} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{986} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9986} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99986} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999986} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{987} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9987} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99987} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999987} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{988} := \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 - 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9988} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99988} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999988} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{989} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9989} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999989} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9999989} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{990} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9990} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999990} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9999990} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{991} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9991} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99991} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999991} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{992} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9992} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99992} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999992} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{993} := \frac{1111 - 111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9993} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99993} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999993} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 11 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 22 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 33 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 44 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 55 + 5 + 5 + 5 + 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 66 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 77 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 99 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{994} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9994} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99994} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{999994} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{995} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9995} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{99995} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{999995} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \mathbf{996} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\
 &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{9996} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\
 &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99996} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999996} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 3 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 6 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 7 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 9 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{997} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9997} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99997} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999997} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 1 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 2 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 3 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 4 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 5 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 6 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 7 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 8 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 9 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \mathbf{998} := \frac{1111 - 111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 3 - 3}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9998} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99998} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999998} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 1 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 2 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 3 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 4 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 5 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 6 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 7 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 8 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 9 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{999} &:= \frac{1111 - 111 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444 - 444 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9999} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111 - 1}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222 - 2}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{44444 - 4444 - 4}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555 - 5}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777 - 7}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888 - 8}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{99999} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111 - 1}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222 - 2}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{444444 - 44444 - 4}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555 - 5}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777 - 7}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888 - 8}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{999999} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111 - 1}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222 - 2}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333 - 3}{3} \\ &:= \frac{4444444 - 444444 - 4}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555 - 5}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666 - 6}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777 - 7}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888 - 8}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999 - 9}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \mathbf{1000} &:= \frac{1111 - 111}{1} = \frac{2222 - 222}{2} = \frac{3333 - 333}{3} = \frac{4444 - 444}{4} = \frac{5555 - 555}{5} = \frac{6666 - 666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777 - 777}{7} = \frac{8888 - 888}{8} = \frac{9999 - 999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{10000} &:= \frac{11111 - 1111}{1} = \frac{22222 - 2222}{2} = \frac{33333 - 3333}{3} = \frac{44444 - 4444}{4} = \frac{55555 - 5555}{5} = \frac{66666 - 6666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{77777 - 7777}{7} = \frac{88888 - 8888}{8} = \frac{99999 - 9999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{100000} &:= \frac{111111 - 11111}{1} = \frac{222222 - 22222}{2} = \frac{333333 - 33333}{3} = \frac{444444 - 44444}{4} = \frac{555555 - 55555}{5} = \frac{666666 - 66666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{777777 - 77777}{7} = \frac{888888 - 88888}{8} = \frac{999999 - 99999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1000000} &:= \frac{1111111 - 111111}{1} = \frac{2222222 - 222222}{2} = \frac{3333333 - 333333}{3} = \frac{4444444 - 444444}{4} = \frac{5555555 - 555555}{5} = \frac{6666666 - 666666}{6} \\ &:= \frac{7777777 - 777777}{7} = \frac{8888888 - 888888}{8} = \frac{9999999 - 999999}{9} \end{aligned}$$

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to T.J. Eckman, Georgia, USA (email: jeek@jeek.net) in programming the script to develop the **single letter** and **single digits** representations given in [4]-[11].

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